

A GUIDE FOR NEW REACTOME CURATORS

OVERVIEW OF CURATION

[This set of slides](#) (Appendix C1) provides a high-level overview of the curation process described below.

QUICK GUIDE

[This](#) is a list of the most commonly used steps in the annotation process with links to the relevant guides, and is provided as PDF in Appendix C2.

INTRODUCTION

The goal of Reactome is to describe the known biochemical details of human biological pathways. A Reactome curator's job is to work with experts in different fields of biology to identify and curate suitable human pathways (see below) by breaking them down into subpathways and reactions and describing them in a format that is compatible with the Reactome data model. The purpose of this guide is to describe each step of that curation process to help the curator fully understand the steps involved. The guide is a useful reference for the experienced curator as it is nearly impossible to remember all of the steps and details of the curation process. Curators are actively encouraged to add to sections of the guide providing useful hints that may be missing for current and future curators. Regular use and addition of material to the guide will facilitate the process of curation and increase annotation consistency. If in doubt about any of these steps...do not hesitate to e-mail the internal list for clarification (and then contribute any helpful info that you get to save someone else the trouble of asking later!)

Here we provide basic guidelines as to how data for relevant pathways should be collected, organized and entered into Reactome via the Curator Tool. The process of converting a biological topic should maintain the referential integrity of the reactions, both newly added as well as those already present in Reactome. It is assumed that you (the reader of the guide) have some familiarity with Reactome, and have read the Reactome papers, including the very important paper describing naming conventions for both events and entities (xc).

Our publications are listed on the [Publications](#) page of the Reactome website (<https://reactome.org/community/publications>).

The entire dataset, website, curator, and author tools can be downloaded from the Reactome [download page](#) (<https://reactome.org/download-data>). Installation and configuration instructions are also provided [here](#) (<https://reactome.org/download-data/reactome-curator-tool>).

If you have any problems with the install or tools please contact us at help@reactome.org.

This rest of this guide is divided into the following sections:

1. [Important general guidelines for new curators](#)
2. [Choosing a topic/pathway for curation](#)
3. [Understanding and using the data model](#)

4. [Guideline for Naming Entities and Events](#)
5. [Using Data Inferred from Other Species](#)
6. [Providing evidence for assertions](#)
7. [Using the curator tool](#)
8. [The annotation process for traditional Reactome pathways](#)
9. [Cell lineage path curation guide](#)
10. [Disease pathway curation guide](#)
11. [Infectious disease and Innate Immune System pathway curation guide](#)
12. [Drug curation guide](#)
13. [Complexities of disease and drug curation: special cases](#)
14. [Modifying deleting and merging instances](#)
15. [QA](#)
16. [Curation Tools/Automation](#)
17. [Preparing a pathway report for internal and external review](#)
18. [Reporting bugs](#)
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IMPORTANT GENERAL GUIDELINES FOR NEW CURATORS

- EVIDENCE AND REFERENCES:
 - When considering which type of evidence to use when creating events in Reactome, note that you should **NOT** include events based solely on microarray, proteomics or similar high throughput data, unless either 1) an expert author has indicated that they believe the results are correct and represent the current consensus, or 2) The results are a meta-data analysis that combines several independent studies to show the overlap between them. See guidelines describing External confidence criteria [here](#) (Appendix C3).
 - In general any time you make a statement in your summation you should include a reference. This is to point the user to the paper you found that proves the statement is true, otherwise the reviewer can't go and check. It also shows that it is an established fact, not your own finding or opinion.
 - Making inferences: If reactions (RLEs) have not been demonstrated experimentally, it is OK to include these as long as somewhere in subsequent events there is some kind of experimental data that suggests your inferred events must logically occur to get you to that point. It's essential that you explain the inference you have made (or others have suggested). You must include citations for the characterized mechanism that allows you to make the inference, i.e. why you believe the events you are describing are similar, despite lack of direct experimental proof in humans. It is best to have an expert's approval of this type of event before including it. Note that you should NOT create a pathway in non-human species and use that to infer a human pathway. Instead, create individual non-human reactions and use those to infer the human RLEs where

evidence for the RLE is missing. See the section [below](#) on Creating an inferred event.

- Tools for literature reference searches: See [Litball](#) and [slides](#) describing how to use it.
- **UPDATING EXISTING CONTENT**
 - Be extremely careful changing ANY released instance. This should almost never be done unless new information has become available. Be absolutely sure to check any/all referrers of the instance being changed (entity/event) and make sure that those changes are relevant in ALL referrers. Never change the compartment of an existing entity as that will change the compartment everywhere the entity is used.
 - Changing the species of an event or entity, once it has been committed to gk_central, will change its stableIdentifier. Please contact the managing editor if this has happened. Changing a species once an entity/event has been released will require the deletion of the instance and creation of a new one. The old deleted instance must point to the new one via the deletedInstance that is created. See section on [deleting instances](#) in this guide.
 - Adding an entity with a new species to an existing set (say a new pathogen entity is added to a set of entities from other pathogens to be used in an innate immune response event) can be a bit complicated. You have to then make sure that the species setting for the set includes the new pathogen species and that all referrers of that set are adjusted accordingly with the appropriate relatedSpecies). You can do this by looking for each referrer of the changed entity (all entities and ReactionLikeEvents) and then use the curatorTool species QA check to make sure there are no conflicts.
 - If you change an existing event, especially if it has been released, you need to change the summation to reflect this.
 - Substantive changes to released material (physical entities and events) are automatically tracked each release by the UpdateTracker script (see Appendix C4 for a [description of changes that are caught by UpdateTracker](#))
- **NAMING EVENTS AND ENTITIES:**
 - Use the published guidelines (Jupe et al, 2014) on naming events and entities in Reactome. Note that, despite the statement in this paper, current practice supports using coordinates for *all post-translational modifications, if known.

- Naming of growing complexes: Generally, for serial binding events the 'new' input is named after the existing complex, this gives a better sense that a complex is growing or changing.
- Generally, descriptive words like 'complex' or 'receptor' are not included in physical entity names except in cases where the common name uses those terms, ie RNA pol II complex, Mediator complex etc
- Use of the word 'activated': Activated has a special meaning in Reactome and should only be used to indicate a change of conformational state from inactive (this word is not used) to active or activated.
- Refer to the more detailed [“Guidelines for naming Entities and Events”](#) section in this guide.

REFERENCES

1. Jupe S, Jassal B, Williams M, Wu G. A controlled vocabulary for pathway entities and events. Database (Oxford). 2014 Jun 20;2014:bau060. doi: 10.1093/database/bau060. PMID: 24951798; PMCID: PMC4064568.

- NAMING PEOPLE AND CONSORTIA

- *initial* is a mandatory attribute on a **Person** record, and refers to the first name initial. If no first name is available, enter a dash “-” as the *initial* AND *firstName* attribute
- if a consortium is cited as an author in a **LiteratureReference**, the consortium name should be listed as the *surname* attribute, and a dash “-” should be listed as the *initial* attribute

- USE OF COMPARTMENTS

- Be careful to use the correct compartment. For example: Nucleus vs. nucleolus. Also, be as specific as possible. If you are talking about an event occurring inside the nucleus, use nucleoplasm not nucleus (Also use cytosol not cytoplasm).

CHOOSING A TOPIC/PATHWAY FOR CURATION

Focus first on:

1. Areas of biology that you know well (or one in which you have good contacts).
2. Pathways that are well characterized at the molecular level AND for which there is considerable HUMAN biochemical data and proteins that are new to Reactome.

Points to consider:

1. Give lower priority to topics that will require a large amount of inferences from other species.
2. Don't try to tackle huge pathways all at once.

3. Break large topics into *manageable* pieces. Experts are generally unwilling to commit to a project bigger than a dozen rxns and it is easy to get lost in the details and lose focus which is costly in terms of time.
4. Create a logical hierarchy for the events in the pathway that you are curating.
5. Work on several (preferably related) small projects simultaneously. Experts often fail to come through at critical times so it is good to have a few projects at different stages to keep work flowing through the pipeline.
6. Check the Editorial Calendar to ensure that your plans don't overlap with another curator. If in doubt, contact the curator. Discuss plans with Editor in Chief and managing editor.

UNDERSTANDING AND USING THE DATA MODEL

DATA MODEL GLOSSARY

A detailed understanding of the Reactome data model is important for accurate and consistent curation. The best way to start learning about the different data classes and how to use them is to browse the [Data Model Glossary](#) (Appendix C5). Some classes are used infrequently but you still need to be aware of them. Some of the more important data classes are described in the annotation examples below.

More complex examples are cited in the advance curation section as well as the disease annotation guide.

KEY DATA CLASSES

PHYSICALENTITY

PhysicalEntities can be single entities, such as proteins, small molecules, RNA, DNA, carbohydrates, lipids, or sub-atomic particles. They can also be complexes consisting of a combination of any of the single entities, or polymers synthesized from the single entities. Related entities can be grouped into a set. The use of sets is described [below](#). PhysicalEntities can be inputs, outputs, catalysts, regulators, or requirements in ReactionlikeEvents.

EVENTS

The main concepts in the Reactome data model are Event and PhysicalEntity. At present there are two subclasses of Event: ReactionlikeEvent and Pathway.

ReactionLikeEvent

ReactionLikeEvent (RLE) in Reactome is a single step event in which input entities are converted to output entities by means of structural, chemical or compartmental changes.

The Reactome data model robustly represents biology. The central concept in Reactome is the reaction, which is used together with pathways, macromolecules, small molecules, complexes, and catalyst activities to represent biological processes. The reaction itself is a single step biological event in which input entities are converted to output entities.

The ReactionLikeEvent subclass has 6 subclasses: Reaction, BlackBoxEvent, Depolymerisation, and Polymerisation, FailedReaction, and CellDevelopmentStep. ReactionLikeEvents may be linked to other events that precede them, regulate or are regulated by them.

Participants of ReactionLikeEvents – inputs, outputs, catalysts, regulators and requirements – are PhysicalEntities.

Here are some common examples of different types of ReactionsLikeEvents. The compartment of an RLE that involves participants in more than one compartment (or movement of participants across multiple compartments), should reflect the compartments of all of the participants (inputs, outputs, catalyst).

Reaction

A Reaction is an event that converts inputs to outputs in a single step. Any enzymatically-catalyzed event, or transport of physical entity to adjacent cell compartments, or protein-DNA binding or protein-protein complex formation or disassociation, for example, can be annotated as a reaction:

Complex Association:

reactome 3.7 Pathways for: Homo sapiens

Event Hierarchy:

- Neuronal System
 - Organelle biogenesis and maintenance
 - Mitochondrial biogenesis
 - Cilium Assembly
 - Anchoring of the basal body to the plasma membrane
 - Cargo trafficking to the periciliary membrane
 - VxPx cargo-targeting to cilium
 - BBSome-mediated cargo-targeting to cilium
 - LZTFL1 binds the BBSome and prevents its traffic to the cilium
 - Formation of the BBSome
 - ARL6:GTP and the BBSome bind ciliary cargo
 - ARL6:GTP and the BBSome target cargo to the primary cilium
 - BBSome binds RAB31P
 - Trafficking of myristoylated proteins to the cilium
 - UNC119B binds myristoylated proteins
 - UNC119B stimulates translocation of myristoylated ciliary cargo to the primary cilium
 - ARL3:GTP binds the UNC119B complex
 - Myristoylated NPHP3 translocates into the ciliary membrane
 - RP2 binds ARL3:GTP:UNC119B
 - RP2 activates the GTPase activity of ARL3
 - ARL3 hydrolyzes GTP
 - RP2:ARL3:GDP:UNC119B dissociates
 - ARL13B-mediated ciliary trafficking of INPP5E
 - Intraflagellar transport
 - ATAT acetylates microtubules
 - HDAC6 deacetylates microtubules
 - Programmed Cell Death
 - Protein localization

Search for a term, e.g. pten ...

Description: RP2 binds ARL3:GTP:UNC119B

Molecules: RP2, ARL3:GTP:UNC119B

Id: R-HSA-5638004.2

Species: Homo sapiens

Review Status: 56

Summation

RP2 is an ARL3 GAP that is localized to the cilium and plays a role in trafficking proteins from the Golgi to the ciliary membrane (Vellet et al, 2008a; Hurd et al, 2011; Evans et al, 2010; Wright et al, 2011). RP2 forms a ternary complex with UNC119B and ARL3, activating the ARL3 GTPase activity and promoting the release of UNC119B (Vellet et al, 2008b; Wright et al, 2011; Kuhnel et al, 2006; reviewed in Schwarz et al, 2012; Li et al, 2012)

Input

- ARL3:GTP:UNC119B [cilium]
- RP2 [cilium]

Output

- RP2:ARL3:GTP:UNC119B [cilium]

Preceding Event(s)

- Myristoylated NPHP3 translocates into the ciliary membrane [Homo sapiens]

Cellular compartment

- cilium

View computationally predicted event in

Complex Dissociation:

reactome 3.7 Pathways for: Homo sapiens

Event Hierarchy:

- DNA Repair
 - DNA Replication
 - Drug ADME
 - Extracellular matrix organization
 - Gene expression (Transcription)
 - Hemostasis
 - Immune System
 - Metabolism
 - Metabolism of proteins
 - Metabolism of RNA
 - Muscle contraction
 - Neuronal System
 - Organelle biogenesis and maintenance
 - Mitochondrial biogenesis
 - Cilium Assembly
 - Anchoring of the basal body to the plasma membrane
 - Cargo trafficking to the periciliary membrane
 - VxPx cargo-targeting to cilium
 - BBSome-mediated cargo-targeting to cilium
 - Trafficking of myristoylated proteins to the cilium
 - UNC119B binds myristoylated proteins
 - UNC119B stimulates translocation of myristoylated ciliary cargo to the primary cilium
 - ARL3:GTP binds the UNC119B complex
 - Myristoylated NPHP3 translocates into the ciliary membrane
 - RP2 binds ARL3:GTP:UNC119B
 - RP2 activates the GTPase activity of ARL3
 - ARL3 hydrolyzes GTP
 - RP2:ARL3:GDP:UNC119B dissociates
 - ARL13B-mediated ciliary trafficking of INPP5E
 - Intraflagellar transport
 - ATAT acetylates microtubules
 - HDAC6 deacetylates microtubules
 - Programmed Cell Death
 - Protein localization
 - Reproduction
 - Sensory Perception
 - Signal Transduction
 - Transport of small molecules
 - Vesicle-mediated transport

Search for a term, e.g. pten ...

Description: RP2:ARL3:GDP:UNC119B dissociates

Molecules: RP2:ARL3:GDP:UNC119B, ARL3:GDP, UNC119B

Id: R-HSA-5638016.2

Species: Homo sapiens

Review Status: 55

Summation

ARL3 hydrolysis of GTP promotes the release of UNC119B, dissociating the complex (Wright et al, 2011; reviewed in Schwarz et al, 2012).

Input

- RP2:ARL3:GDP:UNC119B [cilium]

Output

- ARL3:GDP [cilium]
- UNC119B [cilium]
- RP2 [cilium]

Preceding Event(s)

- ARL3 hydrolyzes GTP [Homo sapiens]

Cellular compartment

- cilium

View computationally predicted event in

Select a species to go to ...

References

- An ARL3-UNC119B-RP2 GTPase cycle targets myristoylated NPHP3 to the primary cilium

Enzyme-catalyzed biochemical reactions:

The screenshot shows the Reactome database interface for the reaction "HDAC6 deacetylates microtubules". The reaction is shown as a network diagram where HDAC6 (catalyst) acts on acetylated microtubule (input) to produce microtubule (no TUBA4B) and CoA-SH (output). The reaction is associated with the GO term "tubulin deacetylase activity" and is located in the cytosol compartment.

Reaction Details:

- Reaction ID:** R-HSA-5618331.3
- Species:** Homo sapiens
- Review Status:** 4/5

Summation: HDAC6 is a microtubule-associated deacetylase that targets the K40 acetyl groups of alpha tubulin (Hubbert et al, 2002; Loktev et al, 2008; Zhang et al, 2008). HDAC6 also interacts with BBIP1, a component of the BBSome that is required for BBSome assembly, and additionally (and independently of its role in the BBSome) plays a role in microtubule polymerization and acetylation (Loktev et al, 2008). Depletion of BBIP1 causes a marked reduction in cytoplasmic microtubule acetylation, and this defect is partially overcome by inhibition of HDAC6. These data suggest that BBIP1 may exert its effect on microtubule acetylation by negatively regulating HDAC6, although other mechanisms are also possible (Loktev et al, 2008).

Input: CoA-SH [cytosol], acetylated microtubule [cytosol]

Output: Ac-CoA [cytosol], microtubule (no TUBA4B) [cytosol]

Catalyst Activity: tubulin deacetylase activity of HDAC6 [cytosol]

Physical Entity: HDAC6 [cytosol]

Represents GO Molecular Function: tubulin deacetylase activity

Cellular compartment: cytosol

The compartment of a Reaction that involves participants in more than one compartment (or movement of participants across multiple compartments), should reflect the compartments of all of the participants (inputs, outputs, catalyst, regulator).

BlackBoxEvent

A BlackBox event converts inputs to outputs of a multiple step biological process in which intervening steps are not annotated because:

1. We don't know all of the intervening steps.
2. The intervening steps are known but we do not want to curate them for the purposes of the module. Examples are:
 1. The transactivation of a gene leading to production of a protein....we don't want to include all the steps of translation of that protein
 2. The degradation of a protein.
 3. Transport from one cellular organelle to another.

The compartment of a BlackBoxEvent that involves participants in more than one compartment (or movement of participants across multiple compartments), should reflect the compartments of all of the participants (inputs, outputs, catalyst).

reactome 3.7 12 Pathways for: Homo sapiens

Event Hierarchy:

- Muscle contraction
- Neuronal System
- Organelle biogenesis and maintenance
- Programmed Cell Death
 - Apoptosis
 - Caspase activation via extrinsic apoptotic signalling pathway
 - Intrinsic Pathway for Apoptosis
 - Activation, myristoylation of BID and translocation to mitochondria
 - Activation of BH3-only proteins
 - Activation of BAD and translocation to mitochondria
 - Activation of NOXA and translocation to mitochondria
 - Activation of PUMA and translocation to mitochondria
 - TP53 binds the BBC3 (PUMA) promoter
 - TP53 stimulates BBC3 (PUMA) expression**
 - E2F1 binds BBC3 (PUMA) promoter
 - Transactivation of BBC3 (PUMA) by E2F1
 - Translocation of BBC3 (PUMA) protein to mitochondria
 - Activation of BIM and translocation to mitochondria
 - Activation of BMF and translocation to mitochondria
 - BH3-only proteins associate with and inactivate anti-apoptotic BCL-2
 - Activation, translocation and oligomerization of BAX
 - Activation and oligomerization of BAK protein
 - Apoptotic factor-mediated response
 - Apoptotic execution phase
 - Regulation of Apoptosis
 - Regulated Necrosis
 - Protein localization
 - Reproduction

Search for a term, e.g. pten ...

Reaction: TP53 stimulates BBC3 (PUMA) expression

Id: R-HSA-139913.7 Species: Homo sapiens Review Status: 55

Summation

TP53 (p53) stimulates the transcription of BBC3 (PUMA) (p53 upregulated modulator of apoptosis) (Nakano and Vousden 2001). The transcription of BBC3 is also stimulated by p53 family members TP63 (p63) and TP73 (p73) (Bergamaschi et al. 2004, Patel et al. 2008). ASPP proteins PPP1R13B (ASPP1) and TP53BP2 (ASPP2) form a complex with p53 family members and enhance transcriptional activation of BBC3 (Bergamaschi et al. 2004, Patel et al. 2008, Wilson et al. 2013).

Input

- BBC3 gene [nucleoplasm]

Output

- BBC3 [cytosol]

Positively regulated by

- Positive gene expression regulation by '(p-S15,S20-TP53,TP63,TP73):(PPP1R13B,TP53BP2):BBC3 Gene [nucleoplasm]'

Preceding Event(s)

- TP53 binds the BBC3 (PUMA) promoter [Homo sapiens]

Cellular compartment

- nucleoplasm

FailedReaction

See Disease section of the curator guide [here](#) (Annotating loss-of-function reactions).

Pathway

Pathway in Reactome is a multiple step event which can be broken down to subpathways and/or ReactionLikeEvents. A concrete curated example is the Reactome Apoptosis pathway which consist of the subpathways "Caspase activation via extrinsic apoptotic signalling pathway", "Intrinsic pathway for Apoptosis", "Apoptotic execution phase" and "Regulation of Apoptosis".

[Pathway:109581] Apoptosis	
Pathway Properties	
Property Name	Value
Regulation of Apoptosis 	
name	Apoptosis
releaseDate	2004-09-20
Homo sapiens	
Apoptosis is a distinct form of cell death that i...	
Alnemri, E, Hengartner, Michael, Tschopp, Jür...	
compartment	
Gopinathrao, G, Matthews, L, Gillespie, ME, Jo...	
lastUpdatedDate	2022-06-09
Hengartner, M, Ranganathan, S, Vaux, D, 000...	
_doRelease	true
crossReference	
definition	
disease	
doi	
evidenceType	
/figures/Pathway_Illustrations/Apoptosis_72_o... 	
apoptotic process	
hasEHL	true
inferredFrom	
internalReviewed	
isCanonical	
The Bcl2 family: regulators of the cellular life-... 	

MANDATORY, REQUIRED, AND OPTIONAL PROPERTIES (FIELDS) FOR DATA CLASSES

All the classes of data in Reactome have a number of properties (fields of information) that MUST be filled in before they can be 'released', i.e. made visible to the public. They also have required (where relevant) fields, optional fields, and non-editable fields.

When viewing an instance of a class in the curator tool, its properties all have a symbol that indicates the type, either a red box with a letter superimposed, or a yellow diamond with n superimposed. The yellow diamond with n indicates fields that are automatically completed. The red squares indicate, by letter,

Property Name	Value
TPX2 promotes AURKA autophosphorylation	
DB_ID	8854518
_displayName	AURKA Activation by TPX2
_doRelease	true
Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2016-01-27	
compartment	
Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2016-01-27	
crossReference	
definition	
disease	
doi	10.3180/r-hsa-8854518.1
Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2016-01-27	
evidenceType	
figure	
regulation of G2/M transition of mitotic cel...	

- m - Mandatory - you must provide this information.
- r - Required - you must provide this information if it is possible - a good example of this is species, required for defined sets of proteins, but not required for defined sets of small molecules.
- o - Optional - not available for every instance, so cannot be "Mandatory" or 'Required' but in some circumstances may be a procedural requirement, e.g. inferredFrom must be completed for human reactions that are inferred from a model organism.

GUIDELINES FOR NAMING ENTITIES AND EVENTS

The guidelines were first set out in this [paper](#) (Jupe et al, 2014) describing "A controlled vocabulary for pathway entities and events".

Please read the paper to learn how to name EWASs and events.

Here are some guidelines for the different classes of entities:

EWAS

Names are based on the UniProt gene symbol (the gene name), which is typically the same as the HGNC symbol. Post-translational modifications are represented by a

prefix, cleavage events or differences from the canonical form are represented by a suffix.

SMALL MOLECULES

Please use the short name recommendations for small molecules found [here](#) (Appendix C6).

COMPLEXES

These guidelines are an extension of the ideas for a pathway controlled vocabulary set out in this [paper](#) (Jupe et al, 2014). You should familiarize yourself with the rules for naming EWASs and simple entities.

In a typical scenario the names of sets and complexes are simply a joined list of the entities they contain, which in the Curator Tool can be copied to the name field from the hasComponent or hasMember fields.

Complexes should be named after the names of their components, separated by the colon symbol. Some examples: GRB2:SOS1 IL3:IL3RA:IL3RB:JAK2 IL4:p-Y-IL4R:JAK2:p-Y-IL2RG:JAK3:p-Y-JAK1:p-Y705-STAT3,p-Y641-STAT6 RXFP4:RXFP4 ligands

For cardinality (number of copies) use 2x, 3x etc. in front of the name. Is it OK to use dimer, tetramer etc. to indicate multimerization but NOT hetero- or homo- or the word complex.

When a complex is extended by the addition of further components, the name of the complex produced should show the 'added' component on the right end of the complex name.

For complexes larger than 4 components, it is acceptable, though less desirable, to use a descriptive name from the literature IF widely used, e.g. high-affinity IL3 receptor.

What about synonyms? You can add as many extra names as you like, listed after the 'correct' name in the name slot.

Authors/reviewers should NOT be allowed to dictate the name used. We have a controlled vocabulary designed to consistently name entities throughout the Reactome database. Authors may not like the name we use but that is usually because they have become used to a different name from the literature. Unfortunately there are often many alternative names in the literature and there is rarely 100% agreement on the best name to use. We can't make everyone happy, but we must pick one name from the alternatives. The only way we can justify not using names suggested by (highly biased) authors is to be 100% consistent and always use our controlled vocabulary!

Remember - if you diverge from the simple list of colon separated entity names, you **must** check your name is not the same as existing complexes!

SETS

Set names: Small sets (less than 5 members) should be named as a list of the members e.g. IL3,IL3RA,CSF2RB.

Candidate sets should include the candidates within parentheses, e.g. CCR2,(CCR4,CCR6) is a candidate set where CCR2 is a member and CCR4 and CCR6 are candidates.

For large sets (5 or more) it is acceptable, though less desirable, to use a descriptive name from the literature IF widely used, e.g. XXXXXX or a 'function-defining' name that indicates the usage of the set, e.g. 'RXFP4 ligands'. If the large set includes an entire family of proteins, it is OK to use the name of the family, e.g. CCRs (note the s suffix to indicate that there is more than one entity represented), there's no need to add the word family. If the set represents a range of members, use hyphen to indicate the range e.g. CCR2-5. For complicated sets that have diverse members, a descriptive name based on function may be the best option. Try to describe the attribute that is the basis for grouping the entities, their shared property or function, e.g. SLC receptors, VAV2-activated RhoGEFs.

What about sets that have a common name stem, but are not so simple? It's tempting to try and come up with complicated abbreviations around the gene name common prefixes, e.g. for the real example set of genes PLA2G1B PLA2G2A PLA2G2D PLA2G2E PLA2G2F PLA2G5 PLA2G10 PLA2G12A, the name might be PLA2G1B,G2A,G2D,G2E,G2F,G5,G10,G12A but don't - this is too hard to interpret.

Remember - if you diverge from the simple list of comma separated entity names, you **must** check your name is not the same as existing sets!

SEQUENCE VARIANTS

Reactome's approach to annotating sequence variants of proteins is described in detail in the section on Disease Annotation, [below](#) (Annotating Disease Entities), and is informed by the [Human Genome variation society description](#) (<http://www.hgvs.org/mutnomen/examplesAA.html>) of sequence changes at protein level.

REFERENCES

1. Jupe S, Jassal B, Williams M, Wu G. A controlled vocabulary for pathway entities and events. Database (Oxford). 2014 Jun 20;2014:bau060. doi: 10.1093/database/bau060. PMID: 24951798; PMCID: PMC4064568.

USING DATA INFERRED FROM OTHER SPECIES

Sometimes there is not sufficient experimental support for a set of reactions in one species, simply because the experiments have not been done in the target species. The InferredFrom slot addresses this problem. If the experts (perhaps also the curator) knows that this reaction really occurs in the target species, the reaction or reactions can be constructed in the experimentally supported species and then the InferredFrom slot can be filled in for the reactions in the target species. In this case the experimental species *becomes* the support for the target species. See a more complete description [here](#) under “Creating an inferred event”.

PROVIDING EVIDENCE FOR ASSERTIONS IN REACTOME

PRINCIPLES FOR ASSIGNING LITERATURE REFERENCES FOR REACTIONS

The references associated with a reaction **MUST** provide direct experimental evidence for the occurrence of that reaction in the species you are annotating (i.e. human for human Reactome). If there is no direct experimental evidence in humans, but in other species, then you need to create an inferred human reaction as described in the section “Creating an inferred event”, [below](#). See Guidelines on evidence confidence [here](#) (Appendix C3).

OTHER EVIDENCE TYPES

If applying the fundamental “direct evidence” rule leads to a case where a pathway just misses one or few reactions to be complete, it is possible to add missing reactions with less direct evidence. Such reactions **MUST** have the evidenceType slot filled and the summary **MUST** contain rationale on why the reaction was added, despite the weaker evidence.

It is also possible to use black box reactions when specific evidence is missing, in the following cases:

- localization reactions where the means of transport is unknown but the localization itself has direct evidence (e.g. microscopy)
- enzymatic reactions where the catalytic activity is unknown but the end product(s) themselves are supported by direct evidence (e.g. mass spectrometry, crystals)

HOW TO ASSIGN AN EVIDENCE TYPE

1. In the curator tool, view your reaction and focus on the **evidenceType** slot
2. Set its value from a list of already existing values in your project, or values existing in the Reactome database, like with other slots
3. If you think a value is missing in Reactome database, create a new one by using a term from the Evidence & Conclusion Ontology (ECO) at <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/eco>
In particular, the **name**, **definition**, **identifier**, and **referenceDatabase** slots

need to be filled (see picture)

The screenshot shows a 'Create a New Instance' dialog box for the 'EvidenceType' class. The 'referenceDatabase' property is set to 'ECO'. The table below shows the properties and their values:

Property Name	Value
identifier	0007672
name	computational evidence
DB_ID	-2
_displayName	computational evidence
created	
definition	A type of evidence in which data are ...
instanceOf	
modified	
referenceDatabase	ECO
stableIdentifier	
synonym	

CITING BIOLOGICAL DATABASES

Generally, there shouldn't be a need to create ReferenceDatabase instances. Contact dev@reactome.org if you think you need a new ReferenceDatabase instance.

- Attributes: AccessURL- template used to form the URL that will be used to link to a particular record in an external database. Generally, this should not need to be touched. Contact the developers if you think any changes are necessary.
- URL- URL for the site which gives "summary information" about the database including a description of what information the db contains. This attribute should not need to be modified manually.

In certain cases, there are external databases that include information that is relevant to an annotated pathway.

One example is rare disease database such as RettBase, which describes Rett syndrome-related mutations in MECP2, FOXP1 and CDKL5: <http://mecp2.chw.edu.au/>. This database provides information about variants described in the disease pathway: Loss of function of MECP2 in Rett syndrome.

We are not able to cross-reference RettBase for individual MECP2 variants in the way that we cross-reference COSMIC for cancer variants because RettBase is not organized in a way that allows us to do this. However, we can mention RettBase in the pathway summation and cite their most recent publication

(<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/28544139>) as a literatureReference for the Loss of function of MECP2 in Rett syndrome pathway. In addition, we can also create a second Publication instance of class "URL" and use this to cite the database itself.

****NOTE that you should NOT cite disease databases at the reaction level unless these disease databases capture biochemical/functional information.**

USING THE CURATOR TOOL

DOWNLOADING, INSTALLING, AND MAINTAINING THE CURATOR TOOL

For instructions on downloading and installing the curator tool, see the public website [here](https://reactome.org/download-data/reactome-curator-tool) (<https://reactome.org/download-data/reactome-curator-tool>)

WINDOWS:

Instructions

- After downloading, double-click install.zip to unzip it to an empty folder. This folder should be named "ReactomeCuratorTool" though any name can be used. Please use the latest version of WinZip if you use this application for unzipping.
- After unzipping, an application called ReactomeCuratorTool.exe should be found in the named folder. Double click this application to launch the Reactome Curator Tool.

Notes

- You need to install Java 11. You can download one from [OpenJDK](#).

LINUX:

Instructions

- After downloading open a shell, and cd to the directory where you downloaded the installer.
- At the prompt, type unzip install.zip to unzip the installer.
- Use ./ReactomeCuratorTool.sh to launch the Reactome Curator Tool.

Notes

- You need to install Java 11. You can download one from [OpenJDK](#).

MAC:

Updated March 3, 2024 - Mac users now uses the Linux version of the curator tool. It is just too complicated to hack the native Mac installer. To run the curator tool under Mac, please following the following:

1) Download the installer for linux using a browser. After unzip it (it may be automatically unzipped after download), move it out from your Download folder to other place (e.g. Desktop).

2) Open a Mac OS terminal by double clicking "Terminal" in the Applications -> Utilities folder

3) Enter the following in the terminal to check if you have Java installed:

```
java --version
```

- If this fails ("The operation couldn't be completed.", or something like that), install a Java JRE or JDK from <https://adoptopenjdk.net> (use Java 11, JDK. Make sure you choose the correct CPU architecture.)

4) At the same terminal after validating Java 11 is installed, issue command:

```
bash ReactomeCuratorTool.sh.
```

- The curator tool window should popup as usual.

5) Still another alternative for Mac users. After downloading and unzipping the Linux installer (as in step 1 above), assemble all the files into a single folder and name that folder CuratorTool (or any other unique and easy-to-remember name), and put that folder in a convenient directory on your Mac. (PD leaves it on the desktop). To launch the curator tool, open a terminal window on your Mac and cd to the CuratorTool folder:

```
cd desktop/CuratorTool
```

then, still in the terminal window:

```
bash ReactomeCuratorTool.sh
```

(The terminal window remains open while the curator tool is running.) The CuratorTool should open as usual. After you "quit" the CuratorTool, enter "exit" in the terminal window and quit the terminal window.

ADJUSTING THE DISPLAY FOR THE CURATOR TOOL FOR DIFFERENT SCREEN SIZES

While adjusting the curator tool for a new monitor, I had to adjust the font size and window size of the curator tool. I found some helpful internet info and used the "-Dsun.java2d.uiScale=" option in the command to start the tool. For example "-Dsun.java2d.uiScale=2" doubles the size of the curator tool window and font, while "-Dsun.java2d.uiScale=1.5" increases everything by 1.5X.

The command for linux in ReactomeCuratorTool.sh is:

```
java -Xmx8G -Dfile.encoding=UTF-8 -Dsun.java2d.uiScale=2 -cp ReactomeCuratorTool.jar launcher.Launcher
```

(Possibly also prepending GDK_SCALE=2 may make a difference)

If you are in Windows, you can put this command in a text file and save the file as a .bat file (executable file). Then you just need to double click the .bat file to start the tool.

If the .bat file is located outside the curator tool folder (e.g, on the Desktop), I found I needed to add line to tell the command line where to find the jar file and everything else, so the .bat file contains:

```
cd \Users\yourhomedirectory\path\to\curatortool  
java -Xmx8G -Dfile.encoding=UTF-8 -Dsun.java2d.uiScale=2 -cp ReactomeCuratorTool.jar  
launcher.Launcher
```

CURATOR TOOL DEFAULT SETTINGS

All routine curation uses a connection between your local curator tool and the gk_central database. These are the settings for that connection, which you make via the "database info" tab of "curator tool preferences". Other values of these settings can be used for various specialized purposes, but these are outside the scope of regular curation and can be dangerous.

database host: curator.reactome.org

database name: gk_central

database port: 3306

user name: [your user name]

user password: [your password]

Guanming Wu assigns usernames and passwords for new curators; yours will persist unchanged thereafter.

Some institutional firewalls see connecting to port 3306 of a remote server as a security risk and will block your access to it. If this happens, you, Guanming, and your institutional IT people will need to negotiate a workaround, e.g., whitelisting this port at curator.reactome.org for your individual computer.

CURATOR TOOL USER INTERFACE

The curator tool has three panes to view the content. These different views can be switched using the tabs in the upper left hand corner of the curator tool window.

THE MENU BAR

The menu bar contains a number of shortcut buttons, a scroll over message will tell you the function of each button.

THE SCHEMA VIEW

The Schema view provides a hierarchical list of the data classes. In this view you can search, open, edit and create instances of these classes. This panel is used most often for creating new items, such as an EWAS derived from a ReferenceGeneProduct.

The screenshot displays the 'Event Hierarchical View' interface. On the left, a 'Classes' panel lists various biological categories such as 'DrugActionType', 'ReviewStatus', and 'Pathway'. The central panel shows a hierarchical diagram of the 'Apoptosis' pathway, with 'Apoptosis' selected and expanded to show sub-events like 'Apoptosis induced DNA fragmentation' and 'Apoptotic cleavage of cell adhesion proteins'. On the right, the 'Pathway Properties' table provides detailed information for the selected event.

Property Name	Value
hasEvent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Caspase activation via extrinsic apoptotic signalling pathway Intrinsic Pathway for Apoptosis Apoptotic execution phase Regulation of Apoptosis
name	Apoptosis
releaseDate	2004-09-20
species	Homo sapiens
summation	Apoptosis is a distinct form of cell death that is functiona...
authored	Alnemri, E, Hengartner, Michael, Tschopp, Jürg, Tsujimoto, Yoshih...
compartment	Gopinathrao, G, Matthews, L, Gillespie, ME, Joshi-Tope, G, 0000-...
edited	2022-06-09
lastUpdatedDate	Hengartner, M, Ranganathan, S, Vaux, D, 0000-00-00 00:00:00
reviewed	
doRelease	true
crossReference	
definition	
disease	
doi	
evidenceType	
figure	/figures/ehhd/R-HSA-109581.svg
goBiologicalProcess	apoptotic process
hasEHLID	true
inferredFrom	
internalReviewed	
isCanonical	
literatureReference	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apoptosis and disease: a life or death decision Apoptosis: a basic biological phenomenon with wide-ranging impli... History of the events leading to the formulation of the apoptosis c... Ways of dying: multiple pathways to apoptosis. The Bcl-2 family: roles in cell survival and oncogenesis. Targeting death and decoy receptors of the tumour-necrosis facto... The Bcl2 family: regulators of the cellular life-or-death switch
negativePrecedingEvent	
normalPathway	
orthologousEvent	
precedingEvent	
previousReviewStatus	five stars
relatedSpecies	
reviewStatus	two stars
revised	
DB_ID	109581
displayName	Apoptosis
created	Alnemri, E, Hengartner, Michael, Tschopp, Jürg, Tsujimoto, Yoshih... Joshi-Tope, G, 2004-01-17 16:00:00 Joshi-Tope, G, 2004-01-21 12:12:58

THE EVENT VIEW

This view is where most curation is done. The event view displays a hierarchical, alphabetical list of the events in the local project on the left, a graphic in the middle that shows the relationship between objects for selected events, and on the right the details of selected events. Unfurling a pathway by clicking on the + symbol to the left of its name in this view reveals all of its component Reaction events. DON'T CONFUSE these symbols for the check box - clicking on an unchecked box marks the event as ready for release onto the public website; clicking on a checked box has the opposite effect. For pathways the check box selects the ENTIRE pathway, doing this by mistake can be time-consuming and tedious to reverse so be warned!

The screenshot displays the Entity Level View (ELV) for Apoptosis. The interface is divided into three main sections:

- Tree View (Left):** A hierarchical tree structure showing the organization of apoptosis-related events. The root is 'Apoptosis', which branches into 'Caspase activation via extrinsic apoptotic signalling pathway', 'Intrinsic Pathway for Apoptosis', 'Apoptotic execution phase', and 'Regulation of Apoptosis'. Each branch further details specific molecular events and regulatory steps.
- Graphic Display (Center):** A graphical representation of the pathway. It features four distinct boxes: 'Caspase activation via extrinsic apoptotic signalling pathway', 'Intrinsic Pathway for Apoptosis', 'Apoptotic execution phase', and 'Regulation of Apoptosis'. These boxes are arranged to show the flow and interaction of different components within the pathway.
- Pathway Properties (Right):** A detailed list of properties for the selected pathway. Key properties include:
 - name:** Apoptosis
 - releaseDate:** 2004-09-20
 - species:** Homo sapiens
 - summation:** Apoptosis is a distinct form of cell death that...
 - author:** Alnemri, E, Hengartner, Michael, Tschoopp, J...
 - compartment:** Apoptosis
 - edited:** Gopinathrao, G, Matthews, L, Gillespie, ME, J...
 - lastUpdatedDate:** 2022-06-09
 - reviewed:** Hengartner, M, Ranganathan, S, Vaux, D, 00...
 - doRelease:** true
 - crossReference:** true
 - definition:** Apoptotic process
 - disease:** Apoptosis and disease: a life or death decision
 - doi:** /figures/ehld/R-HSA-109581.svg
 - evidenceType:** /figures/Pathway_Illustrations/Apoptosis_72...
 - figure:** Apoptosis: a basic biological phenomenon wi...
 - goBiologicalProcess:** Apoptosis
 - hasEHLID:** true
 - inferredFrom:** Apoptosis
 - internalReviewed:** Apoptosis
 - isCanonical:** Apoptosis and disease: a life or death decision
 - literatureReference:** Apoptosis: a basic biological phenomenon wi...
History of the events leading to the formulati...
Ways of dying: multiple pathways to apoptosis.
The Bcl-2 family: roles in cell survival and on...
Targeting death and decoy receptors of the ...
The Bcl2 family: regulators of the cellular life...
 - negativePrecedingEvent:** Apoptosis
 - normalPathway:** Apoptosis
 - orthologousEvent:** Apoptosis
 - precedingEvent:** Apoptosis
 - previousReviewStatus:** five stars
 - relatedSpecies:** Apoptosis
 - reviewStatus:** two stars
 - revised:** Apoptosis
 - DB_ID:** 109581
 - displayName:** Apoptosis
 - created:** Alnemri, E, Hengartner, Michael, Tschoopp, J...
Joshi-Tope, G, 2004-01-17 16:00:00
Ioshi-Tope, G, 2004-01-21 12:12:58

THE ENTITY LEVEL VIEW (ELV)

The ELV is where pathway diagrams are created and subsequently represented. In this view the pathway is laid out graphically showing the inputs, outputs, catalyst where appropriate, and regulatory molecules, each in the correct cellular compartment.

For the usage please see the chapter on “Drawing a pathway diagram”, [below](#).

USING THE PRECEDING EVENT SUGGESTION FEATURE IN THE CURATOR TOOL
 See slides describing this process [here](#) (Appendix C7).

CLONING TOOL

BE CAUTIOUS WHEN USING THE CLONING TOOL. Use it carefully and thoughtfully. The use of the cloning tool is restricted to making a copy of something that will be changed. When using the tool you must be absolutely sure that at least one of the defining attributes of that entity is different from the original.

Be particularly careful when cloning a complex or a set and are faced with the option to “clone contained subunits recursively” - the answer to this is almost always “no” since the danger of creating hard-to-track duplicate entities is high.

Once the cloning is done, immediately go back and change the defining attributes that need to be changed.

Once changed use the Select Match instance in DB to make sure that you have made a meaningful change.

"Match instance in DB" feature to ensure that the instance is really different from the entity in gk_central. Do this by right clicking on the newly created instance.

SYNCHRONIZING LOCAL PROJECTS WITH THE DATABASE

Synchronize at least once a day. It is good practice to synchronize your local project with the gk_central database to ensure that your work is not lost should the local copy become corrupted or lost due to hard drive failure. It is useful for other curators who may be able to reuse EWASs or other instances that you have created. It is perfectly acceptable to 'check-in' incomplete work unless it is marked as 'doRelease'.

To keep the data in the opened project and the database repository consistent, you need to synchronize the local project with the database periodically. Several actions are available for you to do synchronizing. The following is the "Database" menu for doing database-related actions:

"Match Instance in DB..." can find a matched instance in the database repository for the selected instance in the local repository. A matched instance has the same defining attributes as the local one. If a matched instance can be found, you can merge the local one to the database one. "Compare Instance in DB..." can compare a selected instance

with the corresponding one in the database. Corresponding means the same DB_IDs. So you should not compare one instance checked from database A to an instance in database B because the same DB_ID might be assigned to different instances. "Update from DB" will update a checked out instance from the database. "Check In" is used to check in newly created or modified instances to the database. It is recommended that you should use "Compare Instance in DB..." first before "Update from DB" or "Check In". After a new instance or modified instance is checked into the database, the marker ">" will be removed to indicate that the local and the database copies are the same.

The "Synchronize with DB..." menu is used to check all instances in the selected schema class in the schema view or in the whole opened project if no class is selected. There are four possible inconsistency categories between the two repositories: instances different between the local and the db repositories resulting from instance modification either locally or in the database, instances created locally, instances deleted in the database by you or others, and instances deleted locally by you. You can choose appropriate action for the selected instances in different categories. Please be aware that if you do a multiple selection from different categories, the enabled actions are applied to all selected categories. For example, actions "Update from DB" and "Commit to DB" can be applied to instance "AIF-mediated response" in the first category, but only "Commit to DB" can be applied to instance "TestPathway" in the second category. If you select both "AIF-mediated response" and "TestPathway", only "Commit to DB" is enabled and "Update from DB" is disabled. Double clicking an instance in the first category will popup a comparison dialog of the local and database instances, while double clicking an instance in other categories will show the contents of the clicked instance. To deselect a single instance, hold the control key and click the selected instance.

There are three different cases in the first category, instances different between the

local and the db repositories: instance is modified in the local project but not in the database, instance modified in the database but not in the local project, and instances are modified in both the local and database. The user can commit changes to the database or overwrite changes by updating from database for the first case. The user cannot commit changes for an instance in the second or third case, but can update from database for both cases.

The following is the list of icons used in the synchronization dialog:

Icon	Applicable actions	Note
	Update from DB, Commit to DB, Show Comparison	New changes in local instance only
	Update from DB, Show Comparison	New changes in database instance only
	Update from DB, Show Comparison	New changes in both local and database instances
	Commit to DB	New local instance
	Update from DB, Commit to DB	Local instance is deleted but still exists in the database
	Update from DB, Commit to DB, Clear Record	Database instance is deleted but still exists in the local

WHAT DO I DO IF THE CURATOR TOOL FLAGS INSTANCES AS BEING DUPLICATED IN GK_CENTRAL

You will need to evaluate each instance that is flagged as being a duplicate and compare it to the instance that is flagged in gk_central. This is easiest to do before synchronizing your project with the database as described below:

Search the local project for all database instances that contain '-', then highlight each one in turn, right-click to open a pop-up menu, and choose "match instance in DB". Any results returned by that query are already-existing instances that, by the rules of gk_central, are duplicated by the new local instance. Mostly, that's right and you should accept the option offered by the form, to replace the local instance in the local project with the already-existing one from gk_central. That cleanly gets rid of the duplication and preserves all references correctly in the local project and in gk_central. Sometimes (rarely) the form is wrong because, despite identical defining attributes, two instances are genuinely different, e.g., if a person instance has already been created for J(ohn) Doe and you have now created one for J(ane) Doe. In this case, you should refuse the offer made by the form and should make a note to force the new instance into gk_central at synchronize-and-commit time.

WHAT TO DO IF THE CURATOR TOOL REPORTS AN EXCEPTION WHEN COMMITTING A PROJECT

In the event that an exception is reported by the curator tool during the commit to gk_central, this may be the result of a dropped connection with the database. Try to rerun the synchronization. If any conflicts in instances are revealed (this should be rare), send Guanming the project and explanation of the problem. If, after resynchronizing and attempting to commit again, if you still get an exception, verify that you have a connection to the database. If no connection is available, try the commit again when the connection is reestablished. Contact Guanming if there are any problems.

PROBLEM OF COMMIT SIZE

Usually as a curator in a team, you want to make many small commits instead of one big chunk. The reason is to minimize the chance of other curators changing the database entities while you are working on them. Resolving these conflicts is much easier with small project files

Solution: selected rewrite

After checking a project file for correctness the Reactome editor synchronizes the local project with the database. Here conflicts with commits of other curators become visible, and a list of DB_IDs that are in conflict is presented. Instead of rewriting the whole project file, the external curator can follow these steps:

-
- Refresh your view of the gk_central (menu Database-->Database Browser-->...)
- Select the conflicting entities, one by one, in your project file (not in the database)
- Right-click on an instance with the conflict, select "Update from DB"—this resets the instance to the version in the current database
- Re-enter your work on that reset instance
- save the project file with a different name
- Repeat above three steps for each instance with a conflict.
- Commit project.

THE ANNOTATION PROCESS FOR TRADITIONAL REACTOME PATHWAYS

Note that this section refers to “traditional” Reactome pathway. The annotation of a special class of pathways referred to as Cell Lineage Paths is described in detail in a separate section below.

Create the framework for the pathway(s) you intend to curate before filling in the details. Start by creating a pathway, add to this new or existing reactions in the correct order, complete the summations and literature citations, then identify the EWASs, Complexes, Sets etc. required and complete the details of the reactions consecutively. Cascading signaling processes can involve very complicated Complexes, in these circumstances

the Graphic Display in Entity Hierarchical View is very useful as an overview of the order of events.

PRECURATION

1. Create a basic outline of pathway: Regulation of Apoptosis as an example. Further description of the annotation process will focus on the subpathway highlighted below in yellow.

I. Regulation of Apoptosis

II. Regulation of activated PAK-2p34 by proteasome mediated degradation

IIa Ubiquitination of PAK-2p34

IIb Proteasome mediated degradation of PAK-2p34

III. Regulation of PAK-2p34 activity by PS-GAP/RHG10

IIIa. Rho GTPase-activating protein 10 (RHG10) interacts with caspase-activated PAK-2p34

IIIb. Interaction of PAK-2p34 with RHG10/ PS-GAP results in accumulation of PAK-2p34 in the perinuclear region

IV. Role of DCC in regulating apoptosis

IVa. Caspase cleavage of DCC

IVb. DCC interacts with DIP13alpha

IVc. Caspase-9 binds DCC:DIP13alpha complex

IVd. Activation of caspase-3

IVe. Caspase cleavage of UNC5B

IVf. DAPK binds UNC5B

IVg Caspase cleavage of UNC5A

IVh UNC5A binds NRAGE

2. Flesh out outline with information including: molecules, compartment, species, text summary, references (PMIDs)

Text Summary
 Cell compartment
 Inference

Species
 PMID
 GO term

II. Regulation of activated PAK-2p34 by proteasome mediated degradation **PMID:12853446**

Summary

Stimulation of cell death by PAK-2 requires the generation and stabilization of the caspase-activated form, PAK-2p34 (Walther et al., 1998 PMID: 9786869 ;Jakobi et al., 2003 PMID: 12853446). Levels of proteolytically activated PAK-2p34 protein are controlled by ubiquitin-mediated proteolysis. PAK-2p34 but not full-length PAK-2 is degraded by the 26 S proteasome (Jakobi et al., 2003). It is not known whether ubiquitination and degradation of PAK-2p34 occurs in the cytoplasm or in the nucleus.

Ia Ubiquitination of PAK-2p34 [cytosol]

phospho-PAK-2p34 (Thr 402) [cytosol] + Ubiquitin [cytosol] => phospho-PAK-2p34:Ubiquitin [cytosol] complex

Catalyst: unknown ubiquitin ligase

GO:0004842 Ubiquitin protein ligase activity

Inferred: *Oryctolagus cuniculus*, *Homo sapiens* PMID: 12853446

phospho-PAK-2p34 (Thr 402) (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) [cytosol] + Ubiquitin (*human*) [cytosol] => phospho-PAK-2p34 (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*):Ubiquitin (*human*) [cytosol] complex

Summary

PAK-2p34 is ubiquitinated prior degradation (Jakobi et al., 2003 PMID: 12853446). Here, ubiquitination of PAK-2p34 is described as occurring in the cytosol. However, to date it is not known whether this occurs in the nucleus or in the cytoplasm. Evidence for this reaction comes from experiments using both human and rabbit proteins.

Ib Proteasome mediated degradation of PAK-2p34 [cytosol]

PAK-2p34:ubiquitin [cytosol] => ubiquitin [cytosol]

catalyst =ubiquitin ligase [cytosol]

GO:0004175 Endopeptidase activity

Inferred: *Oryctolagus cuniculus*, *Homo sapiens* PMID: 12853446

PAK-2p34:ubiquitin (*human*,*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) [cytosol] => ubiquitin (*human*) [cytosol]

catalyst =ubiquitin ligase [cytosol]

GO:0004175 Endopeptidase activity

Summary

Proteolytically activated PAK-2p34, but not full-length PAK-2, is degraded rapidly by the proteasome (Jakobi et al., 2003 PMID: 12853446). Here, degradation of PAK-2p34 is described as occurring in the cytosol. However, to date it is not known whether this occurs in the nucleus or in the cytoplasm.

3. Create table of molecules participating in the pathway

- Each modified form of a protein as a separate entry
- Look up/enter corresponding UniProtID identifiers

	A	B
1	Molecule	Uniprot ID
2	Graf-2/ Arhgap10	A1A4S6
3	Death-associated protein kinase 3 DAPK3 DAPK3_HUMAN DAPK3	O43293
4	DCC's fragment with the ADD domain (fragment)	P43146
5	DCC DCC_HUMAN Netrin receptor DCC	P43146
6	DCC's inhibitory C-terminal domain (fragment)	P43146
7	Death-associated protein kinase 1 DAPK1 DAPK1_HUMAN DAPK1	P53355
8	phospho-PAK-2p34 (Thr 402)	Q13177
9	UNC5C	O95185-1
10	UNC5A fragment with death domain	Q6ZN44
11	UNC5A Netrin receptor UNC5A UN5A_HUMAN	Q6ZN44
12	UNC5B fragment with death domain	Q8IZJ1
13	UNC5B Netrin receptor UNC5B UN5B_HUMAN	Q8IZJ1
14	Death-associated protein kinase 2 DAPK2 DAPK2_HUMAN DAPK2	Q9UIK4
15	DCC-interacting protein 13-alpha DP13A_HUMAN APPL1	Q9UKG1
16	NRAGE Melanoma-associated antigen D1 MGD1_HUMAN MAGED▶	Q9Y5V3
17	unidentified caspase	unknown
18	Ubiquitin ligase	unknown
19	DAPKs	Candidate set
20	ubiquitin	Defined set

DATA ENTRY

IDENTIFY EXISTING PROTEINS/MOLECULES

In many cases the proteins on your list will already exist in the database. You should make every effort to reuse existing instances wherever possible to avoid unnecessary and confusing duplications. Use the curator tool to search the ReferenceGeneProduct (RGP) class using Uniprot identifiers as follows:

Searching the database

Choose Class: ReferenceGeneProduct

Choose attribute: identifier

Attribute value: Use REGEXP

Enter your identifier in the search box. You can enter several as a pipe separated list (e.g A1A4S6|O43293|P43146|P43146....).

Classes

- ⊙ DatabaseObject [1144084]
 - ▼ ⊙ AbstractModifiedResidue [14037]
 - ▼ ⊙ GeneticallyModifiedResidue [5545]
 - ▼ ⊙ FragmentModification [2190]
 - ⊙ FragmentDeletionModification [99]
 - ⊙ FragmentInsertionModification [153]
 - ⊙ FragmentReplacedModification [1938]
 - ▼ ⊙ ReplacedResidue [3355]
 - ⊙ NonsenseMutation [1140]
 - ▼ ⊙ TranscriptionalModification [48]
 - ⊙ ModifiedNucleotide [48]
 - ▼ ⊙ TranslationalModification [8444]
 - ▼ ⊙ CrosslinkedResidue [275]
 - ⊙ InterChainCrosslinkedResidue [147]
 - ⊙ IntraChainCrosslinkedResidue [128]
 - ⊙ GroupModifiedResidue [2063]
 - ⊙ ModifiedResidue [6106]
 - ⊙ Affiliation [356]
 - ⊙ CatalystActivity [11397]
 - ▼ ⊙ ControlReference [4194]
 - ⊙ CatalystActivityReference [1314]
 - ⊙ MarkerReference [304]
 - ⊙ RegulationReference [2576]
 - > ⊙ ControlledVocabulary [34]
 - ⊙ DatabaseIdentifier [72047]
 - ⊙ EntityFunctionalStatus [922]
 - ▼ ⊙ Event [35185]
 - ⊙ InteractionEvent [0]
 - ▼ ⊙ Pathway [5585]
 - ⊙ CellLineagePath [105]
 - ▼ ⊙ ReactionlikeEvent [29600]

Search Instances

Choose Class: ReferenceGeneProduct 6|O43293|P43146|Q13177|P53355

Select the ReferenceGeneProduct (RGP) returned, if a list select them one at a time, right click and opt to "View referrers". The resulting Referrers Dialog box lists Referrers by property name. At the top of the list can be isoforms of the protein, if present in Uniprot. Do not use isoforms unless you are certain that only specific isoforms have the functionality you intend to represent. Isoforms may have their own referrers and you should check this - if someone took the trouble to create an isoform-specific EWAS they probably had good reason to do so. Items listed with the property name referenceEntity are EntitiesWithAccessionedSequence (EWASs), a Reactome identifier for specific forms/locations of a protein. Often there will be more than one EWAS for a single RGP, because post-translationally modified forms of proteins and proteins in different cellular compartments are each represented by a different EWAS. If any of the listed EWASs correspond to your needs, right click and opt to "Check Out" that referrer. If the correct molecular compartment or post-translationally modified form is not present, you can still check out an EWAS and later use the Curator tool to clone it and modify it to your needs.

The screenshot shows the Reactome Curator interface. On the left, a 'Classes' tree is expanded to 'ReferenceGeneProduct'. Below it, a 'Search Instances' dialog is open, showing a search for 'ReferenceGeneProduct' with the attribute 'identifier' and value 'A1A456|O43293'. The main window displays a list of 'Found instances of ReferenceGeneProduct: 11', including UniProt:O43293 DAPK3. A 'Referrers Dialog' box is open, showing 'UniProt:O43293 DAPK3's Referrers'. The dialog lists referrers with their property names and values. A context menu is open over the 'referenceEntity' row, with 'Check out' selected. On the right, the 'ReferenceGeneProduct Properties' table is visible, showing details for UniProt:O43293 DAPK3, including its identifier, species (Homo sapiens), and various annotations.

Property Name	Value
identifier	O43293
referenceDatabase	UniProt
species	Homo sapiens
DB_ID	88737
_chainChangeLog	chain:1-454 added on Fri F...
_displayName	UniProt:O43293 DAPK3
chain	chain:1-454
checksum	56773008A6A61CF0
comment	FUNCTION Serine/threonine...
created	
crossReference	
description	recommendedName: Death...
geneName	DAPK3
isSequenceChanged	false
keyword	3D-structure Activator Alternative splicing Apoptosis ATP-binding Chromatin regulator Cytoplasm Kinase Nucleotide-binding Nucleus Phosphoprotein Reference proteome Serine/threonine-protein ki... Transcription Transcription regulation Transferase Translation regulation Tumor suppressor
modified	Weiser, Joel, 2023-05-25 Weiser, Joel, 2023-11-03
name	DAPK3

CREATE NEW PROTEINS/MOLECULES

Please see the guidelines on naming entities in this [paper](#) (Jupe et al, 2014)! If you search for a RGP that does NOT have referrers in the database you will get this message:

The screenshot shows the Reactome Schema View interface. On the left, a tree view of classes is visible, with 'ReferenceGeneProduct' selected. The main area displays a list of instances, with 'UniProt:O95185-1 UNC5C' highlighted. A dialog box titled 'Instance Refers' is open, displaying a message: 'There are no instances referring to the instance: [ReferenceIsoform:402105] UniProt:O95185-1 UNC5C'. The dialog box has an 'OK' button. On the right, a table of 'ReferenceIsoform Properties' is visible, showing various attributes and their values for the selected instance.

Property Name	Value
identifier	O95185
referenceDatabase	UniProt
species	Homo sapiens
variantIdentifier	O95185-1
DB_ID	402105
_chainChangeLog	signal peptide:1-40 a...
_displayName	UniProt:O95185-1 UN...
chain	signal peptide:1-40 chain:41-931
sum	98A95995129532A7
parent	FUNCTION Receptor fo...
id	Schmidt, EE, 2009...
Reference	
option	recommendedName: ...
name	UNC5C
name	UNC5H3
referenceChang...	false
parent	UniProt:O95185 U...
keyword	Alternative splicing Alzheimer disease Amyloidosis Apoptosis Cell membrane Cell projection Developmental protein Disulfide bond Glycoprotein Immunoglobulin domain Membrane Neurodegeneration Phosphoprotein Receptor Reference proteome Repeat Signal Synapse

In this case, you will need to create the EWAS.

Creating a new EWAS

To do this, first check out the RGP of interest into your local project. Then, in the curator tool, select RGP in the class list, then scroll or search for the RGP of interest. Right click and opt to create EWAS from RGP.

It will ask if you want to accept the end coordinates described by Uniprot. Only say yes if you can confirm them to be accurate. If the end coordinates are not certain, the convention is to represent the start as 1, and end as -1.

In the newly created EWAS, the ReferenceEntity will have a name and species entered by default. You can add an alternative name if this was specified by the Author, do this by right-clicking on the existing name and select Add. You must define the compartment. To do this, right click in the compartment slot and select the correct compartment in your local repository. Select the compartment and hit OK. If you don't see the desired compartment in your local project, click the "Browse database" button

to search in gk_central. **If you still don't find the necessary compartment, DO NOT create a new one. Contact the managing editor. New compartment creation requires multiple steps as well as changes in the UI which need to be coordinated with developers.**

References

1. Jupe S, Jassal B, Williams M, Wu G. A controlled vocabulary for pathway entities and events. Database (Oxford). 2014 Jun 20;2014:bau060. doi: 10.1093/database/bau060. PMID: 24951798; PMCID: PMC4064568.

Translational modifications (see note [below](#) about how to make sure all PTMs register correctly in diagrams):

If the protein you want to represent with an EWAS is **post-translationally modified**, then the hasModifiedResidue slot of the EWAS is to be filled. Right clicking on the hasModifiedResidue slot of the EWAS will allow you to select a modification instance from one of the 3 child subclasses of the 'TranslationalModification' class, namely ModifiedResidue, GroupModifiedResidue and CrosslinkedResidue. You will be prompted to choose from your local project, browse gk_central or create a new modified residue instance. Almost always you will want to create a new instance, as modified

residue instances are specific to the RGP and residue position. If EWAS instances are created from the same RGP but belong to two or more cellular compartments, then these EWASs, e.g., EWAS (cytosol) and EWAS (nucleoplasm), may share modified residue instances when modified at the same residue.

- *ModifiedResidue:*

This instance is added to EWAS to indicate that a chemical group such as phosphate or methyl group is added to an amino acid residue of a protein. Two mandatory slots need filling for a modifiedResidue instance - psiMod and referenceSequence. For example, to indicate that CDC25A protein has a phospho-serine modification at residue 124 you need to right click in the hasModifiedResidue slot of the EWAS, then select 'Add' from drop-down list and choose ModifiedResidue as a schema class in the pop-up window. Then, click on the 'New Instance' button to open a 'Create a New Instance' form. Right click in the PsiMod slot of the modification instance to select O-phospho-L-serine [MOD:00046] as a modification type and hit ok (a modification type can be found within the local repository or by searching the gk_central database).

If a needed modification is not already present in gk_central, look up its identifier (a five-digit number) at the PSI-MOD website; copy-paste it into the "create new instance" form in the curator tool, and allow the wizard associated with the form to retrieve all other needed data from PSI-MOD. Once created, such an instance (like all other reference instances in gk_central) should not be modified. If an instance is needed that is not already in PSI-MOD, or if a PSI-MOD instance appears to be incorrect, contact PSI-MOD to resolve the problem.

Similarly, right clicking in the ReferenceSequence slot of the modification instance allows selecting RGP with Uniprot identifier for CDC25A protein. Finally, enter the residue number 124 in the coordinate slot and hit ok.

Note that the curator tool does not prevent you from adding a modifiedResidue instance with one ReferenceGeneProduct onto the EWAS record with a different ReferenceGeneProduct, and the confusion that results is substantial!

The modified residue instance can now be applied to the EWAS by clicking ok.

The modified EWAS is shown below. Make sure that the EWAS name is edited to reflect the modification, e.g., p-S124-CDC25A.

[EntityWithAccessionedSequence:69588] p-S124-CDC25A [...]	
EntityWithAccessionedSequence Properties	
Property Name	Value
cellType	
compartment	cytosol
endCoordinate	524
hasModifiedResidue	O-phospho-L-serine at 124
referenceEntity	UniProt:P30304 CDC25A
startCoordinate	1
DB_ID	69588
_displayName	p-S124-CDC25A [cytosol]
authored	
created	
crossReference	
definition	
disease	
edited	
figure	
goCellularComponent	
inferredFrom	
inferredTo	
literatureReference	
modified	Schmidt, EE, 2004-06-09 05:34:08
	Matthews, L, 2004-12-30 22:28:30
	Wu, G, 2013-02-13
	Wu, G, 2013-05-03
	Wu, G, 2013-05-03
	D'Eustachio, Peter, 2022-12-28
name	p-S124-CDC25A
	phospho-Cdc25A
	M-phase inducer phosphatase 1
	Dual specificity phosphatase Cdc25A
reviewed	
revised	
species	Homo sapiens
stableIdentifier	R-HSA-69588.2
summation	
systematicName	

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- *GroupModifiedResidue (GMR)*

This instance is linked to EWAS instance to indicate that a protein has a modification formed by attachment of two (or more) either peptide or chemical moieties. 3 mandatory slots need filling in a GMR instance - modification, psiMod and referenceSequence. For example, GMR is extensively used to annotate EWASs in protein glycosylation process that involves stepwise addition of sugar moieties, attached to an amino acid residue of a protein. In the synthesis of several GAGs, the 4 sugar moieties, i.e., xylose (Xyl), 2 x galactose (Gal) and glucuronic acid (GlcA), are added in a stepwise fashion. The first reaction is the addition of Xyl to a Ser residue. The product, a protein with a Xyl-modified Ser residue, is represented by EWAS with a modifiedResidue instance where psiMod slot value is O-xylosyl-Ser [MOD:00814]. The second reaction requires Gal to be attached to O-xylosyl-Ser to form the protein product with Gal-Xyl-yl group attached to Ser. Right click in the hasModifiedResidue slot of the EWAS instance and select GroupModifiedResidue class. In the modification instance right click in the modification slot and add 'beta-D-Gal-(1->4)-beta-D-Xyl-yl group' [ChEBI:63502] as a referenceGroup. The psiMod slot still needs to be filled with O-xylosyl-Ser [MOD:00814]. Enter the Uniprot identifier for the ReferenceGeneproduct in the ReferenceSequence slot. GMR may also be linked to an EWAS instance to indicate that a protein is modified by attaching polypeptide chains such as polyUb or polySUMO. Polypeptide chain instances are selected from the Polymer class and added in the modification slot in GMR.

- *CrosslinkedResidue*

This instance is linked to a target EWAS instance to annotate disulfide, thioester, mono-sumoylated lysine, monoubiquitinated lysine or other protein crosslinks, where two

coordinates describe a modification. The "crosslinkedResidues" subclass has two child classes - IntraChainCrosslinkedResidue and InterChainCrosslinkedResidue.

1. **IntraChainCrosslinkedResidue**

is a value of hasModifiedResidues slots in EWAS records used to annotate crosslinking within the same amino acid sequence. The attributes and requirements are similar to those of ModifiedResidue, but it also includes a secondCoordinate slot.

2. **InterChainCrosslinkedResidue**

To indicate that two different peptide chains are crosslinked you create an InterChainCrosslinkedResidue instance for each corresponding EWAS instance of these two proteins. The interchain modification instances are linked by having each other as values in their equivalentTo slots. There are 4 mandatory slots - psiMod, referenceSequence, secondReferenceSequence and equivalentTo. For example, to indicate that disulfide bond occurs between Cys343 of DHH and Cys53 of P4HB, two interChainCrosslinkedResidue instances are needed, one instance for modified DHH, the second instance for modified P4HB protein. Right click in the hasModifiedResidue slot of EWAS of modified DHH protein and select InterChainCrosslinkedResidue class. Then, right click in the referenceSequence slot of the modification instance and enter RGP with UniProt identifier 'UniProt:O43323 DHH'. A modified cysteine residue involved in the disulfide bond can be described as a half cystine (MOD:00798 , DB_ID 448182). Enter half cystine [MOD:00798] as a modification type in the psiMod slot. Enter half-cystyl group as a reference group value in the modification slot (optional). Enter 343 in the coordinate slot to state that DHH protein has a half cystyl group at position 343. Enter 53 in the secondCoordinate slot and RGP with identifier 'UniProt:P07237 P4HB' in the secondReferenceSequence slot to state the position on the second amino acid sequence. Repeat these steps for EWAS of modified P4HB but enter 53 as a coordinate value and select RGP with identifier 'UniProt:P07237 P4HB' in the referenceSequence slot, while secondCoordinate value is 343 and secondReferenceSequence value is RGP with the identifier 'UniProt:O43323 DHH'. Finally, right click in the equivalentTo slot of the first instance (linked to EWAS of modified DHH) and select the other one that is linked to EWAS of modified P4HB. Similarly, enter the first instance as a value in the equivalentTo slot of the second one.

3. In the event that you are creating a crosslink between two monomers of the same protein, create one InterChainCrosslinkedResidue instance and indicate that the referenceSequence and secondReferenceSequence are the same as are the coordinate and secondCoordinate.

The image displays four panels from the Proteome Discoverer software, showing protein and crosslink data. The top-left panel shows the properties for an entity with accessioned sequence 5358299, identified as N4glycoAsn-HC-DHH(23-396) in the endoplasmic reticulum lumen. The top-right panel shows the properties for an entity with accessioned sequence 5358298, identified as HC-P4HB(DHH) in the endoplasmic reticulum lumen. The bottom-left panel shows the properties for an inter-chain crosslink at residues 343 and 53, with a second reference sequence UniProt:P07237 P4HB. The bottom-right panel shows the properties for an inter-chain crosslink at residues 53 and 343, with a second reference sequence UniProt:043323 DHH. Each panel includes a table of properties such as cellType, compartment, endCoordinate, hasModifiedResidue, referenceEntity, startCoordinate, DB ID, and displayName.

Reactome does not aim to describe all disulfide bonds in all proteins. Curators may choose to annotate disulfide bonds at their discretion when, for example, the bonds or bonding process may be involved in a disease, may regulate the protein's activity, or may be required to hold a complex together.

If you are annotating a protein fragment, you can define the start and end coordinates of the fragment as shown below: Don't forget to change the default name to indicate that it is a fragment.

***To be sure that all PTMS get added correctly to the reactions in diagrams** you have to first make sure you have downloaded TranslationalModifications fully in your project. In the schema view, choose that class to get the whole list of these instances. Select all in the middle list and then select "Update Instances" from the popup menu. Then go to the diagram, right click, and select the option "update node features". Say yes to the question "instances must be fully downloaded, do you want to continue, yes no".

CREATING A COMPLEX

This is done in one of two ways. Either:

Go to the Schema view, select Complex, right-click and select Create Instance. The Create a New Instance dialog box appears. Enter a name in the field for Name. Typically you would also enter the *Compartment, Species and identify the entities (EWASs, sets or complexes) that make up this complex using the field hasComponent. All of these fields are completed by either double-clicking to type, or right clicking to select Add and identify the correct item from the local project.

- *We record two location attributes for every complex. The "core compartment" (the place most closely associated with the function of the complex) will be entered into the compartment slot. This slot will be made single-valued and will be filled manually. All of the "other" compartments of the participating components will be automatically added in the "includedLocation" attribute of the complex at the time of database slicing for release.

Example: Complexes that have component(s) localized to membrane as well as component(s) localized to other adjacent compartments should have the membrane

listed in the "Compartment" slot . The other compartments would be assigned automatically.

CREATING A SET

Reactome has several types of set - refer to the Glossary and User Guide for definitions.

The most commonly used sets are Defined Sets and Candidate Sets.

Defined Set members should be proven equivalents, i.e. all of them have been demonstrated to perform the function that is described by the event they participate in.

Candidate Sets have two categories of inclusion, members, equivalent to defined set members, and candidates, members that are not proven to be functionally equivalent, but are believed to be equivalent based on phylogeny, domain structure etc.

Creating sets is a similar process for all subtypes, select the appropriate type in the Schema view, right-click and select Create Instance, fill in the Name and Species, right click to add the set members.

- All members of a set must have the same compartment. The only time a set can have multiple compartment attributes is if its members themselves all have the same multiple compartment attributes, e.g., a set of membrane-spanning complexes with components explicitly located [on this side], in the membrane, and [on that side].
- The members or candidates of a set should (in most cases) belong to the same class...e.g all EWASs or all simpleEntities or all Complexes. However, there are exceptions under circumstances in which structurally different entities are really functionally indistinguishable (i.e either a monomer or dimer can function in a particular reaction). Since these exceptions are likely to be fairly rare, a QA check is in place to flag sets that have members that are from different classes. The ids of such exceptional acceptable sets may be forwarded to the editorial release manager to be put on a QA skip list.

Using sets

Representing outputs that include sets: When representing the output of a reaction:

Set [A, A', A''] + EWAS B

Use the 'set-to -complex' approach: Set [A, A', A''] + EWAS B → Complex (Set [A, A', A'']:EWAS B), where no individual complex entities are created for the reaction. Entity of the individual complex (for example A:B) will be created if we need to functionally distinguish the potential output complex somewhere else in the diagram. The same dashed lines used to link an EntitySet and its contained members will be used to link the individual complex A:B to Complex (Set [A, A', A'']:EWAS B).

Use of isOrdered attribute:

CREATING A PATHWAY

Please see *note* [below](#) if you are adding a pathway that will be a new top level pathway. Here is a description of how the outlined mini pathway "Regulation of activated PAK-2p34 by proteasome mediated degradation" is built from its component events in the curator tool. The pathway consists of 2 reactions: "Ubiquitination of PAK-2p34" and "Proteasome mediated degradation of PAK-2p34". For simplicity, the reactions have already been created (see section on creating [inferred](#) reactions for an example.)

II. Regulation of activated PAK-2p34 by proteasome mediated degradation PMID: 12853446

Summary

Stimulation of cell death by PAK-2 requires the generation and stabilization of the caspase-activated form, PAK-2p34 (Walter et al., 1998 PMID: 9786869; Jakobi et al., 2003 PMID: 12853446). Levels of proteolytically activated PAK-2p34 protein are controlled by ubiquitin-mediated proteolysis. PAK-2p34 but not full-length PAK-2 is degraded by the 26 S proteasome (Jakobi et al., 2003). It is not known whether ubiquitination and degradation of PAK-2p34 occurs in the cytoplasm or in the nucleus.

IIa Ubiquitination of PAK-2p34 [cytosol]

phospho-PAK-2p34 (Thr 402) [cytosol] + Ubiquitin [cytosol] => phospho-PAK-2p34:Ubiquitin [cytosol] complex

Catalyst: unknown ubiquitin ligase

GO:0004642 Ubiquitin protein ligase activity

Refered: *Oryctolagus cuniculus*, *Homo sapiens* PMID: 12853446

phospho-PAK-2p34 (Thr 402) (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) [cytosol] + Ubiquitin (*human*) [cytosol] => phospho-PAK-2p34 (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*):Ubiquitin (*human*) [cytosol] complex

Summary

PAK-2p34 is ubiquitinated prior to degradation (Jakobi et al., 2003 PMID: 12853446). Here, ubiquitination of PAK-2p34 is described as occurring in the cytosol. However, to date it is not known whether this occurs in the nucleus or in the cytoplasm. Evidence for this reaction comes from experiments using both human and rabbit proteins.

IIb Proteasome mediated degradation of PAK-2p34 [cytosol]

PAK-2p34:ubiquitin [cytosol] => ubiquitin [cytosol]

catalyst =ubiquitin ligase [cytosol]

GO:0004175 Endopeptidase activity

Refered: *Oryctolagus cuniculus*, *Homo sapiens* PMID: 12853446

PAK-2p34:ubiquitin (*human*, *Oryctolagus cuniculus*) [cytosol] => ubiquitin (*human*) [cytosol]

catalyst =ubiquitin ligase [cytosol]

GO:0004175 Endopeptidase activity

Summary

Proteolytically activated PAK-2p34, but not full-length PAK-2, is degraded rapidly by the proteasome (Jakobi et al., 2003 PMID: 12853446). Here, degradation of PAK-2p34 is described as occurring in the cytosol. However, to date it is not known whether this occurs in the nucleus or in the cytoplasm.

With the pathway class highlighted in the class hierarchy, right click and select Create instance, or use the create instance button in the menu bar at the top of the tool.

After adding the pathway title, associate reactions as component events of the pathway by right clicking on the hasEvent slot and selecting "Add"

Properties: [Pathway:- 1] Regulation of activated PAK-2p34 by proteasome mediated degradati...

Pathway Properties

Property Name	Value
name	Regulation of activated PAK-2p34 by proteasome mediated degradation
releaseDate	
species	
summation	
authored	
compartment	
edited	
hasEvent	
reviewed	
_doRelease	
crossReference	
definition	
doi	
evidenceType	
figure	
goBiologicalProcess	
inferredFrom	
isCanonical	
literatureReference	
orthologousEvent	
precedingEvent	
revised	
DB_ID	-1
_displayName	Regulation of activated PAK-2p34 by proteasome mediated degradation
created	
modified	
stableIdentifier	

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You can then select the events that you need one at a time or, as a shortcut, you can search for your newly created events in your project if they have not yet been submitted to gk_central (they will all have DB_ID attributes that are negative). To do this, search in your project for events with DB_ID containing - . From this list, you can hold the control key and select the events of interest.

The order of the events in a pathway is described through the use of the "precedingEvent" attribute on the reactions that are components of the pathway. If/when no preceding events are specified, the order of the events displayed on the webpage reflects the order in which they are listed as components in the pathway instance that you are creating. Curators should check for precedingEvents that they may have missed within a pathway diagram by using the "Infer reaction relationship" curator tool feature (described in more detail [here](#), Appendix C7). This feature can be accessed by right-clicking in a diagram. Here, the curator is offered a list of preceding events based on shared entities. The curator can then opt to approve a preceding event, in which case that reaction is automatically entered into the appropriate reaction's precedingEvent attribute. If the curator decides the precedingEvent is not biologically relevant, it can be rejected with a reason for the rejection specified. This "rejection" of a preceding event is recorded in the "negativePrecedingEvent" attribute for the reaction.

Properties: [Pathway:- 1] Regulation of activated PAK-2p34 by proteasome mediated degradati...

Pathway Properties

Property Name	Value
name	Regulation of activated PAK-2p34 by proteasome mediated degradation
releaseDate	
species	Homo sapiens
summation	Stimulation of cell death by PAK-2 requires the generation ...
authored	
compartment	
edited	Matthews, L, 2011-01-15
hasEvent	Proteasome mediated degradation of PAK-2p34
	Ubiquitination of PAK-2p34
reviewed	
_doRelease	
crossReference	
definition	
doi	
evidenceType	
figure	
goBiologicalProcess	
inferredFrom	
isCanonical	
literatureReference	Caspase-activated PAK-2 is regulated by subcellular targeting and pro...
	Cleavage and activation of p21-activated protein kinase gamma-PAK b...
orthologousEvent	
precedingEvent	
revised	
DB_ID	-1
_displayName	Regulation of activated PAK-2p34 by proteasome mediated degradation
created	
modified	

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Once the component events have been added, the remaining required attributes are added. Identify a GO Biological process (BP) term that corresponds to your pathway, find the corresponding GO_BiologicalProcess instance in gk_central, right click on the goBiologicalProcess slot and select set to add it. If you can't find the term of interest, double check with Peter or Lisa. If no term is available, you can use GOC GitHub Tracker to create a ticket to request a new term as described [here](#). When suggesting a GO term, be sure to look over the guidelines described [here](#) (<https://github.com/geneontology/go-ontology/blob/master/CONTRIBUTING.md>) and

include label (name), definition, references, and position in hierarchy. **Never** create a new GO term instance yourself in gk_central!

- note: If you are creating a top level pathway(check with Peter if this is appropriate), it must be listed as frontPage item. To do this, check out the frontPage instance from gk_central and add your pathways in the frontPageItem slot. Also please mark this in the editorial calendar as a front page item.

CREATING A REACTIONLIKEEVENT

There are subclasses of ReactionlikeEvent: Reaction, BlackBox, Polymerization, Depolymerization, FailedReaction, and CellDevelopmentStep. The latter two will be covered in the Disease and the Cell Lineage Path annotation sections of this guide.

Like all other classes, you can create a new reaction by selecting the Reaction class in the Schema view, right-click and select Create Instance, but it is perhaps better practice and more intuitive to create new reactions inside a pathway. To do this, select a pathway in the Event Hierarchical View, select the hasEvent property name in the details panel on the right, right-click and select Add. This leads to a dialogue for providing details of the reaction.

When creating a reaction, first enter the name:

The dialog box is titled "Create a New Instance" and shows the "Reaction" schema class selected. Below the title bar is a section for "Reaction Properties" containing a table with the following data:

Property Name	Value
compartment	
input	
name	CYCS binds to APAF1
output	
releaseDate	
species	
summation	
authored	
catalystActivity	
edited	
literatureReference	
reviewed	
_doRelease	
catalystActivityReference	
crossReference	
definition	
disease	
entityFunctionalStatus	
entityOnOtherCell	
evidenceType	
figure	
goBiologicalProcess	
hasInteraction	
inferredFrom	
internalReviewed	
isChimeric	false
negativePrecedingEvent	

At the bottom of the dialog are "OK" and "Cancel" buttons.

This may be enough detail for the moment, if you are simply creating a placeholder click OK.

To set the species of the reaction right click and select add in the species field.

If the species that you happen to be working with is not in your local project you can opt to search for it in the database using the "Browse Database" Button in the dialog box. When you set/change the species or the compartment of a reaction, it will ask if you want to propagate the species/compartment to all of the component molecules as well.

Use caution when selecting Yes. Generally, this is **ONLY** done when you have just created (but not committed) all of the entities used in the reaction. **ONLY** say yes here if you know that event and contained molecules have no referrers in the database that would be affected. (In other words **ALL** other reactions or complexes or sets in the db that make use of these now "changed" molecules would be affected).

Next add the compartment to the reaction. Right click in the compartment box and select add.

Again if you don't have the compartment you need in your project, you can Browse Database to find the one you need. ***If you still don't find the necessary compartment, DO NOT create a new one. Contact the managing editor. New compartment creation requires multiple steps as well as changes in the UI which need to be coordinated with developers.***

Now add the input and output molecules. Right click in the respective box and select "Add".

Select the molecule from the appropriate class:

Select Instance for input

Please choose instances from the instance list:

Local Schema View

Allowed Classes

- PhysicalEntity [5925]
 - Cell [0]
 - Complex [2059]
 - Drug [22]
 - ChemicalDrug [20]

Search Instances

Choose Class:

Choose Attribute:

Attribute Value:

Complex: 2059

- APAF1:ADP [cytosol]
- APAF1:ATP [cytosol]
- APAF1:ATP:CYCS [cytosol]
- APAF1:ATP:CYCS heptamer:CASP9 [cyt...
- APAF1:ATP:CYCS heptamer:p-T412-C...
- APAF1:AVEN [cytosol]
- APAF1:CYCS [cytosol]
- APAF1:CYCS:ATP:APIP [cytosol]
- APAF1:CYCS:ATP:CASP9(1-416)dimer
- APAF1:CYCS:CASP9:XIAP:DIABLO [cyto...
- APLN:Apelin peptides [plasma memt...
- ARBS:AGTR1 [plasma membrane]
- ARF1/3:GTP:PI4KB [Golgi membrane]
- ARF1:GTP [Golgi membrane]
- ARF3:GTP [Golgi membrane]
- ATM dimer:KAT5 [nucleoplasm]
- ATP6V [endosome membrane]

Complex Properties

Property Name	Value
cellType	
hasComponent	1 x ADP [cytosol]
	1 x APAF1 [cytosol]
DB_ID	9627055
_displayName	APAF1:ADP [cytosol]
authored	
compartment	cytosol
created	Shamovsky, Veronic...
crossReference	
definition	
disease	
edited	
entityOnOtherCell	
figure	
goCellularCompon...	
includedLocation	

Selected Instances:

Instances	Cardinality
[Complex:9627055] APAF1:ADP [cytosol]	1
[SimpleEntity:113592] ATP [cytosol]	1
[EntityWithAccessionedSequence:53259] CYCS [...]	1

Select Instance for input

Please choose instances from the instance list:

Local Schema View

Allowed Classes

- CandidateSet [114]
- DefinedSet [546]
- GenomeEncodedEntity [2714]
- EntityWithAccessionedSequence [2697]
- OtherEntity [21]

Search Instances

Choose Class:

Choose Attribute:

Attribute Value:

GenomeEncodedEntity: 2714

- CYCS [cytosol]
- CYCS [mitochondrial intermembrane s...
- CYSLTR1 [plasma membrane]
- CYSLTR2 [plasma membrane]
- Calmodulin [cytosol]
- Camk4 [cytosol]
- Camk4 [nucleoplasm]
- Camk4 [nucleoplasm]
- Camkk1 [nucleoplasm]
- Clock [cytosol]
- Clock gene [nucleoplasm]
- Creb1 [nucleoplasm]
- Crk [cytosol]
- DAPK1 [cytosol]
- DAPK2 [cytosol]
- DAPK3 [cytosol]
- DPF4 [nucleoplasm]

EntityWithAccessionedSequence Properties

Property Name	Value
cellType	
compartment	cytosol
endCoordinate	105
hasModifiedResidue	
referenceEntity	UniProt:P99999 CYCS
startCoordinate	2
DB_ID	53259
_displayName	CYCS [cytosol]
authored	
created	
crossReference	
definition	
disease	
edited	
figure	
goCellularCompon...	

Selected Instances:

Instances	Cardinality
[EntityWithAccessionedSequence:53259] CYCS [...]	1

Important: After adding your input and output molecules, it is important to verify that your reaction is balanced (all molecules represented as input are also present as output). See the QA section below for a description of how to do this.

Add the literature reference(s). The references associated with a reaction **MUST** provide direct experimental evidence for the occurrence of that reaction in the species you are annotating (i.e. human for human Reactome). If there is no direct experimental evidence in human then you need to create an inferred human reaction as described in the section below. Enter the PMID for journal articles, and say yes when prompted to have the details filled in automatically.

Select Instance for literatureReference

Please choose instances from the instance list:

Local Schema View

Allowed Classes

- Publication [159]
 - Book [0]
 - LiteratureReference [159]
 - URL [0]

Found instances of LiteratureReference: 0

Properties

Property Name	Value
---------------	-------

Search Instances

Choose Class: LiteratureReference

Choose Attribute: pubMedIdentifier

Attribute Value: Equals 9267021

Search Search More...

Selected Instances:

Instances	Cardinality
-----------	-------------

New Instance

Browse Database

OK Cancel

If you don't see the reference in your local repository then opt to Browse Database.

If you can't find the literature reference in the database either, then you need to create a new one:

Enter the PMID (number only). Click out of the PMID box. You will be asked if you want

to import the PMID record information. Say yes.

Choose a schema class:

Specify properties for new instance:

Property Name	Value
pubMedIdentifier	19801675
DB_ID	-18
_displayName	
author	
created	
journal	
modified	
pages	

Fetching Information?

 Do you want to fetch other information for the specified PMID?

You will now see the full record:

Create a New Instance

Choose a schema class:

LiteratureReference Properties

Property Name	Value
pubMedIdentifier	19801675
DB_ID	-18
_displayName	A new model for the transition of AP...
author	Reubold, TF
	Wohlgemuth, S
	Eschenburg, S
created	
journal	J Biol Chem
modified	
pages	32717-24
stableIdentifier	
title	A new model for the transition of AP...
volume	284
year	2009

OK

Cancel

Look back in your local repository and you will see the new literature reference. You can now add this as a reference for your reaction.

The process is similar for adding other Publication types (Books and urls) with the exception that all information must be added manually - there is no automatic import.

To make a Publication record for a book, all information must be entered manually: author(s), title, year (mandatory attributes), ISBN, title, chapterTitle, pages (optional) as shown:

[Book:9816605] 9780071624961 Brooks, Geo F Chapter 32. Adenoviruses Jawetz, Melnick & Adel...	
Book Properties	
Property Name	Value
ISBN	9780071624961
author	Brooks, Geo F Carroll, Karen C Butel, Janet S Morse, Stephen A Mietzner, Timothy A
chapterTitle	Chapter 32. Adenoviruses
title	Jawetz, Melnick & Adelberg's Medical Microbiology, Twent...
DB_ID	9816605
_displayName	9780071624961 Brooks, Geo F Chapter 32. Adenoviruse...
chapterAuthors	Butel, Janet S
created	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2022-09-12
modified	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2022-09-13
pages	423-432
publisher	McGraw Hill
stableIdentifier	
year	2010

The image below shows an example of a Publication record for a url; again, information must be entered manually.

[URL:9845236] https://www.cdc.gov/media/releases/2023/s0629-rsv.html	
URL Properties	
Property Name	Value
uniformResourceLocator	https://www.cdc.gov/media/releases/2023/s0629-rsv.html
DB_ID	9845236
_displayName	https://www.cdc.gov/media/releases/2023/s0629-rsv.html
author	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention USA, CDC
created	Stephan, Ralf, 2023-09-29
modified	
stableIdentifier	
title	CDC Recommends RSV Vaccine For Older Adults

There is some discretionary latitude in what can be entered as the url title and author. The title may be the heading on the page itself, as in the case below:

[Newsroom Home](#)

[CDC Newsroom Releases](#)

CDC Recommends RSV Vaccine For Older Adults

[Print](#)

Media Statement

For Immediate Release: Thursday, June 29, 2023

Contact: [Media Relations](#)

(404) 639-3286

CDC Director Rochelle P. Walensky, M.D., M.P.H., endorsed the CDC Advisory Committee on Immunization Practices' (ACIP) recommendations for use of new Respiratory Syncytial Virus

If in doubt, consult gk_central for existing records for similar urls.

Once you have added your references, you can add a text summary for the reaction in the "summation"slot. Right click and select add.

Schema View Event Hierarchical View Entity Level View

Classes

- EntityFunctionalStatus [1]
- Event [1727]
 - InteractionEvent [0]
 - Pathway [60]
 - CellLineagePath [0]
 - ReactionlikeEvent [1667]
 - BlackBoxEvent [174]
 - CellDevelopmentStep [0]
 - Depolymerisation [0]
 - FailedReaction [1]
 - Polymerisation [3]
 - Reaction [1489]
- ExternalOntology [46]
 - Anatomy [0]
 - CellType [2]
 - Disease [29]
 - EvidenceType [0]
 - PsiMod [15]
 - SequenceOntology [0]
 - Figure [59]
 - FrontPage [0]
 - FunctionalStatus [1]
 - FunctionalStatusType [0]
 - GO_BiologicalProcess [42]
 - GO_CellularComponent [85]

Search Instances

Choose Class:

Choose Attribute:

Attribute Value:

Found instances of Reaction: 3 Show Settings

- APAF1:CYCS binds APIP
- APAF1:CYCS binds to APAF1**
- CYCS:APAF1 binds procaspase-9

Reaction Properties

Property Name	Value
compartment	cytosol
input	1 x APAF1:ADP [cytosol] 1 x ATP [cytosol] 1 x CYCS [cytosol]
name	CYCS binds to APAF1
output	1 x ADP [cytosol] 1 x APAF1:ATP:CYCS [cytosol]
releaseDate	2004-10-27
species	Homo sapiens
summation	
author	Shamovs...
catalystActivity	Apaf-1...
edited	Apaf-1...
literatureReference	Changes...
reviewed	Matthews...
doRelease	true
catalystActivityReference	
crossReference	
definition	
disease	
entityFunctionalStatus	
entityOnOtherCell	
evidenceType	
figure	
goBiologicalProcess	
hasInteraction	
inferredFrom	
internalReviewed	
isChimeric	
negativePrecedingEvent	
normalReaction	
orthologousEvent	
precedingEvent	TP53 stimulates APAF1 gene expression Release of Cytochrome c from mitoch...
previousReviewStatus	
reactionType	

Select Instance for summation

Please choose instances from the instance list:

Local Schema View

Allowed Classes

- Summation [1568]

Search Instances

Choose Cl...:

Choose At...:

Attribute ...:

Summation: 1568

- DNA fragmentation in res...
- Farnesyltransferase/gera...
- MAPK p38 alpha activate...
- 14-3-3 proteins bind BAI...
- 5-hydroxytryptamine rece...
- A DNA damage-independ...
- A Src family kinase (Lyn) p...
- A costimulatory signal invc...
- A dimer of T1R2 and T1R...
- A fluorescence-activated c...
- A fluorescence-activated c...
- A group of inositol phosph...
- A group of phospholipase...
- A major known function of...

Properties

Pr... Va...

Selected Instances:

Instances	Cardinality

Create a New Instance

Choose a schema class:

Summation Properties

Property Name	Value
text	
DB_ID	-7
_displayName	
created	
literatureReference	
modified	
stableIdentifier	

Then input your text and citations.

Input a New text

The apoptotic protease-activating factor 1 (APAF1) is a cytosolic multidomain adapter protein containing an N-terminal caspase recruitment domain (CARD), followed by a central nucleotide-binding & oligomerization domain (NOD, also known as NB-ARC) and a C-terminal regulatory region with WD40 repeats which form the 7- and 8-bladed β -propellers (Inohara N and Nunez G 2003; Danot O et al. 2009; Yuan S et al. 2011). Under steady-state, non-apoptotic conditions, APAF1 exists as an ADP-bound, autoinhibited monomer (Riedl SJ et al. 2005; Reubold TF et al. 2009). During apoptosis, cytochrome c (CYCS) is released from the mitochondrial intermembrane space to the cytosol where it binds APAF1 between the two WD40 repeat domains in the C-terminal regulatory region (Zou et al. 1997; Liu X et al. 1996; Shalaeva DN et al. 2015; Zhou M et al. 2015). CYCS binding causes an upward rotation of the β -propeller region which is accompanied by conformational changes in APAF1 and the replacement of ADP by dATP or ATP triggering APAF1 oligomerization into a heptameric, wheel-shaped signaling platform (Acehan D et al. 2002; Yu X et al. 2005, Kim HE et al. 2005; Yuan S et al. 2010, 2013; Li P et al. 1997; Jiang X & Wang X 2000; Zhou M et al. 2015). Moreover, the N-terminal CARD in the inactive APAF1 monomer is not shielded from other proteins by β -propellers. Hence, the APAF1 CARD may be free to interact with a procaspase-9 CARD either before or during apoptosome assembly (Yuan S et al. 2013). Physiological concentrations of calcium ion negatively affect the assembly of apoptosome and activation of CASP9 by inhibiting nucleotide exchange in the monomeric, autoinhibited APAF1 (Bao Q et al. 2007).

OK
Cancel

Associate the references associated with the citations in the text summary using the "LiteratureReference" slot for the summation as described above for reactions.

Properties: [Summation:-7] The apoptotic protease-activating factor 1 (AP...

Property Name	Value
text	The apoptotic protease-activating factor 1 (APAF1) is a cytosolic ...
DB_ID	-7
_displayName	The apoptotic protease-activating factor 1 (APAF1) is a cyto...
created	
literatureReference	Apaf-1, a human protein homologous to C. elegans CED-4, pa...
	Apaf-1: Regulation and function in cell death
	A new model for the transition of APAF-1 from inactive monom...
modified	
stableIdentifier	

Once the mandatory attributes have been filled, enter the remaining required attributes. Right click on edited to choose an instanceEdit from your project.

Reaction Properties: [Reaction: 2] CYCS binds to APAF1

Property Name	Value
compartment	cytosol
input	1 x APAF1:ADP [cytosol]
	1 x ATP [cytosol]
	1 x CYCS [cytosol]
name	CYCS binds to APAF1
output	1 x ADP [cytosol]
	1 x APAF1:ATP:CYCS [cytosol]
releaseDate	
species	Homo sapiens
summation	The apoptotic protease-activating factor 1 (APAF1) is ...
authored	
catalystActivity	
edited	
literatureReference	Apaf-1, a human protein homologous to C. elegans CE...
	Apaf-1: Regulation and function in cell death
	Changes in Apaf-1 conformation that drive apoptosom...
reviewed	
_doRelease	
catalystActivityReference	
crossReference	
definition	
disease	
entityFunctionalStatus	
entityOnOtherCell	
evidenceType	
figure	
goBiologicalProcess	
hasInteraction	
inferredFrom	
internalReviewed	
isChimeric	false
negativePrecedingEvent	
normalReaction	
orthologousEvent	
precedingEvent	
previousReviewStatus	
reactionType	

If you haven't created one previously, opt to create a new one by clicking on the New Instance button.

Then right click on author to select a person. If you don't see the one you want locally, browse the database. The edited slot holds the name of the curator that should be credited with creating and editing the event and the date it was edited. This slot is filled with an instanceedit instance that contains this information.

A date time stamp is created automatically for that instanceEdit and clicking "OK" will add this instanceEdit to the edited slot in your reaction.

Create a New Instance

Choose a schema class: InstanceEdit

InstanceEdit Properties

Property Name	Value
DB_ID	-24
_displayName	Matthews, L, 2011-01-15
author	Matthews, L
created	
dateTime	20110115141738
modified	
note	
stableIdentifier	

OK Cancel

The authored and reviewed slots hold the instanceEdits describing the author/reviewer and dates of authoring/reviewing respectively. If a module has an external author (and no external reviewer) the author should be listed in both the authored and reviewed attribute. (These are created as described above for the "editor" slot. When the reaction is read for release, the do_Release flag should be set to TRUE and the releaseDate slot should be filled with the appropriate release date.

Property Name	Value
cytosol	
1 x APAF1:ADP [cytosol]	
	1 x ATP [cytosol]
	1 x CYCS [cytosol]
name	CYCS binds to APAF1
1 x ADP [cytosol]	
	1 x APAF1:ATP:CYCS [cytosol]
releaseDate	
Homo sapiens	
The apoptotic protease-activating factor 1 (APAF1) is...	
authored	
catalystActivity	
Matthews, L, 2011-01-15	
Apaf-1, a human protein homologous to C. elegans ...	
	Apaf-1: Regulation and function in cell death
	Changes in Apaf-1 conformation that drive apoptoso...
reviewed	
_doRelease	
catalystActivityReference	
crossReference	
definition	
disease	
entityFunctionalStatus	
entityOnOtherCell	
evidenceType	
figure	
goBiologicalProcess	
hasInteraction	
inferredFrom	
internalReviewed	
isChimeric	false
negativePrecedingEvent	
normalReaction	
orthologousEvent	

Important: After adding your input and output molecules, it is important to verify that your reaction is balanced (all molecules represented as input are also present as output). See the QA section below for a description of how to do this.

When you can define preceding events for an event it should be done. One precision on that point is that a preceding event for a reaction should always be a reaction/reaction like event and not a pathway and the preceding event for a pathway should be another pathway when relevant and not a reaction or reaction like event.

Creating an inferred event

When constructing a human pathway, a curator will come across events that have no direct experimental evidence in humans, but have supporting experimental data from another/other species. If experts in the field believe that the event can in fact occur in humans, the 'other species event' can be used to infer the human event. In the case below a human reaction is inferred from in vitro experimental results using proteins from human and *Oryctolagus cuniculus* (rabbit).

The reaction "Proteosome mediated degradation of PAK-2p34" is created and the species *Homo sapiens* and *Oryctolagus cuniculus* are assigned

Reaction Properties	
Property Name	Value
catalystActivity	
input	
output	
DB_ID	-2
_displayName	Ubiquitination of PAK-2p34
_doRelease	
authored	
compartment	cytosol
created	
crossReference	
definition	
edited	Matthews, L, 2011-01-15
entityOnOtherCell	
evidenceType	
figure	
goBiologicalProcess	
hasMember	
inferredFrom	
isChimeric	true
literatureReference	Caspase-activated PAK-2 is regulated by subcellular t...
modified	
name	Ubiquitination of PAK-2p34
orthologousEvent	
precedingEvent	
releaseDate	
requiredInputComponent	
reverseReaction	
reviewed	
revised	
species	Oryctolagus cuniculus Homo sapiens
stableIdentifier	
summation	PAK-2p34 is ubiquitinated prior to degradation (Jakobi...

@Local Repository

To avoid having a human and a non-human reaction with identical names, it can be useful to use capitalized forms of object names for the non-human reaction and all-uppercase names for human, e.g. Jak2 and JAK2 for the non-human and human proteins respectively. A text summary and the literature reference providing evidence for this mixed species reaction is added.

The rabbit protein "PAK-2p34" is selected as an input

The human set "ubiquitin" is selected as an input...

...and the mixed species output complex "PAK-2p34" is selected as the output.

Note that this complex is not natural, it only occurs in vitro. To flag this the complex "isChimeric" attribute is set to True.

Select Instance for output

Please choose instances from the instance list:

Local Schema View

Allowed Classes

- PhysicalEntity [387]
 - Complex [69]
 - EntitySet [15]
 - CandidateSet [5]
 - DefinedSet [10]
 - OpenSet [0]
- GenomeEncodedEntity [272]
 - EntityWithAccessionedSequence [264]
- OtherEntity [2]
- Polymer [2]
- SimpleEntity [7]

Search Instances

Choose Class: Complex

Choose Attribute: DB_ID

Attribute Value: Equals

Search Search More...

Complex: 89

- active caspase-3 [cytosol]
- active caspase-6 [cytosol]
- active caspase-6 [nucleoplasm]
- active caspase-7 [cytosol]
- active caspase-7 [nucleoplasm]
- caspase-3-cleaved DFF45 (117,224):DFF40 complex [nucleoplasm]
- importin-alpha:importin-beta [cytosol]
- importin-alpha:importin-beta complex [nucleoplasm]
- perinuclear PAK-2p34:PS-GAP complex [cytosol]
- perinuclear PAK-2p34:RHG10 complex [cytosol]
- phospho-Pak2 (Thr-402, Ser-141): Cdc42-GTP complex [endoplasmic reticulum]
- phospho-Pak2 (Thr-402, Ser-141): Cdc42-GTP complex [endoplasmic reticulum]
- phospho-dynein(DLC1) on microtubules [plasma membrane]
- phospho-dynein(DLC2) on microtubules [plasma membrane]
- polyubiquitinated PAK-2p34 [cytosol]
- polyubiquitinated PAK-2p34 [cytosol]
- tbid bound to inactive BAK (mitochondrial outer membrane)
- tbid bound to inactive BAX [cytosol]
- tbid:BCL-2 [mitochondrial outer membrane]
- ubiquitinated PAK-2p34 [cytosol]
- ubiquitinated PAK-2p34 [cytosol]

Complex Properties

Property Name	Value
entityOnOtherCell	
figure	
goCellularComp...	
hasDomain	
hasInstance	
inferredFrom	
inferredTo	
isChimeric	true
literatureRefere...	
modified	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mathews, L, 2008... Mathews, L, 2008... Mathews, L, 2008... Mathews, L, 2010...
name	ubiquitinated PAK-2p34
reviewed	
revised	
shortName	
species	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Homo sapiens Oryctolagus cunic...
stableIdentifier	REACT_14287.1
summation	

Selected Instances:

Instances	Cardinality
[Complex:211713] ubiquitinated PAK-2p34 [cytosol]	1

New Instance

Browse Database

OK Cancel

Since the reaction is also multispecies and not a natural event, the isChimera flag is also set to true for the reaction.

Properties: [Reaction:-2] Ubiquitination of PAK-2p34

Reaction Properties

Property Name	Value
input	PAK-2p34 [cytosol] ubiquitin [cytosol]
name	Ubiquitination of PAK-2p34
output	
species	Oryctolagus cuniculus Homo sapiens
summation	PAK-2p34 is ubiquitinated prior to degradation (Jakobi et al...)
authored	
catalystActivity	
compartment	cytosol
edited	Matthews, L, 2011-01-15
literatureReference	Caspase-activated PAK-2 is regulated by subcellular targeting and prot...
reviewed	
_doRelease	
crossReference	
definition	
entityOnOtherCell	
evidenceType	
figure	
goBiologicalProcess	
hasMember	
inferredFrom	
isChimeric	true
orthologousEvent	
precedingEvent	true
requiredInputComponent	false
reverseReaction	
revised	
DB_ID	-2
_displayName	Ubiquitination of PAK-2p34
created	
modified	
releaseDate	
stableIdentifier	

@Local Repository

Now that the reaction to be used for inference has been created, create the same reaction for human, using human participating molecules. In the "inferredFrom" field, right click and select "Add" to enter the non-human reaction used for inference. Add literature references and summation as usual.

Properties: [Reaction:-4] Ubiquitination of PAK-2p34

Reaction Properties

Property Name	Value
input	ubiquitin [cytosol] PAK-2p34 [cytosol]
name	Ubiquitination of PAK-2p34
output	polyubiquitinated PAK-2p34 [cytosol]
species	Homo sapiens
summation	PAK-2p34 is ubiquitinated prior to degradation (Jakobi et al...)
authored	
catalystActivity	
compartment	cytosol
edited	Matthews, L, 2011-01-15
literatureReference	
reviewed	
_doRelease	
crossReference	
definition	
entityOnOtherCell	
evidenceType	
figure	
goBiologicalProcess	
hasMember	
inferredFrom	
isChimeric	true
orthologousEvent	
precedingEvent	
requiredInputComponent	
reverseReaction	
revised	
DB_ID	-4
_displayName	Ubiquitination of PAK-2p34
created	
modified	
releaseDate	
stableIdentifier	

@Local Repository

Selecting the mixed species reaction created previously...

...now the link to the inferred reaction has been made.

Properties: [Reaction:-4] Ubiquitination of PAK-2p34

Reaction Properties

Property Name	Value
catalystActivity	
input	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ubiquitin [cytosol] PAK-2p34 [cytosol]
output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> polyubiquitinated PAK-2p34 [cytosol]
DB_ID	-4
_displayName	Ubiquitination of PAK-2p34
_doRelease	
authored	
compartment	cytosol
created	
crossReference	
definition	
edited	Matthews, L, 2011-01-15
entityOnOtherCell	
evidenceType	
figure	
goBiologicalProcess	
hasMember	
inferredFrom	Ubiquitination of PAK-2p34
isChimeric	true
literatureReference	Caspase-activated PAK-2 is regulated by subcellular targeting an...
modified	
name	Ubiquitination of PAK-2p34
orthologousEvent	
precedingEvent	
releaseDate	
requiredInputComponent	
reverseReaction	
reviewed	
revised	
species	Homo sapiens
stableIdentifier	
summation	PAK-2p34 is ubiquitinated prior to degradation (Jakobi et al...

@Local Repository

- Note also that if your annotations involve a species that is new to Reactome, please contact Peter D'Eustachio as it will need to have an abbreviation assigned by him.

CREATING A CATALYST

Reactions that involve a catalyst should include this information. Within the Reaction Details, the field is called `catalystActivity`. To complete this you need two things: the physicalEntity or object that is acting as catalyst, and the Activity of that object, defined as a GO molecular function. If the catalyst is a complex and there is a specific component of the complex that has the catalytic activity, that component must be specified in the "activeUnit" attribute. Note that if there if the whole complex acts as the

catalyst or the component that is acting is not known, this attribute should be left blank. The PhysicalEntity itself should never be listed as the activeUnit. The physicalEntity will be a molecule or set or complex probably in your local project. The GO molecular function can be identified by consulting Uniprot, look at the ontologies section for GO Molecular Function. If none of the listed terms seems to be appropriate, either Browse Database for terms in gk_central, or use the OLS website at <http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ontology-lookup/> to identify the correct term first. Use the most specific term possible.

CREATING A NEW CHEBI ENTRY

See also [Best Practices: Using Chemical Compound Databases](#), Appendix C8 .

Using SMILES strings as input for the ChEBI submission tool

To use the submission tool, you must get a user name and password, and log in. Go [here](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/chebi/submission/login) (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/chebi/submission/login>) to do that. Once you have logged in, click "create a new submission" from the choices at the bottom of the page. That will cause a new line to appear in the table of "your active submissions" on that page. Click the "edit submission" option on that line to open the actual submission form. Under the 'Name And Structure' section of the Submission tool, select 'Edit Structure'. Under the 'Edit' Menu, select 'Import Name'.

An input box named 'The Source – Name' appears, this is the place to paste your SMILES string.

In this example, the following string for 1-PP-IP5 is used:

```
OP(O)(=O)O[C@H]1[C@H](OP(O)(O)=O)[C@@H](OP(O)(O)=O)[C@H](OP(O)(=O)OP(O)(O)=O)[C@H](OP(O)(O)=O)[C@@H]1OP(O)(O)=O
```


After the SMILES string has been pasted, select the 'File' menu in 'The Source – Name' input box. Select 'Import As'. Maybe displace circle or enlarge so as not to hide word "File" in menu

Make sure 'Import as Recognized (SMILES)' Import Mode has been selected and click on 'Import'.

The chemical structure defined by the SMILES string should now be present in the box, ready for editing. Press 'Update structure' to obtain details of the structure.

Edit ChEBI Submission

[Name and Structure*](#) [Cross-References](#) [Synonyms](#) [Ontology](#) [Preview and Submit*](#)

i To complete this step in the submission process, you must enter a name. You must also enter a structure or definition (or both).

[View Structure](#) [Edit Structure](#)

File Edit View Insert Atom Bond Structure Tools Help

Update structure

ChEBI name **ChEBI Name is required**

Definition

Formula

InChI

InChIKey

SMILES

Mass

Charge

Save changes Cancel and return Save and return

Structure details are now displayed on the right of the page. The structure on the left hand side can now be edited as you wish.

CREATING A NEW SPECIES

If a curator needs to create a new "species" instance for their annotation, please contact the Editor-in-Chief, Peter D'Eustachio as it will need to have an abbreviation assigned by him. the superTaxon slot must* be filled with the "taxon" instance from gk_central **corresponding to the genus of the new species** as specified in the NCBI taxonomy entry for the species. For the bacterial species *Bacillus thermoproteolyticus*, that genus taxon is *Bacillus*, so that instance should be imported into the local project and used to fill the superTaxon slot for the new species. If the genus taxon does not exist, then the curator should create it. It too has a superTaxon slot which must be filled with the taxon corresponding to the appropriate family as given in the NCBI taxonomy. This process continues to the root of all life. Note that taxonomists use more levels than the simple kingdom - phylum - class - family - genus - species list. All of the levels shown in NCBI should be instantiated in gk_central for a species.

ANNOTATING THE REGULATION OF A PROCESS

The following organization of regulation events works well for many kinds of processes, and it fits with our view that all parts of a process should be grouped while respecting GO's view that regulatory events should be distinguishable from the rest of the process.

All about [process] (pathway) --The steps of [process] (pathway)

[process]reaction 1

[process] reaction 2

etc.

--Regulation of [process] (pathway)

[process] regulatory reaction 1

[process regulatory reaction 2

etc.

Regulation here can include reactions that are themselves concrete molecular transformations whose effect is to modulate one of the main process reactions by activating an enzyme, or providing or sequestering an input molecule but can also include airy things like "[this regulatory event] by an unknown molecular mechanism positively or negatively regulates [process reaction #] . Note that regulation instances contain a "regulator", activity, and activeUnit. Regulation instances are associated with RLEs through the regulatedBy attribute of the RLE. We should show the RLE within the pathway that is being regulated. The reason for this is that we want to be as specific as possible about the molecular mechanism of the regulation. Annotating Gene Expression:

As far as gene expression regulation is concerned, note that:

- Even if the regulation is at the transcriptional level, show the protein as the output, since we are a protein-oriented database, and we assume that mRNA will get translated into a protein.
- Only show mRNA as the output of the transcription BBE only if this mRNA can be used as an input for another reaction – mainly regulation by microRNAs.
-

A detailed description of how to annotate regulation of gene expression is described below.

NOTE: *When considering which type of evidence to use when creating events in Reactome, note that you should NOT include events based solely on microarray, proteomics or similar high throughput data, unless either 1) an expert author has indicated that they believe the results are correct and represent the current consensus, or 2) The results are a meta-data analysis that combines several independent studies to show the overlap between them.*

Regulation where direct binding of a transcription factor to a regulatory sequence of a target gene has been demonstrated.

At least two of the following three criteria need to be met to create gene expression events and regulatory instances of this type:

1. Presence of specific transcription factor binding elements in regulatory regions of the target gene and/or demonstration of physical association of transcription factor with target gene DNA via chromatin immunoprecipitation (ChIP) or electrophoretic mobility shift assay (EMSA)
2. Evidence that the amount of a transcription factor (altered by overexpression from a recombinant vector and/or downregulation by gene deletion, targeted mutation and/or RNA interference) correlates with the level of target gene expression as measured by luciferase reporter assays and/or quantitative RT-PCR
3. Evidence that disruptive mutations of the transcription factor DNA binding sites in regulatory regions of a target gene affect target gene expression.

For this type of regulation we annotate the binding reaction between transcription factor and target gene. In the following example, the transcription factor is the MTF1 dimer bound to zinc ions (MTF1 dimer:12Zn²⁺). This transcription factor binds to the CSRP1 gene:

Reaction Properties	
Property Name	Value
catalystActivity	
entityFunctionalStatus	
input	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 x CSRP1 gene [nucleoplasm] 1 x MTF1 dimer:12Zn2+ [nucleoplasm]
output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 x MTF1 dimer:12Zn2+:CSRP1 gene...
DB_ID	5660514
_displayName	MTF1 dimer:12Zn2+ binds CSRP1 gene
_doRelease	true
authored	May, Bruce, 2014-12-27
catalystActivityReference	
compartment	nucleoplasm
created	May, Bruce, 2015-01-04
crossReference	
definition	
disease	
edited	May, Bruce, 2014-12-27
entityOnOtherCell	
evidenceType	
figure	
goBiologicalProcess	
hasInteraction	
inferredFrom	Mtf1 dimer:12Zn2+ binds Csrp1 g...
internalReviewed	
isChimeric	false
literatureReference	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> May, Bruce, 2015-03-15 Wu, G, 2016-07-15 May, Bruce, 2017-01-27 Matthews, Lisa, 2023-03-08
modified	
name	MTF1 dimer:12Zn2+ binds CSRP1 gene
negativePrecedingEvent	
normalReaction	
orthologousEvent	
precedingEvent	MTF1 dimer:12Zn2+ translocates f...
previousReviewStatus	
reactionType	
regulatedBy	
regulationReference	
relatedSpecies	
releaseDate	2017-03-27
releaseStatus	
requiredInputComponent	
reverseReaction	
reviewStatus	five stars
reviewed	Ford, Dianne, 2017-01-27
revised	
species	Homo sapiens
stableIdentifier	R-HSA-5660514.2
structureModified	
summation	As inferred from the mouse homol...
systematicName	

This transcription factor to DNA binding reaction is subsequently defined as a preceding event for the gene expression black box event, where input is a gene and the output is either a protein or an mRNA. In the following example, the input is the CSRP1 gene, and the output is protein CSRP1. Please note the preceding event:

BlackBoxEvent Properties

Property Name	Value
deletedInstanceDB_ID	
entityFunctionalStatus	
1 x CSRP1 gene [nucleoplasm]	
1 x CSRP1 [nucleoplasm]	
DB_ID	5660503
_displayName	Expression of CSRP1
_doRelease	true
May, Bruce, 2014-12-27	
catalystActivity	
catalystActivityReference	
nucleoplasm	
May, Bruce, 2015-01-04	
crossReference	
definition	
deletedStableIdentifier	
disease	
May, Bruce, 2014-12-27	
entityOnOtherCell	
evidenceType	
figure	
goBiologicalProcess	
hasInteraction	
Expression of Csrp1	
internalReviewed	
isChimeric	false
Matthews, Lisa, 2023-03-08	
modified	
name	Expression of CSRP1
negativePrecedingEvent	
normalReaction	
orthologousEvent	
MTF1 dimer:12Zn2+ binds CSRP1 gene	
previousReviewStatus	
reactionType	
Positive gene expression regulation by...	
Positive gene expression regulation by...	
relatedSpecies	

Regulation, in cases where regulator is a complex of transcription factor and target gene, is annotated as a **PositiveGeneExpressionRegulation' or a NegativeGeneExpressionRegulation:**

● ● ● [PositiveGeneExpressionRegulation:5660542] Positive gene expression regulati...

PositiveGeneExpressionRegulation Properties	
Property Name	Value
activeUnit	
activity	
regulator	MTF1 dimer:12Zn2+:CSRP1 gene [nucleoplas...
DB_ID	5660542
_displayName	Positive gene expression regulation by 'MTF1 di...
created	May, Bruce, 2015-01-04
goBiologicalProcess	
	May, Bruce, 2015-03-23
	Wu, G, 2016-07-15
modified	Wu, G, 2016-07-15
	Wu, G, 2018-05-08
	Wu, Guanming, 2021-06-04
stableIdentifier	R-HSA-5660542.1
summation	

This is how this two-step CSRP1 gene expression regulation (transcription factor binding to DNA, followed by gene expression black box event) looks like in a pathway diagram:

From a computational modelling standpoint, when a regulator is a complex of a transcription factor and its target gene, it is important to define the **activeUnit of the regulation instance**. For example, TP53 negatively regulates BIRC5 gene expression by binding to the BIRC5 gene promoter. The regulator of the NegativeGeneExpressionRegulation instance is the complex of TP53 and BIRC5 gene (p-S15,S20-TP53 Tetramer:BIRC5 gene). Since the BIRC5 gene is both an input and a

component of the negative regulator of the gene expression black box event, computational modelling tools may predict that increased copy number of the BIRC5 gene results in a decreased amount of BIRC5 protein. If TP53 is annotated as the activeUnit of the negativeGeneExpressionRegulation instance, this computational problem is prevented:

gk_central@curator.reactome.org - Schema View

Found instances of Reactio... **Show Settings** BlackBoxEvent Properties

- ⚙️ CUL9:RBX1 ubiquitinates BIRC5
- ⚙️ TP53 binds the BIRC5 gene
- ⚙️ TP53 inhibits BIRC5 expression

Property Name	Value
entityFunctionalStatus	
input	1 x BIRC5 Gene [nucleoplasm]
output	1 x BIRC5 [nucleoplasm]
DB ID	6797763
	TP53 inhibits BIRC5 expression
	true
	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2015-1...
	nucleoplasm
	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2015-0...
	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2015-1...
	false
	Transcriptional repression of t...
	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2015-1...
	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2016-0...
	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2016-0...
	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2017-0...
	Wu, G, 2018-04-19
	Wu, G, 2019-04-04
	Matthews, Lisa, 2023-03-08
	TP53 inhibits BIRC5 expression
	TP53 binds the BIRC5 gene
	Negative gene expression reg...
	Negative gene expression reg...

[NegativeGeneExpressionRegulation:6797757] Negative gene...

NegativeGeneExpressionRegulation Properties

Property Name	Value
activeUnit	p-S15,S20-TP53 Tetramer [nucleoplasm]
activity	
regulator	p-S15,S20-TP53 Tetramer:BIRC5 Gene [nucleopl...
DB ID	6797757
_displayName	Negative gene expression regulation by 'p-S15,S20-...
created	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2015-09-16
goBiologicalProcess	
	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2015-09-22
modified	Wu, G, 2016-07-15
	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2016-09-23
	Wu, G, 2018-05-08
stableIdentifier	R-HSA-6797757.1

@Database Repository

Property Name	Value
relatedSpecies	
releaseDate	2016-02-22

*Note that for regulatory events in which transcription factor(s) actually bind to an enhancer outside of the regulated gene, the annotation should still show binding of the transcription factor to the gene EWAS (and the gene coordinates should be set -1,1 regardless of gene size and how much of the regulatory region we are trying to capture).

If a translational regulation will be shown, e.g. via noncoding RNAs, then mRNA is annotated as the output of a gene expression black box event. If it is anticipated that a translational regulation will not be made presently but may be added in future releases, then a protein should be annotated as the output of a gene expression black box event that will act as a releasable "placeholder". In a later release, separate transcription and translation black box events will be made and substituted for the "placeholder" black box event. The "placeholder" black box event should be deleted with a deletion instance listing the new transcription and translation black box events as replacements.

Regulation where no direct binding of a regulator to a regulatory DNA sequence has been demonstrated.

For this type of annotation, one criterion needs to be met:

4. Evidence that the amount and/or the activity of a regulator (altered by overexpression from a recombinant vector and/or downregulation by gene deletion, targeted mutation, RNA interference and/or agonists/antagonists) correlates with the level of target gene expression measured by luciferase reporter assays and/or quantitative RT-PCR.

In this case, just a black box gene expression event is created. For example, FOXO3 positively regulates transcription of APP, but no direct binding of FOXO3 to the APP gene locus has been demonstrated:

gk_central@curator.reactome.org - Schema View

Found instances of ReactionBlockSettings BlackBoxEvent Properties

APP gene expression

entityFunctionalStatus

[PositiveRegulation:8870712] Positive regulatio...

PositiveRegulation Properties

Property Name	Value
activeUnit	
activity	
regulator	p-S43,S173,S294,S325-FOXO3 ...
DB_ID	8870712
_displayName	Positive regulation by 'p-S43,S173,S...
created	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2016-05-11
goBiologicalProcess	Wu, G, 2016-07-15 Wu, G, 2016-07-15 Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2016-08-12 Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2016-08-12 Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2017-05-30
modified	Wu, G, 2018-05-08
stableIdentifier	R-HSA-8870712.2

Property Name	Value
entityFunctionalStatus	1 x APP gene [nucleoplasm] 1 x APP(672-713) [extracellular region]
DB_ID	8870710
APP gene expression	true
Shah, Kavita, 2016-02-23	
extracellular region	
nucleoplasm	
Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2016-05-11	
Alzheimer's disease	
Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2016-05-11	
Cdk5-FOXO3a axis: initially neuroprotective, eventually neu...	
Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2016-05-11	
Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2016-05-11	
Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2016-05-11	
Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2016-05-12	
Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2016-06-01	
Wu, G, 2016-07-15	
Wu, G, 2018-04-19	
Wu, G, 2019-04-04	
Matthews, Lisa, 2023-03-08	
APP gene expression	
Phosphorylated FOXO3 translocates to the nucleus	
regulatedBy	Positive regulation by 'p-S43,S173,S294,S325-FOXO3 [nuc...
regulationReference	Positive regulation by 'p-S43,S173,S294,S325-FOXO3 [nuc...
relatedSpecies	
releaseDate	2016-09-19

@Database Repository

Regulation instance, when no direct transcription factor binding has been demonstrated, is captured as a general **positiveRegulation** or **negativeRegulation**:

This is how the one-step APP gene expression regulation looks in a pathway diagram:

Regulation of gene expression at the level of translation

mRNA translation into protein can be regulated by non-coding RNAs, such as microRNAs (miRNAs). We only annotate miRNAs for which direct binding to target mRNAs and regulation of protein expression has been experimentally validated by either:

5. A reporter assay, where the miRNA is combined with a reporter-fused 3'UTR of the mRNA and observed for altered levels of reporter expression;
6. Co-immunoprecipitation of the miRNA:mRNA complex, together with an assay demonstrating that the miRNA alters the levels of either the mRNA (qRT-PCR) or protein (western blot).

MicroRNAs are always shown to bind to target mRNAs in the context of the RISC complex. Two types of RISC complex exist: nonendonucleolytic RISC (interferes with translation without degrading target mRNA) and endonucleolytic RISC (degrades target mRNA to prevent translation). Composition of different RISCs and their interaction with

microRNAs is described in detail in the pathway [Gene Silencing by RNA](#) (R-HSA-211000):

- If an miRNA causes reduction of protein levels, but not mRNA levels of a target gene, it is annotated as a component of a nonendonucleolytic RISC.

The screenshot displays a hierarchical view of miR-26A RISC complexes. At the top is 'miR-26A Nonendonucleolytic RISC [cytosol]', which includes 'TNRC6 (GW182) [cytosol]' and 'MOV10 [cytosol]'. 'TNRC6 (GW182) [cytosol]' has members: 'TNRC6A [cytosol]', 'TNRC6B [cytosol]', and 'TNRC6C [cytosol]'. Below this is 'miR-26A Nonendonucleolytic Minimal RISC [cytosol]', which includes 'Nonendonucleolytic Argonaute [cytosol]' and 'miR-26A [cytosol]'. 'Nonendonucleolytic Argonaute [cytosol]' has members: 'EIF2C1 [cytosol]', 'EIF2C3 [cytosol]', and 'EIF2C4 [cytosol]'. 'miR-26A [cytosol]' has members: 'miR-26A1 [cytosol]' and 'miR-26A2 [cytosol]'.

- If an miRNA causes reduction of both mRNA and protein levels of a target gene, we usually annotate a RISC set where endonucleolytic RISC is a member and non-endonucleolytic RISC, depending on the experimental evidence, is either a candidate or a member.

The screenshot shows a detailed entry for 'miR-26A RISC [cytosol]' in Homo sapiens. It includes a 'Stable Identifier' of 'R-HSA-2318737.1' and a 'Cellular compartment' of 'cytosol'. Under the 'Members' section, two RISC complexes are listed: 'miR-26A Endonucleolytic RISC [cytosol]' and 'miR-26A Nonendonucleolytic RISC [cytosol]'. Each member entry is accompanied by a small icon representing a protein or complex.

If a non-endonucleolytic RISC for an miRNA of interest was definitely experimentally excluded, we would annotate the miRNA as a component of an endonucleolytic RISC only:

The screenshot displays a hierarchical view of biological annotations. At the top is 'miR-26A Endonucleolytic RISC [cytosol]', which includes 'TNRRC6 (GW182) [cytosol]' and 'MOV10 [cytosol]'. 'TNRRC6 (GW182) [cytosol]' further includes 'TNRRC6A [cytosol]', 'TNRRC6B [cytosol]', and 'TNRRC6C [cytosol]'. Below this is 'miR-26A Endonucleolytic Minimal RISC [cytosol]', which includes 'EIF2C2 [cytosol]' and 'miR-26A [cytosol]'. 'miR-26A [cytosol]' includes 'miR-26A1 [cytosol]' and 'miR-26A2 [cytosol]'. The interface uses expandable/collapsible boxes to show these relationships.

The easiest way to create endonucleolytic RISC and non-endonucleolytic RISC is by cloning an already annotated RISC complex and replacing the miRNA component of the clone by the miRNA of interest:

1. As there are over 100 miRNA RISC complexes in `gk_central`, please make sure that the specific RISC that you are trying to create does not already exist in the central repository.
2. Check out an existing human endonucleolytic and/or non-endonucleolytic RISC to your local project.
3. Note that both endonucleolytic RISC and non-endonucleolytic RISC are nested complexes, in which miRNA is a component of a subcomplex named “minimal endonucleolytic RISC” and “minimal non-endonucleolytic RISC”, respectively. Create separate clones of the minimal endonucleolytic RISC/minimal non-endonucleolytic RISC, and endonucleolytic RISC/non-endonucleolytic RISC, **declining the offer to clone contain subunits recursively**.
4. In the clone(s) of minimal endonucleolytic RISC/minimal non-endonucleolytic RISC, replace the miRNA component with your miRNA of interest. Rename the clone to reflect its new miRNA component.
5. In the clone(s) of endonucleolytic RISC/non-endonucleolytic RISC, replace the minimal endonucleolytic RISC/minimal non-endonucleolytic RISC components with cloned and edited minimal endonucleolytic RISC/minimal non-endonucleolytic RISC. Rename the clone to reflect its new minimal endonucleolytic RISC/minimal non-endonucleolytic RISC component.

Translational regulation of gene expression is annotated in two steps, with step1 defined as a preceding event of step2:

1. Binding of an inhibitor (e.g. miRNA-containing RISC complex) to a target mRNA (step1).

2. Gene expression black box event where mRNA is an input and protein is an output (step2).

Step2 BBE has regulatedBy attribute populated by a **negativeGeneExpressionRegulation** instance. The output of step1 is an inhibitor:mRNA complex, which is annotated as a negative regulator of step2. Again, from a computational modeling standpoint, when a regulator is a complex of an inhibitor and its target mRNA, it is important to define the **activeUnit of the regulation instance**. For example, miR-26A negatively regulates PTEN mRNA translation by binding to the 3'UTR of PTEN mRNA. The regulator of the NegativeGeneExpressionRegulation instance is the complex of PTEN mRNA and miR-26A RISC (PTEN mRNA:miR-26A RISC). Since PTEN mRNA is both an input and a component of the negative regulator of the translation black box event, computational modeling tools may predict that the increased level of PTEN mRNA results in a decreased amount of PTEN protein. If miR-26A RISC is annotated as the activeUnit of the negativeGeneExpressionRegulation instance, this computational problem is prevented:

NegativeGeneExpressionRegulation Properties	
Property Name	Value
activeUnit	miR-26A RISC [cytosol]
activity	
regulator	PTEN mRNA:miR-26A RISC [cytosol]
DB_ID	2321906
_displayName	Negative gene expression regulation by 'PTEN mRNA:miR-26A RISC [cytosol]'
created	Orlic-Milacic, M, 2012-06-18
goBiologicalProcess	
modified	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2016-08-19 Wu, G, 2018-05-08
stableIdentifier	R-HSA-2321906.1
summation	

DRAWING A PATHWAY DIAGRAM

Reactome pathway diagrams are drawn and viewed in the curator tool using the ELV pane of the tool.

Below is an example to show how the superpathway "Regulation of Apoptosis" is diagrammed and how it's parent pathway must also be modified in the process to reflect that a new navigable subpathway diagram now exists. These instructions are followed by important hints about revising existing diagrams.

Example of updating the parent of a pathway that has a new diagram

The pathway Regulation of Apoptosis is part of the supercanonical Apoptosis pathway. First, go to gk_central in the Event browser, find Apoptosis, right click and opt to "build project". In the curator tool entitylevel view, unfurl Apoptosis. In this example, you can tell that Regulation of Apoptosis has been annotated but not yet incorporated in the Apoptosis diagram because the pathway is greyed out in the event hierarchy.

Click on apoptosis and open the diagram.

The screenshot displays the Reactome Curator Tool interface. The title bar indicates the file path: `/Users/shamov01/DO_NOT_COMMIT_Apoptosis_images for the curator guide.rtpj - Reactome Curator Tool`. The interface is divided into several panels:

- Event Hierarchy:** Shows a tree view of biological events. The 'Apoptosis' category is selected, and its sub-items are: 'Caspase activation via extrinsic apoptotic', 'Intrinsic Pathway for Apoptosis', 'Apoptotic execution phase', 'Regulation of Apoptosis', and 'Arachidonate is oxidised to 15S-HpETE by ALC'. The 'Apoptosis' category is highlighted in blue.
- Complex Hierarchy:** Shows a hierarchical view of the selected pathway.
- Entity List:** Includes 'Overview' and 'Search Instances' tabs.
- Pathway Editor: Diagram of Apoptosis:** The main workspace showing a diagram of the apoptosis pathway. The diagram is contained within a large orange-bordered box representing the 'cytosol'. Inside this box, there are three smaller boxes: 'Caspase activation via extrinsic apoptotic signalling pathway' (top left), 'Intrinsic Pathway for Apoptosis' (top right), and 'Apoptotic execution phase' (bottom center). Arrows indicate the flow from the top two boxes to the bottom box. The diagram also shows the 'mitochondrial outer membrane' and 'nucleoplasm' as sub-compartments.

At the bottom of the Pathway Editor, there is a 'Slide to Zoom' control and two tabs: 'Graphic Editor' and 'Property Editor'.

To incorporate the Regulation of Apoptosis pathway into the Apoptosis diagram, simply click on, hold, and drag the pathway from the hierarchy to the diagram.

The screenshot displays the Reactome Curator Tool interface. On the left, the 'Event Hierarchy' panel shows a tree structure for 'Homo sapiens' with 'Regulation of Apoptosis' selected. Below it, the 'Complex Hierarchy' and 'Entity List' sections are visible. The main window, titled 'Pathway Editor: Diagram of Apoptosis', shows a detailed diagram of the apoptosis pathway. The diagram is organized into compartments: 'cytosol' (top), 'mitochondrial outer membrane' (middle), and 'nucleoplasm' (bottom). Key components include 'Caspase activation via extrinsic apoptotic signalling pathway', 'Intrinsic Pathway for Apoptosis', 'Apoptotic execution phase', and 'Regulation of Apoptosis'. Arrows indicate the flow of the pathway, and a 'Slide to Zoom' control is located at the bottom of the editor. The 'Graphic Editor' and 'Property Editor' tabs are also visible at the bottom.

Example: Create a diagram for Regulation of Apoptosis

Right click on pathway in the hierarchy or in the diagram and opt to "open diagram"

If one already exists, it will open.

/Users/shamov01/DO_NOT_COMMIT_Apoptosis_images for the curator guide.rtpj - Reactome Curator Tool

Schema View Event Hierarchical View Entity Level View

Event Hierarchy

Show in Homo sapiens

- Apelin receptor binds to apelin
- Apoptosis
 - Caspase activation via extrinsic apoptotic pathway
 - Intrinsic Pathway for Apoptosis
 - Apoptotic execution phase
 - Regulation of Apoptosis
 - Regulation of Caspase activation via extrinsic apoptotic signalling pathway
 - Ubiquitination
 - Proteasome
 - Regulation of Apoptotic execution phase
 - Rho GTPase
 - Interaction
 - OMAL hydrolase

Complex Hierarchy

Entity List

Overview Search

View Instance
Display Referrers
Add Component
Delete
Expand Node
Collapse Node
Open Diagram
View as Disease Diagram
Encapsulate Diagram
Hide Reactions at Top-level

Pathway Editor: Diagram of Apoptosis

cytosol

mitochondrial outer membrane

nucleoplasm

Slide to Zoom: _____

Graphic Editor Property Editor

If it has not, as in the case of Regulation of Apoptosis, you get the below message.

Auto-Generate Diagram?

No diagram has been created for the selected pathway.
Do you want the tool to generate one automatically?

Cancel No Yes

Answering “Yes” may be helpful if there are just a few reactions but can create a tangle of reactions that are difficult/time consuming to readjust. If you do want to create a diagram but want to lay it out yourself, hit “NO” and an empty diagram will be opened in the pathway editor pane.

Adding cellular compartments to diagram

Click on the shaded square in the menu bar for the Pathway editor. It is best to add all the compartments that you will need before you start to lay out reactions. Here cytosol is added.

To reposition the compartment, click on it and drag.

To enlarge the compartment, click on it to select it and then grab the compartment at one of its nodes in the corners. Then drag outward.

Drawing the pathway

To begin drawing, select a reaction from the event hierarchy and drag it onto the diagram.

To see the names of the compartments of the reaction participating molecules, right click anywhere on the diagram and opt to show compartment names. This will make it easier to see that the molecules have been positioned in the correct compartment.

To reposition the reaction you can click and drag different components or you can select the entire reaction by clicking and dragging a selection box over it. Then the reaction and all its component molecules can be moved as a unit.

Additional reactions are dragged out and positioned one at a time.

Reaction types

Reactions are of one of 5 types: Transition, Association, Dissociation, Omitted process, and Uncertain process. Transitions involve the molecules changing state, Association is a binding reaction, Dissociation is the Dissociation of a complex. Omitted process, and Uncertain process can be used to describe Black Box Events (BBEs). Omitted process for a BBE describes a process where steps have been deliberately consolidated eg. a gene producing a protein. Uncertain process for a BBE describes a process where the exact mechanism is unknown. To apply a reaction type to a reaction, right click on reaction, select change type .

Select type of interest. Here it is an association.

Continue to drag out, and map, and assign reaction type to the remaining reactions.

Once all of the reactions have been laid out, the compartment names on molecules can be hidden by right clicking on the diagram anywhere and selecting "Hide compartment in names".

Right click and select "Tight Node Bounds". This will reduce the space left by removing the compartment names.

Here is the completed diagram.

Verify that all entity names are contained in the icons, resizing manually if necessary.

Connecting sets with their members

In some cases sets of entities are used in a pathway, and also the entities themselves. In the diagram you may want to indicate that an entity belongs to a set. To make the connection, click on the set and one of the entities you want to connect to (done by holding shift as you choose both), right-click with both highlighted and choose "Add EntitySet and Member Link". This will link the set to the chosen entity with a dotted line.

Use of pathways icons as links to related "pathways" in diagrams

If you want to include a link to a pathway that is not actually "part of" the pathway that you are diagramming, you can do this by checking out both the pathway you are diagramming (pathway A) as well as the pathway you'd like to include as a icon (pathway B) using the Event view. Open the diagram of pathway A in the ELV view. Then, drag the icon of pathway B into the ELV. **Note that you must indicate the reaction that links the diagrams via a flowline between the pathway icon and the output of the connecting reaction. Save and commit the changes. Note that the pathway whose icon you would like to include MUST have a pathway diagram associated with it.

To make an association between a reaction in one diagram and another pathway diagram in which the reaction (entity) acts as a preceding event (participant), you can draw a flow line from the entity to the pathway icon. Note that the pathway displayed as an icon in such a case MUST, itself, have an ELV in order to link this way.

To make this connection between events (on a mac) go to preferences under Reactome curator tool on top bar and unclick 'Use ELV as drawing tool'.

Then if you go into a diagram and hover over entity you want to connect, you get the shadow arrows that you can extend to your green box icon, with options for either activate or inhibit.

On a PC I go to the Tools tab, select Options, and then uncheck "Use ELV as a drawing tool".

DRAWING A NEW TOP LEVEL PATHWAY DIAGRAM

If you are creating a diagram for a new top level pathway (check with editorial managers if this is appropriate), remember that the pathway itself must be listed as frontPage item in order to see the diagram. To do this, check out the frontPage instance from gk_central and add your pathways in the frontPageItem slot. Also, please mark this in the editorial calendar as a front page item and inform.

EDITING EXISTING PATHWAYS AND CORRESPONDING DIAGRAMS

Any time a change is made to events in a pathway, the corresponding reactions/RLEs in a diagram must be adjusted accordingly. To start on revisions, be sure to "Build" project into a local CT project. Make sure you build the pathway that has the diagram associated with it, as opposed to one of its children.

Note that if you build a project (or try to open a pathway within a built project) that does not have its own pathway diagram, and you opt to open it in the ELV panel of the curator tool, you will get the message “The pathway has no diagram, do you want to automatically generate one?” The first thing you should decide is whether you actually need a new diagram (i.e the pathway is not already part of another parent pathway’s diagram). If the pathway is already drawn in the diagram of a parent pathway, hit “Cancel” and rebuild that parent pathway) or, if the parent is already in your built project, hit “Cancel” and open the diagram for the parent. If you do want to make a new diagram for a pathway, Answering “Yes” may be helpful if there are just a few reactions but can create a tangle of reactions that are difficult/time consuming to adjust if there are many reactions. If you do want to create a diagram but want to lay it out yourself, hit “NO”

ENCAPSULATING A PATHWAY DIAGRAM

Encapsulating a sub-pathway

Encapsulate Diagram: this feature is used to refactor a section of a diagram for a sub-pathway contained by a displayed pathway diagram into a new diagram in the Entity Level View. It works as follows using the diagram for "Metabolism of steroid hormones and vitamins A and D" created by Peter and Bijay as an example:

1. Use "Build Project" or "Check Out" to create a local copy of project for Event 196071 (Pathway: Metabolism of steroid hormones and vitamins A and D)
2. In the Entity Level View, "Open Diagram" to open the diagram for the top-level pathway (Metabolism of steroid hormones and vitamins A and D).
3. Select "Vitamin D (calciferol) metabolism" in the "Event Hierarchy" at the left panel. Right click it to get a pop up menu called "Encapsulate Diagram".
4. Select this action to create a diagram for this selected sub- pathway. A new pathway node for this sub-pathway will be added to the displayed diagram for pathway "Metabolism of steroid hormones and vitamins A and D". All reactions, compartments and reactions used by this sub-pathway only will be deleted from this displayed diagram.
5. To view the diagram for sub-pathway "Vitamin D (calciferol) metabolism", use "Open

Diagram" after selecting this sub-pathway. 6). The user may need some fine adjustments: e.g. resize compartments in both old and new diagrams, add links to the new pathway node.

Encapsulating a connected pathway

Pathway diagrams may not be in a hierarchical relationship but still may have connections via input/output of their reactions, e.g. drug ADME pathways provide the input of drug-target reactions in metabolic pathways. To show a connected pathway B in the diagram of pathway A:

1. Build both projects together from the Database Browser --> Event View by selecting A and Ctrl-Click selecting B, then right-click Build Project
2. Open the Entity Level View, in Event Hierarchy right-click B with Open Diagram, then right-click A with Open Diagram
3. With Diagram A open select pathway B in Event Hierarchy and move it into the diagram. The encapsulated B should appear.
4. Select both the encapsulated B and the entity that is connected with B (e.g. the drug), right-click Create Flow Link.

Guidelines for encapsulating events and reusing events in other diagrams

1. If a pathway (pathway X) that has been drawn out in one pathway diagram is found to be participating in other pathways, consider encapsulating the pathway into its own diagram as described above. In this case, pathway X will be represented as an icon in the pathway diagram(s) in which pathway X participates. ****Note that you can ONLY represent a pathway as a pathway icon in a diagram IF that pathway has a pathway diagram of its own.**
2. It follows from the above rule, that IF pathway X has a diagram of its own, you cannot draw out pathway X in another pathway diagram. It **MUST** be represented as a pathway icon. You **CAN**, however, draw out subevents of pathway X (reactions and subpathways) in another pathway (Y) diagram, as long as the events are represented in the hierarchy of pathway Y **AND** as long as the subpathway you wish to represent does not have a diagram of its own. If it does you'd use the pathway icon of the subpathway.

Using the precedingEvent suggestion feature in the curator tool

See slides [here](#) (Appendix C7).

CELL LINEAGE PATH CURATION GUIDE

INTRODUCTION

Our bodies are built of >30 trillion cells specialized to fulfill diverse roles within our tissues, organs and organ systems. All these cells originate from a single cell, a zygote

formed at conception. From zygote to fetus, and throughout childhood, adolescence and adulthood, cells divide and commit to different fates in order for the organism to develop, sustain and regenerate. The series of steps that lead from an undifferentiated progenitor cell, such as a stem cell, to one of its several possible specialized descendants constitutes a cell lineage path. Recent technological advances have allowed researchers to harvest high-throughput omics data from single cells of multicellular organisms and use it to track and manipulate cell fates (Burgess 2018; Saelens et al. 2019). This opens the door to the possibility of deciphering cell lineage paths at single cell resolution, a critical requirement for the advancement of regenerative medicine and cancer medicine.

Researchers who conduct experiments that involve cell lineage tracing through the study of genomic, epigenomic, transcriptomic and proteomic features of single cells currently expend significant effort extracting information from published sources to create short-lived, limited-scope local annotations of biological markers that are needed to interpret and analyze their high-throughput experimental data. This creates the urgent need for an open source, comprehensive, continuously maintained reference repository of cell lineage paths framed on the pre-existing knowledge of tissue morphogenesis, as well as a cell type-specific pathway resource, which can serve as a framework for interpretation and integration of latest experimental findings. Cytomics Reactome, a database of cell lineage paths and a toolset for analysis of single cell omics data, aims to be an integrative systems biology resource that fulfills this need.

Cytomics Reactome will systematically curate published studies and datasets to create a lasting, up-to-date, broad-scope and peer-reviewed online repository of cell type-specific biological markers, cell lineages, and relevant regulatory networks. The resource will be freely available to the research community, and researchers will be able to take part in the growth and maintenance of this repository by participating in community curation efforts, acting as peer reviewers, and by providing user feedback. To analyze single cell omics data, researchers will be able to download the repository and incorporate it into their own analysis pipelines, or to use online Cytomics Reactome analytic tools to apply cell lineage-oriented or pathway-oriented cell type-tailored analyses to their datasets.

By providing a peer-reviewed, standardized reference of cell lineage paths and milestones, Cytomics Reactome will increase the efficiency and reproducibility of the single cell-based research, and assist in addressing long-standing fundamental questions concerning regulation of progenitor cell division and differentiation by highlighting scientific gaps and acting as a catalyst for hypothesis generation.

DATA MODEL

The Reactome data model provides a robust framework for annotation of biological entities and events (Joshi-Tope et al. 2005) and was easily expanded to accommodate new classes needed for Cytomics Reactome. Reactome web application and pathway visualization tools (Croft et al. 2011) have been extended to enable Cytomics Reactome visual display on the curator website, and we are working on enabling the display and search functions on the live website.

The basic unit of the Reactome data model is a reaction, an event that converts input to output physical entities. Physical entities, which can be simple or complex molecules, or molecular complexes, can also act as reaction catalysts and regulators. Reactions are grouped into causal chains to form pathways (Joshi-Tope et al. 2005).

The Event and PhysicalEntity classes were expanded to accommodate cell lineage path curation. A new Cell class, added as a subclass of the PhysicalEntity class (Figure 1A), has CellType, TissueLayer, Tissue and Organ as single-valued attributes. Multi-valued attributes of the Cell are ProteinMarker, RNAMarker, Proteome, Transcriptome and Epigenome (Figure 1C).

A) PhysicalEntity [392026]		B) Event [112754]		C)	
Cell	[5]	Pathway	[22381]	cellType	[CellType:9725586] stem cell of epidermis
Complex	[102653]	CellLineagePath	[2]	consumedByEvent	[CellDevelopmentStep:R-HSA-9725621] Keratinocyte stem cell differentiates into transit amplifying cell in the basal layer of interfollicular epidermis - Homo sapiens
Drug	[1129]	TopLevelPathway	[406]	created	[InstanceEdit:9725578] Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2021-03-29
ChemicalDrug	[1038]	ReactionLikeEvent	[90373]	dbid	9725559
ProteinDrug	[90]	BlackBoxEvent	[9290]	displayName	keratinocyte stem cell of skin epidermis basal layer
RNADrug	[1]	CellDevelopmentStep	[4]	markerReference	human epidermal stem and transit-amplifying cells: Lrig1 is a regulator of stem cell quiescence [MarkerReference:9731159] LRIG1 [plasma membrane] Single-cell expression profiling of human epidermal stem and transit-amplifying cells: Lrig1 is a regulator of stem cell quiescence [MarkerReference:9861234] COL17A1 mRNA [cytosol] Single-cell RNA sequencing of human epidermis identifies Lunatic fringe as a novel regulator of the stem cell <i>crmsnaartmwr</i>
EntitySet	[43435]	FailedReaction	[448]	modified	[InstanceEdit:9863939] Matthews, Lisa, 2024-03-06
CandidateSet	[8694]	Polymerisation	[227]	name	keratinocyte stem cell of skin epidermis basal layer keratinocyte stem cell of skin epidermis stratum basale
DefinedSet	[34741]	Reaction	[80376]	organ	[Anatomy:9725577] skin of body
GenomeEncodedEntity	[239196]			proteinMarker	[EntityWithAccessionedSequence:R-HSA-9734933] CSPG4 [plasma membrane] - Homo sapiens [EntityWithAccessionedSequence:R-HSA-157089] DLL1 [plasma membrane] - Homo sapiens [EntityWithAccessionedSequence:R-HSA-204439] ITGA6[24-1130] [plasma membrane] - Homo sapiens [EntityWithAccessionedSequence:R-HSA-57596] ITGB1 [plasma membrane] - Homo sapiens
EntityWithAccessionedSequence	[232858]			rNAMarker	[EntityWithAccessionedSequence:R-HSA-9731951] CSPG4 mRNA [cytosol] - Homo sapiens [EntityWithAccessionedSequence:R-HSA-9731949] LRIG1 mRNA [cytosol] - Homo sapiens [EntityWithAccessionedSequence:R-HSA-9861231] COL17A1 mRNA [cytosol] - Homo sapiens
OtherEntity	[346]			schemaClass	Cell
Polymer	[1504]			species	[Species:48887] Homo sapiens
SimpleEntity	[3758]			stid	R-HSA-9725559
				tissue	[Anatomy:9725551] skin epidermis
				tissueLayer	[Anatomy:9725619] stratum basale of epidermis

D)	displayName	Differentiation of keratinocytes in interfollicular epidermis in mammalian skin
	doi	10.3180/R-HSA-9725554.1
	goBiologicalProcess	[GO_BiologicalProcess:528093] keratinocyte development
	hasDiagram	true
	hasEvent	[CellDevelopmentStep:R-HSA-9725621] Keratinocyte stem cell differentiates into transit amplifying cell in the basal layer of interfollicular epidermis - Homo sapiens [CellDevelopmentStep:R-HSA-9727354] Transit-amplifying cell of basal layer differentiates into keratinocyte of spinosum layer in interfollicular epidermis - Homo sapiens [CellDevelopmentStep:R-HSA-9727359] Keratinocyte of spinosum layer differentiates into keratinocyte of granulosum layer in interfollicular epidermis - Homo sapiens
	schemaClass	CellLineagePath
	species	[Species:48887] Homo sapiens
	stid	R-HSA-9725554
	structureModified	
	summation	[Summation:9839718] The interfollicular epidermis is the skin surface layer in b...
	tissue	

E)	displayName	Keratinocyte stem cell differentiates into transit amplifying cell in the basal layer of interfollicular epidermis
	eventOf	[CellLineagePath:R-HSA-9725554] Differentiation of keratinocytes in interfollicular epidermis in mammalian skin - Homo sapiens
	followingEvent	[CellDevelopmentStep:R-HSA-9727354] Transit-amplifying cell of basal layer differentiates into keratinocyte of spinosum layer in interfollicular epidermis - Homo sapiens
	goBiologicalProcess	[GO_BiologicalProcess:528093] keratinocyte development
	input	[Cell:R-HSA-9725559] keratinocyte stem cell of skin epidermis basal layer
	output	[Cell:R-HSA-9725625] transit-amplifying cell of epidermis basal layer
	requiredInputComponent	[EntityWithAccessionedSequence:R-HSA-179837] EGFR [plasma membrane] - Homo sapiens
	regulatedBy	[PositiveRegulation:9725602] Positive regulation by 'EGF [extracellular region]
	schemaClass	CellDevelopmentStep
	species	[Species:48887] Homo sapiens
	stid	R-HSA-9725621
	summation	[Summation:9732161] The keratinocyte stem cells differentiate into keratinocytes...
	tissue	[Anatomy:9725551] skin epidermis

Figure 1. Changes to the Reactome data model to enable Cytomics Reactome annotations. A) Addition of the Cell subclass to the Physical Entity class. B) Addition of Cell Development Step and Cell Lineage Path subclasses to the Event class. C) Attributes of the Cell subclass. D) Attributes of the Cell Lineage Path subclass. E) Attributes of the Cell Development Step subclass.

Developmental relationships among Cells are described by two new event subclasses: Cell Development Step and Cell Lineage Path (Figure 1B), each tied to a Gene Ontology (GO) biological process (The Gene Ontology Consortium 2019). The Cell Development Step, similar to the Reaction subclass, has inputs and outputs defined, which are instances of the Cell class (an input representing the cell of origin, and an output representing the destination cell type). Cell Development Step attributes include regulators (molecules promoting or inhibiting the step) and required input components (input cell biomarkers required for the action of regulators) (Figure 1E). The Cell Lineage Path, resembling the existing Pathway subclass, consists of Cell Development Steps connected through shared input/output Cells (Figure 1D).

PATHWAY BROWSER

Cytomics Reactome webpages will enable users to search and browse the curated lineages through tissue-level view (Figure 2A) or lineage path view (Figure 2B). Based on annotated regulators and required input components of Cell Development Steps that constitute a Cell Lineage Path, and on annotated biomarkers of participating Cells, we will generate a sub-network of Reactome's gene functional-interaction (FI) network (Wu and Stein 2012; Wu and Haw 2017) for each Path. These networks will first be extracted programmatically from annotation and then manually checked to ensure quality. This lineage path gene regulatory network, available to users as a diagram and as an FI table, will be free of cell boundaries and arranged in an approximate time progression order from left to right (Figure 2C).

Figure 2. Development of keratinocytes in skin epidermis. A) Tissue-level view, where users can select a tissue's cell lineages and individual cells to access lists of annotated biomarkers, omics sets, and cell type-specific Reactome pathway viewer. B) Individual cell lineage path view where users can visualize and access detailed information on cell types and development steps that constitute a lineage, including biomarkers and development step regulators. C) Gene regulatory network view of the cell lineage path. Black labeled genes are path-derived biomarkers and regulators. Red labeled genes are linker genes.

Cell lineage paths are grouped into an expanded Developmental Biology chapter and are available among the browsable pathways on Reactome's website (currently available only on www.curator.reactome.org).

A detailed description of visual display and new website features is available in [Cytomics Documentation](#) (Appendix C9) written by Joel Weiser who worked on the new visual features with Guanming Wu.

STEP-BY-STEP ANNOTATION

TissueLayer, Tissue and Organ attributes of Cells are populated using terms from public open source databases, the Cell Ontology (Sarntivijai et al. 2014; Osumi-Sutherland 2017) and UBERON (Haendel et al. 2014), and cross-referenced to these databases. ProteinMarker and RNAMarker attributes were intended to be semi-automatically populated from published immunohistochemistry and RNA in situ hybridization data, using the Reach tool natural language processing system (Valenzuela-Escárcega et al. 2018) and manual curation. Currently, only manual annotation of protein and RNA markers is functional. A good reference resource is the [CellMarker database](http://biocc.hrbmu.edu.cn/CellMarker/) (Zhang et al. 2019; <http://biocc.hrbmu.edu.cn/CellMarker/>).

ANNOTATION OF CELL LINEAGE PATHS

The first step in the creation of a new cell lineage path is to check out a parent cell lineage path, either Developmental Cell Lineages (DB_ID = 9734767) or any of its

children into your local Curator Tool project. Open the parent cell lineage path record, select the hasEvent attribute field, right click and choose Add.

In the window that pops up, select CellLineagePath and click on New Instance.

In the new window that appears, fill in the attributes of the cell lineage path, such as name, species, summation, literatureReference, _doRelease,

goBiologicalProcess, tissue, and hasEvent. The hasEvent attribute(s) can be cellLineagePath(s) and cellDevelopmentStep(s):

Property Name	Value
hasEvent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development of retinal Muller glia cells Development of retinal amacrine cells Development of retinal bipolar cells Development of retinal cone cells Development of retinal ganglion cells Development of retinal horizontal cells Development of retinal rod cells Development of retinal pigmented epithelium cells
DB_ID	9734811
displayName	Developmental Cell Lineages of the Retina
doRelease	False
authored	
compartment	
created	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2021-06-18
crossReference	
definition	
disease	
doi	
edited	
evidenceType	
figure	
goBiologicalProcess	retina development in camera-type eye
hasEHL	
inferredFrom	
isCanonical	
literatureReference	
modified	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2021-08-03
name	Developmental Cell Lineages of the Retina
negativePrecedingEvent	
normalPathway	
orthologousEvent	
precedingEvent	
relatedSpecies	
releaseDate	
releaseStatus	
reviewed	
revised	
species	Homo sapiens
stableIdentifier	R-HSA-9734811.1
summation	
tissue	retina

ANNOTATION OF CELL DEVELOPMENT STEPS

The first step in the annotation of a new cell development step is to identify, from published literature, the input cell type, the output cell type, regulators of the development step (such as growth factors), and required components of the input cell (molecules that regulators act on, such as growth factor receptors).

Open the parent cell lineage path record that a new cell development step belongs to, select the hasEvent attribute field, right click and choose Add.

In the window that pops up, select CellDevelopmentStep and click on New Instance.

In the new window that appears, fill in the attributes of the cell development step, such as **name**, **species**, **summation**, **literatureReference**, **_doRelease**, **goBiologicalProcess**, **tissue**, **input**, **output**, **precedingEvent**, **regulatedBy**, **regulationReference**, and **requiredInputComponent**.

Property Name	Value
entityFunctionalStatus	
DB_ID	9757216
_displayName	Mature osteoblast produces osteocyte
_doRelease	False
authored	
catalystActivity	
catalystActivityReference	
compartment	
created	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2021-10-27
crossReference	
definition	
disease	
edited	
entityOnOtherCell	
evidenceType	
figure	
goBiologicalProcess	bone development
hasInteraction	
inferredFrom	
input	1 x mature osteoblast
isChimeric	False
literatureReference	
modified	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2021-11-01 Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2021-11-01 Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2021-11-04
name	Mature osteoblast produces osteocyte
negativePrecedingEvent	
normalReaction	
orthologousEvent	
output	1 x osteocyte
precedingEvent	Committed osteoblast produces mature osteoblast
reactionType	
regulatedBy	Positive regulation by FGF2(10-155) [extracellular re...
regulationReference	
relatedSpecies	
releaseDate	
releaseStatus	
requiredInputComponent	FGFR [plasma membrane]
reviewed	
revised	
species	Homo sapiens
stableIdentifier	R-HSA-9757216.1
summation	
systematicName	
tissue	bone element

@Local Repository

If there is no sufficient human-based experimental evidence available, a cell development step can be inferred from a model organism, similar to a reactionLikeEvent.

i. Inputs

A single input of the Cell class is to be defined for each cell development step.

In a cellDevelopmentStep record, right click on the **input** field and select “Set”. From the window that pops up, you can choose from already annotated Cells or you can create a new cell instance.

ii. Outputs

A single output of the Cell class is to be defined for each cell development step. If an input cell can produce more than one output cell type, each input-output cell relationship is to be defined in a separate cell development step.

In a cellDevelopmentStep record, right click on the **output** field and select "Set". From the window that pops up, you can choose from already annotated Cells or you can create a new cell instance.

iii. Regulators

Any number of positive and negative regulators can be annotated for a cell development step using the **Regulation** subclasses - either **NegativeRegulation** or **PositiveRegulation**. Create the Regulation instances just like you would create them for a ReactionLikeEvent or use existing ones.

iv. Required Input Components

A required input component can be any PhysicalEntity present in the input cell that is needed for the action of the regulator or that was experimentally shown to be essential for the development step (e.g. a product of a gene whose conditional knockout abrogates the development step).

ANNOTATION OF CELLS

A cell as a PhysicalEntity subclass is annotated by using a curator-selected [Cell Ontology](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/cl) (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/cl>; CL) entry (identifiers starting with "CL_" prefix) as a reference **cellType**. When creating a new CellType instance, a curator needs to enter only the numerical part of the CL identifier, and the CellType record will be automatically populated:

One cellType can serve as a reference for multiple Cells, just like a referenceGeneProduct can serve as referenceEntity for multiple protein EWASs. The reason for this can be:

- a) Cell Ontology does not have a more specific cellType term, so the curator has to use the closest match. For example, retinal horizontal cell (CL_0000745) is a reference cellType for three Cell instances: horizontal cell of retina precursor (DB_ID = 9725431), immature horizontal cell of retina (DB_ID = 9725440), and mature horizontal cell of retina (DB_ID = 9725415)
- b) Two cells are closely related, but differ in their state, reflected in differential expression of key protein or RNA marker(s). The difference, although biologically relevant, is too miniscule to be captured by the CL. For example, retinal progenitor cell (CL_0002672) is a reference cellType for two Cell instances: postmitotic retinal progenitor cell PAX6+/FOXN4+ (DB_ID = 9725412) and postmitotic retinal progenitor cell PAX6+/FOXN4- (DB_ID = 9725454).

v. Protein Markers

Protein markers are proteins that are specific to the cell type and/or the cell state of the Cell or are differentially upregulated in the Cell. In immunohistochemical studies, protein markers can be used to distinguish the Cell from the neighboring cells. In fluorescence-

associated cell sorting (FACS), protein markers localizing to the cell surface can be used to isolate the cells of a desired type.

A useful search term for finding literature references with information on cell type-specific protein markers is [Cell / cellType _displayName] + marker; additional terms, such as “staining” or “sorting”, can be added to narrow down the search. The CL database rarely lists protein markers in a cell type description. The CellMarker database contains 13605 human cell markers (protein and RNA markers combined) across 467 human cell types, but markers are almost exclusively derived from high throughput studies (mostly scRNAseq) and are not reconciled between different studies for the same cell type (markers derived from each study are listed separately). CellMarker entries are, therefore, a good starting point to identify the most prominent markers, which overlap between studies (and, if possible, between human and mouse), and then use these markers + cellType _displayName as search terms. Please note that CellMarker also does not standardize gene names - they derive names directly from the study, and therefore an identical marker can be named several different ways on the cell type webpage (that is, the overlap between the studies may not be obvious - UniProt has to be consulted to retrieve the synonyms). Finally, the content of the CellMarker database has not been updated since it first went live in November 2018. It is uncertain if the database is actively curated or just maintained on the programmatic side (there have been some updates in terms of cross-linking to the CL database, which was not mentioned in their manuscript from January 2019).

To annotate a protein marker, open the Cell record. Right click on the proteinMarker field and select Add. You can currently choose a protein marker from the EWAS class or from the Complex class.

Property Name	Value
cellType	retinal progenitor cell
DB_ID	9725454
RNAMarker	
displayName	postmitotic retinal progenitor cell PAX6+/FOXP4-
authored	
created	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2021-03-29
crossReference	
definition	
disease	
edited	
figure	
goCellularComponent	
inferredFrom	mouse retinal progenitor cell
inferredTo	
literatureReference	
markerReference	PF1a determines horizontal and amacrine cell fates d...
modified	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2021-04-20
name	postmitotic retinal progenitor cell PAX6+/FOXP4- RPC
organ	eye
proteinMarker	PAX6 [rnflood.com] SDX6 [rn] SFRP2 [r]
reviewed	
revised	
species	Homo s
stableIdentifier	R-HSA-
summation	
systematicName	
tissue	retina
tissueLayer	

Select instances for postmitotic

Please choose instances from the instance list:

Local Schema View

Allowed Classes	Instances	Properties
EntityWithAccessionSequence [140]		Property Name Value
Complex [3]		

Search Instances:

Choose Class: Complex

Choose Attribute: DB_ID

Attribute Value: Equals

Search Search More...

Selected Instances:

Instances	Cardinality

New Instance Browse Database

vi. RNA Markers

RNA markers are transcripts that are specific to the cell type and/or the cell state of the Cell or are differentially upregulated in the Cell. In RNA in situ hybridization studies, RNA markers can be used to distinguish the Cell from the neighboring cells. Increasingly, RNA markers are used to identify cells in scRNAseq experiments and to identify novel markers. Curators should evaluate if a novel RNA marker identified via scRNAseq or microarray expression analysis is robust enough to be annotated as an RNAMarker attribute of a Cell.

A useful search term for finding literature references with information on cell type-specific RNA markers is [Cell / cellType _displayName] + marker; additional terms, such as “hybridization” can be added to narrow down the search. The CellMarker database can be used as a starting point, as described above.

To annotate an RNA marker, open the Cell record. Right click on the RNAMarker field and select Add. RNA markers are restricted to the EWAS class.

Property Name	Value
cellType	retinal progenitor cell
DB_ID	9725454
RNAMarker	
displayName	postmitotic retinal pro...
authored	Orlic-Milacic, Marija
created	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2021-04-20
crossReference	
definition	
disease	
edited	
figure	
goCellularComponent	
inferredFrom	mouse retinal pro...
inferredTo	
literatureReference	
markerReference	Prf1a determines horizontal and amacrine cell fates d...
modified	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2021-04-20
name	postmitotic retinal progenitor cell PAX6+/FOXP4- RPC
organ	eye
proteinMarker	PAX6 [nucleoplasm] SDX6 [nucleoplasm] SFRP2 [extracellular region]
reviewed	
revised	
species	Homo sapiens
stableIdentifier	R-HSA-9725454.1
summation	
systematicName	
tissue	retina
tissueLayer	

Select Instance for RNAMarker

Please choose instances from the instance list:

Local Schema View

Allowed Classes	Instances	Properties
EntityWithAccessionSequence [140]		Property Name

Search Instances

Choose Class: EntityWithAccessionSequence

Choose Attribute: DB_ID

Attribute Value: Equals

Search Search More...

Selected Instances:

Instances	Cardinality

New Instance Browse Database

vii. Marker References

To associate literature references with individual protein or RNA markers, use the markerReference attribute of the Cell. Right clicking on the markerReference and selecting Add opens a new window in which MarkerReference is the only permitted class:

Property Name	Value
cellType	retinal progenitor cell
DB_ID	9725454
RNAMarker	
displayName	postmitotic retinal progenitor cell PAX6+/FOXP4-
authored	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2021-03-29
created	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2021-03-29
crossReference	
definition	
disease	
edited	
figure	
goCellularComponent	
inferredFrom	mouse retinal progenitor cell
inferredTo	
literatureReference	
markerReference	Prf1a determines horizontal and amacrine cell fates u...
modified	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2021-03-29
name	postmitotic retinal progenitor cell PAX6+/FOXP4- RPC
organ	eye
proteinMarker	PAX6 [nucleoplasm] SDX6 [nucleoplasm] SFRP2 [extracellular region]
reviewed	
revised	
species	Homo sapiens
stableIdentifier	R-HSA-9725454.1
summation	
systematicName	
tissue	retina
tissueLayer	

Select Instance for markerReference

Please choose instances from the instance list:

Local Schema View

Allowed Classes	Instances	Properties
MarkerReference [12]		Property Name Value

Search Instances

Choose Class: MarkerReference

Choose Attribute: DB_ID

Attribute Value: Equals

Search Search More...

Selected Instances:

Instances	Cardinality

New Instance Browse Database

Select MarkerReference and click on New Instance. A new window will appear in which you can specify a **marker** (an RNA or a protein EWAS), the **cell** it is a marker for and the **literatureReference(s)**

supporting the assertion.. Note that a separate MarkerReference record is required for each marker annotated. Currently, marker in the MarkerReference record cannot be a protein complex, which is inconsistent with the option of specifying a complex as a proteinMarker in the Cell instance record.

MarkerReference Properties	
Property Name	Value
DB_ID	9839486
_displayName	Functional expression of AQP3 in human skin epidermis an...
cell	transit-amplifying cell of epidermis basal layer
created	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2023-07-06
LiteratureReference	Functional expression of AQP3 in human skin epidermis ...
	Impaired stratum corneum hydration in mice lacking epid...
	Osmotic stress up-regulates aquaporin-3 gene expressi...
	PanglaoDB: a web server for exploration of mouse and h...
marker	AQP3 [plasma membrane]

MarkerReference _displayName needs to be improved in the future editions of the Curator Tool. At the moment, the _displayName corresponds to the first literatureReference listed in the record, which makes it impossible to find relevant MarkerReference instances for a given marker by scanning the list of MarkerReferences. The optimal _displayName would be: marker._displayName: literatureReference.pubMedIdentifiers (separated by “,” or “|” in case of multiple literatureReferences).

viii. Anatomical Localization

The [UBERON Ontology](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/uberon) (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/uberon>) is used as a reference database for anatomical localization. Curators can browse UBERON or use the search engine to find anatomical terms they are interested in. UBERON identifiers have a prefix in the form of either “UBERON_” or “UBERON:”.

To annotate any anatomical attribute (tissue, tissueLayer or organ), a curator has to right click on the attribute in the instance record (e.g. Cell) and select Set (each anatomical attribute is single-valued). In the new window that appears, a curator can create a new Anatomy class instance if a relevant instance is not available. Paste the numerical part of the UBERON identifier to the identifier

field of the Anatomy record. The Curator Tool will offer to automatically populate the record.

1. Tissue

Tissue is the mandatory attribute of Cell instances, and a required attribute of CellDevelopmentStep and CellLineagePath instances. When looking for a reference Anatomy term in UBERON, curators should make sure that the Anatomy term is defined as a tissue by UBERON, and not an organ or a tissue layer. For a reference, curators can also consult histology textbooks.

2. Tissue Layer

TissueLayer is an optional attribute of Cell instances. For some highly organized tissues, such as skin epidermis or retina, it makes sense to fill in this attribute. For some other tissues, this attribute may be irrelevant. When looking for a reference Anatomy term in UBERON, curators should make sure that the Anatomy term is defined as a tissue layer by UBERON, and not a tissue or an organ. For a reference, curators can also consult histology textbooks, as mentioned above.

3. Organ

Organ is an optional attribute of Cell instances. When looking for a reference Anatomy term in UBERON, curators should make sure that the Anatomy term is defined as an organ by UBERON, and not a tissue or a tissue layer. For a

reference, curators can also consult histology textbooks, as mentioned above.

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DISEASE PATHWAY CURATION GUIDE

INTRODUCTION

Reactome disease pathways are contained in a separate top-level pathway called “Disease”. Consistent with Reactome’s pathway-centric view, disease pathways are not comprehensive descriptions of given diseases (bladder cancer, diabetes etc), but rather show the perturbations of a given normal pathway that have been characterized, and may include tags for multiple different diseases within one pathway.

Reactome’s disease annotations are grouped by general biological processes (“Diseases of signal transduction by growth factor receptors and second messengers”, “Diseases of metabolism”, “Infectious diseases”, etc.) rather than by specific diseases. The groupings generally mirror the pathway groupings of the normal event hierarchy.

At a high level, there are two main classes of Reactome disease pathway.

The first type of disease pathway has a “normal” counterpart and shows perturbations to a normal biological process that result from disease entities with altered behavior relative to the WT entities. This type includes, for instance, cancer pathways that arise as the result of gain- or loss-of-function mutations in oncogenes or tumor suppressor genes.

Both gain- and loss-of-function reactions with a corresponding normal biological pathway will be displayed (automatically highlighted in red by virtue of the disease tag, see [below](#)) in the context of the greyed-out WT pathway. Loss-of-function and some gain-of-function disease events are automatically overlaid on the corresponding normal reactions by virtue of their “normal reaction” attribute (see [below](#)). Other gain-of-function disease events must be manually laid out in the disease pathway, also described below.

The second type of disease pathway has no “normal” counterpart. This type includes, for instance, events that occur after the introduction and expression of foreign proteins encoded by genomes of infectious agents like viruses and intracellular parasites. These novel events must be manually laid out in the curator tool. Foreign/disease entities are automatically highlighted in red by virtue of the added disease tag (see [below](#)). Because there is no normal WT pathway for these events, the ELV is unique for the disease pathway and does not have the greyed-out background.

While the bulk of disease annotation is the same as normal curation, there are a couple of disease-specific classes and fields that need to be filled out on entity and/or event records. These include:

- FailedReaction (class)
- Disease (field needed for disease entities and events)

- Functional status (field needed for disease RLEs involving genetic disease variants)
- Normal pathway (field needed for non-infectious disease pathways that have a normal pathway counterpart)
- Normal reaction (field needed for non-infectious disease RLEs that will be displayed as an automatic overlay on the corresponding normal reaction)

Relative to normal curation, disease curation also makes heavy use of sets.

Disease curation also requires extra layers of subpathways to make the display work properly, and a corresponding increase in the number of EHLs. This is discussed more fully below.

This disease chapter has three main sections. The first, “Researching a disease”, briefly describes some useful resources for accessing disease information for curation. The second “Structuring the disease hierarchy and disease display” describes how to structure a disease pathway and how this shows up on the live site. The third section “annotating disease events and entities” has the nuts and bolts of disease event and entity curation.

If you are starting with disease curation for the first time, it is important to work closely with a curator that has experience in this area as you get started. It is also important to preserve the normal biology that has been curated and not try to adjust it to fit a disease process. This is because the curation process to date has gone through many changes to standardise it to be done in a consistent way. Any changes to the consensus could result in QA errors and/or affect scripts, download files and analyses based on curation. In the vast majority of cases, the normal biology curated is correct for basing its disease counterpart on it. However, the data model does not support annotation of mutations at the nucleic acid level so, for example, it is not possible to model a failedReaction on a normal gene expression event. Instead, the failedReaction should be modelled on the most proximal normal RLE that uses the gene product (protein) from the output of the gene expression event. Consult with a curator experienced in disease curation before undertaking such curation as it may avoid errors in this complicated process.

A detailed introductory video describing the annotation of disease variants can be found [here](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0irXpoqiDp4) (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0irXpoqiDp4>).

RESEARCHING A DISEASE

- Focus on biology you know well
- Make sure the biology is well characterized at the molecular level with good human biochemical evidence.

- It is generally useful to start off with a few good, high-level reviews to get an overview.
- For non-infectious disease curation, make sure that the normal biological process is adequately covered in its own non-disease pathway before starting the disease annotations. This is because disease pathways and events are overlaid on the normal events for display in the curator tool and the website. It is possible to add a few normal events to the normal pathway if you discover they are needed to support the disease curation, but simultaneously curating both the normal and the disease events is a big job and should be avoided.
- Infectious diseases are novel events that have their own diagrams, independent of underlying normal biology and curated pathways. If you plan to annotate host-pathogen interactions, it can be useful to check that the impacted normal human pathways show the biology you need to reference.

RESOURCES

OMIM

OMIM is the classic resource. The entry for SERPINC1 (antithrombin III) is a good example. The text rambles (it's a cumulative historical narrative of relevant published results) but as an annotated bibliography it is generally quite complete, with very good coverage of papers describing molecular and cellular biology of the gene and molecular bases of associated disease. The entry for each gene includes a list of mutations with phenotypic effects (under the "table of contents" link on the right of the page, choose "allelic variants") and links to locus-specific databases which sometimes have much more extensive catalogues. (For a while, the catalogue that had the most extensive coverage for the most human genes was HGMD, accessible from OMIM "table of contents" -> "external links" -> "variation". It may still, but it's hard to tell because a license is needed to access it now.) It looks like searches in OMIM for a UniProt ID fail (e.g., searching for P01008 in UniProt does not return SERPINC1) but the UniProt record for a protein includes links to its OMIM record.

COSMIC

For cancer mutations, COSMIC is useful, since it provides information on mutations detected in individual tumors (far from ideal, not all types of mutations are equally covered). In addition, it is good to start with one or two good reviews just to get a bird's eye perspective of the landscape, and then to focus on 1-3 research publications where lots of patients were analyzed, which gives you an idea on the frequency of different mutations. This helps you create your mutant top list, since we aren't capturing all of the mutants, of course. After that, you follow your favourites through PubMed. If you're lucky, you may find a group that maintains a database of mutations for a specific gene.

GENE REVIEWS

Gene Reviews provides concise “reviews” of the genetics and clinical biology of many human diseases, as well as links to clinical testing laboratories, support groups, and other clinical resources that are not of much use to us. Its coverage is less comprehensive than OMIM’s and much more narrowly focused on material useful to the working doctor who has just encountered an affected patient and is wondering how to proceed.

IUPHAR/GUIDE TO PHARMACOLOGY

CITING OTHER RESOURCES

In certain cases, there are external databases that include information that is relevant to an annotated pathway.

One example is rare disease database such as RettBase, which describes Rett syndrome-related mutations in MECP2, FOXP1 and CDKL5: <http://mecp2.chw.edu.au/>. This database provides information about variants described in the disease pathway: Loss of function of MECP2 in Rett syndrome.

We are not able to cross-reference RettBase for individual MECP2, variants in the way that we cross-reference COSMIC for cancer variants because RettBase is not organized in a way that allows us to do this. However, we can mention RettBase in the pathway summation and cite their most recent publication (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/28544139>) as a literatureReference for the Loss of function of MECP2 in Rett syndrome pathway. In addition, we can also create a second Publication instance of class "URL" and use this to cite database itself.

**NOTE that you should NOT not cite disease databases at the reaction level unless these disease databases capture biochemical/functional information.

BUILDING A ROUGH OUTLINE

After some preliminary research and reading, you will have a sense of what your disease pathway will look like:

- what normal pathway it is based on (in the case of non-infectious disease annotations)
- what kinds of mutations have been characterized (gain-of-function mutations, loss-of-function mutations)
- what normal functions are perturbed as a result of these genetic changes (ie, kinase-domain mutants in a receptor tyrosine kinase (RTK) don’t trans-autophosphorylate and therefore downstream signaling is abrogated; constitutively active kinases phosphorylate their downstream substrates in an unregulated manner; binding domain mutants of a protein don’t interact with their protein partners etc)
- drug:target interactions

Note that Reactome does not attempt to catalog every variant that has been identified for a given gene/protein. The focus is on capturing a few prevalent, well studied examples of each of the ways that the biological function of a protein can be altered in disease. Your disease pathway will likely involve sets of variants, each of which has

been shown to act in a similar manner. Note that all variants with the same molecular consequence should be grouped together in a set, even if they occur in different diseases. [See below](#) for a more thorough description.

After this groundwork, you should be able to mock-up your disease pathway, grouping major classes of mutants under sub-headings/subpathways in your primary disease pathway.

As a hypothetical example, if you are annotating disease events in a RTK pathway, you might have in your outline:

SIGNALING BY RTK IN CANCER (parent pathway)

- constitutive signaling by overexpressed RTK (gain-of-function subpathway)
- constitutive signaling by RTK kinase domain mutants (gain-of-function subpathway with set of RTK mutants that have ligand-independent dimerization and activation)
- defective signaling by RTK kinase domain mutants (loss-of-function subpathway with set of RTK mutants that have lost kinase activity)
- signaling by RTK fusions (gain-of-function subpathway with set of fusion proteins that have ligand-independent dimerization and activation)
- RTK mutants bind tyrosine kinase inhibitors (essentially normal pathway showing binding of sensitive RTK mutants to known inhibitors)
- Drug resistance of RTK mutants (loss-of-function subpathway showing inability of RTK mutants to bind and be inhibited by specified TKIs)

Once you have a rough outline, you are ready to start annotating in the curator tool.

ASSIGNING LITERATURE REFERENCES FOR DISEASE REACTIONS

As with normal reactions, the references associated with a reaction MUST provide direct experimental evidence for the occurrence of that reaction in the species you are annotating (i.e. human for human Reactome). If there is no direct experimental evidence orderedSet in humans then you need to create an inferred human reaction as described in the section below. See Guidelines on [evidence confidence here](#) (Appendix C3).

STRUCTURING THE DISEASE PATHWAY

Ultimately, all disease pathways will end up under the “Disease” chapter on the website. You may have a general idea of where in the “Disease” hierarchy your pathway will end up, based on the process that you are annotating (“Diseases of Signal Transduction by growth factor receptors and second messengers” or “Diseases of metabolism”, for instance), or this may become more evident as your curation gets underway. This does not need to be decided before you start your curation.

To begin your disease curation, start by making your parent disease pathway. This parent pathway groups all the disease events related to a particular disease(s) that occur in the context of a given normal pathway (except in cases of infectious diseases, which are by-and-large independent of normal pathways).

FOR DISEASE PATHWAYS WITHOUT A CORRESPONDING “NORMAL” PATHWAY IN REACTOME

If the disease pathway will not have a corresponding "normal pathway" in Reactome, the pathway should still be placed under the disease chapter. Since these pathways are generally infectious processes, they will likely belong under the Disease child subpathway “Infectious disease”.

These pathways are labeled with an appropriate disease term (see [below](#)) and all species that contribute to the reactions and events (ie, generally, the human host and the infecting species, which is entered in the “related species slot, see [below](#)).

Pathway structure is much like that of normal curation. RLEs may be grouped into subpathways by the particular biology being described to facilitate comprehension and to manage diagram size, but because infectious disease pathways have their own diagrams and are not overlaid on the WT pathway, there are no particular requirements for how the pathways and subpathways are arranged.

Below is a screenshot of part of the “Toxicity of botulinum toxin type A” pathway, showing disease entities and disease reaction lines highlighted in red by virtue of the applied disease tag (described below). Host (human) proteins have no disease tags, are displayed bordered in black, but complexes of host and viral entities should be disease tagged and will therefore also appear bordered in red.

Because this is a disease-specific ELV, there is no greying out of a “normal pathway” background.

Below is a screenshot of the pathway record, showing the structure of the disease pathway. The parent pathway is labeled with a disease term (see [below](#)), and contains 5 disease events. The pathway is labeled with the two species that contribute to the

reactions: Homo sapiens in the main species slot, and Clostridium botulinum in the “RelatedSpecies” slot. This class was introduced to prevent inappropriate inferring of pathways to the other species during website release. See [below](#) for more detailed description of the annotation of host:pathogen interactions.

Property Name	Value
deletedInstanceDB_ID	
hasEvent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Transcytosis and dissociation of botA:NTNHA:HA botA HC:LC binds SV2A, B, or C and GT1b on the target cell surface botA:SV2:GT1b internalized from target cell plasma membrane to synap... botA HC transports botA LC from target cell synaptic vesicle membrane i... botA LC cleaves target cell SNAP25
DB_ID	S250968
_displayName	Toxicity of botulinum toxin type A (botA)
_doRelease	true
authored	Krupa, S, Gopinathrao, G, 2006-06-15 10:36:11
compartment	
created	D'Eustachio, Peter, 2014-01-31
crossReference	
definition	
deletedStableIdentifier	
disease	botulism
name	Toxicity of botulinum toxin type A (botA)
negativePrecedingEvent	
normalPathway	
orthologousEvent	
precedingEvent	
previousReviewStatus	
relatedSpecies	Clostridium botulinum
releaseDate	2014-03-12
releaseStatus	
reviewStatus	five stars
reviewed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ichtchenko, K, 2007-08-03 18:17:25 Thirunavukkarasu, Nagarajan, Sharma, Shashi, 2014-11-17 D'Eustachio, Peter, 2014-02-10
revised	
species	Homo sapiens
stableIdentifier	R-HSA-5250968.2
structureModified	
summation	Botulinum toxin type A (botA, also known as BoNT/A), a disul...

FOR DISEASE PATHWAYS WITH A NORMAL WT COUNTERPART

These disease pathways need to be linked to the WT ELV to allow proper display of these events. This is accomplished by structuring the disease pathway appropriately and by sharing the WT diagram with the disease pathway. Both of these are explained in more detail below.

To start, make a record in the curator tool for your top level pathway as usual.

- Give your pathway a name. The top level pathway name is often very general.
- Add a disease term from DOID in the appropriate pathway record slot. See [below](#) for guidelines on selecting an appropriate disease term. Adding the disease term triggers the automated coloring of the event or entity in red in the curator tool and in the pathway browser.
- Add the relevant wild-type pathway to the “normal pathway” field on the pathway record. This must be the “ELV-level” pathway (i.e it is listed as a RepresentedPathway for a PathwayDiagram) that contains the reaction-like events for which you intend to annotate corresponding disease events. This is

needed to allow proper overlay of your disease events on the greyed-out background of the WT pathway.

- (two other attributes, '[entityFunctionalStatus](#)' and '[normalReaction](#)' are also required for proper display of disease events, but these are applied at the RLE level not at the pathway level and will be described below.)
- To verify that you have properly set the NormalPathway, normalReaction, and representedPathway for your disease events, navigate to your pathway in the disease hierarchy, make sure the disease RLE overlay is correct. *Also verify that when you select the normalReaction in the details section, the pathway browser brings you to the correct normal pathway hierarchy and diagram.

The sub-structure of the disease pathway (children, grandchildren) can be quite varied, depending on what the biology needs to represent.

SIMPLEST PATHWAY STRUCTURE:

In the simplest case, there is one way a pathway can be altered during the course of a disease. This may be because a single variant in a single gene has been identified that affects the pathway in one way, or because there is a set of variants in a gene that have been identified that all have the same functional effect. In this case, all events can be shown directly under the parent disease pathway (grouped into subpathways if this grouping provides clarity to the user). All events will show up at the same time in a single view of the disease pathway.

As an example of this simple disease structure, look at the [Phenylketonuria](#) (R-HSA-2160456) pathway (under Diseases of metabolism).

[Pathway:2160456] Phenylketonuria	
Pathway Properties	
Property Name	Value
deletedInstanceDB_ID	
hasEvent	Defective PAH does not hydroxylate L-Phe to L-Tyr
DB_ID	2160456
_displayName	Phenylketonuria
_doRelease	true
authored	D'Eustachio, P, 2012-03-04
compartment	
created	D'Eustachio, P, 2012-03-03
crossReference	
definition	
deletedStableIdentifier	
disease	phenylketonuria
name	Phenylketonuria
negativePrecedingEvent	
normalPathway	Metabolism of amino acids and derivatives
orthologousEvent	
precedingEvent	
previousReviewStatus	
relatedSpecies	
releaseDate	2012-06-12

Here, the parent disease pathway Phenylketonuria contains a single failed reaction showing the loss of function of the PAH variant PAH S40L. The pathway is tagged with the disease term “phenylketonuria” and the corresponding normal pathway (Metabolism of amino acids and derivatives) is added in the normalPathway attribute of the disease

pathway record. The failed reaction (described more fully below) is shown in red automatically overlaid on the normal greyed-out pathway background (normal entities in the remainder of the WT pathway are non-interactive).

A simple disease pathway could also show the consequences of a gain-of-function mutation including the initiating event (for instance, ligand-independent dimerization and trans-autophosphorylation) and the downstream signaling events (binding to signaling partners, downstream phosphorylation events etc). All these RLE would be captured under the parent disease pathway and could be shown in the context of a single diagram, appropriately tagged with a disease term and the normal pathway.

MORE COMPLEX PATHWAY STRUCTURES

More often than not, however, a pathway can be altered in a variety of different ways: by mutation of a number of different proteins in the pathway, or by different types of mutations in the same protein that have different functional consequences, for instance. In these more complicated disease pathways, subpathways and sets of mutants become critical.

Reactome annotates the different functional consequences of different variants/sets of variants [separately](#) in their own view of the normal greyed-out WT pathway. For instance, a loss-of-function mutation in protein X would not be displayed in the same diagram view as a gain-of-function mutation in protein X that causes pathway activation- even though the affected pathway is (often, mostly) the same normal pathway.

Variants (or sets of variants) that have the same functional consequence are grouped together and put in a sub-pathway that is distinct from sub-pathways showing the different functional consequences of other variants.

As an example, look at [Signaling by ERBB2 in Cancer](#) (R-HSA-1227990).

Here, the parent pathway is an EHL. The pathway contains 6 child pathways, each describing different ways in which the same normal biology can be altered during cancer (Constitutive Signaling by Overexpressed ERBB2; Signaling by ERBB2 kinase domain (KD) mutants; Drug resistance in ERBB2 (KD) mutants (a special case, see [below](#) for structuring drug resistance annotations); Signaling by ERBB2 extracellular domain (ECD) mutants; Signaling by ERBB2 transmembrane domain/juxtamembrane domain (TMD/JMD) mutants; Drug resistance in ERBB2 TMD/JMD mutants).

- + + **Signaling by ERBB2 in Cancer**
 - + + **Constitutive Signaling by Overexpressed ERBB2**
 - + ERBB2 homodimerization
 - + Trans-autophosphorylation of ERBB2 homodimer
 - + SHC1 binds phosphorylated ERBB2 homodimer
 - + ERBB2 homodimer phosphorylates SHC1
 - + Recruitment of GRB2:SOS1 to p-SHC1 in complex with phosphorylated ERBB2
 - + RAS guanyl-nucleotide exchange mediated by SOS1 in complex with GRB2
 - + ERBB2 binds trastuzumab
 - + ERBB2 binds TKIs
 - + + **Signaling by ERBB2 KD Mutants**
 - + + **Drug resistance in ERBB2 KD mutants**
 - + + **Signaling by ERBB2 ECD mutants**
 - + + **Signaling by ERBB2 TMD/JMD mutants**
 - + + **Drug resistance in ERBB2 TMD/JMD mutants**

The disease reaction-like events of each of these child pathways (leaving aside the drug resistance pathways for the moment) are displayed in separate pathway views but overlaid on the same WT pathway diagram, as shown below for Constitutive Signaling by Overexpressed ERBB2:

===

The screenshot shows the Reactome interface for the pathway 'Constitutive dimerization of FGFR3 cysteine mutants' (Id: R-HSA-2012084.2). The left sidebar lists related pathways, such as 'Signaling by activated point mutants of FGFR3' and 'Constitutive dimerization of FGFR3 cysteine mutants'. The main content area includes a pathway diagram, a 'Description' tab, and a 'Summation' section. The 'Summation' section states: 'Activating mutations in FGFR3 that introduce a mutant cysteine residue to the Ig2-Ig3 linker domain or the extracellular juxtamembrane region have been identified in the lethal neonatal disorder thanatophoric dysplasia (Tavormina, 1995a, b; Rousseau, 1996; reviewed in Webster and Donoghue, 1997; Burke, 1998). The presence of the mutant cysteine residue causes ligand-independent dimerization of the receptor through Cys-mediated intramolecular disulphide bonds and leads to increased biological signaling without changing the intrinsic kinase activity of the receptor (d'Avis, 1998; Adar, 2002). More recently, the same mutations, arising somatically, have been identified in a range of cancers including bladder, prostate and cervical cancer, as well as in multiple myeloma and head and neck squamous cell carcinoma (reviewed in Wesche, 2011).'

Individual sets for groups of functionally related disease variants is also necessary to allow proper display of the disease events on the website. This is particularly true when the sets of variants affect the same WT RLE -in this case, separate sub-pathways are essential to allow proper display. If this is not done, the tool tries (successfully) to overlay multiple disease events onto a single reaction, making all of them illegible:

By consensus (as of August 2024), Reactome annotates loss-of-function failed reactions individually (ie each parent pathway containing a failed reaction should contain one and only one failed reaction). This is true even in cases where the failed reactions affect different reactions in the WT diagram and so could (unlike the case above) all be represented at the same time without 'overlay clashing'. An old example with multiple failed reactions in a single parent pathway is shown in the pathway diagram below:

This convention was adopted to ensure consistent representation of failed reactions when taking into account the possibility of ‘overlay clashing’ when disease reactions need to be overlaid on the same WT reaction - and in spite of some user testing results that suggest that certain users would appreciate a way to combine different defective views into a single display to see all the weak points of a pathway.

In contrast to loss-of-function reactions, a gain-of-function pathway can contain multiple reactions, as the effects of a gain-of-function mutation (or set of gain-of-function mutations) may propagate over many steps of the wild-type pathway. For instance, after ligand-independent dimerization and trans-autophosphorylation of an RTK due to mutation, the activated mutant receptor may recruit intracellular signaling proteins to propagate the signal. By convention, the disease pathway is continued until the mutant entity is no longer directly involved in the events that are being depicted.

STRUCTURE OF PATHWAYS WHEN DISEASE REACTIONS AFFECT MORE THAN ONE NORMAL PATHWAY

If a disease variant affects a normal reaction that is a participant in multiple (say 2) normal pathways, the curator should create disease pathway names that reflect the process that is affected. For example, defects in SLC6A19 are known to cause Hartnup disorder. However, the SLC6A19 transporter functions in both the amino acid transport pathway and the neurotransmitter transport pathway. Therefore, two disease pathways need to be created: “Defective SLC6A19 disrupts the transport of amino acids causing Hartnup disorder” and “Defective SLC6A19 disrupts the transport of neurotransmitters causing Hartnup disorder”. In the former disease pathway, “SLC-mediated transport of amino acids” would be specified as the normalPathway and in the latter SLC-mediated transport of neurotransmitters would be specified as the normalPathway.

STRUCTURE OF PATHWAYS INVOLVING DRUG-BINDING

In Reactome, we annotate the action of drugs/therapeutics that affect pathway and protein activity. In general, drugs are shown binding to their target protein and then inhibiting or activating some other function of the target protein. See [below](#) for a full description of how to annotate drug:target interactions.

For drugs that affect the WT version of a protein, these binding and regulation events are shown in the context of the normal, WT pathway hierarchy and diagram. The drug physical entity and the binding event are labeled with an appropriate disease term, as described [below](#). Drugs are also cross-referenced out to Guide to Pharmacology (GtoP) where possible, or to PubChem, as described below. Drug entities and related events are automatically colored in purple by virtue of these tags, and entities are decorated with the purple Rx icon at the bottom right, as shown below for the drug cinaciguat in the [Smooth Muscle Contraction](#) (R-HSA-9621179) pathway

- ▣ Muscle contraction
 - ▣ Striated Muscle Contraction
 - ▣ Smooth Muscle Contraction
 - ↳ ALDH2 transforms GTN to NO
 - ↳ NO binds to Guanylate Cyclase
 - ↳ sGC stimulators bind sGC:NO
 - ↳ Cinaciguat binds sGC:NO
 - ↳ Soluble guanylate cyclase converts GTP to cGMP
 - ↳ PDE5A dimer binds PDE5A inhibitors
 - ↳ T-type VDCC bind T-type VDCC blockers
 - ↳ Calcium binds calmodulin
 - ↳ MYLK (MLCK) Active Calmodulin Binding
 - ↳ Phosphorylation of Smooth Muscle Myosin Light Chains
 - ↳ Calcium Binds Caldesmon
 - ↳ Release Of ADP From Myosin
 - ↳ Myosin Binds ATP
 - ↳ ATP Hydrolysis By Myosin
 - ↳ DYSF, CAV3 and TRIM72 bind
 - ↳ CAV3:TRIM72:DYSF binds ANXAs

In cases where a drug has been shown to affect (or not affect) variant versions of proteins, Reactome disease pathways are able to capture this as well.

For drug-sensitive variants, the binding and regulation reactions are made in the same manner as for a drug that targets a wild-type protein, but the reactions are contained in the relevant disease pathway, as shown for [FLT3 variants](#) (R-HSA-9702510) in the screenshot below:

Drug resistant variants are shown as failed reactions, not binding to the relevant drug. Generally, sets of variants resistant to distinct drugs are represented individually in their own diagram views, as shown below for FLT3 variants resistant to pexidartinib and quizartinib, respectively:

In this case, the child pathway “Drug resistance of FLT3 mutants” is an EHL level pathway.

The alternative to this representation would be to make a ‘superset’ of all the sub-sets of resistant mutants (“resistant to peixidartinib”, “resistant to quizartinib”, “resistant to ponitinib”) and make a single failed reaction where the superset was the input.

SHARING THE DIAGRAM WITH DISEASE PATHWAYS.

FOR DISEASE PATHWAYS WITH NO NORMAL PATHWAY

For infectious disease pathways, there is no sharing of WT diagrams. Each infectious disease process has its own diagram(s) with no 'normal' pathway slot filled in, and no need to share the WT pathway diagram.

FOR DISEASE PATHWAYS WITH A NORMAL WT COUNTERPART

For disease pathways with a normal WT counterpart, you will need to share the WT pathway diagram with your disease pathway.

In principle, this is very simple. Go to the PathwayDiagram instance associated with your wild-type pathway and add your disease pathway name(s) to the multi-valued "representedPathway" slot.

In practice, which pathway to associate with the PathwayDiagram can be a bit more complicated. One way to think of the rule is: any disease pathways that directly contain disease RLE's that need to be overlaid on the wild-type ELV need to be associated with the wild-type diagram.

Another way to think of this is: any RLEs that needs to be shown overlaid on the same WT reactions have to be in their own subpathway, and each of these subpathways need to be added as a 'representedPathway' in the PathwayDiagram record for the wild-type pathway.

In practice, the disease pathways that are added to the pathwayDiagram record are generally children or grandchildren pathways of your parent pathway.

Consider the hypothetical pathway above:

SIGNALLING BY RTK IN CANCER (parent pathway): this will often be an EHL D depicting the clickable subpathways. The parent pathway is **not added to the WT pathwayDiagram record as a represented pathway**

- constitutive signaling by overexpressed RTK (gain-of-function subpathway; **pathway added to the WT pathwayDiagram record**)
 - Individual RLEs, for instance
 - Constitutive dimerization of overexpressed RTK
 - Trans-autophosphorylation of overexpressed RTK etc
- constitutive signaling by RTK kinase domain mutants (gain-of-function subpathway with set of RTK mutants that have ligand-independent dimerization and activation; **pathway added to the WT pathwayDiagram record**)
 - Individual RLEs, for instance
 - Constitutive dimerization of KD mutants of RTK

- Trans-autophosphorylation of KD mutants of RTK etc
- defective signaling by RTK kinase domain mutants (loss-of-function subpathway with set of RTK mutants that have lost kinase activity; [pathway added to the WT pathwayDiagram record](#))
 - Individual RLEs (failedReactions), for instance
 - KD mutants of RTK don't trans-autophosphorylate
- signaling by RTK fusions (gain-of-function subpathway with set of fusion proteins that have ligand-independent dimerization and activation; [pathway added to the WT pathwayDiagram record](#))
 - Individual RLEs for instance
 - Fusion mutants of RTK dimerize
 - etc
- RTK mutants bind tyrosine kinase inhibitors (essentially normal pathway showing binding of sensitive RTK mutants to known inhibitors; [pathway added to the WT pathwayDiagram record](#))
 - RLEs for instance
 - TKI-sensitive RTK mutants bind TKIs
- Drug resistance of RTK mutants (loss-of-function subpathways showing inability of RTK mutants to bind and be inhibited by specified TKIs; this will have a new EHLID with subpathway icons, [pathway not added to the WT pathwayDiagram record](#))
 - Subpathway for each drug such as
 - Resistance of RTK mutants to TKI 1 ([pathway added to the WT pathwayDiagram record](#))
 - Failed reaction, "TKI 1- resistant RTK mutants don't bind TKI 1"
 - Resistance of RTK mutants to TKI 2 ([pathway added to the WT pathwayDiagram record](#))
 - Failed reaction "TKI 2-resistant RTK mutants don't bind TKI 2"

For a real example:

- [-] **FLT3 signaling in disease**
 - [+] **Signaling by FLT3 ITD and TKD mutants**
 - [-] **FLT3 signaling by CBL mutants**
 - [H] **CBL mutants don't ubiquitinate FLT3**
 - [+] **Signaling by FLT3 fusion proteins**
 - [-] **FLT3 mutants bind TKIs**
 - [>] **FLT mutants bind type II TKIs**
 - [>] **FLT mutants bind type I TKIs**
 - [-] **Drug resistance of FLT3 mutants**
 - [-] **pexidartinib-resistant FLT3 mutants**
 - [H] **pexidartinib-resistant FLT3 mutants don't bind pexidartinib**
 - [+] **quizartinib-resistant FLT3 mutants**
 - [+] **ponatinib-resistant FLT3 mutants**
 - [+] **sorafenib-resistant FLT3 mutants**
 - [+] **sunitinib-resistant FLT3 mutants**
 - [+] **tandutinib-resistant FLT3 mutants**
 - [+] **midostaurin-resistant FLT3 mutants**
 - [+] **tamaninib-resistant FLT3 mutants**
 - [+] **crenolanib-resistant FLT3 mutants**
 - [+] **semamaxinib-resistant FLT3 mutants**

The corresponding PathwayDiagram record shown below lists first the WT pathway and then each of the disease RLE containing subpathways.

 [PathwayDiagram:9645667] Diagram of FLT3 Signaling, Signaling by FLT3 ITD and TKD mutants, FLT3 sig...

PathwayDiagram Properties	
Property Name	Value
	↳ FLT3 Signaling
	↳ Signaling by FLT3 ITD and TKD mutants
	↳ FLT3 signaling by CBL mutants
	↳ Signaling by FLT3 fusion proteins
	↳ FLT3 mutants bind TKIs
	↳ pexidartinib-resistant FLT3 mutants
	↳ quizartinib-resistant FLT3 mutants
	↳ ponatinib-resistant FLT3 mutants
	↳ sorafenib-resistant FLT3 mutants
	↳ sunitinib-resistant FLT3 mutants
	↳ tandutinib-resistant FLT3 mutants
	↳ midostaurin-resistant FLT3 mutants
	↳ tamaninib-resistant FLT3 mutants
	↳ crenolanib-resistant FLT3 mutants
	↳ semamaxinib-resistant FLT3 mutants
	↳ linifanib-resistant FLT3 mutants
	↳ gilteritinib-resistant FLT3 mutants
	↳ lestaurtinib-resistant FLT3 mutants
	↳ KW2449-resistant FLT3 mutants
representedPathway	

Note that the child pathway “Drug resistance of FLT3 mutants” has its own EHL. It is a “grouping” pathway for all of the subpathways showing different drug resistant variants. This “grouping pathway itself does not have a normal pathway counterpart so is NOT associated with the WT pathway diagram. This is because each of the failed reactions (showing that the set of mutants is resistant to drug X, Y or Z etc) needs to be overlaid on the same WT reaction and therefore needs its own subpathway, as shown above.

It is also possible to have different diagrams associated with different disease subpathways, as is shown in the “Signaling by WNT in cancer” pathway.

In this case, the wild-type WNT pathway has three associated normal pathway diagrams: Degradation of beta-catenin by the destruction complex, TCF-dependent signaling in response to WNT and WNT ligand biogenesis.

The parent disease WNT pathway, Signaling by WNT in cancer, has 10 subpathways containing a variety of gain-of-function and loss-of-function events.

As shown below, the first 6 disease subpathways are all associated with the WT diagram “Degradation of beta-catenin by the destruction complex”:

[PathwayDiagram:451075] Diagram of Degradation of beta-catenin by the destruction complex, APC truncation mutants are not...

Property Name	Value
representedPathway	Degradation of beta-catenin by the destruction complex
	APC truncation mutants are not K63 polyubiquitinated
	APC truncation mutants have impaired AXIN binding
	Deletions in the AXIN1 gene destabilize the destruction complex
	AXIN missense mutants destabilize the destruction complex
	Deletions in the AMER1 gene destabilize the destruction complex
	Truncations of AMER1 destabilize the destruction complex
	CTNNB1 S45 mutants aren't phosphorylated
	CTNNB1 T41 mutants aren't phosphorylated
	CTNNB1 S37 mutants aren't phosphorylated
	CTNNB1 S33 mutants aren't phosphorylated
	Signaling by GSK3 beta mutants
	Signaling by TCF7L2 mutants

The next 3 disease subpathways are associated with the WT diagram “TCF-dependent signaling in response to WNT”:

[PathwayDiagram:3238081] Diagram of TCF dependent signaling in response to...

Property Name	Value
representedPathway	TCF dependent signaling in response to WNT
	Signaling by LRP5 mutants
	Signaling by RNF43 mutants
	XAV939 stabilizes AXIN

and the final disease subpathway is associated with the WT diagram “WNT ligand biogenesis and trafficking”:

[PathwayDiagram:3238699] Diagram of WNT ligand biogenesis and trafficking a...

Property Name	Value
representedPathway	WNT ligand biogenesis and trafficking
	LGK974 inhibits PORCN

Note: Any time you need to make revision to a "normal pathway" that has a disease counterpart, please be sure that you start off by "Building" (as opposed to "Checking out") the full disease pathway into a local project. Then open the Disease diagram and make any necessary edits there.

ASSIGNING DISEASE TERM ATTRIBUTES

We want to use “disease” in a broad sense: if a process has a specific bad outcome we can associate it with that outcome even if it hasn’t yet progressed to the point of causing major disease. The association of Amyloidosis with the Amyloids pathway is an example. It is possible, for instance, that amyloid deposition, that is going on in all of us, is pathological, even though most of us will die of something else before the amyloidosis progresses to a point where it’s symptomatic. Targeting these early pathological processes (propathology?) will likely be very important: good for us as patients because early intervention slows or stops the process and keeps us healthy longer; good for the drug companies because that intervention will likely be a continuing one – an additional drug to be taken for life rather than a one-time course.

Reactome disease terms are taken from the [Disease Ontology](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/doid) (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/doid>). If gk-central doesn’t have the disease term you need, you can create a new one by opting to create a new instance. Browse the hierarchy [here](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/doid) (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/doid>), then create a new record in Reactome by entering the corresponding DOID identifier (number only) in the identifier slot. You will be asked if you want to import the entry. Say yes. If the Disease Ontology itself doesn’t have an appropriate term, we can request that one be made.

TO PATHWAYS:

Please be sure to label the top-level disease pathway and its sub-level disease pathway with a disease attribute.

Note that disease terms applied to pathways and events should describe *all entities and events that are captured in that event. For this reason, disease terms applied at the pathway level are often very general (“cancer”, not “lung adenocarcinoma”, for instance). Disease terms tend to get more specific at the entity level, as described below.

TO REACTIONS:

A disease attribute should be added to all reactions involving disease-related physical entities, such as proteins of bacterial/viral/fungal pathogens, disease variant human proteins, and drugs used in disease management. Use the same procedure as the one described for the addition of disease attributes to pathways. If there are several related disease tags that are applicable to reactions and pathways, using the most general tag is preferable, and even if specific disease attributes are added, always include the most general attribute for a given disease type. For example, for cancer-related reactions and pathways, always include the cancer tag.

TO ENTITIES:

Disease attributes should be added to mutant proteins associated with disease and may be very specific, referring to the specific disease type(s) in which a particular mutation was found. For example, EGFR L861Q mutant (DB_ID 1177542), in which L-leucine at position 861 is replaced with L-glutamine has been detected in non-small cell lung carcinoma and adult glioblastoma multiforme. Besides these specific disease tags, it may be advisable to also add more general disease tags to an EWAS, in this case, lung cancer, and cancer, to enable search of mutant EWASs using these general terms. When it comes to entity sets, such as EGFR KD mutants (DB_ID 1182966) which

includes all kinase domain mutants of EGFR in cancer, a very general disease tag, such as cancer, is appropriate. This is because each member of the set has its own range of cancer types (while EGFR L861Q is found in lung cancer and glioblastoma, EGFR L858R is found in lung cancer, thymoma, thyroid cancer, breast cancer, and ovarian cancer), but their biological behavior is identical/similar. For the same reasons, only the general cancer disease tag should be used for events in which cancer disease entities participate.

TO DRUGS:

When annotating drugs used to treat a particular disease, curators should add an appropriate disease tag to a drug entity. For a cancer drug, the general cancer disease attribute should definitely be added, but when it comes to more specific disease tags, it may be advisable to add only those cancer types for which the treatment by a given drug is approved.

ANNOTATING DISEASE REACTION-LIKE-EVENTS (RLEs)

Disease reaction-like events have 3 disease-specific fields that may need to be filled in:

- disease (required for all disease RLE's; as described above)
- normalReaction (required for disease reactions that will be overlaid on a normal WT, described below)
- entityFunctionalStatus (EFS) (absolutely required for disease reactions that will be overlaid on a normal WT reaction, described below, but from a curation policy standpoint, required for *all disease reactions, regardless of overlay, as an additional source of information for users and to facilitate alignment with [ACMG variant criteria](#)).

Disease RLE's are either loss- or gain-of-function events. All loss-of-function are overlaid automatically on top of the corresponding WT reaction by virtue of their disease tag, normalReaction field and entityFunctionalStatus. Gain-of-function reactions may or may not be overlaid on normal WT reactions, as described below.

ANNOTATING LOSS-OF-FUNCTION REACTIONS

Loss-of-function 'reactions' are annotated as "FailedReaction". Failed reactions are labeled with a disease tag as described above but have only inputs (the disease variant entity or complex or set, plus any WT entities that are inputs in the 'normal' reaction), and do not have any outputs. See the note [below](#) about avoiding reaction participant mismatches.

The failedReaction record also lists the corresponding WT reaction in the "normalReaction" slot.

Property Name	Value
catalystActivity	
deletedInstanceDB_ID	
entityFunctionalStatus	loss_of_function of UNC93B1 variants [endoplasmic reticul...
input	1 x TLR3 [endoplasmic reticulum membrane] 1 x UNC93B1 variants [endoplasmic reticulum membrane]
DB_ID	5607838
_displayName	Defective UNC93B1 does not bind TLR3
_doRelease	true
authored	Shamovsky, V, 2014-05-21
catalystActivityReference	
compartment	endoplasmic reticulum membrane
created	Shamovsky, Veronica, 2014-07-14
crossReference	
definition	
deletedStableIdentifier	
disease	primary immunodeficiency disease
edited	Shamovsky, Veronica, 2015-02-09
entityOnOtherCell	
evidenceType	
figure	
goBiologicalProcess	
hasInteraction	
inferredFrom	
internalReviewed	
isChimeric	false
literatureReference	Herpes simplex virus encephalitis in human UNC-93B defi... Impaired intrinsic immunity to HSV-1 in human iPSC-deriv... Shamovsky, Veronica, 2014-10-14 Shamovsky, Veronica, 2014-10-20 Matthews, Lisa, 2014-10-31 Shamovsky, Veronica, 2014-11-07 Shamovsky, Veronica, 2014-11-17 Shamovsky, Veronica, 2015-02-15 Shamovsky, Veronica, 2015-02-16 Shamovsky, Veronica, 2018-11-13 Matthews, Lisa, 2023-03-08
modified	
name	Defective UNC93B1 does not bind TLR3
negativePrecedingEvent	
normalReaction	Full-length TLR3/7/8/9 binds to UNC93B1
orthologousEvent	

FailedReactions are placed in the appropriate disease pathway as usual, but are not dragged into the ELV by the curator. By virtue of the disease tag, the 'normalReaction' field, the EFS, and the appropriate sharing of pathway diagrams, FailedReactions are automatically overlaid on the background of the WT pathway and appear on top of the normal reaction with the disease input and the reaction node highlighted in red and the outputs of the WT reaction X'd out, as shown:

In general, FailedReactions should be named according to the structure “Defective [core protein name] doesn’t [some description of WT function]”, as in “Defective ALG9 does not add mannose to the N-glycan precursor”. The key is using the words ‘defective’ and ‘variant’ to describe the disease related entities.

To avoid [reaction participant mismatches](#), all the inputs of the WT normal reaction must be present in the FailedReaction record (differences in stoichiometry are ignored). A good approach to making a FailedReaction can be to clone the normal WT reaction, switch type to FailedReaction, replace the WT entity with the relevant disease variant or set, and add disease tag, EFS and normal reaction to the relevant slots on the record. See the section [below](#) on avoiding participant mismatches for more considerations.

The molecular biology of the failed reaction should match the molecular biology of the normal reaction closely/exactly, both for biological coherence and to avoid [mismatches](#). For instance, imagine a protein that binds to a substrate and then catalyzes a reaction. If there are subsets of variants identified that a) don’t bind or b) bind but are catalytically dead, these should be represented in two different failed reactions, the first showing a failed binding reaction and the second showing a failed catalysis. In some cases, this may require creating a new normal reaction for the WT pathway (if, for instance, the binding and catalysis are shown happening in a single step in the WT pathway). See [here](#) (Appendix C10, Multiple disease reactions and ENTITYFUNCTIONALSTATUS when using DISEASE VARIANT SUBSETS) for the original discussion of this).

ANNOTATING GAIN-OF-FUNCTION REACTIONS

There are two types of gain-of-function events in Reactome:

1. totally novel events that are not seen in the WT pathway. This may arise through the introduction of an infectious agent or by expression of a variant of a human protein that has an activity not displayed by the corresponding WT protein - for instance binding to a novel protein partner, or forming ligand-independent dimers.
2. gain-of-function events that happen at an elevated rate or efficiency compared to a corresponding event in a wild-type pathway.

All gain-of-function RLE’s are labeled with a disease tag as described above. This is needed for the automatic red line coloring in the ELV.

All gain-of-function RLEs should have their entity functional status slot filled out (described below).

Gain-of-function events not needing a ‘normalReaction’

Some gain-of-function events represent totally novel activities that are not seen in the WT pathway. Novel gain-of-function RLEs of this kind do not have their ‘normalReaction’ slot filled out and are not overlaid on top of a normal WT reaction. These reactions are dragged into the pathway diagram manually by the curator as for WT reactions and occupy their own space in the pathway diagram.

Although the EntityFunctionalStatus slot is not required for display purposes for these RLEs, it should be filled out in any case. This is a new policy as of Feb 2023, so older records may not reflect this. This was introduced for consistency and to allow for better mapping of Reactome variants to ACMG variant criteria (see [below](#)).

[Reaction:1227964] ERBB2 homodimerization	
Reaction Properties	
Property Name	Value
catalystActivity	
deletedInstanceDB_ID	
entityFunctionalStatus	
input	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊕ 2 x ERBB2:ERBIN:HSP90: CDC37 [plasma membrane] ⊕ 2 x CDC37 [cytosol]
output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊕ 1 x ERBB2 homodimer [plasma membrane] ⊕ 2 x ERBIN [plasma membrane] ⊕ 2 x HSP90 [cytosol]
DB_ID	1227964
_displayName	ERBB2 homodimerization
_doRelease	true
authored	⊕ Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2019-07-31
catalystActivityReference	
compartment	⊕ plasma membrane
created	⊕ Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2011-03-14
crossReference	
definition	
deletedStableIdentifier	
disease	⊕ cancer
edited	⊕ Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2019-11-01
entityOnOtherCell	
evidenceType	
figure	
goBiologicalProcess	
hasInteraction	
inferredFrom	
internalReviewed	
isChimeric	false
literatureReference	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊕ Comparison of 3D and 2D tumor models reveals enhanced HER2 act... ⊕ The effects of trastuzumab on HER2-mediated cell signaling in CHO ... ⊕ Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2011-03-14 ⊕ Wu, G, 2016-07-15 ⊕ Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2019-01-09 ⊕ Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2019-01-09 ⊕ Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2019-01-09 ⊕ Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2019-09-23 ⊕ Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2019-10-30 ⊕ Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2019-11-01 ⊕ Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2019-11-01 ⊕ Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2019-11-01 ⊕ Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2019-11-01 ⊕ Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2019-11-12 ⊕ Matthews, Lisa, 2023-03-08
modified	
name	ERBB2 homodimerization 2 x ERBB2:HSP90: CDC37 => ERBB2 homodimer
negativePrecedingEvent	
normalReaction	

Gain-of-function events with a 'normalReaction'

If a disease variant (or set of variants) performs the same reaction as the WT counterpart at an elevated rate or efficiency, the disease RLE can be overlaid on the normal reaction, as for loss-of-function FailedReactions above. In this case, the 'normalReaction' field on the disease RLE must be filled in to allow for proper display.

[Reaction:1248694] Trans-autophosphorylation of ERBB2 homodimer	
Reaction Properties	
Property Name	Value
catalystActivity	protein tyrosine kinase activity of ERBB2 homodimer [plasma...
deletedInstanceDB_ID	
entityFunctionalStatus	
input	12 x ATP [cytosol] 1 x ERBB2 homodimer [plasma membrane]
output	12 x ADP [cytosol] 1 x p-ERBB2 homodimer [plasma membrane]
DB_ID	1248694
displayName	Trans-autophosphorylation of ERBB2 homodimer
doRelease	true
authored	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2019-07-31
catalystActivityReference	
compartment	plasma membrane cytosol extracellular region
created	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2011-04-12
crossReference	
definition	
deletedStableIdentifier	
disease	cancer
edited	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2019-11-01
entityOnOtherCell	
evidenceType	
figure	
goBiologicalProcess	
hasInteraction	
inferredFrom	
internalReviewed	
isChimeric	false
literatureReference	Analysis of protein-protein interactions involved in the activa... Identification of autophosphorylation sites of HER2/neu The effects of trastuzumab on HER2-mediated cell signaling... Comparison of 3D and 2D tumor models reveals enhanced ... Wu, G, 2016-07-15 Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2019-01-09 Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2019-01-09 Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2019-01-09 Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2019-01-09 Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2019-01-10 Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2019-09-23 Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2019-10-30 Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2019-10-30 Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2019-11-01 Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2019-11-01 Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2019-11-01 Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2019-11-01 Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2019-11-12 Matthews, Lisa, 2023-03-08
modified	
name	Trans-autophosphorylation of ERBB2 homodimer
negativePrecedingEvent	
normalReaction	Trans-autophosphorylation of ERBB2 heterodimers
orthologousEvent	

Often, a signaling pathway for a particular variant or set of variants will start with a novel gain-of-function event (ligand-independent binding, for instance) and then be followed by a series of reactions that mirror the steps performed by the WT protein downstream of the initiating event. These 'conserved' downstream events are also tagged with the corresponding 'normalReaction' and an EFS, and are automatically overlaid on the normal pathway events.

This can be seen in the “[Constitutive signaling by Overexpressed ERBB2](#)” (R-HSA-9634285) pathway. In the first step, a novel homodimerization of ERBB2 is depicted, resulting from overexpression of the protein in cancer. This reaction has no ‘normalReaction’. Downstream of dimerization, the receptor trans-autophosphorylates, binds and phosphorylates SHC1, recruits GRB2:SOS1 and activates RAS, among other actions. Each of these downstream events has a normal counterpart in the WT pathway that is captured in the disease RLE record and each of these is automatically overlaid on the WT pathway diagram. All the RLEs related to overexpressed ERBB2 homodimers are shown at the same time in the same diagram representation:

FunctionalStatus

Overriding the automatic overlay

In some cases, a curator may wish to manually lay out a disease gain-of-function RLE even though it could theoretically be overlaid on a WT reaction. This may be to avoid reaction participant mismatches, described [below](#), or for another reason. This is fine, and a curator would simply leave the ‘normalReaction’ slot empty and drag the reaction into the pathway diagram as usual. Disease tag and EntityFunctionalStatus fields should be filled out as usual.

ENTITYFUNCTIONALSTATUS

EntityFunctionalStatus is used to mark a disease event as either a gain- or a loss-of-function, and to describe the underlying reason for the change in behavior. This tag, along with the “NormalReaction” attribute, is especially important for loss-of-function events, as it is needed for deploying the red lines and X’ing out of WT outputs in the website display. Note that EFS’s are applied at the reaction-like-event level and not to entities themselves. This is because a given variant/set of variants may play different functional roles in different disease or reaction contexts.

The screenshot below shows the EFS of AKT1 E17K in the disease RLE “AKT1 E17K mutant binds PIP2”.

[Reaction:2219536] AKT1 E17K mutant binds PIP2

Property Name	Value
catalystActivity	
deletedInstanceDB_ID	
entityFunctionalStatus	gain_of_function of AKT1 E17K [cytosol]
input	1 x AKT1 E17K [cytosol] 1 x PI(4,5)P2 [plasma membrane]
output	1 x AKT1 E17K mutant:PIP2 [plasma membrane]
DB_ID	2219536
_displayName	AKT1 E17K mutant binds PIP2

The EntityFunctionalStatus has three fields, diseaseEntity, functionalStatus and normalEntity:

[EntityFunctionalStatus:2362350] gain_of_function of AKT1 E17K [cytosol]

Property Name	Value
diseaseEntity	AKT1 E17K [cytosol]
functionalStatus	gain_of_function via non_conservative_missen...
normalEntity	
DB_ID	2362350
_displayName	gain_of_function of AKT1 E17K [cytosol]

- The disease entity is the disease variant (or complex or set containing the relevant disease variant(s)) that is responsible for the phenotype.
- The normalEntity is the corresponding normal protein that takes part in the RLE captured in the 'normalReaction' slot of the disease RLE. This field must be filled out if a 'normalReaction' is specified in the disease RLE. This field helps the overlay find the appropriate normal entity to overlay the disease variant on and helps to avoid reaction participant mismatches, described below.
- The FunctionalStatus itself consists of 2 fields, FunctionalStatusType, and structural variant:

[FunctionalStatus:2362351] gain_of_function via non_conservative_missense_v...

Property Name	Value
functionalStatusType	gain_of_function
structuralVariant	non_conservative_missense_variant
DB_ID	2362351
_displayName	gain_of_function via non_conservative_missense_...

The structuralVariant field takes terms from [SequenceOntology](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/so) (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/so>) and describes the nature of the underlying genetic change that gives rise to the variant.

The functionalStatusType describes the functional consequence of this genetic change (gain-of-function, loss-of-function etc)

Many of the commonly used FunctionalStatus already exist in gk_central, but new combinations may be generated as required.

A given EFS may be used on as many disease RLEs as appropriate..

EFSs for variant sets:

The EFS shown above for AKT1 E17K is a simple case, where the disease variant is a single EWAS. Disease annotations often describe sets of mutants that function similarly. These sets can also be represented by a single EFS record that has multiple FunctionalStatus attributes to cover all the variants contained in the set, as shown in the screenshot below:

Property Name	Value
diseaseEntity	PTEN Mutants [cytosol]
functionalStatus	loss_of_function via missense_variant loss_of_function via stop_gained
normalEntity	PTEN [cytosol]
DB_ID	5674405
_displayName	loss_of_function of PTEN Mutants [cytosol]

Here, the disease entity is a set of PTEN mutants, some of which arise as a consequence of missense mutations and some as a result of novel stop mutations.

Best practice says that the set of PTEN mutants should itself contain subsets corresponding to each of the functional status types indicated in the EFS record, as shown below:

Property Name	Value
cellType	
hasMember	PTEN Phosphatase Domain Missense Mutants [cytosol] PTEN Truncation Mutants [cytosol]
DB_ID	2317393
_displayName	PTEN Mutants [cytosol]
authored	

(Original discussion of this is [here](#); Appendix C10)

AVOIDING REACTION PARTICIPANT MISMATCHES IN DISEASE CURATION

In order for the overlay function to work properly, there must be careful attention paid to aligning the inputs and outputs of disease and WT reaction participants. If this is not done properly, a Reaction Participant mismatch error will be generated during QA.

Tips to avoid reaction participant mismatches:

1. A disease reaction must have exactly one or zero 'normalReaction' counterparts.
2. The curator can always draw disease reactions directly onto pathway diagrams to bypass auto-generating reaction diagrams. However, to make sure auto-generation work, the curator must specify values in the entityFunctionalStatus slot. The disease PE wrapped in EFS will be mapped to normal reaction participant.
3. Mapping between disease reaction participants and normal reaction participants are always based on participants' referenceEntity values. If two normal reaction participants refer to the same ReferenceEntity instance, but having different roles (e.g. one input, and another catalyst), the mapping will not be reliable. Manual drawing is highly recommended for such a case.
4. If it is to be overlaid, a disease reaction, including FailedReaction and GoF reaction, must have exactly the same number of input entities as its normal reaction counterpart without considering stoichiometries (e.g. a disease reaction has input A, B, and its normal counterpart has A, A, B. This is fine, or vice versa). Creating failedReaction instances by cloning the normal event, switching the type of the clone to failedReaction, and then editing further as needed might be a good way to minimize this kind of mistake.
5. If a protein normally functions as part of a complex, there are two ways to annotate the disease reaction that occurs when a mutant form of the protein is expressed.
 - a) If the mutant form of the protein still associates with the other members of the complex, but the complex does not function, then create a complex instance identical to the normal one except that the one affected normal protein is replaced with its disease counterpart. Then use that variant complex to create an entityFunctionalStatus instance.
 - b) If the mutant form of the protein is incapable of forming a complex at all, then create a preceding normal reaction to annotate formation of the normal complex (if that doesn't already exist), and create a failedReaction version of the normal complex-formation one, not of the later one in which the normal complex carries out its normal function. That yields the needed exact matching between the disease reaction and its normal counterpart.

ANNOTATING DISEASE ENTITIES

GENERAL APPROACHES TO DISEASE ENTITY ANNOTATION AND NAMING

Naming

Reactome variant protein names are formulated in accordance with the [HGVS nomenclature](https://hgvs-nomenclature.org/stable/) (<https://hgvs-nomenclature.org/stable/>), with the exception of using single letter abbreviations for amino acid residues.

When a descriptor is added (usually to set names), ‘variant’ is to be used rather than ‘mutant’ as in “PI3K variants”. Specific rules for the naming of different variants are described more fully in the relevant sections below.

Aligning with ACMG variant guidelines

Where possible, we try to align our annotations with The American College of Medical Genetics and Genomics (ACMG) Standards and Guidelines for the interpretation of sequence variants ([Richards et al. 2015](#)). This framework classifies sequence variants into benign or pathogenic based on 1) population data, 2) computational and predictive data, 3) functional data, 4) segregation data, 5) de novo data, 6) allelic data, 7) other database, and 8) other data. Detailed criteria are listed for assessing the strength of evidence in each of the eight categories as supporting (BP1 to BP7) or strong (BS1 to BS4) for benign variants, and as supporting (PP1 to PP5), moderate (PM1 to PM6), strong (PS1 to PS4) or very strong (PVS1) for pathogenic variants.

Because Reactome’s disease variant annotation focuses on annotating events at a molecular or biochemical level, (ie variants that have been functionally characterized) and on clinically relevant, pathogenic variants, benign variants are outside Reactome’s scope.

In consequence, Reactome-annotated disease variants correspond to only 6 of the 27 ACMG criteria (PM1, PM4, PM5, PS1, PS3, and PVS1), as indicated in Table 1 and described more fully below. Of the remaining 21 ACMG criteria, BS1-4 and BP1-7, used for categorization of variants as benign, can be used for exclusion of potentially pathogenic variants from consideration when the relevant data is available. The criteria PP1-PP5, PM2, PM3, PM6, PS2, and PS4 are used for categorization of clinically relevant pathogenic variants but are not used in Reactome because they do not provide sufficient information to functionally annotate disease variants. These criteria can only be used to corroborate pathogenicity of a disease variant that conforms to criteria PM1, PM4, PM5, PS1, PS3 or PVS1.

Criterion	Evidence strength	Pathogenicity	Evidence type	Evidence definition	Suitability as direct Reactome evidence
BS1	strong	benign	population data	variant represents minor allele whose frequency is too high for disorder	-
BS2	strong	benign	population data	variant incidence in controls is inconsistent with disease penetrance	-
BS3	strong	benign	functional data	well-established functional studies show no deleterious effect for variant	-
BS4	strong	benign	segregation data	variant does not segregate with disease	-
BP1		benign	computational	missense variant is found in gene in which	-

	supporting		computational and predictive data	only truncating variants cause disease	
BP2	supporting	benign	allelic data	variant is observed in trans with dominant variant or in cis with pathogenic variant	-
BP3	supporting	benign	computational and predictive evidence data	variant is an in-frame indel in repeat without known function	-
BP4	supporting	benign	computational and predictive evidence data	multiple lines of computational evidence suggest variant has no impact on gene or gene product	-
BP5	supporting	benign	other data	variant is found in disease case with an alternate cause	-
BP6	supporting	benign	other database	a reputable source without shared data defines variant as benign	-
BP7	supporting	benign	computational and predictive evidence data	variant is silent variant with non predicted splice impact	-
PP1	supporting	pathogenic	segregation data	variant co-segregates with disease in multiple affected family members	-
PP2	supporting	pathogenic	functional data	variant represents missense variant in gene in which there is low rate of benign missense variants and in which pathogenic missense variants are common	-
PP3	supporting	pathogenic	computational and predictive data	multiple lines of computational evidence support a deleterious effect of variant on gene/gene product	-
PP4	supporting	pathogenic	other data	variant is detected in a patient whose phenotype of family history are highly specific for disease gene	-
PP5	supporting	pathogenic	other database	a reputable source identifies variant as pathogenic	-
PM1	moderate	pathogenic	functional data	variant represents mutational hotspot or is within functional domain without benign	✓

	e			variation	
PM2	moderate	pathogenic	population data	variant is absent in population databases	-
PM3	moderate	pathogenic	allelic data	for recessive disorders variant is detected in trans with known pathogenic variant	-f
PM4	moderate	pathogenic	computational and predictive data	variant represents protein length changing variant	✓
PM5	moderate	pathogenic	computational and predictive data	variant represents novel missense change at amino acid residue previously reported to be affected by pathogenic missense change	✓✓
PM6	moderate	pathogenic	de novo data	de novo variant is detected (without paternity or maternity confirmed)	-
PS1	strong	pathogenic	computational and predictive data	variant leads to same amino acid change as an established pathogenic variant	✓✓✓
PS2	strong	pathogenic	de novo data	de novo variant is detected (with paternity and maternity confirmed)	-
PS3	strong	pathogenic	functional data	well-established functional studies show variant's deleterious effect	✓✓✓
PS4	strong	pathogenic	population data	prevalence of variant in affected patients is statistically significantly increased over controls	-
PVS1	very strong	pathogenic	computational and predictive data	variant is predicted to be null variant in gene where LOF is known disease mechanism	✓✓

PS3, PVS1 and PS1

Of the 6 ACMG criteria suitable as direct evidence for annotation of disease variants in Reactome, PS3 is the gold standard - variants whose deleterious effect(s) are supported by well-established functional studies. An additional requirement for Reactome is that these functional studies are at the molecular mechanism resolution level. Variants with this classification may be of any type - missense, fusion, in-frame insertion-deletion (in-frame indel), nonsense, frameshift, etc. - so long as they have been functionally characterized. PS3 variants are annotated as direct disease reaction participants or as members of disease variant sets.

PM5

ACMG classifies as PM5 any variant that represents a novel missense change at an amino acid previously reported to be affected by a pathogenic missense change.

Reactome extends this classification to include variants of any type (missense, fusion, in-frame indel, etc.) that have not been directly functionally characterized but contain mutations analogous or equivalent to those found in annotated PS3 variants. PM5 variants are annotated as “candidates” within Reactome’s disease variant sets.

PM1 and PM4

Nonsense and frameshift variants not directly functionally studied that conform to the criteria PM1 (moderate pathogenic based on functional data where variant represents mutational hotspot or is within functional domain without benign variation) and PM4 (moderate pathogenic based on computational and predictive data where variant represents protein length changing variant) so that these variants are protein length changing variants that result in truncation or complete ablation of functional domains key to a particular protein function, are annotated as candidates of disease variants sets.

References

1. Richards S, Aziz N, Bale S, Bick D, Das S, Gastier-Foster J, Grody WW, Hegde M, Lyon E, Spector E, Voelkerding K, Rehm HL; ACMG Laboratory Quality Assurance Committee. Standards and guidelines for the interpretation of sequence variants: a joint consensus recommendation of the American College of Medical Genetics and Genomics and the Association for Molecular Pathology. *Genet Med.* 2015 May;17(5):405-24. doi: 10.1038/gim.2015.30. Epub 2015 Mar 5. PMID: 25741868; PMCID: PMC4544753.

DISEASE ENTITY OVERVIEW

When making a record for a disease variant, it is often most efficient to start by cloning the WT record and then changing the relevant fields and adding the disease-specific classes.

Like disease events, disease entities must be labeled with a disease tag (described above).

Where possible, disease entities will have a cross reference to an external database like COSMIC, OMIM, ClinGen or other, as shown. An entity can have as many cross-references as needed. COSMIC cross-referencing should make use of the Genomic Mutation ID where available, not the Legacy Identifier. ClinGen Canonical Allele (CA) identifiers are used wherever possible, but ClinVar IDs may be used if CA IDs are not available.

Disease entities should also have their literature field filled in citing the work where the variant was identified or characterized unless they are annotated as disease variant candidates.

[EntityWithAccessionedSequence:4791272] CTNNB1 S45P [cytosol]	
EntityWithAccessionedSequence Properties	
Property Name	Value
cellType	
compartment	cytosol
endCoordinate	781
hasModifiedResidue	L-serine 45 replaced with L-proline
referenceEntity	UniProt:P35222 CTNNB1
startCoordinate	1
DB_ID	4791272
_displayName	CTNNB1 S45P [cytosol]
authored	
created	Rothfels, K, 2013-10-28
crossReference	COSMIC: COSM12639
	COSMIC: COSV62687880
definition	cancer
	hepatocellular carcinoma
	kidney cancer
	colorectal cancer
	adrenal gland cancer
	connective tissue cancer
disease	
edited	
figure	
goCellularComponent	
inferredFrom	
inferredTo	
literatureReference	AXIN1 mutations in hepatocellular carcinomas, and growth...
	Mutational spectrum of beta-catenin, AXIN1, and AXIN2 i...
	Nuclear accumulation of beta-catenin protein in Wilms' tu...
modified	Rothfels, K, 2013-11-01
	Rothfels, K, 2014-02-04
name	CTNNB1 S45P
	Catenin beta-1
	CTNB1_HUMAN
reviewed	
revised	
species	Homo sapiens
stableIdentifier	R-HSA-4791272.1
summation	
systematicName	

Data model classes for 'hasModifiedResidue'

The changes in sequence that lead to the formation of a variant protein are captured by the field "hasModifiedResidue" using the modified residue class "GeneticallyModifiedResidue" to distinguish genetically encoded variants from post-translational modifications (TranslationalModifications class) and RNA editing (TranscriptionalModification class).

Note that in both its variant naming convention and in the annotation of 'hasModifiedResidue', Reactome focuses on amino acid (protein level) changes and does not capture changes at the nucleic acid level.

The data model includes the following classes of modified residues to capture the amino acid changes leading to a protein variant (under "GeneticallyModifiedResidue" to distinguish them from post-translational modifications).

- ✓ **Ⓢ** AbstractModifiedResidue [13640]
 - ✓ **Ⓢ** GeneticallyModifiedResidue [5460]
 - ✓ **Ⓢ** FragmentModification [2171]
 - Ⓢ** FragmentDeletionModification [99]
 - Ⓢ** FragmentInsertionModification [167]
 - Ⓢ** FragmentReplacedModification [1905]
 - ✓ **Ⓢ** ReplacedResidue [3289]
 - Ⓢ** NonsenseMutation [1133]
 - ✓ **Ⓢ** TranscriptionalModification [18]
 - Ⓢ** ModifiedNucleotide [18]
 - ✓ **Ⓢ** TranslationalModification [8162]
 - ✓ **Ⓢ** CrosslinkedResidue [257]
 - Ⓢ** InterChainCrosslinkedResidue [130]
 - Ⓢ** IntraChainCrosslinkedResidue [127]
 - Ⓢ** GroupModifiedResidue [2005]
 - Ⓢ** ModifiedResidue [5900]

The following sections will go through annotation and naming strategies for common classes of amino acid variations leading to variant protein forms.

Missense mutations

These are perhaps the most straightforward variants to annotate. These variants are the consequence of the replacement of a single amino acid codon with a non-synonymous amino acid codon without change in the reading frame.

Naming

Format: “prefix” + “wild-type amino_acid” + “position” + “new_amino_acid”

Where “prefix” is the HGNC gene name and the amino acids are represented by single letter codes

example, MTR P1173L: substitution of proline 1173 with leucine

How to annotate

Missense mutations are captured with the “ReplacedResidue” class of GeneticallyModifiedResidue.

Use PSI-MOD IDs to construct the replaced residue, identifying both the normal residue with an [amino acid] removal instance and its mutant replacement with an [amino acid] residue instance. Here, L-proline is replaced by L-leucine at coordinate 1173.

[ReplacedResidue:3321905] L-proline 1173 replaced with L-leucine

Property Name	Value
coordinate	1173
psiMod	L-proline removal [MOD:01645] L-leucine residue [MOD:00020]
referenceSequence	UniProt:Q99707 MTR
DB_ID	3321905
_displayName	L-proline 1173 replaced with L-leucine

[EntityWithAccessionedSequence:3321944] MTR P1173L [cytosol]

Property Name	Value
cellType	
compartment	cytosol
endCoordinate	1265
hasModifiedResidue	L-proline 1173 replaced with L-leucine
referenceEntity	UniProt:Q99707 MTR
startCoordinate	1
DB_ID	3321944
_displayName	MTR P1173L [cytosol]
authored	
created	Jassal, B, 2013-05-02
crossReference	
definition	
disease	methylmalonic aciduria and homocystinuria type cbIG
edited	
figure	
goCellularComponent	
inferredFrom	
inferredTo	
literatureReference	
modified	Jassal, B, 2013-06-07
name	MTR P1173L Methionine synthase
reviewed	
revised	
species	Homo sapiens
stableIdentifier	R-HSA-3321944.1

Nonsense mutations

Nonsense variants are the consequence of mutations that replace a single amino acid codon with a nonsense codon.

Naming

Format: “prefix” + “amino_acid” + “position” + “*” (stop codon asterisk shown in red just so it doesn’t get lost in the background)

Where “prefix” is the HGNC gene name, the amino acid is represented by single letter code and the stop codon is represented by an asterisk (*)

Example : BRCA2 R2318* - arginine 2318 replaced with stop codon

How to annotate

Nonsense mutations are captured using the “NonsenseMutation” subclass of “ReplacedResidue”. A single PSI MOD term is entered in the record indicating the removal of the WT amino acid. On the EWAS record, the endCoordinate is changed to be the last amino acid encoded by the variant (one less than the position of the stop codon).

Property Name	Value
coordinate	2318
L-arginine removal [MOD:01632]	
UniProt:P51587 BRCA2	
DB_ID	9711451
_displayName	Nonsense mutation at L-arginine 2318

On the EWAS record, the endCoordinate is changed to be the last amino acid encoded by the variant (one less than the position of the stop codon).

● ● ● [EntityWithAccessionedSequence:9711457] BRCA2 R2318* [cytosol]

EntityWithAccessionedSequence Properties	
Property Name	Value
cellType	
compartment	cytosol
endCoordinate	2317
hasModifiedResidue	Nonsense mutation at L-arginine 2318
referenceEntity	UniProt:P51587 BRCA2
startCoordinate	1
DB_ID	9711457
_displayName	BRCA2 R2318* [cytosol]
authored	
created	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2021-01-13
crossReference	COSMIC:CO5V66459219
definition	
disease	cancer
edited	
figure	
goCellularComponent	
inferredFrom	
inferredTo	
literatureReference	
modified	
name	BRCA2 R2318*
reviewed	

FragmentModifications

The next section describes slightly more complicated variants involving changes to more than a single amino acid in the reference protein. These variants are captured under the AbstractModifiedResidue class “FragmentModification” that itself has three subclasses, as shown below:

- ✓ AbstractModifiedResidue [80]
 - ▼ GeneticallyModifiedResidue [0]
 - ▼ FragmentModification [0]
 - FragmentDeletionModification [0]
 - FragmentInsertionModification [0]
 - FragmentReplacedModification [0]

In-frame deletions:

These variants are the consequence of the removal of a stretch of the WT amino acids between the initiator methionine and the stop codon without changing the reading frame of the protein.

Naming

Format: “prefix” + “first deleted amino_acid” + “first deleted amino acid position” + “_” + “last deleted amino acid” + “last amino acid position” + “del”

Where “prefix” is the HGNC gene name, the deleted amino acids are represented by single letter codes separated by underscore.

Example: HK1 H577_C672del: a deletion of residues H577 to C672, inclusive

How to annotate

Deletions are captured using the `FragmentDeletionModification` class specifying the start and stop coordinate of the deleted stretch of amino acids as shown below:

[FragmentDeletionModification:5621917] Deletion of residues 577 to 672	
FragmentDeletionModification Properties	
Property Name	Value
endPositionInReferenceSequence	672
referenceSequence	UniProt:P19367 HK1
startPositionInReferenceSequence	577
DB_ID	5621917
_displayName	Deletion of residues 577 to 672

The corresponding EWAS record. Note that in this case, the end coordinate of the protein is not adjusted relative to the WT protein to account for the deleted stretch of amino acids.

[EntityWithAccessionedSequence:5621873] HK1 H577_C672del [cytosol]	
EntityWithAccessionedSequence Properties	
Property Name	Value
cellType	
compartment	cytosol
endCoordinate	917
hasModifiedResidue	Deletion of residues 577 to 672
referenceEntity	UniProt:P19367 HK1
startCoordinate	1
DB_ID	5621873
_displayName	HK1 H577_C672del [cytosol]
authored	
created	Jassal, Bijay, 2014-09-05
crossReference	
definition	
disease	congenital nonspherocytic hemolytic anemia

For deletion of a single amino acid, the start and end position of the `FragmentDeletionModification` are the same:

● ● ● [FragmentDeletionModification:3325558] Deletion of residues 88 to 88

FragmentDeletionModification Properties

Property Name	Value
endPositionInReferenceSequence	88
referenceSequence	UniProt:Q9NPF0 CD320
startPositionInReferenceSequence	88
DB_ID	3325558
_displayName	Deletion of residues 88 to 88

And the EWAS is named without a range of amino acids (CD320 E88del) as shown below:

● ● ● [EntityWithAccessionedSequence:3325560] CD320 E88del [plasma membrane]

EntityWithAccessionedSequence Properties

Property Name	Value
cellType	
compartment	plasma membrane
endCoordinate	282
hasModifiedResidue	Deletion of residues 88 to 88
referenceEntity	UniProt:Q9NPF0 CD320
startCoordinate	36
DB_ID	3325560
_displayName	CD320 E88del [plasma membrane]

In-frame insertions

These variants are the consequence of adding a stretch of the amino acids between the initiator methionine and the stop codon without changing the reading frame of the protein. The inserted amino acids are NOT a copy of the sequence immediately upstream of the insertion site. If this is the case, these are annotated as duplications ([below](#)).

For example, for a sequence “YMVA”,

An insertion is **Y**YMVA**MVA** - the YMVA in red is NOT a direct repeat of the upstream because the upstream sequence is interrupted by the insertion.

YMVA with a duplication is YMVA**YMVA** - the YMVA in red IS a direct repeat of the upstream sequence.

Naming

Format:

“prefix” + “N-terminal flanking amino acid” + “position of N-terminal flanking amino acid” + “_” + “C-terminal flanking amino acid” + “position of C-terminal flanking amino acid” + “ins” + “inserted sequence”

Where “prefix” is the HGNC gene name, the N- and C-terminal flanking amino acids are represented by single letter codes separated by underscore, and the inserted sequence is listed as single letter amino acid codes.

Example: - EGFR D770_N771insNPG - in this variant the three amino acids NPG are inserted between D770 and N771.

The WT protein sequence in this region is 770-DNPHV-774 and the variant sequence is 770-DNPGNPHV-(original sequence in blue, insertion in red). NPG is inserted at position 771.

How to annotate

Insertions are captured using `FragmentReplacedModification` class specifying the start and stop coordinates which overlap with positions of the N-terminal and C-terminal flanking amino acids, respectively, and specifying the `alteredAminoAcidFragment`, so that the first letter in the string is the one letter code for the N-terminal flanking amino acid, the last letter in the string is the one letter code for the D-terminal amino acid and the string in between correspond to the one letter codes of the inserted amino acids. The insertion site should be $(StartPositionInReferenceSequence+1)$.

Property Name	Value
alteredAminoAcidFragment	DNPGN
endPositionInReferenceSequence	771
UniProt:P00533 EGFR	
startPositionInReferenceSequence	770
DB_ID	9831473
_displayName	Replacement of residues 770 to 771 by DNPGN

In the EWAS record, the end coordinate of the WT protein is not changed to accommodate the insertion.

● ● ● [EntityWithAccessionedSequence:1996322] EGFR D770_N771insNPG [plasma membrane]

EntityWithAccessionedSequence Properties	
Property Name	Value
cellType	
compartment	plasma membrane
endCoordinate	1210
hasModifiedResidue	Replacement of residues 770 to 771 by DNPGN
referenceEntity	UniProt:P00533 EGFR
startCoordinate	25
DB_ID	1996322
_displayName	EGFR D770_N771insNPG [plasma membrane]
authored	
created	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2011-11-19
crossReference	
definition	
disease	cancer lung cancer non-small cell lung carcinoma
edited	
figure	
goCellularComponent	
inferredFrom	
inferredTo	
literatureReference	Structural, biochemical, and clinical characterization of... Orlic-Milacic, M, 2013-06-06 Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2023-03-20
modified	
name	EGFR D770_N771insNPG Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor D770_N771insNPG EGFR Asp770_Asn771insAsnProGly

In-frame duplications

These variants are the consequence of in-frame insertion of a stretch of the amino acid codons between the initiator methionine and the stop codon without changing the reading frame of the protein. The inserted amino acids ARE a copy of the sequence immediately upstream of the insertion site.

Naming

Format: “prefix” + “first amino acid in the duplicated string” + “position of the first amino acid in the duplicated string” + “_” + “last amino acid in the duplicated string” + “position of the last amino acid in the duplicated string” + “dup”

Where “prefix” is the HGNC gene name, the amino acids flanking the duplication are represented by single letter codes.

Example: KIT A502_Y503dup: a duplication of residues A502 and Y503. Because duplications are defined to happen at the C-terminal end of the sequence, the duplicated amino acids are located at coordinate 504, as shown below. For duplications, the site of insertion in the reference EWAS should always be (insertion end coordinate +1).

So in this example, WT KIT sequence is A502,Y503,F504,N505 etc and the variant sequence in A502,Y503,A502,Y503,F504,N505 etc, with duplicated residues shown in red and located at position 504 of WT sequence

How to annotate

Duplications are captured using the `FragmentInsertionModification` class specifying the start and end coordinates of the duplicated stretch of amino acids in the reference sequence, and with the coordinate of the insertion at $(\text{endPositionInReferenceSequence}+1)$ as shown below:

● ● ● [FragmentInsertionModification:9680027] Insertion of residues 502 to 503 at 504 from UniProt:P10721 KIT

FragmentInsertionModification Properties	
Property Name	Value
coordinate	504
endPositionInReferenceSequence	503
referenceSequence	UniProt:P10721 KIT
startPositionInReferenceSequence	502
DB_ID	9680027
_displayName	Insertion of residues 502 to 503 at 504 from UniProt:P10721 KIT

Notice that the `referenceSequence` of the `FragmentInsertionModification` is the same as the `referenceEntity` of the disease variant EWAS itself. This is in contrast to the annotation of fusion proteins, which are also annotated with `FragmentInsertionModifications`, as described [below](#) - but in the case of fusion proteins, the `referenceEntity` of the `FragmentInsertionModification` is different from that of the disease variant EWAS `referenceEntity`.

As is the case with in-frame deletions and in-frame insertions, the end coordinate of the duplication variant EWAS is NOT changed relative to the WT protein.

● ● ● [EntityWithAccessionedSequence:9680030] KIT A502_Y503dup [plasma membrane]

EntityWithAccessionedSequence Properties	
Property Name	Value
cellType	
compartment	plasma membrane
endCoordinate	976
hasModifiedResidue	Insertion of residues 502 to 503 at 504 from UniProt:P10721 KIT
referenceEntity	UniProt:P10721 KIT
startCoordinate	26
DB_ID	9680030
_displayName	KIT A502_Y503dup [plasma membrane]
authored	
created	Rothfels, Karen, 2020-03-25
crossReference	COSMIC: COSM12444
definition	
disease	cancer gastrointestinal stromal tumor
edited	
figure	
goCellularComponent	
inferredFrom	
inferredTo	
literatureReference	Pediatric mastocytosis is a clonal disease associated with D816V ...
modified	
name	KIT A502_Y503dup
reviewed	

Fusion proteins

Fusion proteins are the consequence of an in-frame fusion of coding sequences from two different genes, usually through chromosomal translocation. By convention, Reactome annotates these fusions as the insertion of a stretch of the C-terminal partner as a `FragmentInsertionModification` into the `hasModifiedResidue` slot of the N-terminal partner.

Naming

Format: “prefix (N-terminal protein)” + “(included amino acids from N-terminal protein)” + “-” “prefix (C-terminal protein)” + “(included amino acids from C-terminal protein)” + “fusion”.

Where “prefix” is the HGNC gene name and (included amino acids) represents the start and end coordinates- but not the amino acid codes- of each fusion partner relative to their WT reference sequences, in accordance with Reactome’s controlled vocabulary for naming of protein fragments.

Example: ZMYM2(1-913)-FGFR1(429-822) - this is the insertion of FGFR1 residues 429-822 (relative to full-length WT FGFR1) after residue 913 of ZMYM2.

How to annotate

Fusions are captured as “`FragmentInsertionModifications`” class, specifying the start and stop codon of the C-terminal partner with coordinates from the WT C-terminal partner as shown below:

 [FragmentInsertionModification:1604543] Insertion of residues 429 to 822 at 914 from UniProt:P11362 FGFR1

Property Name	Value
coordinate	914
endPositionInReferenceSequence	822
UniProt:P11362 FGFR1	
startPositionInReferenceSequence	429
DB_ID	1604543
_displayName	Insertion of residues 429 to 822 at 914 from UniProt:P11362 FGFR1

In the EWAS record, the end coordinate of the N-terminal partner is changed to the last amino acid of the N-terminal partner sequence that is contained in the fusion.

[EntityWithAccessionedSequence:1604544] ZMYM2(1-913)-FGFR1(429-822) fusion [cytosol]

EntityWithAccessionedSequence Properties	
Property Name	Value
cellType	
compartment	cytosol
endCoordinate	913
hasModifiedResidue	Insertion of residues 429 to 822 at 914 from UniProt:P11362 FGFR1
referenceEntity	UniProt:Q9UBW7 ZMYM2
startCoordinate	1
DB_ID	1604544
_displayName	ZMYM2(1-913)-FGFR1(429-822) fusion [cytosol]
authored	
created	Rothfels, K, 2011-09-16
crossReference	
definition	
disease	subacute leukemia myelodysplastic myeloproliferative cancer precursor lymphoblastic lymphoma/leukemia
edited	
figure	
goCellularComponent	
inferredFrom	
inferredTo	
literatureReference	FGFR1 is fused with a novel zinc-finger gene, ZNF198, in the t(8;13) leukae... Consistent fusion of ZNF198 to the fibroblast growth factor receptor-1 in the... Fibroblast growth factor receptor 1 is fused to FIM in stem-cell myeloprolifer... Rothfels, K, 2011-09-21 Rothfels, K, 2011-10-05 Rothfels, K, 2011-11-22 Rothfels, Karen, 2014-11-20 Rothfels, Karen, 2021-09-13
modified	ZMYM2(1-913)-FGFR1(429-822) fusion ZMYM2-FGFR1 fusion t(8;13) ZMYM2-FGFR1 fusion ZNF198-FGFR1 fusion ZNF198(1-913)-FGFR1(429-822) fusion t(8;13) ZNF198-FGFR1 fusion FIM-FGFR1 fusion RAMP-FGFR1 fusion
name	

Post-translational modifications to either partner in the fusion protein are numbered according to each respective WT reference protein sequence and do not reflect the amino acid positions in the fusion. For instance, if in the context of the fusion protein, the FGFR1 partner is phosphorylated at (WT FGFR1 position) Y766, the fusion EWAS would be ZMYM2-pY766-FGFR1, despite the fact that in linear sequence the phosphorylation occurs at residue 1250 of the fusion (913+(822-429)).

Fusion proteins with in-frame non-coding insertion sequences

If a fusion protein includes an in-frame insertion of amino acids encoded by an intronic or UTR sequence that are not present in the reference protein sequences of either of the two fusion partners, the insertion is defined in the name of the fusion protein in the format:

Naming

“prefix (N-terminal protein)”+ “(included amino acids from N-terminal protein)” + “ins” + “inserted sequence” + “-” + “prefix (C-terminal protein)” + “(included amino acids from C terminal protein)”+ fusion,

where the inserted sequence is listed as single letter amino acid codes.

Example: FIP1L1(1-391)ins**AQCP**-PDGFRA(577-1089) fusion - this is an insertion of the amino acid string AQCP between the amino acid 391 of FIP1L1 and amino acid 577 of PDGFRA.

How to annotate:

An in-frame insertion of an amino acid string encoded by an intronic or UTR sequence that is not present in the reference protein sequences of either of the two fusion partners is annotated using the replacedFragmentModification, specifying that the last amino acid of the N-terminal fusion partner (proline at position 391 of FIP1L1 in this example) is replaced by a string of amino acids, where the first amino acid in the string is identical to the last amino acid in the N-terminal fragment, followed by the actual inserted string - PAQCP in this example, with the actual inserted string shown in bold.

● ● ● [FragmentReplacedModification:9672470] Replacement of residues 391 to 391 b...

FragmentReplacedModification Properties	
Property Name	Value
🌱 alteredAminoAcidFragment	PAQCP
📏 endPositionInReferenceSequence	391
📏 referenceSequence	UniProt:Q6UN15 FIP1L1
📏 startPositionInReferenceSequence	391
🔗 DB_ID	9672470
🔗 _displayName	Replacement of residues 391 to 391 by PAQCP

In the EWAS record, the end coordinate of the N-terminal partner is changed to the last amino acid of the N-terminal partner sequence that is contained in the fusion.

● ● ● [EntityWithAccessionedSequence:9672502] FIP1L1(1-391)ins**AQCP**-PDGFRA(577-1089) fusion [cytosol]

EntityWithAccessionedSequence Properties	
Property Name	Value
🌱 cellType	
📏 compartment	cytosol
📏 endCoordinate	391
🔗 hasModifiedResidue	Replacement of residues 391 to 391 by PAQCP Insertion of residues 577 to 1089 at 392 from UniProt:P16234 P...
📏 referenceEntity	UniProt:Q6UN15 FIP1L1
📏 startCoordinate	1
🔗 DB_ID	9672502
🔗 _displayName	FIP1L1(1-391)ins AQCP -PDGFRA(577-1089) fusion [cytosol]

Indels

In-frame indels are variants that are the consequence of simultaneous insertion and removal of a stretch of amino acids from the WT sequence without change in the reading frame..

Naming

Format: “prefix” + “first deleted amino acid” + “position of first deleted amino acid” + “_” + “last deleted amino acid” + “position of last deleted amino acid” + “delins” + “inserted sequence”

Where “prefix” is the HGNC gene name, amino acids+positions deleted specifies position and single letter code of the removed amino acids and inserted sequence specifies the new amino acids with their single letter codes.

Example: F8 V2144_Y2351delinsHGVLENGKNWEPSYRW - this is removal of residues V2144 to Y2351 from F8 and their replacement with the specified stretch of amino acids

How to annotate

In-frame indels are captured with the `FragmentReplacedModification` class, specifying the start and end coordinates of the deleted amino acid stretch and specifying the inserted amino acid stretch that replaces them as an `alteredAminoAcidFragment`, using single letter codes entered as the start and stop positions, as shown below.

● ● ● [FragmentReplacedModification:9666370] Replacement of residues 2144 to 2351 by HGVLENGKNWEPSYRW

FragmentReplacedModification Properties	
Property Name	Value
<code>alteredAminoAcidFragment</code>	HGVLENGKNWEPSYRW
<code>endPositionInReferenceSequence</code>	2351
<code>referenceSequence</code>	UniProt:P00451 F8
<code>startPositionInReferenceSequence</code>	2144
<code>DB_ID</code>	9666370
<code>_displayName</code>	Replacement of residues 2144 to 2351 by HGVLENGKNWEPSYRW

The end coordinate of the variant protein on the EWAS record is not changed relative to the WT protein to accommodate the indel.

● ● ● [EntityWithAccessionedSequence:9666353] F8 V2144_Y2351delinsHGVLENGKNWEPSYRW [endoplasmic reticulum lu...

EntityWithAccessionedSequence Properties	
Property Name	Value
<code>cellType</code>	
<code>compartment</code>	endoplasmic reticulum lumen
<code>endCoordinate</code>	2351
<code>hasModifiedResidue</code>	Replacement of residues 2144 to 2351 by HGVLENGKNWEPSYRW
<code>referenceEntity</code>	UniProt:P00451 F8
<code>startCoordinate</code>	20
<code>DB_ID</code>	9666353
<code>_displayName</code>	F8 V2144_Y2351delinsHGVLENGKNWEPSYRW [endoplasmic reticulum...
<code>authored</code>	
<code>created</code>	Shamovsky, Veronica, 2019-11-05
<code>crossReference</code>	ClinVar:RCV000010863
<code>definition</code>	
<code>disease</code>	factor VIII deficiency
<code>edited</code>	
<code>figure</code>	
<code>goCellularComponent</code>	
<code>inferredFrom</code>	
<code>inferredTo</code>	
<code>literatureReference</code>	Endogenous factor VIII synthesis from the intron 22-inverted F8 loc... The intron-22-inverted F8 locus permits factor VIII synthesis: expl...
<code>modified</code>	Shamovsky, Veronica, 2019-12-27
<code>name</code>	F8 V2144_Y2351delinsHGVLENGKNWEPSYRW FVIII V2144_Y2351delinsHGVLENGKNWEPSYRW

Frameshifts

Perhaps the most challenging to annotate! These are often incompletely described in papers, and in order to capture the amino acid changes that result, the curator may have to do quite a bit of leg work.

Frameshift variants are the consequence of mutations that lead to the insertion or deletion of nucleotides where the total number of inserted or deleted nucleotides is not a multiple of three, leading to a change in the reading frame. The published literature generally provides an exact description of the mutation at the *DNA* level, from which the curator may need to infer the altered C-terminal sequence of the mutated protein to create a "FragmentReplacedModification" in Reactome.

Before embarking on this exercise, however, consider the biology. Most (perhaps all) nonsense mutations that occur anywhere in a gene except its final exon trigger the process of nonsense-mediated decay. This process is part of mRNA maturation and its effect is to cause the mutant RNA to be degraded before it is ever translated. Thus, at the protein level annotated by Reactome, the result of the mutation is almost certainly disappearance of the protein, not appearance of an altered one. If the goal is to annotate the existence of a non-functional protein a better choice, other things being equal, would be to choose a missense mutation that has been shown to encode a protein whose normal activity (binding, catalysis, transport, etc.) is lost.

Naming

Format: "prefix" + "first amino acid altered due to frameshift" + "position of the first altered amino acid" + "fs" + "*" + "position of the stop codon relative to the first altered amino acid"

Where "prefix" is the HGNC gene name, and is followed by a single letter code description of the first affected amino acid, "fs" indicates frameshift, and "*#" indicates the length of amino acids before the first stop codon is reached.

Example: EXT1 L490Rfs*9 - in this protein, a frameshift mutation causes conversion of L490 to R, and is followed by a novel stretch of 7 amino acids (8 altogether, counting from the first substituted amino acid) before a stop codon is reached at the 9th position.

How to annotate

Frameshifts are captured using the FragmentReplacedModification class, specifying the start and end coordinates of the altered sequence, where the startPositionInReferenceSequence matches the position of the first amino acid substituted due to frameshift (490 in this example) and the endPositionInReferenceSequence is calculated by the formula:

$$\text{endPositionInReferenceSequence} = \text{startPositionInReferenceSequence} + \text{frameshift length} - 2$$

The frameshift length is specified in the name of the frameshift variant (the number after the asterisk and equals the length of the substituted amino acid string + 1 (as it takes into account the stop codon).

In the EXT1 L490Rfs*9 example,

$$\text{endPositionInReferenceSequence} = 490 + 9 - 2 = 497$$

The altered amino acid sequence itself is specified using the `alteredAminoAcidFragment` attribute. The end coordinate of the EWAS is changed to reflect the new C-terminal amino acid.

● ● ● [FragmentReplacedModification:5357998] Replacement of residues 490 to 497...

FragmentReplacedModification Properties	
Property Name	Value
alteredAminoAcidFragment	RSLSPSQC
endPositionInReferenceSequence	497
UniProt:Q16394 EXT1	
startPositionInReferenceSequence	490
DB_ID	5357998
_displayName	Replacement of residues 490 to 497 by RSLSPSQC

If the paper does not completely describe all the details needed to annotate a frameshift variant, and if such details cannot be obtained from a disease variant database, they have to be deciphered.

The basic steps are

1. Alter the reference coding sequence for the wild-type protein to match the coding sequence of the variant. The reference coding sequence can be obtained from the RefSeq mRNA cross-referenced by the UniProt record that is used as the reference for the wild-type proteins.
2. Translate the altered coding sequence in silico using EMBOSS TransSeq.
3. Align the resultant mutant peptide sequence with wild type protein sequence using EMBOSS Needle open software to determine the `alteredAminoAcidFragment` and the anime of the frameshift protein variant if not provided in the research article.

UniProt records provide the normal peptide sequence in FASTA format. They also provide a link to RefSeq (under the “Sequence databases” section) which links to the NCBI reference mRNA sequence. This is the starting point from where the nucleotide sequence is copied to Transeq below.

Several EMBOSS programs are available to translate and compare sequences.

*[Transeq](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/jdispatcher/st/emboss_transeq) (https://www.ebi.ac.uk/jdispatcher/st/emboss_transeq) translates nucleic acid sequences to their corresponding peptide sequences.

*[Needle](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/jdispatcher/psa/emboss_needle) (https://www.ebi.ac.uk/jdispatcher/psa/emboss_needle) can align two peptide sequences to provide a global sequence alignment.

An example below shows how these steps are utilized to decipher a frameshift mutation.

The disorder “Hereditary multiple exostoses 1” (EXT1) is caused by loss of function mutations in Exostosin 1 (EXT1). One mutation is a 1-bp deletion at nucleotide 1469 in the EXT1 gene, resulting in a frameshift mutation with a premature stop codon ([Philippe et al. 1997](#) , [Ahn et al. 1995](#)).

Go to the [UniProt record for human EXT1](https://www.uniprot.org/uniprotkb/Q16394/entry) (<https://www.uniprot.org/uniprotkb/Q16394/entry>), and scroll to the FASTA sequence for the WT peptide sequence.

Sequenceⁱ

Tools ▾ Download Add Highlight ▾ Copy sequence

Length 746
Mass (Da) 86,255

Last updated 2002-03-27 v2
Checksum¹ 842CD7E6C1312C1A

10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90
MQAKKRYFIL	LSAGSCLALL	FYFGGLQFRA	SRSHSRREEH	SGRNLGHHPS	PDHFWPRFPD	ALRPFVPWDQ	LENEDSSVHI	SPRQKRDANS
100	110	120	130	140	150	160	170	180
SIYKGGKCRM	ESCFDFTLCK	KNGFKVYVYP	QQKGEKIAES	YQNILAAIEG	SRFYTS DPSQ	ACLFVLSLDT	LDRDQLSPQY	VHNLRSKVQS
190	200	210	220	230	240	250	260	270
LHLWNNGRNH	LIFNLYSGTW	PDYTEDVGF	IGQAMLAKAS	ISTENFRPNF	DVSIPLFSKD	HPRTGGERGF	LKFNTIPPLR	KYMLVFKGKR
280	290	300	310	320	330	340	350	360
YLTGIGSDTR	NALYHVHNGE	DVLLTTCKH	GKDWQKHKDS	RCDRDNTEYE	KYDYREMLHN	ATFCLVPRGR	RLGSFRFLEA	LQAACVPVML
370	380	390	400	410	420	430	440	450
SNGWELPFSE	VINWNQAAVI	GDERLLLQIP	STIRSIHQDK	ILALRQQTQF	LWEAYFSSVE	KIVLTITLEII	QDRIFKHISR	NSLIWNKHPG
460	470	480	490	500	510	520	530	540
GLFVLPQYSS	YLGDFPYYYA	NLGLKPPSKF	TAVIHAVTPL	VSQSQPV LKL	LVAAAKSQYC	AQIIVLWNC	KPLPAKHRWP	ATAVPVVVIE
550	560	570	580	590	600	610	620	630
GESKVMSSRF	LPYDNIITDA	VLSLDEDTV	STTEVDFAFT	VWQSFPERIV	GYPARSHFWD	NSKERWGYTS	KWTNDYSMVL	TGAAIYHKYY
640	650	660	670	680	690	700	710	720
HYLYSHYLPA	SLKNMVDQLA	NCEDILMNFL	VSAVTKLPPI	KVTQKKQYKE	TMMGQTSRAS	RWADPDHFAQ	RQSCMNTFAS	WFGYMPLIHS
730	740							
QMRLDPVLFK	DQVSILRKKY	RDIERL						

Click the “Download” link to obtain a text version of the sequence.

```
>sp|Q16394|EXT1_HUMAN Exostosin-1 OS=Homo sapiens OX=9606 GN=EXT1 PE=1 SV=2
MQAKKRYFILLSAGSCLALLFYFGGLQFRASRSHSRREEHSGRNLGHHPSPDHFWPRFPD
ALRPFVPWDQLENESSVHISPRQKRDANSSIYKGGKCRMESCFDFTLCKKNGFKVYVYP
QQKGEKIAESYQNILAAIEGSRFYTS DPSQACLFVLSLDTLDRDQLSPQYVHNLRSKVQS
LHLWNNGRNH LIFNLYSGTWPDYTEDVGF DIGQAMLAKASISTENFRPNFDVSIPLFSKD
HPRTGGERGFLKFNTIPPLRKYMLVFKGKRYLTGIGSDTRNALYHVHNGEDVLLTTCKH
GKDWQKHKDSRCDRDNTEYEKYDYREMLHNATFCLVPRGRRLGSFRFLEALQAACVPVML
SNGWELPFSEVINWNQAAVIGDERLLLQIPSTIRSIHQDKILALRQQTQFLWEAYFSSVE
KIVLTITLEIIQDRIFKHISRNSLIWNKHPGGLFVLPQYSSYLGDFPYYYANLGLKPPSKF
TAVIHAVTPLVSQSQPV LKLLVAAAKSQYCAQIIVLWNC DKPLPAKHRWPATAVPVVVIE
GESKVMSSRFLPYDNIITDAVLSLDEDTVSTTEVDFAFTVWQSFPERIVGYPARSHFWD
NSKERWGYTSKWTNDYSMVLTGAAIYHKYYHYLYSHYLPASLKNMVDQLANCEDILMNFL
VSAVTKLPPIKVTQKKQYKETMMGQTSRASRWADPDHFAQRQSCMNTFASWFGYMPLIHS
QMRLDPVLFKDQVSILRKKYRDIERL
```

Copy the peptide sequence to EMBOSS Needle and paste it into the first window.

A mutated nucleotide sequence needs to be created from which the translated mutant peptide sequence will be obtained.

In the UniProt record for EXT1, scroll to Sequence databases and select the nucleotide sequence from RefSeq (format NM_XXXXXX.X)

Sequence databases

CCDS | [CCDS6324.1](#) | RefSeq | [NP_000118.2](#) | [NM_000127.2](#)

SEQUENCE	PROTEIN	MOLECULE TYPE	STATUS
S79639 (EMBL GenBank DDBJ)	AAB62283.1 (EMBL GenBank DDBJ)	mRNA	
AK313129 (EMBL GenBank DDBJ)	BAG35949.1 (EMBL GenBank DDBJ)	mRNA	
CH471060 (EMBL GenBank DDBJ)	EAW91972.1 (EMBL GenBank DDBJ)	Genomic DNA	
BC001174 (EMBL GenBank DDBJ)	AAH01174.1 (EMBL GenBank DDBJ)	mRNA	
U70539 (EMBL GenBank DDBJ)	AAC51154.1 (EMBL GenBank DDBJ)	Genomic DNA	

[Expand table](#)

This opens the [NCBI nucleotide record for EXT1 mRNA](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nuccore/NM_000127.2). (https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nuccore/NM_000127.2). Scroll down to the “ORIGIN” section where you will find the nucleotide sequence conveniently numbered. Copy the sequence and paste it into EMBOSS Transeq.

ORIGIN

1 ggcgaccgaa cgcggcggtc ggcagcgttc gcgcgggggc ctgcgaagcg ctgctcgggg
 61 ccggcactgc ccgcggggag gacgcgccgc cgccgccacc cagcgccgcc gcccgcccg
 121 cctccagccg ggccgcccgc cgtcccgggg gccggccccg cgagcgagg agtaaacacc
 181 gccggagtct tggagccgct gcagaaggga ataaagagag atgcagggat ttgtgaggtt
 241 acggcgcccc agctgcaaga tgactagacc ggctgaaccg gggatcggct gacttgttgg
 301 aaccggagtg ctctgcacgg agagtgggtg atgagttgaa gttgccttcc cggggctcat
 361 tttccacgct gccgagagga atccgagagg caaggcaatc acttcgtctt gccattgatt
 421 gggatcggg agcttttttt ttctcccctc tctctttctt ttctcccgtc ttgttgcattg
 481 caagaaaatt acagtccgct gctcgcccgc cctgggtgcg agatattcag ccccgtctc
 541 tcccgtgcat tgtgcaacc aaagatgaaa gaccgaagg gagaaagta aagaaatcgc
 601 ccacatgccc tggatcagtc cacggcttgg ggaaggcat ccagagaagg tgggagcgga
 661 gagtttgaag tctttacagg cgggaagatg gcggactgga gctgaaagtg ttgattggga
 721 aacttgggtg attcttgtgt ttattacaa tctcttgac ccaggcagga cacatgcagg
 781 ccaaaaaacg ctatttcac ctgctctcag ctggctcttg tctcgccctt ttgttttatt
 841 tcggaggcct gcagtttagg gcatcgagga gccacagccg gagagaagaa cacagcggtg
 901 ggaatggctt gcaccacccc agtccggatc atttctggcc ccgcttcccg gacgctctgc
 961 gcccttcgt tccttgggat caattggaaa acgaggattc cagcgtgcac atttcccccc
 1021 ggcaagaagc agatgccaac tccagcatct acaaggcaa gaagtgccgc atggagtcct
 1081 gcttcgattt cacccttgc aagaaaaacg gcttcaaagt ctacgtatac ccacagcaaa
 1141 aaggggagaa aatcgccgaa agttaccaa acattctagc ggccatcgag ggctccaggt
 1201 tctacacctc ggaccccagc caggcgtgcc tctttgtcct gagtctggat actttagaca
 1261 gagaccagtt gtcacctcag tatgtgcaca atttgagatc caaagtgcag agtctccact
 1321 tgtggaacaa tggtaggaat catttaattt ttaatttata ttccggcact tggcctgact
 1381 acaccgagga cgtgggggtt gacatcggcc aggcgatgct ggccaaagcc agcatcagta
 1441 ctgaaaactt ccgacccaac tttgatggtt ctattcccct cttttctaag gatcatcca
 1501 ggacaggagg ggagaggggg tttttgaagt tcaacacat ccctcctctc aggaagtaca
 1561 tgctggtatt caaggggaag aggtacctga cagggatagg atcagacacc agaatgcct
 1621 tatacacgtt ccataacggg gaggacgttg tgctcctcac cacctgcaag catggcaaa
 1681 actggcaaaa gcacaaggat tctcgtgtg acagagacaa caccgagtat gagaagtatg
 1741 attatcggga aatgctgcac aatgccactt tctgtctggt tctcgtggt cgcaggcttg
 1801 ggtccttcag attcctggag gctttgcagg ctgcctgcgt ccctgtgatg ctcagcaatg
 1861 gatgggagtt gccattctct gaagtatta attggaacca agctgccgtc ataggcgatg
 1921 agagattggt attacagatt cttctacaa tcaggcttat tcatcaggat aaaatcctag
 1981 cacttagaca gcagacacaa ttcttgggg aggttattt ttcttcagtt gagaagattg
 2041 tattaactac actagagatt attcaggaca gaatttcaa gcacatatca cgtaacagtt
 2101 taatatggaa caaacatcct ggaggattgt tcgtactacc acagtattca tcttatctgg
 2161 gagattttcc ttactactat gctaatttag gtttaaagcc cccctccaaa ttcactgcag
 2221 tcatccatgc ggtgaccccc ctggtctctc agtcccagcc agtgttgaag cttctcgtgg
 2281 ctgcagccaa gtcccagtac tgtgccaga tcatagttct atggaattgt gacaagcccc
 2341 taccagccaa acaccgtgg cctgccactg ctgtgcctgt cgtcgtcatt gaaggagaga
 2401 gcaaggttat gagcagccgt tttctgcctt acgacaacat catcacagac gccgtgtca
 2461 gccttgacga ggacacgggt ctttcaacaa cagaggtgga tttcgcctc acagtgtggc
 2521 agagcttccc tgagaggatt gtgggtacc ccgcgcgag ccacttctgg gataactcta
 2581 aggagcggtg gggatacaca tcaaagtgga cgaacgacta ctccatggtg ttgacaggag
 2641 ctgctattta ccacaaatat tatcactacc tatactccca ttacctgcca gccagcctga
 2701 agaacatggt ggaccaattg gccaattgtg aggacattct catgaacttc ctgggtgctg
 2761 ctgtgacaaa attgcctcca atcaaagtga cccagaagaa gcagtataag gagacaatga
 2821 tgggacagac ttctcgggct tcccgttggg ctgaccctga ccactttgcc cagcgacaga
 2881 gctgcatgaa tacgtttgcc agctggtttg gctacatgcc gctgatccac tctcagatga
 2941 ggctcgacc cgtcctcttt aaagaccagg tctctatttt gaggaagaaa taccgagaca
 3001 ttgagcgact ttgaggaatc cggctgagtg ggggagggga agcaagaagg gatgggggtc
 3061 aagctgctct ctcttcccag tgcagatcca ctcatcagca gagccagatt gtgccaacta
 3121 tccaaaaact tagatgagca gaatgacaaa aaaaaaagg ccaatgagaa ctcaactcct
 3181 ggctcctggg actgcaccag actgctcaa actcacctca ctggcttctg tgtcccaaga
 3241 ctaggttgtg tacagtttaa ttatggaaca ttaaataatt atttttgaaa tgattgctat
 3301 gcaggtttaa acttttttaa tgatcaaac tattaanaac cagagttctt tgtttaatca
 3361 aaaaaaaaa aaaaaa

In the Transeq window where the sequence is copied to, edit the nucleotide sequence according to evidence from literature. The coding sequence in the RefSeq record starts at position 774. The nucleotide change, from literature, is a 1-bp thymidine deletion at 1469 ([Philippe et al. 1997](#)] (table 2), [Ahn et al. 1995](#)] (Fig.6)).

Table 2

Characteristics of EXT1 and EXT2 Gene Defects in Patients with Multiple Exostoses

Family	Location of Mutation	Mutation	Consequence	Name of Mutation ^a
Familial cases:				
1	EXT1/Intron 5	TAG g ta→TAGata	Altered splicing	1417 (+1G→A)
2	EXT2/Exon 4	TAC→TAG(Tyr→Stop)	Nonsense	Y222X
6	EXT2/Exon 4	GAT→AAT (Asp→Asn)	Missense	D227N
9	EXT1/Exon 3	TGG→TGA (Trp→Stop)	Nonsense	W374X
19	EXT2/Exon 2	TATATC→TATTATC	Frameshift	77- or 78insT
21	EXT1/Exon2	GGT→GAT (Gly→Asp)	Missense	G339D
25	EXT2/Exon4	GAT→AAT (Asp→Asn)	Missense	D227N
36	EXT1/Exon 6	CCCCCCTGG→CCCCCGG	Frameshift	1469delT ^b
Isolated cases (<i>de novo</i> mutations):				
5	EXT1/Exon 6	CCCCCCTGG→CCCCCGG	Frameshift	1469delT ^b
7	EXT2/ Exon 8	CAG→TAG (Glu→Stop)	Nonsense	Q401X
13	EXT1/Exon 1	GCTTCCCGG→GCTTCCGG	Frameshift	174-, 175- or 176delC
35	EXT1/Exon 2	CGC→TGC (Arg→Cys)	Missense	R340C

^a According to the nomenclature defined by Beaudet and Tsui (1993). For both EXT1 and EXT2, base no. 1 corresponds to the first base of the initiation codon in the cDNA sequences (Ahn et al. 1995; Stickens et al. 1996; Wuyts et al. 1996).

^b Already reported by Ahn et al. (1995) and by Wells et al. (1997).

Fig. 6 Analysis of the *EXT1* mutation in family D. Direct sequencing of the PCR products amplified from genomic DNA with the 'forward' primer (see Methods). a, Sequence of a healthy individual corresponding to nucleotides 2113-2128 of the cDNA. b, Patient HD (individual I2) is heterozygous for the 1-bp deletion (T) at position 2120 of the cDNA. c, Segregation analysis in family D. The PCR products were digested with *MspI* and separated on an agarose gel. DNAs of healthy family members remain uncut whereas approximately half of the PCR products from affected individuals are cut into 159- and 139-bp fragments. The point mutation cosegregates with the disease in family D and has been verified by direct sequencing in all family members.

Many times in literature, researchers only use the coding sequence in their experiments and count from that point onwards to the mutation site. As the coding sequence starts at 774, add that to 1469 (the deletion position) which equals 2243. Check this region in the sequence pasted into TranSeq. The region matches that found in literature. Delete the t after the 6 c's and submit the job.

(Note, TranSeq can translate your sequence in any of the 6 reading frames. If you don't know which frame your initiator methionine is, you can translate the WT seq in all 3 forward reading frames and search the results for the amino acid sequence of the WT protein to orient yourself before submitting the variant allele DNA as described in the figure below.)

EMBOSS Transeq

EMBOSS Transeq translates nucleic acid sequences to their corresponding protein translations at once.

STEP 1 - Enter your input sequence

Enter or paste a set of sequences in any supported format:

```
1981 cacttagaca gcagacacaa ttcttgagg aggcttatt ttctcagtt gagaagattg
2041 tattaactac actagagatt attcaggaca gaattattca gcacatatca cgtaacagtt
2101 taatatggaa caacatcct ggaggattgt tctactacc acagtattca tctatctgg
2161 gagattttcc ttactactat gctaatag gttaaagcc ccctccaaa ttactgcag
2221 tcatccatgc ggtgaccccc ctggctctc agtcccagcc agtgtgaag ctctcgtgg
2281 ctgcagcaa gtccagtac tggcccaga tcatagttct atggaattgt gacaagcccc
2341 taccagcaa acaccgctgg cctgccactg ctgtgctgt cgtcgtcatt gaaggagaga
2401 cccccctt cccccctt cccccctt cccccctt cccccctt cccccctt cccccctt
```

Deleting a sequence in TranSeq

The result is below. Copy the mutant peptide sequence from the start to the first stop (“*”) in the sequence

```
>EMBOSS_001_3
RPNAAVGSVRAGACEALLGAGTARGEDAPPPPPSAAAAAASSRAAARPGGRPRERRSKHR
RSLGAAAEGNKERCDDL*GYGAPAARCTSRNLNPGSADLLEPECSARRVVDELKLPGRGSF
STLPRGIREARQSLRLAIDWVSGAFFSPLSFSSVLLHARKLQSAARPPWRDIQPRSL
PCIVQPKDERPKGRKLLKKSPTCAGSVHGLGKGIQRRWERRV*SLYRREDGGLELKVLIK
LG*FLCLFTILLTQAGHMQAkkRYFILLSAGSCLALLFYFGGLQFRASRSHSRREEHSGR
NGLHHPSPDHFWRFPDRLRPFVWDQLENESSVHISPRQKRANSSIIYKGGKCRMESC
FDFTLCKKNGFKVYVYPQKGEKIAESYQNILAAIEGSRFYTS DPSQA CLFVLSLDTLDR
DQLSPQYVHNLRSKVQSLHLWNNGRNHLIFNLVSGTWPDYTEDVGFIDIGQAMLAKASIST
ENFRPNFDVSIPLFSKDHPRGTGGERGFLKFNTIPPLRKYMLVFKGKRYLTGIGSDTRNAL
YHVHNGEDVLLTTCKHGKDWQKHKDSRCRDNTEYEKYDYREMLHNATFCLVPRGRRLG
SFRFLEALQAACVPVMLSNWELPFSEVINWNAAVIGDERLLLQIPSTIRSIHQDKILA
LRQQTQFLWEAYFSSVEKIVLTLEIIQDRIFKHISRNSLIWNKHPGGLFVLPQYSSYLG
DFPYYYANLGLKPPSKFTAVIHAVTPRSLSPSQC*SFSWLQSPSTVPRS*FYGIVTSPY
QPNTAGLPLLCLSSSLKERARL*AAVFCPTTSSQTPCSALTRTRCFQQQRWISPSQCGR
ASLRGLWGT PRAATSGITLRSGGDTHQSGRTTTPWC*QELLFTTNIITTYTPITCQPA*R
TWTNWP IVRTFS*TSWCLL*QNCLQSK*PRRSSIRRQ*WDRLLGLPVGLTLTTLPSDRA
A*IRLPAGLATCR*STLR*GSTPSSLKTRSLF*GRNTE TLSDFEESG*VGEGKQEGMGVK
LLSLPSADPLISRARLCQLSKNLDEQNDK KKKANENSTPGSWDCTRLLQTHLTGFCVPRL
GCVQFN YGTLNNYF*NDCYAGLNFFNDQNY*KPEFFV*SKKKKKX
```

Paste into the second window of the Needle program. You had already pasted the w/t sequence (FASTA format) at the beginning of this exercise.

The first amino acid to change due to the frameshift is leucine to arginine at position 490. The altered mutant sequence after the frameshift is “RSLSPSQC” then the mutant sequence terminates. We can now fill in our FragmentReplacedModification instance.

● ● ● [FragmentReplacedModification:5357998] Replacement of residues 490 to 497 by RSLSPSQC

FragmentReplacedModification Properties	
Property Name	Value
🔗 alteredAminoAcidFragment	RSLSPSQC
📏 endPositionInReferenceSequence	497
📏 referenceSequence	UniProt:Q16394 EXT1
📏 startPositionInReferenceSequence	490
🔗 DB_ID	5357998
🔗 _displayName	Replacement of residues 490 to 497 by RSLSPSQC

After 8 altered amino acids, the 9th position is a stop (“*”). The name of the EWAS will reflect the mutation and fill in the hasModifiedResidue slot with the FragmentReplacedModification. Note that here, the end coordinate of the EWAS is changed to reflect the new C-terminal amino acid.

● ● ● [EntityWithAccessionedSequence:3730975] EXT1 L490Rfs*9 [Golgi membrane]

EntityWithAccessionedSequence Properties	
Property Name	Value
🔗 cellType	
📏 compartment	Golgi membrane
📏 endCoordinate	497
📏 hasModifiedResidue	Replacement of residues 490 to 497 by RSLSPSQC
📏 referenceEntity	UniProt:Q16394 EXT1
📏 startCoordinate	1
🔗 DB_ID	3730975
🔗 _displayName	EXT1 L490Rfs*9 [Golgi membrane]
🔗 authored	
🔗 created	Jassal, B, 2013-06-17
🔗 crossReference	
🔗 definition	
🔗 disease	hereditary multiple exostoses
🔗 edited	
🔗 figure	
🔗 goCellularComponent	
🔗 inferredFrom	
🔗 inferredTo	
🔗 literatureReference	
🔗 modified	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔗 Jassal, B, 2013-06-17 🔗 Jassal, B, 2013-06-20 🔗 Jassal, B, 2014-03-27 🔗 Jassal, B, 2014-03-28
📏 name	EXT1 L490Rfs*9 Exostosin-1 EXT1_HUMAN

Frameshifts that produce a stop in the first affected codon affected:

It is possible for a frameshift mutation to introduce an immediate stop codon. Although these should properly be annotated as frameshifts, Reactome is not able to capture a stop codon as a replaced residue, as would be required for `FragmentReplacedModification` as described [above](#) for lengthier frameshifts.

For this reason, frameshifts that produce a stop codon as the first affected codon are annotated as nonsense mutations as described [above](#).

Frameshifts that produce a stop codon in the second affected codon:

Annotated as usual for a frameshift, as described [above](#).

Mutations affecting the initiator methionine

Mutations creating a new downstream initiation site

A mutation that eliminates the initiator methionine and results in the aberrant initiation of translation from a downstream methionine is annotated as an in-frame deletion, as per HGVS recommendations, with the variant protein name specifying a deletion that stretches from the first amino acid in the reference sequence to the alternative initiator methionine.

Naming

Named in accordance with the deletion naming rules.

Format: “prefix” + “amino acid at position 2” + “2” + “_” + “M” + “position of methionine residue now used as initiator” + “del”

Where “prefix” is the HGNC gene name, the deleted amino acids are represented by single letter codes separated by underscore.

Example: SERPING1 A2_M53del - in this variant, a missense mutation substitutes the WT M1 with a leucine codon, leading to the usage of methionine at position 53 as an alternative start codon.

How to annotate

● ● ● [FragmentDeletionModification:9651392] Deletion of residues 1 to 52

FragmentDeletionModification Properties	
Property Name	Value
endPositionInReferenceSequence	52
referenceSequence	UniProt:P05155 SERPING1
startPositionInReferenceSequence	1
DB_ID	9651392
_displayName	Deletion of residues 1 to 52

Note that although by HGVS naming convention the variant EWAS is named SERPING1 A2_M53del, the FragmentDeletionModification record captures the biologically relevant deletion of residues M1-K52.

The protein variant EWAS record specifies the start coordinate as 53, without changing the end coordinate relative to the WT reference sequence.

● ● ● [EntityWithAccessionedSequence:9651435] SERPING1 A2_M53del [endoplasmic reticu...]

EntityWithAccessionedSequence Properties	
Property Name	Value
cellType	
compartment	endoplasmic reticulum lumen
endCoordinate	500
hasModifiedResidue	Deletion of residues 1 to 52
referenceEntity	UniProt:P05155 SERPING1
startCoordinate	53
DB_ID	9651435
_displayName	SERPING1 A2_M53del [endoplasmic reticulum lumen]
authored	
created	Shamovsky, Veronica, 2019-06-25
crossReference	ClinVar:VCV000626353
definition	
disease	C1 inhibitor deficiency
edited	
figure	
goCellularComponent	
inferredFrom	
inferredTo	
literatureReference	Targeted next-generation sequencing for the mol... F12-46C/T polymorphism as modifier of the clini... Shamovsky, Veronica, 2020-01-10
modified	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2023-03-16 Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2023-03-17 Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2023-03-22
name	SERPING1 A2_M53del C1Inh A2_M53del plasma protease C1 inhibitor A2_M53del C1-In A2_M53del SERPING1 M1L SERPING1 Met1Leu

If a gene translocation fuses the promoter of one gene with the coding sequence of another gene, with accompanying truncation of the N' terminal coding sequence of the C-terminal fusion partner, the resulting disease variant is annotated as described above for mutations affecting the initiator methionine. The only such example in Reactome is the NOTCH1 variant NOTCH1 P2_M1580del (commonly known as TAN-1), which results from a translocation t(7;9) that fuses the promoter of T cell receptor beta to intron 24 of NOTCH1, resulting in the usage of an alternative start codon at position 1580 of the reference NOTCH1 sequence.

[FragmentDeletionModification:9830728] Deletion of residues 1 to 1579	
FragmentDeletionModification Properties	
Property Name	Value
endPositionInReferenceSequence	1579
referenceSequence	UniProt:P46531 NOTCH1
startPositionInReferenceSequence	1
DB_ID	9830728
_displayName	Deletion of residues 1 to 1579

[EntityWithAccessionedSequence:2220929] NOTCH1 P2_M1580del extracellula...	
EntityWithAccessionedSequence Properties	
Property Name	Value
cellType	
compartment	extracellular region
endCoordinate	1664
hasModifiedResidue	Deletion of residues 1 to 1579
referenceEntity	UniProt:P46531 NOTCH1
startCoordinate	1580
DB_ID	2220929
_displayName	NOTCH1 P2_M1580del extracellular fragment [e...

Mutations activating an upstream methionine initiation site.

A mutation that eliminates the initiator methionine and results in the aberrant initiation of translation from an upstream methionine is annotated as an insertion.

Naming

Named in accordance with insertion rules, above.

Format: “prefix” “amino_acids+positions_flanking” “ins” “inserted_sequence”

Where “prefix” is the HGNC gene name, the amino acids flanking the insertion are represented by single letter codes separated by underscore, and the inserted sequence is listed as single letter amino acid codes.

How to annotate

Annotate as for an insertion, with a FragmentInsertionModification, but preserve methionine 1 from the WT sequence and delete the novel initiator methionine to accommodate HGVS guidelines as described below:

As an example (made up, not annotated in Reactome)

WT coding sequence *MRSTMLRSQ...* (WT initiating M in blue, upstream sequence in small italics)

Mutation in the initiator M changes it to V, and activates the methionine four amino acids upstream:

*MRSTV*LRSQ - this is what really happens, blue M converted to blue V, and inclusion in the coding sequence of upstream MRST.

By HGVS convention, this is actually annotated as:

*MRSTV*LRSQ - insertion of RSTV between the 'original' M and the second position amino acid (L).

Extension variants

The only currently annotated extension variant is IKBKG *420Wext*447, which represents a 3' extension, with replacement of the stop codon at position 420 with tryptophan codon and extension of the protein sequence by a total of 27 amino acids, with a new stop codon at position 447, counting from the start codon of the reference wild-type protein sequence.

How to annotate

Both 3' and 5' extensions can be annotated using `FragmentReplacedModification` class. In the case of 3' extensions, the wild-type stop codon coordinate is specified as the start and end coordinate of the replacement, and the added stretch of amino acids, in single letter abbreviations, is defined in the `alteredAminoAcidFragment` attribute. In the case of 5' extensions, the -1 would be specified as the start and end coordinate of the replacement.

 [FragmentReplacedModification:5262861] Replacement of residues 420 to 420 by WGRPVQGHCLPRTCPGPCSLRPFLPPA

FragmentReplacedModification Properties	
Property Name	Value
<code>alteredAminoAcidFragment</code>	WGRPVQGHCLPRTCPGPCSLRPFLPPA
<code>endPositionInReferenceSequence</code>	420
UniProt:Q9Y6K9 IKBKG	
<code>startPositionInReferenceSequence</code>	420
<code>DB_ID</code>	5262861
<code>_displayName</code>	Replacement of residues 420 to 420 by WGRPVQGHCLPRTCPGPCSLRPFLPPA
Shamovsky, V, 2014-02-09	

On the EWAS record, the stop codon is changed relative to the WT reference sequence to reflect the extension.

[EntityWithAccessionedSequence:5262978] IKBKG *420Wext*447 [cytosol]	
EntityWithAccessionedSequence Properties	
Property Name	Value
cellType	
compartment	cytosol
endCoordinate	446
hasModifiedResidue	Replacement of residues 420 to 420 by WGRPVQGHCLPRTCPGPCSLRPFLPPA
referenceEntity	UniProt:Q9Y6K9 IKBKG
startCoordinate	1
DB_ID	5262978
displayName	IKBKG *420Wext*447 [cytosol]
authored	
created	Shamovsky, V, 2014-02-09
crossReference	
definition	
disease	primary immunodeficiency disease
edited	
figure	
goCellularComponent	
inferredFrom	
inferredTo	
literatureReference	X-linked anhidrotic ectodermal dysplasia with immunodeficiency is caused b... Shamovsky, Veronica, 2014-07-14 Shamovsky, Veronica, 2014-12-08 Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2023-02-06
modified	IKBKG *420Wext*447 NEMO *420Wext*447 IKKG X420WextX447
name	IKK-gamma X420W Inhibitor of nuclear factor kappa-B kinase gamma subunit IKBKG *420Trpext*447 IKBKG Ter420TrpextTer447

Splicing variants

Splicing variants, if the exact effect of the mutation has been determined experimentally at the protein level, are annotated in one of the previously described categories, depending on the consequence of the splicing mutation on the amino acid sequence, and named accordingly, as HGVS currently does not provide guidelines for nomenclature of splicing variants at the protein level. This also applies to inversion variants. Of the 6 splicing variants currently annotated in Reactome, four are annotated as frameshift variants (EXT2 A361Pfs*44, NF1 Q616Gfs*4, NF1 R69Nfs*7, and UNC93B1 L230Afs*188), one is annotated as an in-frame insertion (POMT2 I444_N445insLLWQ), and one as an in-frame deletion (SLC11A2 L104_P142del). Two inversion variants currently annotated in Reactome, F8 A20_M2143delinsMRIQDPGK and F8 V2144_Y2351delinsHGVLENGKNWEPSYRW, are annotated as in-frame indels, as their names imply.

Variants with multiple in-cis mutations

These usually contain a primary mutation and a secondary mutation that was selected for during the course of treatment with target therapy as a drug-resistance mechanism. Each mutation is annotated independently and they are separated with a semicolon in the disease variant name, e.g. EGFR E746_A750del;T790M, where T790M is a mutation associated with resistance to small tyrosine kinase inhibitors.

Guideline for automated annotation of disease variants

Automated annotation of disease variants in Reactome proceeds through the following steps:

- 1) Starting from manually annotated disease variants grouped into functional sets, define external database-derived and/or literature-derived variants with matching disease association that conform to Reactome-expanded ACMG criterion PM5 or to combined ACMG criteria PM1 and PM4.
- 2) Categorize variants of interest by mutation type (missense, nonsense, etc.).
- 3) Run the script that creates individual disease variant records for automatic upload to the Reactome Curator Tool.
- 4) Import automatically annotated disease variants into existing disease variant functional sets.
- 5) Expanded disease variant functional sets are readily displayed in interactive pathway diagrams.

References

1. Philippe C, Porter DE, Emerton ME, Wells DE, Simpson AH, Monaco AP. Mutation screening of the EXT1 and EXT2 genes in patients with hereditary multiple exostoses. *Am J Hum Genet.* 1997 Sep;61(3):520-8. doi: 10.1086/515505. PMID: 9326317; PMCID: PMC1715939.
2. Ahn J, Lüdecke HJ, Lindow S, Horton WA, Lee B, Wagner MJ, Horsthemke B, Wells DE. Cloning of the putative tumour suppressor gene for hereditary multiple exostoses (EXT1). *Nat Genet.* 1995 Oct;11(2):137-43. doi: 10.1038/ng1095-137. PMID: 7550340.

ADDING CROSS-REFERENCES TO DISEASE ENTITIES

We cross reference disease entities to [COSMIC](https://cancer.sanger.ac.uk/cosmic) (cancer-associated mutations; <https://cancer.sanger.ac.uk/cosmic>) and/or [ClinGen](https://reg.clinicalgenome.org/redmine/projects/registry/genboree_registry/landing) (https://reg.clinicalgenome.org/redmine/projects/registry/genboree_registry/landing) where appropriate. An entity can have as many cross-references as needed. COSMIC cross-referencing should make use of the Genomic Mutation ID where available, not the Legacy Identifier. ClinGen Canonical Allele (CA) identifiers are used wherever possible, but ClinVar IDs may be used if CA IDs are not available.

FINAL STEPS

Once your curation is done, you will need to add your pathway into the Disease hierarchy in the relevant subpathway. Check out the disease chapter, add your pathway to the proper spot in the subpathways (or create a new child of Disease pathway, if appropriate) and commit the Disease chapter back into gk_central.

You will also have to check if any parent pathway EHLs or the Disease parent EHL requires updating to accommodate your new disease pathway. Coordinate with Cris to incorporate your updates to any EHLs. Update any affected pathway summations to incorporate your new pathway.

INFECTIOUS DISEASE AND INNATE IMMUNE SYSTEM PATHWAY CURATION GUIDE

The Reactome's concept of host-pathogen interactions refers to the relationship between a host organism and a pathogen (which can be any microorganism) at the

molecular level. These interactions involve the recognition of the pathogen by the host's immune system, the activation of immune responses, and the evasion strategies employed by pathogens to avoid detection and destruction by the host's immune system.

We have set the disease / normal boundary by asking what the outcome of the host-pathogen interaction is. If the host wins and the pathogen is really neutralized, that counts as normal. If the pathogen wins to cause overt infection or to establish a stable latent state that could result in disease later, that counts as disease.

Entry and growth of pathogenic microorganisms within the host cell (e.g., HIV life cycle) also counts as disease and is annotated as a part of the "Infectious Diseases" module (see [above](#)).

In most cases, interactions involving host and pathogen entities are captured as a binding between the host PE (e.g., EWAS or a complex) and a pathogen-associated molecular pattern (PAMP), which could be a wide range of molecules found in pathogens. Examples of PAMPs include bacterial lipopolysaccharides, viral nucleic acids, and fungal cell wall components.

ANNOTATING PHYSICAL ENTITIES

1. Genomic, transcript, and protein sequences, including those of microbial origin, are annotated as EWASs which have their referenceEntity slot filled in with referenceSequence instance containing NCBI nucleotide, ENSEMBL, EMBL or UniProt identifier.
 - Note: Microbial nucleic acids can be annotated as direct children of GenomeEncodedEntity (GEE) class with microbial species assigned.
2. A simpleEntity should be used to annotate molecules such as bacterial lipopolysaccharides, peptidoglycans or fungal mannans. A referenceEntity is filled with a referenceMolecule instance containing a ChEBI identifier.

ASSIGNING COMPARTMENT FOR ENTITIES OF MICROBIAL ORIGIN

We assign location on Reactome instances using GO compartment terms. The GO terms allow to distinguish Pathogen associated molecular patterns (PAMP) molecule locations in the pathogen compartments (e.g., "cell wall" or "virion membrane") and locations in infected host cells (e.g., "host cell endoplasmic reticulum membrane", "host cell cytosol"). The GO terms distinguish these locations of PAMPs from locations of endogenous host proteins in a normal cell ("endoplasmic reticulum membrane", "cytosol" etc.).

In contrast to GO, we use normal cell terms (for example, "endoplasmic reticulum membrane" and **not** "host cell endoplasmic reticulum membrane") to localize virus- or bacteria- or other pathogen-derived entities in an infected cell.

The GO terms that are used to localize proteins in a normal cell are listed in the Compartment class. Thus,

1. The compartment slot must be filled with a GO term from the Compartment list which includes those involving pathogen/symbiont patterns.
2. When the species slot value for a PE is a pathogen species and the compartment slot value is a normal cell term, then the **goCellularComponent** slot of that PE should also be filled with the GO "host cell [compartment]" term corresponding to the one chosen for the entity.
3. The Compartment list also includes GO terms that describe parts of bacteria or viruses ("cell wall", "viral capsid"). These terms can be also used to assign compartments for pathogen-derived entities.
 - Note: Individual pathogen proteins/entities localized in pathogen compartments ("viral capsid", "virion membrane") may form a complex, which functions in the host compartment. In this case, the record of the complex with microbial components should have a normal cell compartment term (e.g., "extracellular region").
 - The goCellularComponent slots in PE records of these pathogen-derived entities can be filled in with a GO "host cell compartment"

Complex Properties	
Property Name	Value
cellType	
hasComponent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 x 7a:O-glycosyl 3a tetramer [virion membrane] 1 x S3:M lattice:E protein [virion membrane] 1 x encapsidated SARS-CoV-2 genomic RNA [viral capsid]
DB_ID	9694500
displayName	S3:M:encapsidated SARS-CoV-2 genomic RNA: 7a:O-glycosyl 3a tetramer [extracellular region]
authored	
compartment	extracellular region
created	Cook, Justin, 2020-07-07
crossReference	
definition	
disease	COVID-19
edited	
entityOnOtherCell	
figure	
goCellularComponent	
includedLocation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> viral capsid virion membrane
inferredFrom	S3:M:encapsidated SARS coronavirus genomic RNA: 7a:O-glycosyl 3a tetramer [extracellular region]
inferredTo	
isChimeric	false
literatureReference	
modified	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Orlic-Milacic, Marja, 2020-07-28 Gillespie, Marc E, 2020-08-14 Rothfels, Karen, 2020-08-28 Rothfels, Karen, 2021-09-01
name	S3:M:encapsidated SARS-CoV-2 genomic RNA: 7a:O-glycosyl 3a tetramer
relatedSpecies	
reviewed	
revised	
species	Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2
stabledentifier	R-COV-9694500.2
stoichiometryKnown	

term to depict their roles as invaders of a host cell.

- Note: A complex involving a pathogen protein/entity and host PE(s) should have a host compartment assigned, while microbial compartments assigned to individual components will be automatically added in the includedLocation slot.

ASSIGNING SPECIES IN PEs, PATHWAYS AND REACTIONS THAT INVOLVE HOST-PATHOGEN INTERACTIONS

1. The “species” slot on the event identifies the environment where the reaction is happening. This should almost always be human for human Reactome curation. The exceptions are when we have annotated reactions (RLEs) in other species for inference (e.g Mus) or when we are specifically annotating another species pathways as part of another project (e.g Gallus and Mycobacterium tuberculosis).

In disease or immune system processes that involve host-pathogen interactions the host would be listed as the “species” in the records of RLE and complexes, which are formed by host and pathogen entities.

- Note: When creating a chimeric reaction to be used for inference (i.e one that involves entities from multiple species and (usually) observed in vitro) ALL species should be listed in the species slot.
- Note: A complex involving only simpleEntities should have NO species listed. A complex involving a pathogen protein/entity and simpleEntity or an OtherEntity (i.e not having a species) should have the pathogen species listed in the species attribute and no relatedSpecies.

2. The “related species” is used to tag the source (or sources) of genome-encoded entities from “elsewhere” that act as “bystanders” in a process. In disease or immune system processes, the pathogen(s) would be listed as “relatedSpecies” in RLEs and complex instances.

- Note: relatedSpecies value(s) specified in RLEs should be assigned to a first parent pathway.

3. The use of "species" and "relatedSpecies" in sets follows the same rule as for complexes and events.

- Note: When the set members contain participants from different non-host pathogen species, ALL microbial species should be listed in the species slot.
- Note: If your annotations involve a species that is new to Reactome, please contact Peter D'Eustachio as it will need to have an abbreviation assigned by him.

ASSIGNING A DISEASE TERM FOR ENTITIES AND REACTIONS THAT INVOLVE HOST-PATHOGEN INTERACTIONS

1. For all kinds of pathogen entities in human (or other host) pathways the disease slots are filled in with a value corresponding to the disease they would cause if not neutralized. The effect of this rule is to automatically color all pathogenic entities red, both when they are involved in a disease and also when they are in the process of being detected and neutralized by the innate immune system.

2. Assigning a disease value for complexes and reactions depends on the outcome of the host-pathogen interaction.

2a. In the disease-preventing innate immune reactions (e.g., [E. coli flagellin binds to human TLR5](#) (R-HSA-188025) as part of the human TLR cascade) the disease slot is not filled thus leaving a reaction with its default value (black, normal). Complexes formed between pathogen entities and the host ones that detect and neutralize them have empty disease slot, so in a normal reaction a red (disease) pathogen gets incorporated into a default (black, normal) pathogen : human receptor complex.

2b. In a disease-causing event (e.g., uptake of diphtheria toxin, Corynebacterium beta, which enters and destroys the human cell), a pathogen-derived entity (a disease slot is filled in) interacts with a normal host cell protein (default) to form an abnormal complex (a disease slot is filled in). A reaction-like event for an infectious disease process has a non-null disease slot value thus coloring its edges and nodes red. The entities will be automatically colored red if they are from a pathogen or complexes of human and pathogen proteins. Normal human entities that participate in these reactions are default (black).

2c. Disease-causing events are placed under disease, either infectious disease or diseases of a corresponding normal pathway. Disease host-pathogen interaction pathways have their own diagrams.

EXAMPLES OF HOST-PATHOGEN INTERACTIONS:

1. [C-ter TLR7 dimer binds TLR7, TLR8 ligands \(reaction\)](#) (R-HSA-167983)

Here a defined set of viral single stranded RNAs binds a human TLR7, setting off events that neutralize viruses and leave the human healthy – in our human-centric view, a normal process.

The reaction record lists all viruses in the 'relatedSpecies' slot, while human is indicated as the host in the species slot. The disease value is NULL.

Reaction Properties	
Property Name	Value
catalystActivity	
deletedInstanceDB_ID	
entityFunctionalStatus	
input	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊕ 1 x C-ter TLR7 dimer [endosome membrane] ⊕ 1 x TLR7, TLR8 ligands [endosome lumen]
output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊕ 1 x C-ter TLR7 dimer:TLR7, TLR8 ligands [endos...
DB_ID	167983
_displayName	C-ter TLR7 dimer binds TLR7, TLR8 ligands
_doRelease	true
authored	⊕ Luo, F, 2005-11-10 11:23:18
catalystActivityReference	
compartment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊕ endosome membrane ⊕ endosome lumen
created	⊕ Gillespie, ME, 2005-11-10 16:24:09
crossReference	
definition	
deletedStableIdentifier	
disease	
edited	⊕ Shamovsky, V, 2011-08-12
entityOnOtherCell	
evidenceType	
name	C-ter TLR7 dimer binds TLR7, TLR8 ligands
negativePrecedingEvent	
normalReaction	
orthologousEvent	
precedingEvent	
previousReviewStatus	
reactionType	
regulatedBy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊕ Negative regulation by 'C-ter TLR7 dimer:HCQ [e...
regulationReference	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊕ Negative regulation by 'C-ter TLR7 dimer:HCQ [e... ⊕ Human SARS coronavirus ⊕ Human immunodeficiency virus 1 ⊕ Influenza A virus ⊕ Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2
relatedSpecies	
releaseDate	2010-12-14
releaseStatus	
requiredInputComponent	
reverseReaction	
reviewStatus	⊕ five stars
reviewed	⊕ Gay, NJ, 2006-04-24 16:48:17
revised	
species	⊕ Homo sapiens
stableIdentifier	⊕ R-HSA-167983.5
structureModified	

In this reaction, a viral ssRNA is annotated as GenomeEncodedEntity (GEE) for each virus. Viral EWASs are combined in the defined set, listing all microbial species in the “species” slot, and all disease values in the disease slot. The compartment slot is filled in with “endosome lumen”, while goCellularComponent indicates that this PE is located in “host cell endosome lumen”.

[DefinedSet:9684903] GU-rich ssRNA [endosome lumen]	
Property Name	Value
cellType	SARS-CoV-1 GU-rich ssRNA [endosome lumen] HIV1 GU-rich ssRNA [endosome lumen] Influenza GU-rich ssRNA [endosome lumen] SARS-CoV-2 GU-rich ssRNA [endosome lumen]
DB_ID	9684903
displayName	GU-rich ssRNA [endosome lumen]
authored	endosome lumen
created	Shamovsky, Veronica, 2020-04-22
crossReference	
definition	Human immunodeficiency virus infectious disease influenza severe acute respiratory syndrome COVID-19 viral infectious disease
disease	
edited	
figure	
goCellularComponent	host cell endosome lumen
inferredFrom	
inferredTo	
isOrdered	
literatureReference	Cook, Justin, 2020-05-15 Cook, Justin, 2020-05-15 Shamovsky, Veronica, 2020-08-21 Shorser, Solomon, 2021-02-17 Shorser, Solomon, 2021-05-05 Weiser, JD, 2021-08-11 Shamovsky, Veronica, 2021-10-02 Weiser, JD, 2021-11-08 Wright, Adam, 2022-02-25 Shamovsky, Veronica, 2022-03-03 Weiser, Joel, 2022-05-04
modified	
name	GU-rich ssRNA
relatedSpecies	
reviewed	
revised	
species	Human SARS coronavirus Human immunodeficiency virus 1 Influenza A virus Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2
stableIdentifier	R-NUL-9684903.8

[GenomeEncodedEntity:9684900] HIV1 GU-rich ssRNA [endoso...]	
Property Name	Value
cellType	
compartment	endosome lumen
name	HIV1 GU-rich ssRNA
species	Human immunodeficiency virus 1
DB_ID	9684900
displayName	HIV1 GU-rich ssRNA [endosome lumen]
authored	
created	Shamovsky, Veronica, 2020-04-22
crossReference	CHEBI:33697
definition	Human immunodeficiency virus infectious disease viral infectious disease
disease	
edited	
figure	
goCellularComponent	host cell endosome lumen
inferredFrom	
inferredTo	
literatureReference	
modified	Shamovsky, Veronica, 2020-08-21
reviewed	
revised	
stableIdentifier	R-HV-9684900.2

[GenomeEncodedEntity:9754729] SARS-CoV-2 GU-rich ssRNA [...]	
Property Name	Value
compartment	endosome lumen
name	SARS-CoV-2 GU-rich ssRNA
species	Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2
DB_ID	9754729
displayName	SARS-CoV-2 GU-rich ssRNA [endosome lumen]
authored	
created	Shamovsky, Veronica, 2021-10-02
crossReference	CHEBI:33697
definition	COVID-19 viral infectious disease
disease	
edited	
figure	
goCellularComponent	host cell endosome lumen
inferredFrom	
inferredTo	
literatureReference	
modified	Shamovsky, Veronica, 2022-02-28 Weiser, Joel, 2022-05-04
reviewed	
revised	
stableIdentifier	R-COV-9754729.3

The resulting complex of the human TLR7 homodimer and viral ssRNA has values similar to the reaction record:

[Complex:188132] C-ter TLR7 dimer:TLR7, TLR8 ligands [endosome membrane]	
Property Name	Value
hasComponent	1 x C-ter TLR7 dimer [endosome membrane] 1 x TLR7, TLR8 ligands [endosome lumen]
DB_ID	188132
displayName	C-ter TLR7 dimer:TLR7, TLR8 ligands [endoso...
authored	
compartment	endosome membrane
created	de Bono, B, 2006-09-30 14:23:12
crossReference	
definition	
disease	
edited	
entityOnOtherCell	
figure	
goCellularComponent	
includedLocation	
inferredFrom	
inferredTo	
isChimeric	
literatureReference	Homology modeling of human Toll-like rece... Comparative analysis of species-specific lig... Human TLR7 or TLR8 independently confer... Species-specific recognition of single-stran... de Bono, B, 2006-09-30 14:57:57 Shamovsky, V, 2010-09-22 Shamovsky, V, 2011-09-06 Shamovsky, V, 2011-10-19 Shamovsky, V, 2011-10-20 Shamovsky, V, 2012-08-08 Shamovsky, Veronica, 2020-04-22 Shamovsky, Veronica, 2020-05-06 Jassal, Bijay, 2020-06-09 Shamovsky, Veronica, 2022-02-28
modified	
name	C-ter TLR7 dimer:TLR7, TLR8 ligands
relatedSpecies	Human SARS coronavirus Human immunodeficiency virus 1 Influenza A virus Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavi...
reviewed	
revised	
species	Homo sapiens
stableIdentifier	R-HSA-188132.4

2. [Translocation of Vpr to the mitochondria](#) (Reaction: R-HSA-180855)

Here an HIV protein is translocated to the mitochondria and while no human proteins are involved, the **species** listed for this reaction should still be human because it is a RLE occurring in the context of a human process.

The **relatedSpecies** should be Human immunodeficiency virus 1.

The **disease slot** is filled in with 'human immunodeficiency virus infectious disease':

3. [Uptake and function of diphtheria toxin](#) (Pathway: R-HSA-5336415)

As in case 1, the process is occurring in a human, so the pathway "species" is human involving a diphtheria protein (Corynephage beta). In this case, the result is that the bacterial protein enters and destroys the human cell – in our human-centric view, a disease process. The pathway records are filled in as follows:

species: Homo sapiens **relatedSpecies:** Corynephage beta **disease:** diphtheria

4. Host physical entity is transferred into a pathogen cell.

Consistent with the logic in case 1, 2 and 3, the following reactions are part of the human process, so it is reasonable to label them as human reactions, even in cases in which reactions are occurring inside the bacterium.

a. [Cathelicidin LL-37 localizes to bacterial cell wall](#) (Reaction: R-HSA-1222685)

species: Homo sapiens **relatedSpecies:** Mycobacterium tuberculosis **disease:** NULL

b. [Nitric oxide enters the bacterium](#) (Reaction: R-HSA-1222662)

species: Homo sapiens **relatedSpecies:** Mycobacterium tuberculosis **disease:** NULL

- Note: When a reaction involves only SimpleEntities (e.g., case 4b), RLE instance goes on skip list because QA check will detect a conflict because there are no human entities specified as reaction components.

5. [Cry proteins stabilize unphosphorylated Bmal1:Clock,Npas2](#) (Reaction: R-MMU-549451)

Here, the reaction describes a process occurring in a non-human species (Mus) and *only* mouse proteins are involved.

species: Mus musculus **relatedSpecies:** NULL **disease:** NULL

The environment is mouse, the proteins are mouse, and success in the event keeps the mouse healthy. So this is a normal reaction whose species is mouse and whose related species is NULL.

[Additional information about these attributes and examples of how the species and relatedSpecies attributes are used in disease and normal curation can be found [here](#).]

FINAL STEPS

Once your curation is done, you will need to add your pathway into the Disease hierarchy in the relevant subpathway. Check out the disease chapter, add your pathway to the proper spot in the subpathways (or create a new child of Disease pathway, if appropriate) and commit the Disease chapter back into gk_central.

You will also have to check if any parent pathway EHLs or the Disease parent EHL requires updating to accommodate your new disease pathway. Coordinate with Cris to incorporate your updates to any EHLs. Update any affected pathway summations to incorporate your new pathway.

DRUG CURATION GUIDE

GENERAL POINTS

When annotating drugs used to treat a particular disease, curators should add an appropriate disease tag to a drug entity. For a cancer drug, the general cancer disease attribute should definitely be added, but when it comes to more specific disease tags, it may be advisable to add only those cancer types for which the treatment by a given drug is approved.

In **most** cases, a drug will affect a target protein after it binds to it. Therefore, it will usually be the case that two steps are needed for any drug curated; a drug binding event to the target then whatever effect (in the form of a regulation) the drug has on the target (usually at an existing event). Sometimes (rarely), drugs will behave in other ways, for example, as group donors. The appropriate reaction must then be created.

THE DRUG INTERACTION FILE

The drug interaction file used in curation is a set of autogenerated drug reactions from GtP in an .rtpj. Bijay and Guanming devised a solution to create auto-generated drug reactions from GtP data. In a nutshell, the criteria used to create the file was to collect any approved drugs that bind the same human target, which is the primary target of those drugs, and create a Reactome-type reaction that has input of drug(s) and target and output of the drug(s): target complex. Also, collect all references from each drug page that describe them binding to this target into the Reactome reaction litRef slot.

See this file below.

Latest drug:target auto-generated GtP reaction file **IUPHAR_reactions_051821.rtpj** (in Reactome Team Drive > Curation > [Drug curation](#)).

Note most of these reactions are NOT checked into Reactome. Instead, identify the reaction you wish to curate and check that in ONLY from this file. Once in gk_central, check out into your local project and work on revising it.

This file provides a good starting point to revise any chosen reaction from this list you want to curate into Reactome. You'd still need to investigate whether these drugs are still in use or are experimental, for instance. As long as strong evidence exists to confirm pharmacological action, that drug can be curated.

Where you've found a drug in the literature that doesn't have a GtP ID, you can request new drug entries from GtP as long as you can provide evidence for the pharmacological effect of that drug. By consensus, Reactome primarily annotates drugs that have been approved for human use. If an exception is made in cases where a drug is biologically interesting / distinctive but not universally approved, it is crucial to explain in the summation why we have nevertheless chosen to annotate it.

Example - drug binds target, resultant complex regulates that target's event(s)

The drug **rivaroxaban** (Xarelto) functions as an anticoagulant that binds to and inhibits Factor Xa in the blood clotting cascade. This has the effect of slowing down the rate of blood coagulation, helping to prevent the formation of blood clots.

Find the pathway of the target protein where this drug acts and download the ELV-level pathway into your tool. The relevant pathway here is [Formation of Fibrin Clot \(Clotting Cascade R-HSA-140877\)](#)

You need to determine what type of drug this is, so you can create the relevant drug instance. Reading some literature and/or checking its identifiers (Chebi, GtP) will determine this.

There are two ways to create the drug reaction; either use the auto-generated reaction (recommended, Steps 1a, 2a) or create from scratch (Steps 1b, 2b).

STEP 1A

Find the reaction from the auto-generated drug reaction file (above) which should have the entity and target information already filled. Check it into gk_central then check out into your local project.

STEP 1B

Below is the process to create new drug instances (steps 1b and 2b) if there is no auto-generated reaction.

This example is a chemical drug so create an instance of chemicalDrug in the curator tool. The instance has mandatory slots

name - enter the common name and a brand name (optional)

rivaroxaban, Xarelto

compartment - same as the target protein in most cases (exception for example target is a membrane protein, drug will be extracellular)

extracellular region

disease - A DOID identifier that most closely matches the disease this drug is involved in

pulmonary embolism (DOID:9477)

referenceEntity - a referenceTherapeutic instance containing an GtP identifier. Any drug you create **must** have an GtP identifier so check their website first for one before curating

GtP:6388

(On the rare occasion that an GtP ID is not available for your drug, you can use other resources like PubChem Compound, DrugBank or Chebi as alternative identifiers. Remember to fill in the 'approved' slot in the referenceEntity instance when using these alternatives as this slot is mandatory. If you can't find a suitable identifier, see instructions below describing how to request a Chebi identifier.).

crossReference - currently optional but desirable - Add a Chebi identifier. If one is not available, easy to request one (see [Best Practices- Using Chemical Compound Databases](#), Appendix C8).

Chebi:68579

literatureReference - currently optional but desirable - Indicate the specific references for the drug instance. This is useful for data dumps as well as users wanting specific references for a drug, rather than trying to match a specific reference from the summation for a set of drugs

reactionType - currently optional but desirable. Choose an item from this list (taken from the IUPHAR / Guide to Pharmacology [glossary](https://www.guidetopharmacology.org/helpPage.jsp#glossary), <https://www.guidetopharmacology.org/helpPage.jsp#glossary>) to classify the effect of the drug on the reaction:

Activator - "A ligand that activates an ion channel by binding directly to it, including ligands that cause a change in the voltage dependence of channel gating that favours activation."

Agonist - "A ligand that binds to a receptor and alters the receptor state resulting in a biological response. Conventional agonists stabilise an active conformation of a receptor and increase receptor activity. When the receptor stimulus induced by an agonist reaches the maximal response capability of the system (tissue), then it will produce the system maximal response and be a full agonist in that system."

Allosteric modulator (is_a modulator) - "A ligand that increases (positive) or decreases (negative) the action of an agonist or antagonist by combining with a distinct site on the receptor macromolecule. Neutral allosteric ligands bind to an allosteric site without affecting the binding or function of orthosteric ligands but can still block the action of other allosteric modulators that act via the same allosteric site."

Antagonist - "A drug that reduces the action of another drug, generally an agonist"

Antibody binding - A drug that is an antibody (immunoglobulin) and acts by binding the epitope for which it is specific.*

Channel blocker - "A ligand that blocks ion movement through an ion channel."

Channel opener - A ligand that facilitates ion movement through an ion channel.*

Inhibitor - "A ligand that inhibits ion channel gating by directly binding to the channels, including ligands that inhibit ion channel activation and those that inhibit ion channel inactivation."

Modulator - A ligand that changes the activity of its target protein on binding

Positive modulator (is_a modulator) - A ligand that increases the activity of its target protein on binding*.

Allosteric antagonist - (is_a antagonist) A ligand that decreases the action of an agonist or antagonist by combining with a distinct site on the receptor macromolecule*.

Antisense inhibitor - (is_a inhibitor) An RNA oligonucleotide ligand that base-pairs with an endogenous mRNA, to form a rapidly degraded complex.*

Gating inhibitor - (is_a inhibitor) ???

Inverse agonist - (is_a agonist) A ligand that by binding to unoccupied receptors reduces the fraction of them in an active conformation. For nuclear receptors, an inverse agonist refers to ligands that can promote co-repressor recruitment. A drug that binds to the same receptor as an agonist but induces a pharmacological response opposite to that of the agonist.

Negative allosteric modulator - (is_a allosteric modulator) A ligand that decreases the action of an agonist or antagonist by combining with a distinct site on the receptor macromolecule.*

Partial agonist - (is_a agonist) Agonists that in a given tissue, under specific conditions, cannot elicit as large an effect (even when applied at high concentration, so that all the receptors should be occupied) as can another agonist acting through the same receptors in the same tissue.

Positive allosteric modulator - (is_a allosteric modulator) A ligand that increases the action of an agonist or antagonist by combining with a distinct site on the receptor macromolecule.*

rivaroxaban chemicalDrug entry

ChemicalDrug Properties	
Property Name	Value
cellType	
compartment	extracellular region
disease	pulmonary embolism
referenceEntity	rivaroxaban [IUPHAR:6388]
DB_ID	9015055
_displayName	rivaroxaban [extracellular region]
authored	
created	Jassal, Bijay, 2017-08-08
crossReference	ChEBI:68579
definition	
edited	
figure	
goCellularComponent	
inferredFrom	
inferredTo	
literatureReference	Discovery of the novel antithrombotic ... Rivaroxaban: a novel, oral, direct fact... The discovery and development of riv... Pharmacology of anticoagulants used i...
modified	Jassal, Bijay, 2017-08-09 Jassal, Bijay, 2017-08-15 Weiser, JD Jassal, Bijay, 2018-03-14 Weiser, JD Shorser, Solomon, 2018-08-13 Wu, G, 2018-09-19 Jassal, Bijay, 2018-10-18 Jassal, Bijay, 2018-10-18 Wu, G, 2018-11-05 Wu, G, 2018-12-12
name	rivaroxaban Xarelto
reviewed	
revised	
stableIdentifier	R-ALL-9015055.1
summation	
systematicName	

Rivaroxaban is one of a number of 'xabans' that are direct oral anticoagulants (DOACs) and all act on Factor Xa in an inhibitory way. Since they all act in the same way, a set of these drugs can be constructed.

[DefinedSet:9038743] Factor Xa inhibitors [extracellular region]	
DefinedSet Properties	
Property Name	Value
cellType	
hasMember	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> apixaban [extracellular region] betrixaban [extracellular region] edoxaban [extracellular region] rivaroxaban [extracellular region] eribaxaban [extracellular region]
DB_ID	9038743
_displayName	Factor Xa inhibitors [extracellular region]
authored	
compartment	extracellular region
created	Jassal, Bijay, 2018-03-14
crossReference	
definition	
disease	
edited	
figure	
goCellularComponent	
inferredFrom	
inferredTo	
isOrdered	
literatureReference	
modified	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Jassal, Bijay, 2018-03-14 Jassal, Bijay, 2018-03-23
name	Factor Xa inhibitors
relatedSpecies	
reviewed	
revised	
species	
stableIdentifier	R-ALL-9038743.1
summation	
systematicName	

STEP 2A

In the autogenerated reaction, check the 'functional form' of the target. In pharmacological databases, the target is described as a single protein. This is what will be populated in the autogenerated reaction. However, in Reactome, the target protein may be in a complex, a cleaved form or PTM'd, etc etc. You will need to replace the target protein in the autogenerated reaction IF IT IS DIFFERENT to what is curated in Reactome. Check the compartments of all entities at this stage.

STEP 2B

If creating a new reaction from scratch, find the ‘functional form’ of the target in the relevant Reactome reaction to be used in the drug reaction.

Factor Xa inhibitors (“xabans”) binds Factor Xa. The resulting complex will act on Factor Xa event. Fill in the disease slot (same as for the drug).

Property Name	Value
catalystActivity	
entityFunctionalStatus	
input	factor Xa [plasma membrane] Factor Xa inhibitors [extracellular region]
output	factor Xa:Factor Xa inhibitors [plasma membrane]
DB_ID	9015111
_displayName	Factor Xa inhibitors binds Xa

Factor Xa inhibitors also bind complexed Factor Xa (Va:Xa). The resulting complex will act on the Va:Xa event. Fill in the disease slot (same as for the drug).

Property Name	Value
catalystActivity	
entityFunctionalStatus	
input	Va:Xa [plasma membrane] Factor Xa inhibitors [extracellular region]
output	Va:Xa:Factor Xa inhibitors [plasma membrane]
DB_ID	9015122
_displayName	Factor Xa inhibitors bind Va:Xa

STEP 3

(will most likely be existing event/s or if not, you’ll need to create one to be the regulated event).

Find the event that Factor Xa is involved in and create a negative regulation of that event with the complex “Factor Xa:Factor Xa inhibitors”.

Create the negative regulation instance as below

NegativeRegulation Properties	
Property Name	Value
regulator	factor Xa:Factor Xa inhibitors [plasma membrane]
DB_ID	9015052
_displayName	Negative regulation by 'factor Xa:Factor Xa inhibitors [plasma membrane]'
activeUnit	
activity	
created	Jassal, Bijay, 2017-08-08
goBiologicalProcess	
literatureReference	Jassal, Bijay, 2017-08-08
	Jassal, Bijay, 2017-08-08
	Jassal, Bijay, 2017-08-08
modified	Jassal, Bijay, 2017-10-25
	Jassal, Bijay, 2018-03-02
	Jassal, Bijay, 2018-03-14
	Wu, G, 2018-05-08
stableIdentifier	R-HSA-9015052.3
summation	Factor Xa is a target for direct oral anticoagulant (DOAC d...

...as seen in the curator tool central panel

...and as seen in the web display. Any entity containing a drug will be coloured purple.

Note - the actual regulation 'line' will be color-sensitive in the future* (ie purple for drugs).

*[This feature is currently on hold]

Add appropriate supporting references to both events.

CURATOR TOOL PROTOCOL

To support the new gk_central schema for drug annotation, a new feature has been added to the tool: auto-fetch the required information for the new ReferenceTherapeutic class based on the drug identifier in [GtP \(https://www.guidetopharmacology.org/\)](https://www.guidetopharmacology.org/). Here is an example of how to use it:

1. On the GtP web page, <http://www.guidetopharmacology.org>, search for imatinib in their search box.
2. On the result page, imatinib is the first entry. Click it.
3. On the imatinib page, find Ligand ID for it: 5687.
4. In the curator tool, create a new ReferenceTherapeutic instance, and enter 5687 as the identifier.
 - o The curator tool will ask you if you want to fetch information from GtP.
 - o Choose "Yes". Information for 5687 will be fetched automatically.

NEW MOLECULE REQUEST IN CHEBI

To request new identifiers for chemicals (and drugs) from ChEBI, follow this [submission process](#). To submit to Guide to Pharmacology, you need to contact one of their curators to ask if the drug you want curated in GtP has an appropriate pharmacological action they are willing to add. Literature references always help your cause. The person to contact is Elena Faccenda, a senior curator at GtP.

CHECKLIST

Here is a checklist for the whole drug curation process:

- Drugs in Guide to Pharmacology (GtP, formerly GtP) must be target-specific and approved (can be special cases eg. cancer therapeutics). See the GtP file [here](#) (Appendix C11).
- Check if the drug already exists in gk_central (NOT Reactome's public website)
- Build projects (multiple at once if necessary) for all diagrams to be changed
- Create Drug entities, if necessary for different compartments
- Add ChEBI cross-references
- Drug entities have their disease attribute filled in
- Literature goes in the (binding) reaction
- Set the reaction's doRelease=false
- In the reaction summary, mention all participating drugs
- In the ELV, the drug reactions need to be type changed to "Association"
- Only after review can the Regulation/Reference be added to a reviewed physiological reaction
- Fill in the [tracking sheet](#), one item for every new drug reaction

COMPLEXITIES OF DISEASE AND DRUG CURATION: SPECIAL CASES

EXAMPLE 1 - DRUG-TARGET INTERACTION IN DISEASE:

The cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator (CFTR) is a low conductance chloride-selective channel that mediates the transport of chloride ions in human airway epithelial cells. Chloride ions play a key role in maintaining homeostasis of epithelial secretions in the lungs. Defects in CFTR can cause cystic fibrosis (CF), resulting in an ionic imbalance that impairs clearance of secretions, not only in the lung, but also in the pancreas, gastrointestinal tract and liver. More than 1500 mutations in the CFTR gene have been identified. CF patients with a particular mutation, G551D, have shown lung function improvements when given the drug Ivacaftor.

To curate the mutation reversal effect of the drug, create two events; first the drug binding to mutant protein and second, this complex reviving the function equivalent to the w/t protein.

Reactions showing ivacaftor binding the mutant protein (highlighted blue) and the following reaction (centre) showing channel functionality restored. The left-side reaction shows defective CFTR which cannot transport Cl⁻ ions.

The construct in the hierarchy is complicated by having the loss-of-function (LoF) reaction (the left side) as part of the display. LoF reactions are generated automatically on the website. To add the reactions involving drugs, they must be drawn manually on the diagram shared by the disease pathway and the normal pathway, in this case, the PathwayDiagram instance lists the normal pathway (ABC-family proteins mediated transport) and the disease pathway (Defective CFTR causes cystic fibrosis), together with other disease pathways relevant to this diagram as representedPathway. The two disease drug reactions are drawn in this diagram and their edges coloured red. The cystic fibrosis disease attribute is associated with both.

Now the LoF reaction can be viewed being switched between it and its normal counterpart and will work independently of these two drug-mutant reactions which only appear when looking at the disease counterpart.

EXAMPLE 2 - DISEASES CAUSED BY ACCUMULATION OF SUBSTRATE OVER TIME:

Special case in Reactome where the reaction describing a particular substrate's metabolism occurs in normal physiology but over time, accumulation of the substrate leads to toxic consequences which can lead to disease. Examples are neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's diseases, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and retinal macular degeneration.

The bisretinoid A2E (di-retinoid-pyridinium-ethanolamine) is a major component of lipofuscin, a yellow-brown pigment grain composed mainly of lipids but also sugars and certain metals whose accumulation is associated with degenerative diseases. In the eye, A2E is the end-product of the condensation of 2 molecules of all-trans-retinal and phosphatidylethanolamine in photoreceptor outer disc membranes. Once formed, A2E is phagocytosed, together with outer segments, to retinal pigment epithelial (RPE) cells where it accumulates. There is no evidence as yet to indicate that A2E can be catabolised. The relationship between lipofuscin accumulation and retinal degeneration is illustrated by Stargardt disease type 1. Because the reactions can be considered "normal" (they occur as part of the normal metabolism of retinoids) as well as disease-causing, they are drawn in the normal pathway diagram and coloured red. To display in the disease view of the diagram, these reactions are added as components of the disease container pathway "Diseases associated with visual transduction". These reactions will now display in both normal and disease diagrams.

Diseases associated with visual transduction

- Retinoid cycle disease events
 - Defective STRA6 does not transport atROL
 - Defective LRAT does not esterify atROL and PALM to RPALM
 - Defective ABCA4 does not transport atRAL or NRPE from disc membranes
 - Defective OPN1SW causes tritanopia
 - Defective OPN1MW causes DCB and BCM
 - Defective OPN1MW causes COD5
 - Defective OPN1LW causes BCM
 - Defective OPN1LW causes CBP
 - Defective RDH12 does not reduce atRAL to atROL and causes LCA13
 - Defective RDH12 does not reduce atRAL to atROL and causes RPS3
 - Defective RDH5 does not oxidise 11cROL to 11tRAL and causes RPA
 - Defective RBP4 does not bind atROL
- Biosynthesis of A2E, implicated in retinal degradation
 - atRAL can spontaneously react with PE to form NRPE
 - NRPE condenses with atRAL to form A2PE
 - A2PE hydrolyses to A2E
 - A2E is phagocytosed
 - A2E translocates to RPE cells

EXAMPLE 3 - DISEASE-SPECIFIC GENE EXPRESSION

See discussion [here](#) (Appendix 12) of how to handle cases where gene expression is stimulated downstream of a disease-specific event, but the gene expression doesn't inherently include a disease entity.

MODIFYING, DELETING AND MERGING INSTANCES

If you locally modify or delete an instance you checked out from `gk_central`, it will also be **modified/deleted in `gk_central`** when you synchronize. You must **ALWAYS CHECK FIRST** that the instance you intend to modify/delete is not in use elsewhere, outside your local project. The best way to do this is to search for it in `gk_central` using the Database Browser Schema View, and select "display referrers". If it has any you didn't know about, do not modify or delete it!

Always use the curatortool database browser to check gk_central for referrers. Right clicking on a database object will allow you to look for referrers.

There may be circumstances when you think something should be modified or removed but if it has been used by another curator, check with them first, or contact an experienced curator for advice.

PROCEDURE FOR DELETING INSTANCES (ENTITIES, EVENTS OR REGULATION) THAT HAVE BEEN RELEASED:

A `_deleted` instances **MUST** be created any time a **released** Event or Entity is retired/deleted from the database. For example, when event restructuring occurs, any previously released events should NOT simply be flipped to `do_release false`. When this happens, this instance "disappears without a trace" to users. Before removing the instance, it should be replaced (by a replacement instance if available) in all referrers (where relevant) AND THEN deleted with the creation of a "`_deleted`" instance that gives a reason for deletion, a replacement instance (where relevant) and an explanation of the deletion in the `curatorComment`.

*Please note if you are deleting a pathway because it has been restructured and that pathway has a DOI, it is *essential* to specify the replacement instances in the `_deleted` instance. The historic author and reviewer instances should also be transferred to the replacement instance.

The procedure for choosing the appropriate "reason" and "replacement" instances is described below. This rule applies not only if an EWAS is retired or deleted, but also if the `referenceGeneSequence` associated with the EWAS is changed, e.g., because a UniProt entry is made obsolete and a different UniProt entry is to be used in its place.

Deleted Instance Options - When you opt to delete an instance you will be presented with a "Deleted Instance Dialog". If the instance has been released, a `_deleted` instance **MUST** be created. You can determine if the entity/event has been released by checking if the "released" attribute of its `stableID` is set to "True". **Note:** `_deleted` instances **MUST** have "reason" attribute filled. There are several options:

- **Killed and not replaced** - Used for events or physical entities that are simply wrong and must be removed. The event/entity is deleted and killed and not replaced in all of its referrers. It is **CRITICAL** that you also identify all diagrams in which the deleted instance has been used and make sure that the entity/event is deleted there as well. If you have the diagram open at the time that you delete the deprecated instance the diagram may updated automatically, but you should

verify this. When selecting Killed and not replaced as "reason", the curator must also fill in a "curatorComments" that provides an explanation.

- **Duplicate** - When two separate but duplicate events or physical entities (A and B) are discovered within the data set. These events or physical entities must be exactly the same. Chose the duplicate instance with the greatest number of referrers (A) as the one to retain. B will be deleted. BEFORE deleting B, you will need to replace it with "A" in all of the referrers of "B". It is CRITICAL that you also identify all diagrams in which the deleted instance has been used and make sure that the entity/event is replaced there as well. If you have the diagram open at the time that you make the replacement of the deprecated instance the diagram may be updated automatically, but you should verify this.
When ready to delete B, use "Duplicate" as the reason in the `_deleted` instance. In this case, you MUST specify the replacement instance `DB_ID` in the "replacement" attribute. ****Note for discussion: it is also possible to resolve duplicate instances via a merge in the curator tool as long as ALL of the referrers of both A and B are in the project during the merge. However, in the case of the merge, it is not possible to specify which instance is preserved as far as I know. Also, with a merge the history is lost (there is no record of the deleted instance). Question: should merge be used for "unreleased" duplicates?
- **Split** - When a single entity is found to represent two separate and distinct entities. If the entity is to be split as a result of an external database change (UniProt) this is handled by the managing editor (L. Matthews), and clean up instructions will be provided. If splitting an event such as a high level pathway, the deletion must be discussed with the editors. If the instance to be split is an event, the common practice is to duplicate and then partition the components accordingly. Generally we feel that split should not be used for reactions and low-level pathway events at this time.
- **Merged** - Very similar to duplicate. When a number of similar (but not exactly the same) events/entities A and B are merged to a single instance A and B is deleted. These could be steps in a pathway that are collapsed to a single step. When Uniprot merges entries (say 2 proteins thought to be different turn out to be the same), this is reported in the Uniprot update and is managed by the release manager. Again, BEFORE deleting B, you will need to replace it with "A" in all of the referrers of "B"! It is CRITICAL that you also identify all diagrams in which the deleted instance has been used and make sure that the entity/event is replaced there as well. If you have the diagram open at the time that you make the replacement of the deprecated instance the diagram may be updated automatically, but you should verify this.
When ready to delete B, use "Merged" as the reason in the `_deleted` instance. In this case, you MUST specify the replacement instance (A) `DB_ID` in the "replacement" attribute.
- **Obsolete** - Instance A is "killed" but has a replacement B. BEFORE deleting A, you will need to replace it with "B" in all of the referrers of "B"! It is CRITICAL that you also identify all diagrams in which the deleted instance has been used and make sure that the entity/event is replaced there as well. If you have the diagram open at the time that you make the replacement of the deprecated instance the

diagram may be updated automatically, but you should verify this. When ready to delete A, use "Obsolete" as the reason. In this case, you **MUST** specify the replacement instance (B) in the "replacement" attribute. Provide an explanation for replacement in the "curatorComments" attribute.

UPDATING MODIFIED REACTIONS IN THE ELV (CRITICAL!)

When modifying existing reactions that have already been drawn into diagrams and deployed, be aware that not all changes made to participants in reactions will be automatically reflected in a diagram. For example, if you plan to replace the input of a reaction that is an EWAS with a set, the set will be drawn into the diagram, but the original EWAS will not disappear. It will have to be manually removed as described in the example below.

Example:

The original reaction had a single EWAS (FDX1L) as an input. I then made a defined set of 2 FDX proteins (FDX1, FDX1L) and substituted the defined set for the single EWAS as an input for the reaction. The ELV correctly showed the change (use of the set as an input) but also continued to show FDX1L (as a member of the defined set). I don't really want the EWAS FDX1L on the ELV anymore so I tried to delete it but received the error message "In the ELV drawing mode an entity cannot be deleted if it is linked to a reaction...").

To remove the EWAS (From the diagram only!!!) deselect the "Use ELV as a drawing tool" within the curatortool preferences panel, select to delete the EWAS from the ELV but retain the EWAS in the project. **After you delete these unwanted objects, please turn on this checkbox again to avoid any side-effects in the future.**

Toggling the "Use ELV as a drawing tool" option to off allows the drawing tool to directly modify the data in your project. Be very careful and be sure to reselect this option once you are done.

Please note that if an unused entity icon is still connected by lines to other entities (e.g., an orphan EWAS is connected to a set that includes it), you need to delete these connecting lines before the curator tool will allow you to delete the unused entity icon.

The bottom line is that you should always review and update the pathway diagram after modifying the reaction, and if the reaction is used in multiple diagrams ALL diagrams will need to be updated, so check for referrers of any reaction that is being modified.

MERGING DUPLICATE ENTITIES

To perform merging (for a complex for example), do the following:

- 1). In the database schema view, get these two complexes together in the instance list (the central panel) by doing REGEXP search: list DB_IDs together as this: DB_ID|DB_ID (Note | between two DB_IDs)
- 2). Check out these two instances.
- 3). While still in the view from step 1, search for Referrers for one complex, and check out all referrers in the Referrer dialog. Do this for the other instance.
- 4). In the local project schema view, merge these two complexes.
- 5). Find all instances that have been changed based on flag ">".

6). Find pathway diagrams containing changed reactions. You may have to do this manually for the time being. In the db schema view, get pathways containing these changed reactions and see if they have diagrams (if the pathway listed does NOT have a diagram, look upwards at parent pathways until you find one that DOES have a diagram. Check these diagrams out by using "Build Project". Re-open diagrams should fix references automatically. But you may need to re-position auto-inserted complex in the diagrams. So please check it manually to make sure.

7). Commit all changes into gk_central.

8). Delete the deprecated instance AFTER all other changes. Do NOT commit the deletion first. By committing the deletion first, the curator tool automatically updated referrers of the deleted instance by removing the deleted instance from their attributes and attached an InstanceEdit to these referrers. Consequently, you will see conflicts if the deletion is done first.

DELETING DIAGRAMS

If you are deleting a pathway diagram, you must delete the corresponding PathwayDiagram instance, you don't need to delete SearchableVertex instances that are associated with that diagram. In the future, this will be handled automatically.

DIAGRAM CHECKS AFTER DELETING ENTITIES OR REACTIONLIKEEVENTS

If and when you need to delete an entity from gk_central, you must run the deleted object in diagram check over gk_central to find any diagrams that have used those instances.

QA

PROJECT QA USING THE CURATOR TOOL QA CHECKS

Within the Tools menu the "QA Check" menu can be found.

QA Check Menu

This menu has nine separate QA script items within it.

- Imbalance Check: checks that the EWAS referenceEntities present as input are also present as output and in the correct stoichiometry.
- Mandatory Attributes Check: Checks that the mandatory attributes for a class have been entered.
- Required Attributes Check: Checks that the required attributes for a class have been entered.
- EntitySet Type Check: Checks that set members belong to the same data model class.
- Compartment Check:
 - EntitySet: Looks for conflicts between compartment of a set and the compartment of members of that set.
 - Complex: Looks for conflicts between compartment of a complex and the compartment of individual components.
 - Reaction: Looks for conflicts between compartment of a reaction and the compartment(s) of individual participants.
- Species Check for
 - Entity Set: Looks for conflicts between the species of set members and the species of the set containing them..
 - Complex: Looks for conflicts between species of a complex and the species of individual components of that complex.
 - Reaction: Looks for conflicts between species of reactionLikeEvent and the species of all reaction participants.
 - Pathway: Looks for conflicts between the species of a pathway and the species of its contained events.
- EntityFunctionalStatus check
 - DiseaseEntity: Verifies that the diseaseEntity specified in the EntityFunctional status of an disease RLE is a participant of the disease RLE
 - NormalEntity: Verifies that the normalEntity specified in the EntityFunctional status of the disease RLE is a participant of the normalReaction specified in the disease RLE.
 -
- ReviewStatus Check: Flags Events have not been reviewed after structureModified instanceEdit date stamp. This should only be run on the sliceDB (editorial release manager does this at release time).
- Cell MarkerReference: Checks for proper assignment of Marker references in Cell instances.

Note: In order for the QA checks to effectively pick up errors, the project that you are working on must be fully extracted from the database. Instructions on how to do a full extraction can be found [here](#) (Appendix C13).

IMBALANCE CHECK

You must select Reactions in the hierarchy to perform this check.

The screenshot shows a software interface with a 'QA Check' menu open. The 'Imbalance Check' option is selected. The interface includes a class hierarchy on the left, a search area, and a detailed view of a reaction instance on the right.

QA Check

- Launch PSI-MOD Browser
- Launch Disease Browser
- Open Reach NLP
- Update Schema From DB
- Check for Software Update

Imbalance Check

- Mandatory Attribute Check
- Required Attributes Check
- EntitySet Type Check
- Compartment Check for >
- Species Check for >
- EntityFunctionalStaeue Check >
- ReviewStatus Check
- Cell MarkerReference

Classes

- InteractionEvent [0]
- > Pathway [60]
 - CellLineagePath [0]
- > ReactionlikeEvent [1668]
 - BlackBoxEvent [174]
 - CellDevelopmentStep [0]
 - Depolymerisation [0]
 - FailedReaction [1]
 - Polymerisation [3]
 - > Reaction [1490]
- ExternalOntology [46]
 - Anatomy [0]
 - CellType [2]
 - Disease [29]
 - EnzymeType [0]

Search Instances

Choose Class: Reaction

Choose Attri...: DB_ID

Attribute Val...: IS NOT NULL

Search Search More...

Value

regulatedBy	
regulationReference	
relatedSpecies	
requiredInputComponent	
reverseReaction	
reviewStatus	five stars
revised	D'Eustachio, P, 2010-01-... D'Eustachio, Peter, 2015-...
systematicName	
DB_ID	70342
_displayName	ALDOB tetramer cleaves Fru...
created	Vastrik, I, 2005-04-29 ... Gopinathrao, G, 2005-0-... D'Eustachio, P, 2006-05-... D'Eustachio, P, 2010-01-... D'Eustachio, P, 2010-01-... D'Eustachio, Peter, 2014-... Jassal, Bijay, 2015-01-29 D'Eustachio, Peter, 2015-... D'Eustachio, Peter, 2015-...

modified

Reactions are flagged as cleavage reactions if the output differs from the input only that the output contains "fragments" of the input molecule. A true imbalance is shown below:

Results for checking input-output imbalance for reactions

The following reactions are not balanced: 1 instances

Imbalance Reaction: 1

- >TNF Binds TNF-R1

Property Name	Value
catalystActivity	
input	TNF-alpha [plasma membrane]
output	TNF-alpha:TNF-R1 complex ...
DB_ID	83660
_displayName	TNF Binds TNF-R1
_doRelease	true
authored	
compartment	cell
created	Tschopp, J, 2004-01-28 14:...
crossReference	
definition	
edited	
entityOnOtherCell	
evidenceType	
figure	
oaBiologicalProcess	

Imbalance Check for "TNF Binds TNF-R1 [83660]"

	Input	Output
P19438	0	1

Dump to File Close

MANDATORY ATTRIBUTE CHECK

A list of instances missing mandatory attributes (by class) is shown. To make the missing attributes of the instance easier to see, you can use the "order attribute" button (downward arrow with circle and triangle) in the upper right side of the tool. This orders the instances by type (mandatory, required, optional...etc)

Attributes Check Results

Mandatory attributes for class "Reaction" are: output, input, releaseDate, species, compartment, name, summation.

Classes	Instances	Reaction Properties																																										
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> BlackBoxEvent [12] Reaction [36] Pathway [5] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> CellLineagePath [0] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activated alpha-2 adrenoceptor binds G- Activation of Pak2 by autophosphorylation Association of Pak2 with Cdc42-GTP Association of mature ERBB2 with HSP90 c CCL4, CCL4L1 bind CCR5, CCR1 >>CYCS binds to APAF1 Ca(4)CaM => Calmodulin + 4 Ca2+ Caspase mediated cleavage of Ataxin-7 Caspase- mediated cleavage of Tensin-4 Caspase-activated PAK-2 phosphorylates Caspase-activated PAK-2 phosphorylates Caspase-mediated cleavage of Huntingtin Caspase-mediated cleavage of MITF Caspase-mediated cleavage of ZO-1 Caspase-mediated cleavage of cytokeratir Dissociation of Cdc42-GTP from activated Dissociation of Cdc42-GTP from activated Dissociation of the alpha-2 adrenergic rec Gz activation by alpha 2 adrenoceptor LTCC pentamer transports Ca2+ from ext MARK2 phosphorylates MAPT PKC alpha phosphorylates AKT1 at S473 PKCalpha/betall phosphorylate AKT at S47 PLC-beta:G-alpha(a/11) binds PIP2 	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Property Name</th> <th>Value</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>compartment</td> <td>cytosol</td> </tr> <tr> <td>input</td> <td>1 x APAF1:ADP [c... 1 x ATP [cytosol] 1 x CYCS [cytosol]</td> </tr> <tr> <td>name</td> <td>CYCS binds to APAF1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>output</td> <td>1 x ADP [cytosol] 1 x APAF1:ATP:C...</td> </tr> <tr> <td>releaseDate</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>species</td> <td>Homo sapiens</td> </tr> <tr> <td>summation</td> <td>The apoptotic pro...</td> </tr> <tr> <td>authored</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>catalystActivity</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>edited</td> <td>Matthews, L, 201... Apaf-1, a human ...</td> </tr> <tr> <td>literatureReferen...</td> <td>Apaf-1: Regulatio... Changes in Apaf-...</td> </tr> <tr> <td>reviewed</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>_doRelease</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>catalystActivityR...</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>crossReference</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>definition</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>disease</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>entityFunctional...</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>entityOnOtherCell</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>evidenceType</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Property Name	Value	compartment	cytosol	input	1 x APAF1:ADP [c... 1 x ATP [cytosol] 1 x CYCS [cytosol]	name	CYCS binds to APAF1	output	1 x ADP [cytosol] 1 x APAF1:ATP:C...	releaseDate		species	Homo sapiens	summation	The apoptotic pro...	authored		catalystActivity		edited	Matthews, L, 201... Apaf-1, a human ...	literatureReferen...	Apaf-1: Regulatio... Changes in Apaf-...	reviewed		_doRelease		catalystActivityR...		crossReference		definition		disease		entityFunctional...		entityOnOtherCell		evidenceType	
Property Name	Value																																											
compartment	cytosol																																											
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name	CYCS binds to APAF1																																											
output	1 x ADP [cytosol] 1 x APAF1:ATP:C...																																											
releaseDate																																												
species	Homo sapiens																																											
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catalystActivityR...																																												
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definition																																												
disease																																												
entityFunctional...																																												
entityOnOtherCell																																												
evidenceType																																												

REQUIRED ATTRIBUTE CHECK

This checks work in the same way that the mandatory attribute check works.

COMPARTMENT CHECK

Select the class you want to check in the hierarchy panel

Curator tool QA check menu bar.

The screenshot shows the Curator tool interface with the 'QA Check' menu open. The 'Compartment Check for' submenu is also open, showing 'EntitySet' and 'Complex' options. The 'Complex' option is selected. The background shows the Curator tool interface with a class hierarchy on the left and a list of instances in the center.

QA Check

- Imbalance Check
- Mandatory Attribute Check
- Required Attributes Check
- EntitySet Type Check
- Compartment Check for
 - EntitySet
 - Complex**
 - Reaction
- Species Check for
- EntityFunctionalStature Check
- ReviewStatus Check
- Cell MarkerReference

Classes

- PathwayDiagram [8]
- Person [12576]
- PhysicalEntity [5925]
 - Cell [0]
 - Complex [2059]**
 - Drug [22]
 - ChemicalDrug [20]
 - ProteinDrug [2]
 - RNADrug [0]
 - EntitySet [660]
 - CandidateSet [114]
 - DefinedSet [546]
 - GenomeEncodedEntity [2714]
 - EntityWithAccessionedSeque...

Search Instances

Choose Class: **Complex**

Choose Attri...: **DB_ID**

Attribute Val...: **IS NOT NULL**

Search Search More...

Instances

- (p-S15,S20-TP53,TP63...
- 14-3-3 proteins:p-599...
- 19S RP Lid Module 1 [cytosol]
- 19S RP base [cytosol]
- 19S RP lid [cytosol]
- 19S RP lid particle 2 [cytosol]
- 19S RP lid particle 3 [cytosol]
- 19S regulatory particle [cytosol]
- 20S CP inner ring [cytosol]
- 20S CP outer ring [cytosol]
- 20S core particle [cytosol]
- 26S proteasome [cytosol]
- 2x Activated C1R:2x Activated
- 2x Activated C1R:2xC15 [extra...
- 2x RET:GFRA:GDNF complexes
- 2x p-5Y-RET:GDNF:GFRA com|
- 2xANGPT1:TEK [plasma memb
- 2xC1R:2xC15 [extracellular reg
- 2xIL17A [cytosol]
- 2xIL17a.2xIL17f.II17a:II17f.II17f

Properties

- regulatedBy**
- regulationReference**
- relatedSpecies**
- requiredInputComponent**
- reverseReaction**
- reviewStatus** five stars
- revised** D'Eustachio, P, 2010-01...
D'Eustachio, Peter, 2015...
- systematicName**
- DB_ID** 70342
- _displayName** ALDOB tetramer cleaves Fru...
- created** Vastrik, I, 2005-04-29 ...
Gopinathrao, G, 2005-0...
D'Eustachio, P, 2006-05...
D'Eustachio, P, 2010-01...
D'Eustachio, P, 2010-01...
D'Eustachio, Peter, 2014...
Jassal, Bijay, 2015-01-29
D'Eustachio, Peter, 2015...
D'Eustachio, Peter, 2015...
D'Eustachio, Peter, 2015...
- modified**

Compartment conflicts are indicated in the bottom of the dialog box.

Complex compartment Check Result

The following Complex instances have wrong compartment settings: 663 instances

Instances: 663

Property Name	Value
cellType	1 x CPLX1 [cytosol] 1 x GABA Loaded synap... 1 x RIMS1 [cytosol] 1 x SNAP25 [plasma me... 1 x STX1A [plasma me... 1 x STXBP1-1 [cytosol]
hasComponent	
DB_ID	917774
_displayName	Docked GABA loaded syna...
authored	Mahajan, SS, 2010-08-...
compartment	cytosol
created	Mahajan, SS, 2010-07-...
crossReference	
definition	
disease	
edited	

compartment check for "Docked GABA loaded synaptic vesicle [cytosol] [917774]"

Component	Compartment
GABA Loaded synaptic vesicle [clathrin-sculpted gamma-...	clathrin-sculpted gamma-aminobutyric acid transport ves...
RIMS1 [cytosol] [210407]	cytosol
SNAP25 [plasma membrane] [2029017]	plasma membrane
CPLX1 [cytosol] [210385]	cytosol
HSPA8 [clathrin-sculpted gamma-aminobutyric acid trans...	clathrin-sculpted gamma-aminobutyric acid transport ves...
RAB3A [clathrin-sculpted gamma-aminobutyric acid trans...	clathrin-sculpted gamma-aminobutyric acid transport ves...
SLC32A1 [clathrin-sculpted gamma-aminobutyric acid tra...	clathrin-sculpted gamma-aminobutyric acid transport ves...
SYT1 [clathrin-sculpted gamma-aminobutyric acid transp...	clathrin-sculpted gamma-aminobutyric acid transport ves...
VAMP2 [clathrin-sculpted gamma-aminobutyric acid tran...	clathrin-sculpted gamma-aminobutyric acid transport ves...
DNAJC5 [clathrin-sculpted gamma-aminobutyric acid tran...	clathrin-sculpted gamma-aminobutyric acid transport ves...
GABA [clathrin-sculpted gamma-aminobutyric acid transp...	clathrin-sculpted gamma-aminobutyric acid transport ves...

SPECIES CHECKS

These checks work in the same way that compartment checks work with the exception that Pathways are also checked for species conflicts.

ENTITYFUNCTIONALSTATUS CHECKS

EntityFunctionalStatus disease entity Check Result

The following EntityFunctionalStatus instances have wrong disease entity settings: 10 instances

Instances: 10

- gain_of_function of BRISC complex:K63polyUb-NLRP3 R779C [cytosol]
- gain_of_function of Phosphorylated P780_Y781insGSP heterodimers: p-Y349,N
- loss_of_function of ANO6 variant:Ca2+ [plasma membrane]
- loss_of_function of CMAHP [cytosol]
- loss_of_function of CMO [chloroplast]
- loss_of_function of GNAT1 G38D [photoreceptor disc membrane]**
- loss_of_function of JAK3 E481G [cytosol]
- loss_of_function of JAK3 G589S [cytosol]
- loss_of_function of TUSC3 mutants [endoplasmic reticulum membrane]
- loss_of_function of unknown

EntityFunctionalStatus Properties

Property Name	Value
diseaseEntity	GNAT1 G38D [photoreceptor disc m...
functionalStatus	loss_of_function via point_mutation
normalEntity	GNAT1-GTP [photoreceptor disc me...
DB_ID	2528986
_displayName	loss_of_function of GNAT1 G38D [photo...
created	Jassal, B, 2012-10-15
modified	Wu, G, 2013-06-17
stableIdentifier	Wu, G, 2018-12-12

disease entity check for "loss_of_function of GNAT1 G38D [photoreceptor disc membrane] [2528986]": DiseaseEntity not an RLE's participant

DiseaseRLE_DB_ID	DiseaseRLE_DisplayName	DiseaseRLE_Participants
2514900	Defective GNAT1 does not activate PDE6	[Complex:74049] GNAT1-GTP [photoreceptor disc m...

Check Out Dump to File Close

EntityFunctionalStatus normal entity Check Result

The following EntityFunctionalStatus instances have wrong normal entity settings: 3 instances

Instances: 3

- loss_of_function of ERBB2 L755S heterodimers [plasma membrane]**
- loss_of_function of RBX1:SKP1:CUL1:beta-TrCP1:phosphorylated CTNNB1 ubiqu
- loss_of_function of unknown

EntityFunctionalStatus Properties

Property Name	Value
diseaseEntity	ERBB2 L755S heterodimers [plasma ...
functionalStatus	loss_of_function via missense_variant
normalEntity	ERBB2 heterodimers [plasma membr...
DB_ID	9655372
_displayName	loss_of_function of ERBB2 L755S hetero...

normal entity check for "loss_of_function of ERBB2 L755S heterodimers [plasma membrane] [9655372]": normalEntity not a normal RLE's participant

NormalRLE_DB_ID	NormalRLE_DisplayName	NormalRLE_Participants
9652264	ERBB2 binds TKIs	[DefinedSet:9652360] lapatinib, neratinib, afatinib, AZ...

Check Out Dump to File Close

REVIEWSTATUS CHECKS

This Event check flags instances that have a structureModified date after the last reviewed date as displayed in the dialog box below:

Event ReviewStatus in Event Check Result

The following Event instances have wrong ReviewStatus in Event settings: 6 instances

Instances: 6

- LIG3 (Ligase III) ligates nascent mitochondrial DNA strands
- Oxidative Stress Induced Senescence**
- PINK1-PRKN Mediated Mitophagy
- Regulation of PTEN localization
- Starch biosynthesis
- Transport of nucleotide sugars

Pathway Properties

Property Name	Value
	RAS signaling and prolonged i...
	ROS oxidize thioredoxin and ...
	Expression of MINK1/TNIK is ...
	MAP3K5 phosphorylates MKK...
	Phosphorylated MKK3/MKK6 ...
	Activated human MKK3/MKK...
	Active p38 MAPK phosphoryl...
	MAP3K5 (ASK1) phosphorylat...
	Phosphorylation of human JN...
	Activated human JNKs migrat...
	Activated JNKs phosphorylate...

ReviewStatus in Event check for "Oxidative Stress Induced Senescence [2559580]"

Attribute	Value	latestDateTime
reviewStatus	five stars	N/A
structureModified	Stephan, Ralf, 2023-08-20	2023-08-20 07:28:33
reviewed	Samarajiwa, Shamith, 2013-09-03	2013-09-03 04:00:00
internalReviewed	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2023-08-21	2023-08-21 15:33:42
Issue	reviewed before structureModified	N/A

CELL MARKER REFERENCE

DIAGRAM CHECKS

- Deleted objects in diagrams

When participants in a reaction are modified (or a reaction is deleted) in the instance view of the curator tool, curators must verify that these changes have propagated to the diagram(s) in which the reaction has been drawn. This does not happen automatically. It is best to have the diagram open while modifying reaction instances in the instance browser. Make sure, before committing changes to reactions, that you have opened and scanned the diagram(s) housing any modified reactions to check for hanging entities.

The "Deleted objects in diagram check" will help verify that you haven't missed anything after committing. Running this check over all of gk_central will identify any diagram that has "unconnected entities" due to changes in the reaction or ReactionLikeEvent participants. You may also select and check individual pathway diagrams of interest this way, but running across the whole database ensures you haven't missed/forgotten other diagrams in which your modified reactions may be

drawn.

The screenshot shows the 'gk_central@curator.reactome.org - Schema View' interface. The 'QA Check' menu is open, listing various checks such as 'Imbalance Check', 'Mandatory Attribute Check', 'Required Attributes Check', 'EntitySet Type Check', 'Compartment Check for', 'Species Check for', 'Pathway Diagram Check', 'EntityFunctionalStatus Check', 'New StableIdentifier Check', 'ReviewStatus Check', and 'Cell MarkerReference'. The 'PathwayDiagram' class is selected in the 'Classes' list. The 'Search Instances' section shows 'PathwayDiagram' selected with 'DB_ID' as the attribute and 'Equals' as the value. The main panel displays a list of pathway diagrams, with 'Deleted Objects in Diagram' highlighted in the search results.

Any affected diagrams will be flagged. The DB_ID of the deleted instance will be displayed, but to see where the affected "objects" are in the diagram, you will need to view the diagram in gk_central.

PathwayDiagram Check Result

The following PathwayDiagram have wrong settings: 1 instances

Instances: 1

- Diagram of Mitotic M-M/G1 phases

PathwayDiagram Properties	
Property Name	Value
representedPathway	Mitotic M-M/G1 phases
DB_ID	508493
_displayName	Diagram of Mitotic M-M/G1 pha...
created	Matthews, L, 2010-02-12
height	1570
modified	D'Eustachio, P, 2010-04-13
	Matthews, L, 2010-05-07
	Wu, G, 2011-06-02
	D'Eustachio, P, 2011-08-27
	Orlic-Milacic, M, 2011-10-07
Orlic-Milacic, M, 2011-10-07	
stableIdentifier	
width	1902

check for "Diagram of Mitotic M-M/G1 phases [508493]"

Pathway	DB_IDs without Instances
Mitotic M-M/G1 phases [453277]	163040

Check Out Dump to File Close

Select that diagram in gk_central, right click and opt to "Show diagram".

Affected objects will be flagged

and the objects in the diagrams highlighted in red.

QA OF PROJECTS BEFORE RELEASE

Curators can reduce the number of QA fixes required at release time by running a number of QA checks in the curator tool before committing the final version of their projects.

- Top Six List Of Problems Identified During the Slice
 - Missing mandatory attributes
 - Species conflicts
 - Unbalanced reactions

Open the curator tool QA check under to “tool menu bar” at the top of the tool as shown [above](#)

- Missing modifiedResidue nodes in diagram

CURATOR TOOL QA CHECKS:

1. All of the instances must be updated from gk_central in order for these checks to be meaningful. This checks out any shell attributes for the instances you want to check.

Everyday QA includes:

- Complete check-outs (No shell instances)
- Match instance in DB
- QA Tools

CURATION TOOLS/AUTOMATION

LITBALL TOOL FOR EXHAUSTIVE LITERATURE REFERENCE SEARCHING

The LitBall tool is described [here](#). A link to the slides describing its use can be found [here](#).

REMOTE ATTRIBUTE SEARCH TOOL

See [here](#) (Appendix C14) for description of the remote attribute search tool.

To search Reactome curator, use:

http://curator.reactome.org/cgi-bin/remotearch2?DB=gk_central

To search reactomerelease, use:

https://release.reactome.org/cgi-bin/remotearch2?DB=slice_test

USING IDG TO FIND INTERACTING PATHWAYS FOR GENE LISTS:

Still have to ask Guanming to do this with a list you provide. To see results of the analysis of an example set of IBD related genes, see below:

Please see the results uploaded in this folder:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1YzmrDrtnHMhX0VJg2A7tdAHi5GMxJiJd>

Please read READM.txt first to see what they are. I used the scatter pathway plot (see the two plots in that HTML file) we developed at OHSU to show the hits of pathways. Please use that CSV file to see what genes each pathway is associated with.

I tried to overlay to ReactomeFoam, but it is just too complicated. You may check with Chuqiao if she has an easier way to overlay the counts using the CSV file. But I think these scatter plots should serve the purpose.

USING REACH NLP FEATURE IN THE CURATOR TOOL TO PROCESS A PERSONALIZED LIST OF PMCID.

The Reach tool embedded in the curator tool uses automated NLP technology to extract pathways information from journal articles and suggest potentially annotateable interactions. The below protocol allows the curator to specify the list of PMCIDs through which REACH will search.

1. Formulate a PubMed search term, e.g. "(CDH2 OR "cadherin-2" OR "N-cadherin") AND (expression or transcription or promoter or binding or complex or interaction or regulation) and adhesion"
2. Note the number of results: e.g. 2,312 results for the above search term (on June 16, 2022). If a gene is poorly studied, it's best to just use gene name + synonyms as a search term. If it's a well-studied, popular gene, there will be too many results to process, most of which will be of no use for Reactome. In the latter case, it's best to add additional words that imply some mechanistic evidence (second bracket in the above search term) and the annotation context (in the case of CDH2 it's cell adhesion). You can build the search term interactively, depending on whether the number of results seems manageable and if the content of results seems appropriate.
3. Filter the results with the Free Full Text filter, the left-hand tab in PubMed: 1,230 results.
4. Change Display options FORMAT in the upper right corner from Summary (default) to PMID.
5. Save the list of PMIDs for your reference.
6. Go to <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/tools/idconv/> . This tool allows conversion of PMIDs to PMCIDs that need to be fed to NLP Reach. Paste the list of PMIDs and select csv as the output format (underneath the entry window). Unfortunately, the tool can process no more than 200 PMIDs at a time, unless an API is used – perhaps curators could get some training on how to do this. Otherwise, a long list of PMIDs will have to be processed in more than one run.
7. Look at the output file – if no PMCID is available for a PMID, then the PMCID column will stay blank. The PMIDs with no matching PMCID have to be manually evaluated for relevance by a curator.
8. Copy-paste the list of PMCIDs into a text editor such as Notepad and submit for processing (at the moment, forward to Guanming; the processing time is substantial, so it's best to do it well in advance).

9. After obtaining the results file in the .rtf format (the file can be quite big, so a Dropbox needs to be used for sharing), follow Guanming's instructions for opening them in the Curator Tool:
 - a. In the Curator Tool, use menu Tools/Open Reach NLP to open the window for Reach
 - b. Find a button called "Import" at the bottom. Please use Import to load the results from the rtf file

10. After importing the NLP results, you can visualize them using different filters:
 - a. The number of rows will appear overwhelming. However, most rows do not contain proteins/genes/RNAs as their Entities (please note Entity A and Entity B). Filter the results to contain your gene of interest or one of its synonyms as either Entity A or Entity B. Currently, it's not possible to filter for several things at once using the OR statement, so you have to filter the results for keywords one-by-one. Please note that the filter is case-sensitive. For example, if you filter for "cdh2", you may get 0 results, while you will get quite a few if you filter with "CDH2".
 - b. You can filter by the number of statements that support a relationship. Please note that more than 1 statement can originate from a single publication. Manual inspection is required to verify that a relationship is supported by at least 2 publications.

Examples of how to use the remoteattsearch tool can be found [here](#) (Appendix C14).

IDENTIFYING LIST MEMBERS THAT ARE UNIQUE TO ONE OF TWO LISTS USING MICROSOFT EXCEL

[Here](#) (Appendix C14) is a procedure that describes how to take two lists and compare entries to identify those that are present in only one of the two lists. This procedure can be useful, for example, to compare the list of proteins in the gk_central vs. live site to find those that are unreleased.

PREPARING A PATHWAY REPORT FOR INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL REVIEW

When you prepare a word document for external review, include (or highlight within the document) ONLY the events that you are asking to be reviewed. Longer documents tend to be harder to get reviewed. If you need to include previously reviewed content for context, "gray" this out (using lighter gray text or highlighting) and make reference to this fact out at the top of the word document. Also, point this fact out to the managing editor sending out reviewer requests so that this fact can be pointed out in the letter as well.

REPORTING BUGS

Please use [JIRA](#) to report bugs in the tool

APPENDICES

APPENDIX C1: [OVERVIEW OF CURATION](#)

APPENDIX C2: [QUICK GUIDE FOR NEW CURATORS](#)

APPENDIX C3: [EVIDENCE CONFIDENCE](#)

APPENDIX C4: [UPDATETRACKER](#)

APPENDIX C5: [DATA MODEL GLOSSARY](#)

APPENDIX C6: [SMALL MOLECULE RENAMING - SMALL MOLLS SHORT NAMES](#)

APPENDIX C7: [REVIEW OF THE PRECEDING EVENT SUGGESTION FEATURE](#)

APPENDIX C8: BEST PRACTICES: [USING CHEMICAL COMPOUND DATABASES](#)

APPENDIX C9: [CYTOMICS DOCUMENTATION](#)

APPENDIX C10: [MULTIPLE DISEASE AND ENTITY FUNCTIONAL STATUS WHEN USING DISEASE VARIANT SUBSETS](#)

APPENDIX C11: [GTP_ALL_INTERACTIONS](#)

APPENDIX C12: [DISEASE-SPECIFIC GENE EXPRESSION](#)

APPENDIX C13: [DEEP EXTRACTION OF EVENTS](#)

APPENDIX C14: [REMOTE ATTRIBUTE SEARCH AND EXAMPLES](#)

APPENDIX C15: [REMOVE DUPLICATES MS EXCEL](#)

APPENDIX C16: [RHEA-GO ALIGNMENT](#)

V95_Dec 2025

- Added a description of naming guideline for disease pathways where the same defective RLE affects more than one pathway.

V94_Sept 2025

- Added a note to verify normalPathway has been assigned to a disease pathway.

V93_March 2025

- Added a link to the LitBall comprehensive literature search tool in the Literature reference description and in the Tool section.

V92_March 2025

- Added missing description of ActiveUnit of CatalystActivity and its intended use.
- Added precisions about handling deletion/replacement of pathways with DOIs
- Added Appendix C16: RHEA-GO alignment
- Updated outdated regulation instance descriptions.
- Added a note about how not to create a empty pathway diagram instance by accident under: Editing existing pathways and corresponding diagrams

V91_Dec 2024

- Added: If a module has an external author (and no external reviewer) the author should be listed in both the authored and reviewed attribute.
- Added: Under Curation Tools, added a description of how to identify interacting pathways for a list of genes using the IDG tool.

V90_Sept 2024

- update to Disease pathway curation guide
- incorporation of Cell lineage curation guide
- general updates and reorganization

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V90_Sept 2024

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Appendix C1: Overview of Reactome Pathway Curation

The Reactome Knowledgebase

Reactome curation & annotation

From text to computer-accessible pathway data

Nature 407(6805):770-6. The Biochemistry of Apoptosis.

"Caspase-8 is the key initiator caspase in the death-receptor pathway. Upon ligand binding, death receptors such as CD95 (Apo-1/Fas) aggregate and form membrane-bound signalling complexes (Box 3). These complexes then recruit through adapter proteins, several molecules of procaspase-8, resulting in a high local concentration of zymogens. The induced proximity model posits that under these crowded conditions the low intrinsic protease activity of procaspase-8 (ref. 20) is sufficient to allow the various proenzyme molecules to mutually cleave and activate each other (Box 2). A similar mechanism of action has been proposed to mediate the activation of several other caspases, including caspase-2 and nematode caspase CED-3 (ref. 21)."

Tree View

- CCPS1 hexamer transfers PFF to GFP
- isopentenyl pyrophosphate rearranges to dimethylallyl pyrophosphate
- Pfk3 produces P3P and other phosphidyl inositides
- P3P activates AKT signaling
- RAS/MAP kinase cascade
- SOS1-mediated nucleotide exchange of RAS downstream of RAS
- Signaling by ALK
 - ALK binds ligand pleiotrophin (PTN)
 - ALK-PTN dimerization
 - ALK binds ligand midkine (MDK)
 - ALK-MDK dimerization
 - PTN/MDK/ALK dimer binds type I ALK-binding TRK
 - ALK autophosphorylation downstream of PTN and MDK
 - PTN/PTN dephosphorylation ligand-bound ALK dimer
 - PTN and MDK bind to PTPN22
 - PTN/MDK/PTN22 oligomerizes
 - Active ALK dimer binds IRS1
 - Active ALK phosphorylates IRS1
 - Active ALK binds SHC1
 - Active ALK phosphorylates SHC1
 - Active ALK binds FRK2
 - Active ALK phosphorylates FRK2
 - Active ALK recruits PI3K
 - PI3K synthesizes PIP3 downstream of ALK
 - Active ALK binds PLC1
 - Active ALK phosphorylates PLC1
 - Active ALK binds SRC
 - Active ALK phosphorylates SRC
 - Active ALK binds JAK1
 - Active ALK phosphorylates JAK1
 - PTN22 dephosphorylates JAK1
 - STAT3 is phosphorylated downstream of active ALK
 - STAT3 dimerizes
 - p-Y705, S727-STAT3 dimer translocates to the nucleus
 - STAT3 nuclear events downstream of ALK signaling
 - ALK gene expression
 - MYC/MYC bind the ALK gene
 - ALK-stimulated MYC gene expression
 - Signaling by ALK in cancer
 - p-TY ALK dimer phosphorylates FRK2

Search Events

Choose Class: Event

Choose Attribute: DB ID

Entity Level View

entityFunctionalStatus	1 x ALK (plasma membrane)
input	1 x PTN (intracellular region)
output	1 x PTN/ALK receptor (plasma membrane)
DB ID	201486
displayName	ALK binds ligand pleiotrophin (PTN)
doRelease	true
author	Chat-ranayomri, A. 2006-10-11 08:2...
catalyticActivityReference	extracellular region
compartment	plasma membrane
created	Jassal, B. 2007-08-21 12:50:53
crossReference	
definition	
disease	
edited	Chat-ranayomri, A. 2006-10-11 08:2...
entityOnOtherCell	
evidenceType	
figure	
galioleologicalAffness	
hasInteraction	
inferredFrom	1:ChEMBL
isChEMBL	
literatureReference	Identification of anaplastic lymphoma kin... Anti-apoptotic signaling of pleiotrophin T... Wu, G. 2010-11-13 Wu, G. 2016-07-15 OICR Micr. Man. 2019-11-18 Roethlis, Karen. 2021-04-30 Roethlis, Karen. 2021-05-04 Jassal, B. 2007-08-21 09:12 ALK binds ligand pleiotrophin (PTN)
modified	
name	normalReaction
orthologousEvent	
precedingEvent	
reactionType	
regulatedBy	
regulationReference	
relatedSpecies	
releaseDate	2021-06-09
releaseStatus	
requiredInputComponent	
reversibleReaction	
reviewed	Inghram, Giorgio. 2021-05-04
revised	
species	Homo sapiens
stableIdentifier	R-HSA-201486.1
summation	Pleiotrophin (PTN) is a secreted growth f...
synonyms	

is formed from procaspase-8 as a cleavage product. However, the cleavage itself appears not to be sufficient for the formation of the death-inducing signaling complex (DISC) by homophilic interactions with the FADD protein, which results in the formation of catalytically active form of procaspase-8. (Boatright KM et al 2003; Doneudi M et al 2010).
monomers, which are recruited to the death-inducing signaling complex (DISC) by homophilic interactions with the FADD protein, which results in the formation of catalytically active form of procaspase-8. (Boatright KM et al 2003; Doneudi M et al 2010).
n via Death Receptors in the presence of ligand

Data Model

- Reactome is a reaction-based database
- Explicitly describes HUMAN biological processes as a series of biochemical reactions and events

Entities

protein ([UniProt](#))
molecule ([ChEBI](#))
set
complex
ncRNA ([miRBase](#))
disease variant ([ClinGen](#), [COSMIC](#))
drug ([GtP](#))

Reactome supports many types of events

Reactions are linked by shared participants to form pathways and ultimately make up part of a vast, interconnected network

Example of linked reactions forming part of the Signaling by EGFR pathway

The curation process

Crediting Contributors

- 817 Reactome contributors since 2002
- Reactome has always recorded and displayed contributors' names as part of the record
- Any pathway revision is associated with a DOI and the DOI is associated with the name of all contributors
- DOIs make pathways citable

Crediting Contributors

Reactome now is fully searchable by contributor names

The screenshot shows the Reactome website's search interface. At the top left is the Reactome logo. To the right are navigation links: About, Content, Docs, Tools, and Co. A search bar contains the text 'bijay' and a 'Go!' button. Below the search bar, the text reads 'Search results for bijay' and 'Showing 16 results out of 352'. On the left side, there are filter sections for 'Species' (with checkboxes for 'Entries without species (232)' and 'Homo sapiens (120)'), 'Types' (with checkboxes for 'Icon (351)' and 'Person (1)'), and 'Search properties' (with a checked checkbox for 'Group by type'). A 'Reset filters' button is located below these filters. The main content area displays two result categories: 'Person (1 results from a total of 1)' and 'Icon (15 results from a total of 351)'. The 'Person' result is for 'Jassal, Bijay', showing 'Authored Pathways: 504', 'Reviewed Pathways: 93', 'Authored Reactions: 2103', and 'Reviewed Reactions: 387', along with an ORCID ID. The 'Icon' result is for 'LRAT', showing 'Species: Homo sapiens', 'Curator: Bijay Jassal', 'Designer: Cristoffer Sevilla', and the enzyme name 'Lecithin retinol acyltransferase'. A blue 'LRAT' button is visible next to the enzyme name.

reactome

About Content Docs Tools Co

bijay Go!

Search results for **bijay**

Showing 16 results out of 352

Species

- Entries without species (232)
- Homo sapiens (120)

Types

- Icon (351)
- Person (1)

Search properties

- Group by type

Reset filters

Person (1 results from a total of 1)

Jassal, Bijay

Authored Pathways: 504 Reviewed Pathways: 93
Authored Reactions: 2103 Reviewed Reactions: 387
ORCID: [0000-0002-5039-5405](#)

Icon (15 results from a total of 351)

LRAT

Species: Homo sapiens
Curator: [Bijay Jassal](#)
Designer: [Cristoffer Sevilla](#)
Lecithin retinol acyltransferase

LRAT

Crediting Contributors

e.g. O95631, NTN1, signaling by EGFR, glucose, GO:0043293

Go!

 Bijay Jassal

Expand All

 ORCID

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5039-5405>

Are you Bijay Jassal ? Register or Connect your ORCID

Project
Affiliation

Reactome
Ontario Institute for Cancer Research

Authored Pathways (15/504)

Date	Identifier	Pathway	Reference
2020-08-14	R-HSA-9694516	SARS-CoV-2 Infection	BibTex
2020-03-23	R-HSA-9679191	Potential therapeutics for SARS	BibTex
2020-02-05	R-HSA-9658195	Leishmania infection	BibTex
2020-01-09	R-HSA-9673324	WNT5:FZD7-mediated leishmania damping	BibTex

Crediting Contributors

SIGN IN/REGISTER English

- ABOUT
- FOR RESEARCHERS
- MEMBERSHIP
- DOCUMENTATION
- RESOURCES
- NEWS & EVENTS

Bijay Jassal

ORCID ID

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5039-5405>

Print view

Country

United Kingdom

Works (50 of 587)

Sort

Items per page: 50 1 - 50 of 587

Triglyceride biosynthesis

2019-02-28 | data-set

DOI: 10.3180/REACT_1190.2

Source: Reactome

★ Preferred source

Lewis blood group biosynthesis

2018-02-20 | data-set

OTHER-ID: R-HSA-9037629

Source: Reactome

★ Preferred source

Rhesus blood group biosynthesis

2018-02-20 | data-set

OTHER-ID: R-HSA-9037628

Source: Reactome

★ Preferred source

Getting started: Creating a pathway outline

1 Metabolism of steroids Pathway

2 Cholesterol biosynthesis Pathway

3 reactions Reaction

3 Cholesterol biosynthesis via lathosterol Pathway

3 Cholesterol biosynthesis via desmosterol Pathway

2 Regulation of cholesterol biosynthesis by SREBP (SREBF) Pathway

3 reactions Reaction

3 Activation of gene expression by SREBF (SREBP) Pathway

- Metabolism of steroids
 - Cholesterol biosynthesis
 - ACAT2 condenses 2 Ac-CoA to form ACA-CoA
 - HMGCS1 condenses Ac-CoA and ACA-CoA to form bHMG-CoA
 - HMGCR dimer reduces bHMG-CoA to MVA
 - HMGCR dimer binds statins
 - Mevalonate is phosphorylated to mevalonate-5-phosphate
 - Mevalonate-5-phosphate is further phosphorylated.
 - MVD decarboxylates MVA5PP to IPPP
 - Isopentenyl pyrophosphate rearranges to dimethylallyl pyrophosphate
 - FDPS dimer transfers IPPP to DMAPP
 - GGPS1 hexamer transfers IPPP to DMAPP
 - FDPS dimer transfers IPPP to GPP
 - GGPS1 hexamer transfers IPPP to GPP
 - holo-FDPS dimer binds NBPs
 - Two FPP molecules dimerize to form presqualene diphosphate
 - Phospholipid phosphatase 6 hydrolyses Presqualene diphosphate to presqualene
 - Reduction of presqualene diphosphate to form squalene
 - Squalene is oxidized to its epoxide
 - Squalene 2,3-epoxide cyclizes, forming lanosterol
 - CYP51A1 demethylates LNSOL
 - 4,4-dimethylcholesta-8(9),14,24-trien-3beta-ol is reduced to 4,4-dimethylcholesta-8(9),14,24-trien-3beta-ol
 - 4,4-dimethylcholesta-8(9),14,24-trien-3beta-ol is reduced to 4,4-dimethylcholesta-8(9),24-dien-3beta-ol
 - 4,4-dimethylcholesta-8(9),24-dien-3beta-ol is oxidized to 4-methyl,4-carboxycholesta-8(9),24-dien-3beta-ol
 - 4-methyl,4-carboxycholesta-8(9),24-dien-3beta-ol is decarboxylated and oxidized to 4-methylcholesta-8(9),24-dien-3-one
 - 4-methylcholesta-8(9),24-dien-3-one is reduced to 4-methylcholesta-8(9),24-dien-3beta-ol
 - 4-methylcholesta-8(9),24-dien-3beta-ol is oxidized to 4-carboxycholesta-8(9),24-dien-3beta-ol
 - 4-carboxycholesta-8(9),24-dien-3beta-ol is decarboxylated and oxidized to 4-methylcholesta-8(9),24-dien-3-one
 - Zymosterone (cholesta-8(9),24-dien-3-one) is reduced to zymosterol (cholesta-8(9),24-dien-3beta-ol)
 - Cholesterol biosynthesis via desmosterol
 - Cholesterol biosynthesis via lathosterol
 - ARV1 transports CHOL from ER membrane to plasma membrane
 - Regulation of cholesterol biosynthesis by SREBP (SREBF)
 - SREBP1A,1C,2 binds SCAP:cholesterol:INSIG and is retained in the endoplasmic reticulum
 - SREBP1A,1C,2 binds SCAP:INSIG:oxysterol and is retained in the endoplasmic reticulum
 - SREBP1A,1C,2:SCAP binds CopI Coat Complex
 - SREBP1A,1C,2:SCAP translocates to the Golgi
 - S1P hydrolyzes SREBP1A,1C,2
 - S2P hydrolyzes SREBP1A,1C,2
 - SREBP1A,1C,2 binds SREBP1A,1C,2 forming dimers
 - SREBP1A,1C,2 binds Importin beta-1
 - SREBP1A,1C,2 translocates to the nucleus
 - SREBP1A,1C,2:Importin beta-1 dissociates
 - Activation of gene expression by SREBF (SREBP)

Expert knowledge capture - plan structure

Pathway hierarchy

Level description	Reactome sld	Pathway Name
top pathway	R-HSA-191273	Cholesterol biosynthesis
subpathway of Cholesterol biosynthesis	R-HSA-6807047	Cholesterol biosynthesis via desmosterol
subpathway of Cholesterol biosynthesis	R-HSA-6807062	Cholesterol biosynthesis via lathosterol
top pathway	R-HSA-1655829	Regulation of cholesterol biosynthesis by SREBP (SREBF)
subpathway Regulation of cholesterol biosynthesis by SREBP (S	R-HSA-2426168	Activation of gene expression by SREBF (SREBP)

D	E	F	G
Summation	GO_BP	GO_BP name	PubMed refs
Cholesterol is synthesized de novo from acetyl CoA. The overall synthetic p	GO:0006695	cholesterol biosynthetic process	11969204 12668600 3524618 1390320 16054061
The transformation of zymosterol into cholesterol can follow either of routes,	GO:0033489	cholesterol biosynthetic process via desmosterol	26114596
The transformation of zymosterol into cholesterol can follow either of routes,	GO:0033490	cholesterol biosynthetic process via lathosterol	14404284 26114596
Sterol regulatory element binding proteins (SREBP _α , SREBF _α) respond to k	GO:0045540	regulation of cholesterol biosynthetic process	18974038 19933148 15457548
After transiting to the nucleus SREBPs (SREBP1A/1C/2, SREBFs) bind sho	GO:0019216	regulation of lipid metabolic process	15589694 9748295 15457548

Expert knowledge capture - Reaction details

add new or revise?	Pathway Name	Reaction name	Reaction type	Tissue/Cell type	Summation	input n
Revise	top pathway	existing reaction 1	Reaction	(eg Human kidney/HEK-293)	revise rxn1	
New	subpathway 1	new reaction 2	BlackBoxEvent		describe rxn2	
New	subpathway 1	new reaction 3	Reaction		describe rxn3	
New	subpathway N	new reaction 4	Reaction		describe rxn4	

Reaction naming - catalysed reactions

PROTEIN “does something” to **SUBSTRATE** (to **PRODUCT**)

HMGR dimer reduces **bHMG-CoA** to **MVA**

3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl-CoA reductase dimer reduces **beta-hydroxy-beta-methylglutaryl-CoA** to **mevalonate**

“Dimeric 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl-CoA reductase (HMGR dimer) catalyzes the four-electron reduction of beta-hydroxy-beta-methylglutaryl-CoA (bHMG-CoA) to mevalonate (MVA). MVA concentrations in the cell are tightly controlled through the activity of HMGR dimer, which is one of the most highly regulated enzymes in metabolism (Goldstein & Brown 1990).”

Cholesterol biosynthesis

- ACAT2 condenses 2 Ac-CoA to form ACA-CoA
- HMGRS1 condenses Ac-CoA and ACA-CoA to form bHMG-CoA
- HMGR dimer reduces bHMG-CoA to MVA
- Mevalonate is phosphorylated to mevalonate-5-phosphate

Reaction naming - non-catalysed reactions

SUBSTRATE 1 “binds” SUBSTRATE 2

TTPA binds alpha-TOH

TTPA + alpha-TOH => TTPA:alpha-TOH

A COMPLEX “dissociates”

VD3 dissociates from GC

VD3:GC => VD3 + GC

SUBSTRATE “translocates” from compartment 1 to compartment 2

VD3 translocates from ER membrane to extracellular region

VD3 [ER membrane] => VD3 [extracellular region]

Data entry - Curator Tool

Schema View | Event Hierarchical View | Entity Level View

Tree View | Show in: All | Graphic Display

Reaction Properties

Property Name	Value
catalystActivity	beta-galactosidase activity of BG...
entityFunctionalStatus	
input	1 x GM1 [lysosomal membrane] 1 x H2O [lysosomal lumen]
output	1 x GM2 [lysosomal membrane] 1 x Gal [lysosomal lumen]
DB_ID	1605624
_displayName	Beta-galactosidase hydrolyses GM1 ...
_doRelease	true
authored	Jassal, Bijay, 2011-09-21
catalystActivityReference	
compartment	lysosomal lumen lysosomal membrane
created	Jassal, Bijay, 2011-09-21
crossReference	
definition	
disease	
edited	Jassal, Bijay, 2011-09-21
entityOnOtherCell	
evidenceType	
figure	
goBiologicalProcess	
inferredFrom	
isChimeric	false
literatureReference	Human small-intestinal beta-gala... Human beta-galactosidase gene ... Human beta-galactosidase gene ... Jassal, B, 2011-09-21 Jassal, Bijay, 2011-09-23 Jassal, Bijay, 2011-10-31
modified	
name	Beta-galactosidase hydrolyses GM1 ...
normalReaction	
orthologousEvent	
precedingEvent	
regulatedBy	
regulationReference	
relatedSpecies	
releaseDate	2011-12-06
releaseStatus	
requiredInputComponent	
reverseReaction	
reviewed	Stephan, Ralf, 2011-10-31
revised	
species	Homo sapiens
stableIdentifier	R-HSA-1605624.1
summation	gangliosides are glycosphingolipi...
systematicName	

Entity Level View

Search Events

Disease pathways and processes in Reactome

- Reactome can annotate disease pathways such as cancer, metabolic, immune and infectious diseases
- Disease is overlaid normal pathways to show context
- Disease events may be loss-of-function or gain-of-function compared to the normal process
- Infection pathways are captured as host:pathogen interactions

Expert knowledge for disease annotation

- Experts for normal pathways may already know details of disease events.
- Popular resources can be used as points of reference - OMIM, COSMIC (for cancer), Gene Reviews, Scriver encyclopedia of human genetic diseases
- For non-infectious disease pathways, the disease pathway should be constructed in the context of an annotated normal process
- Key/prevalent pathogenic variants are created for use in disease reactions

Disease variants

- Used in disease reactions that can be overlaid normal diagrams to show the effect of the disease
- Reactome can annotate missense, nonsense, fragment deletion, insertion and replacement variants as well as fusion proteins.

The disease phenylketonuria is caused by a missense mutation in the enzyme phenylalanine hydroxylase which normally converts the amino acid phenylalanine to tyrosine. The defective enzyme allows the build-up of phenylalanine to toxic levels which can cause intellectual disability and impair cognitive development.

Drug curation in Reactome

- The majority of drugs curated in Reactome “bind then regulate” a target
- Regulation can be described as either positive or negative (agonist/stimulatory/channel opener or antagonist/inhibitory/channel blocker drugs respectively)
- “Drug” class - chemical, protein and RNA subclasses
- Guide to Pharmacology IDs used as the main “reference” identifier for drugs
- Can group drugs into sets which have same MoA for a given target
- Any entity containing a drug will be filled in purple - visual impact in a diagram

Drug visualisation

Angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) mediates blood pressure by catalysing the cleavage of the hormone angiotensin to its vasoconstrictor form.

ACE inhibitors (ACEIs) bind to and inhibit the actions of ACE -> angiotensin cleavage is blocked -> ultimately results in the lowering of blood pressure.

Data Requirement Overview

	Level	Name	Summation	GO: BP	GO: MF	GO: CC	PMID	Input	Output	Catalyst	Regulator	Preceding Event	Mutation	Drug
Pathway	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory		When available/relevant	Mandatory							
Normal Reaction		Mandatory	Mandatory		When available/relevant	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory	When available/relevant	When available/relevant	When available/relevant		
Disease Reaction		Mandatory	Mandatory		When available/relevant	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory	When available/relevant				
Drug Reaction		Mandatory	Mandatory		When available/relevant	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory	When available/relevant	When available/relevant	When available/relevant	When available/relevant	Mandatory

 Mandatory

 When available/relevant

Appendix C2. Quick curation guide/reference

[Overview of the Curation process \(slides\)](#)

Full guide is available [here](#) for fine details.

The Curator Tool – download, use, upload

Choosing a topic

The main data classes and attributes

Guide to naming entities and events

Drawing diagrams

The Curator Tool (CT)

The CT provides a standalone GUI for curation. It provides all the classes from which you can create instances to use in your pathway annotations. It also allows access to the central repository (gk_central) from which you can import instances already created to use in your annotation. Once your pathways are thoroughly curated and have all their must-have attributes filled, you can upload them to gk_central via synchronisation. This will check for duplicates before uploading.

Download the CT from the “Downloads” page [here](#).

Install for your particular platform from [here](#). Follow installation instructions on this page.

Open tool and go to “Preferences” to add connection details on the “Database info” tab.

Database Host: the server you upload new content to

Database Name: gk_central, the central data repository

User Name: ask

User Password: ask

With these username and password credentials, you are able to create and download content from gk_central but you can't upload material to it yet.

Choosing a topic

1. Focus on biology you know well.
2. Make sure reactions are well characterized at the molecular level with good HUMAN biochemical evidence that you should **NOT** include events based solely on microarray, proteomics or similar high throughput data
3. Check the [Projects](#) sheet to check you are not duplicating another curator's work

Main [Data Classes](#) for curation

For more information, see full data model glossary [here](#).

Event

[Pathway](#), [Reaction](#), [BlackBoxEvent](#), [Depolymerization](#), [Polymerization](#), [FailedReaction](#)

PhysicalEntity

[EntityWithAccessionedSequence](#) (EWAS), [SimpleEntity](#), [Complex](#), [Polymer](#), [EntitySet](#)

ReferenceEntity

[ReferenceGroup](#), [ReferenceMolecule](#), [ReferenceSequence](#), [ReferenceDNASequence](#), [ReferenceGeneProduct](#)

[CatalystActivity](#)

[Summation](#)

[Taxon \(Species\)](#)

[Publication](#) – Book, LiteratureReference, URL

[GO BiologicalProcess](#)

[GO CellularComponent](#)

[GO MolecularFunction](#)

[Disease](#)

[Attributes](#)

Data classes have a number of details that must be completed before being made public.

m - Mandatory, you must provide this information

r – Required, provide this is possible. Example is species, required for a set of proteins but not for a set of small molecules
o – Optional, not available for every class instance but may be a procedural requirement eg. `inferredFrom` should be filled in if evidence for an event comes from another species

Naming entities and events

For detailed background reading, please refer to [this](#) paper.

We have created a controlled vocabulary (cv) to consistently name entities and the events they participate in. Names are based on familiar biological names and terms, minimize ambiguity and support data mining.

Proteins (represented as EWASs in Reactome) are constructed around a ‘core’ Human Gene Organization (HUGO) Gene Nomenclature Committee (HGNC) approved gene symbol. The HGNC is the only worldwide authority that assigns standardized nomenclature to human genes, and as such is widely recognized as the authoritative source of names for genes. No such similar body exists for protein names; consequently, HGNC is the only practical source of short unambiguous names that can be used to name the translated products of those genes. Reactome obtains HGNC gene symbols indirectly from UniProt, an attribute associated with every peptide EWAS.

The CV also caters for coordinates and PTMs. For coordinates, to describe cleaved products, we use UniProt’s ‘Chain’ feature. Example

Caspase-9 precursor, with peptide coordinates start:1 end:416 is named CASP9. The large and small subunits of caspase-9 are respectively named **CASP9(1–315)** and **CASP9(316–416)**.

For PTMs, we add a prefix and hyphen to the gene symbol. Reactome defines PTMs with `hasModifiedResidue` annotations. These use terms obtained from the Protein Standards Initiative modifications ([PSI-MOD](#)) ontology. Examples

p-Y139-DAPP1 is DAPP1 phosphorylated on tyrosine-139.

p-Y150,S343,T346-WASF2 is WASF2 phosphorylated on tyrosine-150, serine-343 and threonine-346. Note that phosphorylations are ordered by coordinate.

p-Y55,S112,S121,Y227-SPRY2 —note that the ordering is by coordinate, not grouped by phosphorylation subtype.

p-Y-GAB2 is GAB2 phosphorylated on a tyrosine; the coordinate position of this tyrosine is unknown.

p-GLI3 is GLI3 phosphorylated; both the phosphorylation subtype and position are unknown.

When combinations of phosphorylation and another PTM occur, the phosphorylations are represented after everything else:

2xPalmC-MyrG-p-S1177-NOS3(2-1203) is NOS3 fragment 2-1203 with two palmitoylated cysteines, one myristoylated glycine and a phosphorylation on serine-1177.

Small molecules (represented by SimpleEntity in Reactome) have abbreviated names in most cases created by us. A big benefit of these 'short' names is reduced space and avoids clutter.

Complexes and sets also catered for.

Reactions

Reactome reaction names are created using free text, which can lead to ambiguity and inconsistency. Use of a controlled vocabulary for reaction names creates consistency and allows users to predict, search and understand these names more easily. They also facilitate bulk computational queries and data mining.

Reactions can be transformations (catalysed), binding, dissociation, transport, diffusion, (de)polymerisation and it is important to name these types consistently.

When a catalyst is involved, that should be the focus of the reaction name followed by the type of activity it performs followed by the substrate it acts upon.

CATALYST verb **SUBSTRATE** (to **PRODUCT**) – the product name is optional

PLB1 hydrolyses RPALM to atROL
PTGDS isomerizes PGH2 to PGD2

See naming doc for details of these types of reaction names.

When there is no catalyst involved in a reaction (binding, dissociation, translocation) then the focus is on the substrate. These reactions styles are

a **BINDS** b forming c

c **DISSOCIATES TO** a AND b

a **TRANSLOCATES FROM** [compartment x] **TO** [compartment y]

Drawing diagrams

To display the molecular details annotated in pathways and reactions, entity-level views (ELVs) are created using the Entity Level View tab in the CT. Refer to the [curator guide](#) for full details.

Annotations infectious disease

Disease pathways are housed under the 'Disease' chapter in Reactome's hierarchy.

Event Hierarchy:

- **Cell Cycle**
- Cell-Cell communication
- Cellular responses to external stimuli
- Chromatin organization
- Circadian Clock
- Developmental Biology
- Digestion and absorption
- **Disease**
 - **Diseases of signal transduction**
 - **Disorders of transmembrane transporters**
 - **Diseases of metabolism**
 - **Diseases of glycosylation**
 - **Infectious disease**
 - **HIV Infection**
 - **Influenza Infection**
 - **Latent infection of Homo sapiens with Mycobacterium tuberculosis**
 - **Uptake and actions of bacterial toxins**
 - **Listeria monocytogenes entry into host cells**

Reactions for your pathway will be created in the CT as below

Reaction Properties	
Property Name	Value
catalystActivity	glutathione hydrolase activity of GgtA [periplasmic space]
entityFunctionalStatus	
input	GSNO [periplasmic space] Amino Acid [periplasmic space]
output	L-Glutamyl amino acid [periplasmic space] S-Nitroso-L-cysteinylglycine [periplasmic space]
DB_ID	1222712
_displayName	Nitrosogluthathione gets cleaved to Cys(NO)-Gly
_doRelease	true
authored	Stephan, R, 2011-01-10
compartment	periplasmic space
created	Jassal, B, 2011-02-28
crossReference	
definition	
disease	tuberculosis
edited	Jassal, B, 2011-02-28
entityOnOtherCell	
evidenceType	
figure	
goBiologicalProcess	
inferredFrom	
isChimeric	false
literatureReference	Characterization of a glutathione metabolic mutant of My... Jassal, B, 2011-08-08 Jassal, B, 2011-10-11 Jassal, B, 2011-11-03 Matthews, L, 2011-11-18 Jassal, Bijay, 2011-11-23 Jassal, B, 2012-02-08 Jassal, B, 2012-02-10 Jassal, Bijay, 2012-02-25 Jassal, B, 2012-04-20 Jassal, B, 2012-04-30 Jassal, B, 2013-05-20 Jassal, Bijay, 2014-07-14
modified	
name	Nitrosogluthathione gets cleaved to Cys(NO)-Gly
normalReaction	
orthologousEvent	
precedingEvent	
regulatedBy	
relatedSpecies	Mycobacterium tuberculosis
releaseDate	2012-06-12
releaseStatus	
requiredInputComponent	
reverseReaction	
reviewed	Warner, D, 2012-04-30
revised	
species	Homo sapiens
stableIdentifier	R-HSA-1222712.1
summation	Most gamma-glutamyl transpeptidases (GGT) cleave bot...
systematicName	

The “species” slot on the event identifies the environment where the reaction is happening. This should almost always be human for human Reactome curation. The pathogen(s) would be listed in the “relatedSpecies”. The ELV you need to create would be the same as a normal ELV but with pathogenic proteins in them. When drawing infection reactions that involve pathogenic proteins, the node and edges need to be coloured red but leave human proteins in their original colours

V90_Sept 2024

- updated links to the V90 Curator Guide and V90 Data Model Glossary

Appendix C3: Evidence confidence			
Evidence	Comment	Examples	% Confidence
Two experimental papers from independent groups demonstrating the same mechanism	Gold standard, can be included as reaction unless reviewer expresses doubt.	879925	100
One experimental paper and external expert author indicates that they believe the event is proven by this	Can be included as reaction unless reviewer expresses doubt	1067640	90
One experimental paper with more than one experimental method determining the mechanism of the event	Not sufficient		
One experimental paper, reported as established in a review paper	Can be included unless Reactome reviewer expresses doubt		70
Two instances of correlated observations but no proof of mechanism, e.g. addition of recombinant kinase A, observation that protein X is phosphorylated, or addition of novel protein ligand leads to upregulation of signal, but no demonstration of ligand binding or mechanism that leads to signal	Black-box	8950269	50
Ligand binds receptor leading to some kind of signal. Ligand and/or receptor clearly belong to known family, other family members have well characterized mechanism of receptor activation and signaling. Inference made by curator that mechanism of signaling is the same for other single family member	Reaction for demonstrated molecular events e.g. ligand binding, specific phosphorylations or other activating events. Black box events should be included to represent events equivalent to the full series of molecular events demonstrated for the well characterized system.		80
Molecular details obtained for one member of a set used to infer that the same generic mechanism exists for the other set members, where set represents a family.	This is the intended usage for candidate sets and such sets can be used in reactions. Also sufficient for defined sets used in reactions that are part of a generic pathway such as GPCR signaling, where multiple literature sources suggest without question that the actions of all members of the family are mechanistically similar. Would not be sufficient for defined set used in a non-generic pathway event.	379048	80
Two reports of gene expression stimulated by transcription factor binding to specific promoter region	Reaction		100
One reports of gene/ expression stimulated by transcription factor binding to specific promoter region	Not sufficient		
Two reports of protein expression regulated following activation of a specific factor but no evidence of TF binding to gene promoter	Black box with regulation		60
Two reports of gene/protein expression regulation following activation of a specific transcription factor, but no evidence of binding to promoters	Black box with regulation		60
One reports of gene/protein expression regulation following activation of a specific transcription factor, but no evidence of binding to promoters	Not sufficient		
Dissociation events where dissociation is inferred from subsequent involvement in another event such as binding or translocation	Black box		70
Evidence that describes actions of a complex component where evidence is in vitro, not experimentally demonstrating activity while part of a complex	This is typically considered sufficient for a reaction as long as complex formation has been demonstrated (would be a preceding event).	446694	90
Single experiment evidence obtained with relative used to infer similar mechanism	Not sufficient	157644	70
Evidence of translocation but mechanism not identified	Black box unless small molecule capable of passive movement		
Event inferred from model organism			score of human event - 20
Note - in all cases, if publications refute the evidence, the event is controversial and should not be included			

The UpdateTracker Class instances describe revisions to events that have occurred between releases. These instances are created automatically during database slicing and require a comparison between the current slice and previous slice databases.

The following changes constitute a revision in an RLE or Pathway.

I. RLE:

An RLE is considered revised if:

- A Catalyst added/removed/changed
- A regulator added/removed/changed
- A change is made in inputs/outputs
- A significant change in summation (?) (curator discretion(?))

II. Pathway:

A pathway is considered revised if::

1. An immediate child RLE is added/removed
2. An immediate child RLE revised
 - A Catalyst added/removed/changed
 - A regulator added/removed/changed
 - A change is made in inputs/outputs
 - A significant change in summation (?) (curator discretion(?))
3. An immediate child Pathway added/removed
4. An immediate child Pathway is revised as in **#1, #2, #3**

UpdateTracker instances register changes as "action" attributes.

The possible action types are:

"add"

"remove"

"add_remove" (i.e. both addition and removal on a multi-valued **instance** attribute)

"modify" (i.e. changed value on a multi-valued **text** attribute)

"update" (i.e. a contained child event in a pathway has changed)

They are paired with specifically what changed:

For Pathways:

"hasEvent"

"literatureReference"

"summation" (the actual instances in the slot)

"text" (the summation text content rather than the summation instance)

"updateContainedRLE" (a direct RLE child has a change)

"updateIndirectRLE" (a descendant, non-immediate RLE in a sub-pathway for a child has a change)

"updateContainedPathway" (a direct pathway child has a change)

*NOTE: If "updateIndirectRLE" is indicated for a pathway, this means one or more of its sub-pathways should have "updateContainedPathway".

For ReactionlikeEvents:

"input"

"output"

"catalystActivity"

"literatureReference"

"summation" (the actual instances in the slot)

"text" (the summation text content rather than the summation instance)

****Note:** If an event has the same type of action occurs more than once in a release cycle, it is only listed once but multiple actions will be recorded for a single release if more than one type of action occurred (for example, "addInput", "addOutput" in an update tracker for an RLE can occur together but if 2 inputs were added "addInput" would only show up once).

PhysicalEntity Update types:

UpdateTracker instances register changes as "action" attributes.

The possible action types are:

"add"

"remove"

"add_remove" (i.e. both addition and removal on a multi-valued **instance** attribute)

"modify" (i.e. changed value on a multi-valued **text** attribute)

"update" (i.e. a contained child event in a pathway has changed)

The update types checked for all physical entities are:

"cellType",

"compartment",

"disease",

"literatureReference",

"name",

"summation",

"systematic name"

In addition, the following are checked for each type of Physical Entities:

Cell: "markerReference", "organ", "proteinMarker", "RNAMarker", "species", "tissue", "tissueLayer"

Complex: "hasComponent", "entityOnOtherCell", "species", "stoichiometryKnown"

Drug: "species"

EWAS: "referenceEntity", "endCoordinate", "startCoordinate", "hasModifiedResidue"

GEE: "inferredFrom", "species"

Polymer: "maxUnitCount", "minUnitCount", "repeatedUnit"

SimpleEntity: "species"

Set: "hasCandidate", "hasMember", "species"

Appendix C5. Data Model Glossary

Overview

Reactome is [a slot-and-frame knowledge representation](#) of a network of molecular transformations mediated by gene products. Classes (frames) are categories like reaction and protein. Related classes are grouped into superclasses to allow inheritance of shared attributes. For example, the "PhysicalEntity" superclass has child classes such as Complex and GenomeEncodedEntity. Classes have slots (attributes) whose values define properties of instances (e.g., the names and numbers of copies of the molecules that make up a complex). "Defining" attributes are used in the data model to distinguish instances of a class, to ensure that identical information, e.g., a water molecule localized to the cytosol, or a reaction by which a particular molecule from extracellular space is translocated into the cytosol mediated by a particular transport protein, is represented exactly once in Reactome. Many attributes of a class instance are instances of other classes. For example, a **Person** instance has a *surname* attribute that is a text string not taken from anywhere else but can also have an *affiliation* attribute that is an instance of the **affiliation** class, a class of *names* and *addresses* of institutions. In this glossary, **boldface** type indicates use of a word or phrase as a class name (the **CatalystActivity** of a particular enzyme) and *italic* type indicates use as an attribute (the *catalystActivity* that mediates a chemical transformation reaction). Words that can be either class names or attributes are defined under "Reactome Classes"; ones that are only attributes are defined under "Reactome attributes".

Glossary of Key Reactome Classes

AbstractModifiedResidue [superclass]

Used to maintain logical integrity of data model, not used for manual annotation. The superclass in the Reactome data model from which the GeneticallyModifiedResidue, TranscriptionalModification, and TranslationalModification classes inherit their shared attributes. Describes a modification to reference sequence. The three subclasses of modifications are GeneticallyModifiedResidue, TranscriptionalModification, TranslationalModification.

GeneticallyModifiedResidue [superclass]

Used to maintain logical integrity of data model, not used for manual annotation. Subclass of abstractModifiedResidue from which the FragmentModification and ReplacedResidue classes inherit their shared attributes. Describes a protein sequence change resulting from a genetic modification

FragmentModification [superclass]

Used to maintain logical integrity of data model, not used for manual annotation. Children of this class (FragmentDeletionModification, FragmentInsertionModification and FragmentReplacedModification) are used to capture the deletion, insertion or replacement of consecutive amino acid residues in an EWAS in a disease variant of a gene product.

FragmentDeletionModification

The deletion of a continuous fragment of an EntityWithAccessionedSequence, e.g. deletion of amino acid residues 30 to 297 in the EGFR mutant protein EGFRvIII in glioblastoma. Attributes of the FragmentDeletionModification instance are the *referenceSequence* (UniProt P00533 EGFR in the case of EGFRvIII), the *startPositionInReferenceSequence*, which is the first amino acid of the deleted fragment (30 in the case of EGFRvIII), and the *endPositionInReferenceSequence*, which equals the last amino acid of the deleted fragment (297 in the case of EGFRvIII).

FragmentInsertionModification

Used to describe the modification of an EntityWithAccessionedSequence through insertion of a continuous fragment. This class is used to annotate variants EWASs containing duplications or fusions. A duplication is defined as the insertion of a stretch of WT amino-acid(s) that is the direct repeat of the amino-acid(s) immediately 5' to the inserted sequence. For duplications, the *referenceSequence* specified in the FragmentInsertionModification record is the same as the *referenceEntity* specified in the EWAS record.

Fusions are the result of the insertion of a continuous stretch of amino-acids derived from a second EWAS at a specified residue in a first EWAS. For fusions, the *referenceSequence* specified in the FragmentInsertionModification record is the *referenceEntity* for the C-terminal fusion partner, and is different from the *referenceEntity* specified in the EWAS record, which represents the N-terminal partner.

FragmentReplacedModification

The modification of an EntityWithAccessionedSequence through the replacement of the WT amino-acid sequence with a specified alternate sequence of amino-acids as the result of an insertion, fusion, indel, frameshift or extension of the WT sequence. Details of these annotations vary depending on the type of replacement, and are outlined in the Curator Guide. Unlike FragmentDeletionModification and FragmentInsertionModification, FragmentReplacementModification requires that the curator explicitly annotate the single letter amino-acid sequence that arises in the variant protein. Note also that, by Reactome convention, insertions are captured by FragmentReplacedModification, not FragmentInsertionModification. In the FragmentReplaceModification record for an insertion, the *alteredAminoAcidFragment* includes both the flanking WT 5'- and 3' amino-acids as well as the inserted amino-acids. For example, in the variant EGFR D770_N771insNPG, amino acids NPG are inserted between D770 and N771, and the specified *alteredAminoAcidFragment* in the FragmentReplacedModification is DNPGN.

ReplacedResidue

A subclass of **GeneticallyModifiedResidue**, **ReplacedResidue** describes the replacement of an amino acid residue of a UniProt *referenceSequence* with a different amino acid residue or a stop codon as the result of a mutation, germline or somatic, in the corresponding gene. Class attributes identify the *coordinate* of the affected residue in the protein sequence, the identity of the residue specified in the UniProt sequence (first *psiMOD* attribute value), and the identity of the replacement residue (second *psiMOD* attribute value).

NonsenseMutation

A subclass of the **ReplacedResidue** class, **NonsenseMutation** describes the *coordinate* at which a protein *referenceSequence* is truncated due to a nonsense mutation. In the **NonsenseMutation** record, a single *psiMod* is specified, indicating as an amino acid removal the amino acid that is altered to generate a stop codon.

TranscriptionalModification [superclass]

Used to maintain logical integrity of data model, not used for manual annotation. Subclass of **AbstractModifiedResidue**. Describes an RNA sequence modification.

ModifiedNucleotide

Describes the location and chemical nature of a nucleotide modification in an RNA sequence.

TranslationalModification [superclass]

Used to maintain logical integrity of data model, not used for manual annotation. Subclass of **AbstractModifiedResidue**. Includes children **CrosslinkedResidue**, **GroupModifiedResidue** and **ModifiedResidue**. Describes a post translational chemical modification to a protein. Modifications are cross referenced to the psi-MOD ontology of terms that describe protein chemical modifications.

CrosslinkedResidue [superclass]

Used to maintain logical integrity of data model, not used for manual annotation. Subclass of **TranslationalModification**. Two subclasses, **Inter-** and **IntraChainCrosslinkedResidue**, are used to annotate disulfide, thioester or other protein crosslinks, including to ie sumoyl or ubiquitin groups.

InterChainCrosslinkedResidue

Subclass of **CrosslinkedResidue**. Used to annotate cross-linking between two different peptide chains.

IntraChainCrosslinkedResidue

Subclass of **CrosslinkedResidue**. Used to annotate cross-linking between amino acid residues within the same peptide chain. **IntraChainCrosslinkedResidue** instances are made in pairs, one associated with the EWAS record of each of the cross-linked proteins, and the **IntraChainCrosslinkedResidue** records are associated with each other through their *equivalentTo* attribute.

GroupModifiedResidue

Subclass of **TranslationalModification**. Describes the modification of an amino acid residue in protein with a chemical entity that cannot be specified in atomic detail, e.g., the attachment of a dextrin or glycogen moiety to a tyrosine side chain in the protein glycogenin. Such incompletely specified chemical entities are beyond the scope of the psi-MOD ontology but are available in the ChEBI ontology. The *psiMod* attribute would take a value such as MOD:00166 O4'-glucosyl-L-tyrosine, which describes the linkage between the protein and the modifying group. The modifying group is then specified with a *ReferenceGroup* instance (ChEBI terms) such as CHEBI:28912 "limit dextrin", as in the example: limit dextrans on L-Tyrosine [ChEBI:17895] 194 of UniProt:P46976 GYG1.

ModifiedResidue

Subclass of **TranslationalModification**. Used to describe the translational or post-translational modification of an amino-acid, such as phosphorylation, gamma-carboxylation etc. The **ModifiedResidue** record defines the associated EWAS reference sequence along with the coordinate of the modified amino-acid and the nature of the modification, taking terms from *psiMOD*. **ModifiedResidue** class is used when the chemical natures of the modifying group can be specified in atomic detail with a *psiMod* term. This is in contrast to **GroupModifiedResidue**, which is used when the modification can not be completely described by a term from *psi-MOD*.

Affiliation

The name and address of an institution, e.g. [Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory / 1 Bungtown Road, Cold Spring Harbor NY USA](#). Any **Person** instance can have an *affiliation* attribute, but at present this information is recorded only for Reactome authors, reviewers, and curators.

CatalystActivity

Describes the catalyst in a **ReactionLikeEvent**: associates one *physicalEntity* with one *GO_molecularFunction*., e.g., [cysteine-type endopeptidase activity of active caspase-8](#). If the *physicalEntity* is a **Complex** and a component of the complex mediates the molecularFunction, that component should be identified as the *activeUnit* of the **CatalystActivity**.

If a **PhysicalEntity** can enable multiple **MolecularFunctions**, a separate **CatalystActivity** instance is created for each..

ControlReference [superclass]

Used to maintain logical integrity of data model, not used for manual annotation. Associates one or more **Publications** with an instance (e.g., *catalystActivity*) of another class.

CatalystActivityReference

Associates a **CatalystActivity** instance with one or more **Publications**.

MarkerReference

Associates an RNA or protein **EntityWithAccessionedSequence** that has been identified as a *proteinMarker* or *RNAmarker* of a **Cell** with one or more **Publications**. *MarkerReference* is an attribute of the *Cell* class of *PhysicalEntity*.

RegulationReference

Associates any kind of **Regulation** instance with one or more **Publications**.

ControlledVocabulary [superclass]

Used to maintain logical integrity of data model, not used for manual annotation. Lists of words that can be used in attributes (slot values) in specific classes, optionally connected to one another with *is_a* relationships, created by Reactome (as opposed to ones imported from external reference resources like the Gene Ontology, ChEBI, or NCBI Taxonomy)

Has three subclasses **DeletedControlledVocabulary** (for use in “reason” attribute of *_Deleted* instances), **NegativePrecedingEventReason** (for use in “reason” attribute of *NegativePrecedingEvent* instances) and *ReactionType* (for use in *reactionType* attribute of **ReactionLikeEvent**).

NegativePrecedingEvent

Used to flag an **Event** that should not be annotated as a value of another **Event**'s *precedingEvent* attribute.

NegativePrecedingEventReason

A subclass of *ControlledVocabulary* used to indicate why a computationally inferred causal connection (*precedingEvent*) between two **ReactionLikeEvents** was manually rejected by a curator (e.g. Abundant Molecules).

ReactionType

Terms used as attributes to classify **ReactionLikeEvents** in ways that support data mining and classification, e.g., in connection with the conversion of Reactome events into GO-CAM models (under development).

DrugActionType

Terms used as attributes to classify **ReactionLikeEvent** involving **drugs** to indicate the mode of action of the drug in the **ReactionLikeEvent**.

DatabaseObject [superclass]

Used to maintain logical integrity of data model, not used for manual annotation. The root term of the Reactome data model; parent to all classes of instances; not edited manually.

Databaselfentifier

Refers to an external database identifier. An instance of this class is used in for the *databaselfentifier* attribute as an optional *crossReference* attribute of a Reactome instance to associate it with the representation of that instance in an external *ReferenceDatabase*, in addition to the required *crossReferences* to external referenceDatabases. . E.g., the Reactome **SimpleEntity** instance [PQQ \(pyroquinoline quinone\)](#), *crossReferenced* to [ReferenceMolecule:29568 pyrroloquinoline quinone \[ChEBI:18315\]](#) has a *crossReference* attribute to the *databaselfentifier* [COMPOUND:C00113](#) that links the Reactome instance to the record for this molecule maintained by the [KEGG “compound” database](#).

_Deleted

Created when an instance is deleted from the database. Includes attributes for the *deletedInstanceDB_ID*, *replacementInstanceDB_IDs* (if relevant), reason that the instance was deleted (see *DeletedControlledVocabulary* below for reason definitions), as well as optional *curatorComment* about the deletion. Additional information about the deleted Instance is provided in the *_DeletedInstance* attribute.

DeletedControlledVocabulary

An attribute of the *_Deleted* instance (which is created when a curator opts to delete an instance). Describes the reason an instance was deleted from the database. Reasons are: *Duplicated* (instance was a duplicate of an existing instance), *Killed not replaced* (instance was found to be invalid and removed without replacement), *Merged* (an instances was merged with another instance), *Obsoleted* (no longer in use: see specified replacement or comment), *Split* (the instance was split into multiple instances).

DeletedInstance

Attribute of `_Deleted` that includes the class of the deleted instance, `deletedInstanceDB_ID`, `deletedInstanceStableIdentifier`, name of the deleted instance, and species of the deleted instance (if relevant).

Disease

Disease encompasses terms that describe impairments of normal functions caused by pathogenic genetic mutations or environmental factors, such as microbial pathogens from an ExternalOntology, the Disease Ontology (DO) (<https://disease-ontology.org/>). Terms from the Disease class are used to populate the disease attribute which identifies any abnormal physicalEntity (**GenomeEncodedEntitiy**, **Complex**, EntitySets) and any abnormal event (**ReactionLikeEvent**, **Pathway**), and specifies the disease(s) with which these abnormal instances are associated. **Disease** instances include *identifier* and *name* attributes taken from DO.

EntityFunctionalStatus

EntityFunctionalStatus is used to mark a disease ReactionLikeEvent as either a gain- or a loss-of-function, and to describe the underlying reason for the change in behavior. The EntityFunctionalStatus has three attributes, *diseaseEntity*, the variant **EWAS** or **Complex** or *set* of variants, responsible for the phenotype, *normalEntity*, the wild-type instance corresponding to the disease **PhysicalEntity** and *functionalStatus*, that relates the molecular change to the functional one.

FunctionalStatus

Class used to describe the molecular basis of a change in function; combines a term from the *functionalStatusType* controlled vocabulary maintained by Reactome that identifies alterations in gene function (e.g., gain-of-function) and a *structuralVariant* term from the externalOntology Sequence Ontology that describes the nature of the genetic change (e.g., copy number gain). Class **FunctionalStatus** is used to populate the *functionalStatus* attribute of **EntityFunctionalStatus**

Event [superclass]

Used to maintain logical integrity of data model; not used for manual annotation. Any transformation of input entities to output entities in one step (**ReactionlikeEvent**) or two or more steps (**Pathway**).

Pathway

A sequence of two or more causally connected **ReactionlikeEvents** and/or other **Pathways**, identified as *hasEvent* attributes of the pathway being annotated.

CellLineagePath

A **CellLineagePath**, organizationally similar to the **Pathway** subclass, is composed of other **CellLineagePath** instances or **CellDevelopmentSteps** as subevents that are connected through shared input/output Cells.

Both Cell Development Step and Cell Lineage Path are associated with a Gene Ontology (GO) biological process term and with a “tissue” term from UBERON, an ExternalOntology of Anatomy terms.

ReactionLikeEvent [superclass]

Used to maintain logical integrity of data model; not used for manual annotation.

ReactionLikeEvent is a superclass that is used to organize other concrete reaction types, such as **Reaction**, **Polymerization** and **BlackBoxEvent**. A molecular process in which one or more input *physicalEntities* are transformed in a single step into output *physicalEntities*, optionally mediated by a *catalystActivity* and subject to *regulation*. Kinds of transformation include chemical reactions, translocation of molecules from one **compartment** to another, association of molecules to form **complexes** and **polymers**, dissociation of **complexes** and polymers, and developmental/differentiation relationships among Cell instances.

BlackBoxEvent

This class can be used to describe an incompletely specified **ReactionLikeEvent** or series of RLEs. A BlackBoxEvent for a reaction is for one that is known to happen but whose molecular details are incompletely known, e.g., a partially purified protein catalyzes a reaction so no EWAS can be identified, or degradation of a protein yields unspecified polypeptide products. BBEs may also be used to represent a multistep process (such as the transcription and translation of a gene into a protein) when the details don't need to be specified in full. A fully annotated sequence of events for a BBE may be depicted in full elsewhere in Reactome.

CellDevelopmentStep

A **CellDevelopmentStep** is a **ReactionlikeEvent** that contains **Cell** instances as its inputs and outputs. The input attribute represents the cell of origin, the starting point of this development event, and the output attribute represents the destination cell type, the outcome of the event. Additional CellDevelopmentStep attributes include regulators (molecules promoting or inhibiting the step) and required input components (input cell biomarkers required for the action of regulators). **CellDevelopmentStep** is also associated with a relevant Gene Ontology (GO)

biological process term and with a “tissue” term from the UBERON, an ExternalOntology of Anatomy terms.

Depolymerisation

A subclass of **ReactionlikeEvent** that is used to annotate depolymerisation and follows the pattern: Polymer -> Polymer + Unit (reverse situation of Polymerisation).

FailedReaction

A **FailedReaction** instance is a step in a disease process that is directly affected by a loss-of-function (LoF) mutation (germline or somatic). This type of disease event has its normal **ReactionLikeEvent** counterpart (the reaction mediated by the un-mutated gene product) specified at its normalReaction attribute and is represented as having *inputs* (an abnormal physicalEntity plus any wild-type entities that are inputs in the normal reaction), but no *outputs*.

FailedReaction instances are labeled with disease term(s) that are used to populate the disease attribute of the associated abnormal **PhysicalEntity (GenomeEncodedEntitiy, Complex or EntitySet)**.

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Polymerisation

A subclass of reactionlikeEvent in which two or more identical molecules or complexes are assembled into a polymer.

Reaction

The transformation of input physical entities into output ones in a single step. Transformations include chemical changes, as in metabolism, the transport of an entity between locations, the association of entities to form a complex, and the dissociation of complexes. These transformations can be catalyzed and regulated.

EvidenceType

EvidenceType is a subclass of ExternalOntology, manually populated with [Gene Ontology evidence code](#) terms. Used only to flag inferred orthologous events created computationally as part of the release process (IEA, inferred by electronic annotation) and not for human manual annotation by curators.

ExternalOntology

An ExternalOntology is one developed and maintained outside of Reactome and used as-is by Reactome to align our annotation with the community vocabularies and logical relationships incorporated into these ontologies. This is a superclass and used for generalizing sharing

attributes among multiple types of external ontologies. This class should not be used for instance creation.

Anatomy

Anatomy encompasses terms representing body parts, organs and tissues from an ExternalOntology, Uberon (<https://obophenotype.github.io/uberon/>). Anatomy terms are used to populate organ, tissue, and tissueLayer attributes of the Cell subclass of PhysicalEntity and tissue attribute of CellDevelopmentStep and CellLineagePath subclasses of Event.

CellType

CellType terms represent different categories of animal cells, characterized by their specific structure, function, and biochemistry, derived from an ExternalOntology, Cell Ontology (<https://obofoundry.org/ontology/cl.html>). CellType terms are used to populate the *cellType* attribute of Cell and EntityWithAccessionedSequence subclasses of PhysicalEntity.

Disease

Disease encompasses terms that describe impairments of normal functions caused by pathogenic genetic mutations or environmental factors, such as microbial pathogens. Terms are derived from EBI Disease Ontology (DO) (<https://disease-ontology.org/>) and are used to populate the disease attribute of abnormal physicalEntities (genomeEncodedEntity, complex, entitySet) and abnormal events (reactionLikeEvents, and pathways) to specify the disease(s) with which these abnormal instances are associated. Disease instances include *identifier* and *name* attributes taken from DO.

PsiMod

PsiMod encompasses terms representing post-translational chemical modifications of proteins derived from an ExternalOntology Protein Modification Ontology (MOD: <https://ontobee.org/ontology/MOD>). The psiMod is an attribute of all the subclasses of TranslationalModification.

SequenceOntology

SequenceOntology is a local copy of portions of the ExternalOntology Sequence Ontology (<http://www.sequenceontology.org/>). It encompasses terms representing the variant features and attributes of biological sequence, used to populate the structuralVariant attribute of the subclasses of FunctionalStatus.

Figure

Figures for Reactome events are created in collaboration with Reactome's graphic illustrator. Curators needing to add a figure should consult with the illustrator and plans entered into to the

illustration calendar. The *url* attribute of the **figure** instance holds the address of the image file in the Reactome CVS website repository, and the *figure* attribute of the data object to be illustrated holds the name of the **figure** instance. Example:

/figures/apoptotic_factor_responses.jpg is this file location for the figure used to illustrate the pathway "[Apoptotic factor-mediated response](#)".

FrontPage

A list of the top-level pathways of the Reactome event hierarchy (autophagy, cell cycle, cell-cell communication, ...) listed on the [Reactome pathway browser page](#). The single instance of this class is maintained by the Editor-in-Chief and Managing Editor.

GO_BiologicalProcess

A local copy of the [Gene Ontology Biological Process ontology](#). Instances of this class provide *goBiologicalProcess* attributes for Reactome **Events** and **Regulation** instances.

GO_CellularComponent

A local copy of the [Gene Ontology Cellular Component ontology](#). Instances of this class provide the subcellular location or locations of Reactome **Events** and **PhysicalEntities** .

Compartment

A subset of GO_CellularComponent terms manually curated by Reactome to specify non-overlapping subcellular locations (*compartment* attribute values) of **Events** or **physicalEntities**. If a **physicalEntity** occurs in more than one compartment, different instances of the entity are created for each location, distinguished from one another by their *compartment* attributes.

GO_MolecularFunction

A local copy of the [Gene Ontology Molecular Function ontology](#). Instances of this class provide the *activity* of an instance of **catalystActivity**.

InstanceEdit

Records the date and time when a Reactome instance was *created* or *modified* (and, in the case of events, when they were authored, reviewed, or edited). It identifies the *person* responsible for the creation or modification and a timestamp. InstanceEdit instances are automatically generated when the central database is updated from the curator tool, and should not be manually edited.

PathwayDiagram

An SBML-compliant graphical representation of one or more **pathways** (*representedPathway* attribute values). Every **ReactionlikeEvent** in the included pathways is represented in the diagram, with icons that represent PhysicalEntities and edges that represent causal connections (provides input / output, catalyzes, regulates) among the physicalEntities. These are superimposed on icons that represent **compartments** (subcellular locations).

Person

The name of a person. Used to identify curators, authors, reviewers, and **literatureReference** authors. Any **Person** instance can have an *affiliation* attribute, but at present this information is recorded only for Reactome contributors, i.e., authors, reviewers, and curators. A contributor identifier such as ORCID can be associated with a person instance via the CrossReference attribute allowing to claim their contributions to Reactome in ORCID.

PhysicalEntity [superclass]

Used to maintain logical integrity of data model, not used for manual annotation. **PhysicalEntity** contains the classes **Cell**, **Complex**, **Drug**, **EntitySet**, **GenomeEncodedEntity**, **OtherEntity**, **Polymer**, and **SimpleEntity**. A PhysicalEntity is a physical substance that can interact with other substances. PhysicalEntities include all kinds of small molecules, proteins, nucleic acids, chemical compounds, complexes, larger macromolecular assemblies, atoms (including ionized atoms), electrons, and photons.

Cell

A subclass of **PhysicalEntity**, represents a type of cell in a particular state of development/differentiation. A Cell instance has *cellType*, *tissueLayer*, *tissue*, and *organ* as single-valued attributes which are populated using terms from the Cell Ontology. Anatomy terms from the UBERON ExternalOntology are used to populate *tissueLayer*, *tissue*, and *organ* attributes. Cell instances also have multi-valued *ProteinMarker* and *RNAMarker* attributes, which are specific to the cell type and/or the cell state or are differentially upregulated in the Cell. The markers (protein or RNA) are manually curated and associated with literature references for evidence.

Complex

A **PhysicalEntity** that represents a larger functional unit formed by the covalent or noncovalent association of two or more **PhysicalEntity components** (which can themselves be **Complexes** or **Sets**). Usually, complex components are proteins, but they can also be RNA or DNA molecules, or simpleEntity chemicals, e.g. metal ions, nucleotides, lipids that function as enzyme cofactors. Complexes include homomultimers, e.g., [ESR1 homodimer \(nucleoplasm\)](#), heteromultimers, e.g., [FANCD2:FANCI \[nucleoplasm\]](#), and complexes composed of other complexes, e.g., [PPARG:RXRA:Corepressor Complex \[nucleoplasm\]](#).

Drug

A superclass which is not used to instantiate specific instances, the **Drug** superclass contains subclasses **ChemicalDrug**, **ProteinDrug**, and **RNADrug**. A drug may be defined as any substance that is administered as a medicine to alter metabolic processes in the body, most often processes involved in diseases or abnormal states.

Reactome does not classify as drugs those substances, such as insulin or epinephrine, that are produced naturally by the human body, though these substances may be administered as medicines and may be considered drugs in other databases.

Artificial derivatives of naturally produced human substances, such as glargine (a derivative of insulin), are considered drugs, as are natural non-human substances such as quinine and caffeine.

ChemicalDrug

A subclass of the **Drug** class. A ChemicalDrug is a synthetic substance or non-human natural substance that is not a protein, RNA, or DNA molecule and is administered to the body to modify a metabolic reaction or reactions, usually to treat a disease or abnormal state.

Mandatory attributes of ChemicalDrug include one or more *diseases* treated by a drug, and *referenceEntity*, which is a reference to a corresponding entity in a database such as Guide to Pharmacology.

ProteinDrug

A **ProteinDrug** is a substance that contains an active component that is a protein, whether modified or unmodified, and is administered to the body to modify a metabolic reaction or reactions, usually to treat a disease or abnormal state. A subclass of the **Drug** class. Mandatory attributes of ProteinDrug include *disease*, which is a reference to the disease treated by a drug, and *referenceEntity*, which is a reference to a corresponding entity in a database such as Guide to Pharmacology. Examples of **ProteinDrugs** are semaglutide, a chemically modified form of GLP1, and etanercept, a fusion between the TNFalpha receptor and the Fc portion of IgG1. Naturally occurring human proteins such as insulin are considered instances of the class EntityWithAccessionedSequence rather than instances of the class ProteinDrug. Artificially

modified versions of human proteins, such as glargine or lispro insulin, are considered **ProteinDrugs**.

RNADrug

A subclass of the **Drug** class. Mandatory attributes of RNADrug include *disease*, which is a reference to the disease treated by a drug, and *referenceEntity*, which is a reference to a corresponding entity in a database such as Guide to Pharmacology. A RNADrug is a substance that contains an active component that is a ribonucleic acid, whether modified or unmodified, and is administered to the body to modify a metabolic reaction or reactions, usually to treat a disease or abnormal state. **EntityWithAccessionedSequence** is the non-drug class that corresponds to **RNADrug**.

Examples of RNADrugs are inclisiran and asvasiran, which are non-natural small interfering RNAs (siRNAs). Naturally occurring human RNAs are considered instances of the class **EntityWithAccessionedSequence** rather than instances of the class RNADrug.

EntitySet [superclass]

Used to maintain logical integrity of data model, not used for manual annotation. Two or more **PhysicalEntities** grouped because of a shared molecular feature or function. The superclass for **CandidateSet** and **DefinedSet**. While sets are, by default, homogeneous (members having the same subclass of PhysicalEntity), they are not required to be. For example, the defined set [platelet alpha granule contents](#) contains, as members, EntitiesWithAccessionedSequences, Complexes and Sets.

CandidateSet

A collection of physical entities that are functionally indistinguishable for the purpose of Reactome annotation, some of which are well-characterized (the “members” of the set) and some of which are incompletely characterized (the “candidates” of the set), as judged by the curator who assembles the set and the outside expert reviewers who evaluate it.

Members of a set are related by an "OR" function. That is, either one member OR another member can participate in a reaction.

Sets may be ordered or unordered as specified in the *isOrdered* attribute. A specific member of an ordered set has a correspondence with a specific member of another ordered set, as specified by their positions within the sets. For example, consider an ordered set containing substrate1 and substrate2 that reacts to yield an ordered set containing product1 and product2. In this case, substrate1 will yield product1 and substrate2 will yield product2. In the case of unordered sets, any member in an input set can correspond to any member in an output set. Sets in Reactome are considered ordered by default.

Example:

RIP2 ubiquitin ligases

One (*member*) has been shown to participate as a ubiquitin ligase (ITCH); the other (*candidates*) are thought to do so. <https://reactome.org/content/detail/R-HSA-1248659>

DefinedSet

A collection of well-characterized physical entities that are functionally indistinguishable for the purpose of Reactome annotation, e.g., a collection of isoforms of a protein that all mediate the identical metabolic reaction. A set is formally a list of instances linked by logical ORs.

Sets may be ordered or unordered as specified in the *isOrdered* attribute. A specific member of an ordered set has a correspondence with a specific member of another ordered set, as specified by their positions within the sets. For example, consider an ordered set containing substrate1 and substrate2 that reacts to yield an ordered set containing product1 and product2. In this case, substrate1 will yield only product1 and substrate2 will yield only product2. In the case of unordered sets, any member in an input set can correspond to any member in an output set. Sets in Reactome are considered ordered by default.

GenomeEncodedEntity

Any informational macromolecule (DNA, RNA, protein) or entity derived from one by post-synthetic modifications, for example, covalently modified forms of proteins.

GenomeEncodedEntity is a subclass of **PhysicalEntity** and has one subclass: **EntityWithAccessionedSequence**. Unlike an **EntityWithAccessionedSequence**, a **GenomeEncodedEntity** is not required to have a reference entity, though a reference to an entity in a database can be specified in the *crossReference* attribute.

EntityWithAccessionedSequence

The subclass of **GenomeEncodedEntities** that can be associated through the *referenceEntity* attribute with reference molecules in UniProt (proteins) or ENSEMBL (DNA, RNA) databases. A protein that has been partially purified and whose enzymatic properties are known but whose amino acid sequence is not, is a **GenomeEncodedEntity** but not an **EntityWithAccessionedSequence**.

OtherEntity

PhysicalEntities that we are unable or unwilling to describe in chemical detail and which, therefore, cannot be put in any other class. **OtherEntity** can be used to represent complex structures in the cell that take part in a reaction but which we can't or don't want to define molecularly.

Example 1: Cell membrane. In a case in which protein X associates with the membrane, but the actual membrane component(s) with which protein X interacts are unknown, the membrane can be represented as an "OtherEntity".

Example 2: kinesin-1, a microtubule motor protein, is involved in many kinds of movement in the cell, by 'walking' along microtubules, while dragging things like mitochondria, secretory vesicles,

parts of the golgi, etc. Kinesin-1 binds to these complicated structures that we would not want to describe molecularly and which we can designate as "otherEntities".

Example 3: Holliday structure \[nucleoplasm] <https://reactome.org/content/detail/R-ALL-75220#Homo%20sapiens>

Polymer

Molecules that consist of indeterminate numbers of repeated units, and complexes that contain repeated units whose stoichiometry is variable or unknown. The repeated unit(s) (identified in the *repeatedUnit* attribute) can be any **PhysicalEntity**. The presence of more than one *repeatedUnit* value implies that the relative numbers of units in the polymer are unknown. If the units are present in known proportions, a **complex** of the appropriate numbers of units is used as the *repeatedUnit*. The size range of a **polymer** can be specified with *minUnitCount* and *maxUnitCount* values. Examples:

-\'glycogen\' with \'glucose\' as *repeatedUnit*.

-\'fibrin multimer\' with \'fibrin "monomer"\' (itself a Complex) as *repeatedUnit*.

-A microtubule consisting of equal amounts of alpha and beta tubulin would be constructed as a **polymer** containing a Complex of alpha and beta tubulins in the *repeatedUnit* attribute.

-Completely hypothetical Example: A complex consisting of 1 "part" of A and "4" "parts" of B (i.e. 1:4 ratio) would be represented as a **polymer** with a **complex** of one A and 4 B as its *repeatedUnit*.

-Another hypothetical Example: a complex where the ratio of individual building blocks A and B is unknown or variable is represented as a **polymer** containing A and B directly in the *repeatedUnit* attribute.

SimpleEntity

A defined chemical species not encoded directly or indirectly in the genome, typically a small molecule such as ATP or ethanol. The detailed structure of a **simpleEntity** is specified by linking it to the information provided for the molecule in the ChEBI external database via the *referenceEntity* slot. Separate **simpleEntity** instances are needed for each subcellular location (*compartment*) in which a molecule is found, e.g., ATP [cytosol] and ATP [nucleoplasm]. SimpleEntities such as ATP that occur in many species are not assigned a species.

Publication [superclass]

Used to maintain logical integrity of data model, not used for manual annotation. The Publication superclass encompasses any document, paper or electronic, that makes information available to the public. The subclasses of Publication are Book (chapters of books or entire books), LiteratureReference (journal articles), and URL (uniform resource locators that allow navigation of the internet to an electronic document).

Book

A book may be used in the `literatureReference` attribute of the relevant data class instances (ie pathway, reaction, entity). *Author*, *title*, and *year* of publication are required attributes. Chapters of books can also be cited within a book by using the *chapterTitle* attribute of the Book class.

LiteratureReference

A journal article, typically abstracted in PubMed, cited in a **summation** or linked to an **entity** or **event** instance. The attribute *pubMedIdentifier* contains the PubMed identifier (PMID) obtained from PubMed (<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) and is mandatory. Further information about the literature reference is also obtained from PubMed and is found in the attributes *author*, *year*, *title*, *journal*, *volume*, and *pages*.

URL

A website cited as a literature reference in data class instances such as **summation**, **entity**, or an **event** instance. The URL for the website is listed in the `uniformResourceLocator` attribute. The URL should contain all information, including transfer protocols such as “`http://`”, “`https://`”, or “`ftp://`”, required to navigate to the resource.

psiMod

A local copy of the [PSI-MOD ontology](#), used to create descriptions of *modifiedResidues* of proteins.

ReferenceDatabase

This class describes the source (external database) of an identifier in the **Databaselfentifier** (and **SequenceDatabaselfentifier**) instance, e.g., *Databaselfentifier* [COMPOUND:C00113](#) links the Reactome instance to the record maintained by the [KEGG “compound” database](#).

ReferenceEntity [superclass]

Used to maintain logical integrity of data model, not used for manual annotation.

ReferenceEntity captures the invariant features of a molecule such as its names, molecular structure and links to external community reference databases like UniProt, ENSEMBL or ChEBI, and is created by importing content from those databases. A ReferenceEntity is an attribute of the PhysicalEntity subclasses Drug, EWAS and SimpleEntity, and enables grouping of Reactome PhysicalEntities like ‘Glc ([alpha-D-glucose](#)), [extracellular region](#)’ and ‘Glc ([alpha-D-glucose](#)), [cytosol](#)’ (all linked to the record of alpha-D-glucose maintained by [ChEBI database](#), indicating their identical chemical nature. ReferenceEntities are not used in Reactions directly; they are attached to the PhysicalEntities involved. ReferenceEntities derived from Uniprot and ChEBI usually don’t need to be created by curators; they are imported automatically. In the case of as yet unexisting ChEBI entries, contact the managing Editor.

ReferenceGroup

ReferenceGroup is a chemical group instance (children of [CHEBI:24433](#)) from the ChEBI database, used to populate the *modification* attribute of classes such as **GroupModifiedResidue**. The ReferenceGroup record consists of an *identifier* and a *referenceDatabase*.

ReferenceMolecule

ReferenceMolecule is used to cross-reference individual chemical molecules to the ChEBI database, and is used to populate the *referenceEntity* attribute of **SimpleEntity**. Consists of an *identifier* and a *referenceDatabase*.

ReferenceSequence [superclass]

Used to maintain logical integrity of data model, not used for manual annotation. Molecules with an accessionedSequence. This class is a subclass of **ReferenceEntity**, and is the superclass of **ReferenceDNASequence**, **ReferenceGeneProduct**, and **ReferenceRNASequence**, so instances of it should not be created manually.

ReferenceDNASequence

Used to populate the *referenceEntity* attribute for EWASs describing DNA molecules (for instance EWAS's of human genes). The **ReferenceDNASequence** record consists of a *referenceDatabase* (generally ENSEMBL), the *identifier*, and a *species*.

ReferenceGeneProduct

Used to populate the *referenceEntity* attribute for EWASs describing proteins. The **ReferenceGeneProduct** record consists of a *referenceDatabase* (generally Uniprot), the *identifier* and a *species*. The canonical form of the protein from UniProt is used as the **ReferenceGeneProduct** unless the literature supports the role of a particular isoform of a protein in the described function. **ReferenceGeneProduct** is also used to populate the *referenceSequence* attribute of **ModifiedResidue**.

ReferenceIsoform

Used to populate the *referenceEntity* attribute for EWASs describing proteins, where the experimental literature supports the role of a specified isoform of a protein in a particular function. The **ReferenceIsoform** record consists of a *referenceDatabase* (generally Uniprot), the *identifier* and a *species*.

ReferenceRNASequence

Used to populate the *referenceEntity* attribute for EWASs describing RNA molecules (for instance EWAS's of mRNAs). The **ReferenceRNASequence** record consists of a *referenceDatabase* (generally ENSEMBL), the *identifier*, and a *species*.

ReferenceTherapeutic

Used to populate the *referenceEntity* attribute for **PhysicalEntities** of the **Drug** class, including **ChemicalDrug**, **ProteinDrug**, and **RNADrug**. The **ReferenceTherapeutic** record consists of a *referenceDatabase* (generally Guide to Pharmacology) and the *identifier*.

Regulation [superclass]

Used to maintain logical integrity of data model, not used for manual annotation. Consists of subclasses **NegativeRegulation** and **PositiveRegulation**, along with their subclasses, **NegativeGeneExpressionRegulation** and **PositiveGeneExpressionRegulation** and **Requirement**, respectively. Instances of Regulation subclasses are added to the *regulatedBy* attribute of **ReactionLikeEvents** to capture the negative or positive effect of a **PhysicalEntity** on the described event.

NegativeRegulation

NegativeRegulation is an optional class used to populate the *regulatedBy* attribute of a **ReactionLikeEvent** that describes an inhibitory effect of a Regulator, a **PhysicalEntity**, on that event. The mechanism of action of a Regulator, if known, can be described through the optional *activity* attribute which is populated by terms from an ExternalOntology GO_MolecularFunction. If the Regulator is a Complex, the specific Complex component(s) that play the regulatory role can be specified as *activeUnit(s)* of the **NegativeRegulation** instance.

NegativeGeneExpressionRegulation

NegativeGeneExpressionRegulation is a subclass of **NegativeRegulation** that describes a direct inhibitory effect of a Regulator on a **BlackBoxEvent** that represents gene expression. The Regulator is a complex of regulatory component(s) such as transcription factors with the target gene or mRNA molecule. The regulatory component(s) are defined as *activeUnit(s)* of the **NegativeGeneExpressionRegulation** instance.

PositiveRegulation

PositiveRegulation is an optional class used to populate the *regulatedBy* attribute of a **ReactionLikeEvent** that describes a stimulatory effect of a Regulator, a **PhysicalEntity**, on that event. The mechanism of action of a Regulator, if known, can be described through the optional *activity* attribute which is populated by terms from an External Ontology GO_MolecularFunction.

If the Regulator is a Complex, the specific Complex component(s) that play the regulatory role can be specified as *activeUnit(s)* of the *PositiveRegulation* instance.

PositiveGeneExpressionRegulation

PositiveGeneExpressionRegulation is a subclass of *PositiveRegulation* that describes a direct stimulatory effect of a Regulator on a *BlackBoxEvent* that represents gene expression, so that the Regulator represents a complex of regulatory component(s) such as transcription factors with the target gene or mRNA molecule. The regulatory component(s) are defined as *activeUnit(s)* of the *PositiveGeneExpressionRegulation* instance.

sequence-related comments that are provided by the reference database. It is filled in automatically. Curators should not alter this.

Requirement

A subclass of **PositiveRegulation** that denotes a regulatory **PhysicalEntity** without which the regulated event cannot occur.

ReviewStatus

An attribute of event. Describes the level of internal/external review that the event has undergone.

One star (1): Restructured after internal review NOT RELEASED.

Two star (2) Restructured after external review NOT RELEASED.

Three star (3) Internally reviewed, awaiting external review RELEASED.

Four star (4) Restructured after external review, then internally re-reviewed RELEASED.

Five star. 5 Externally reviewed RELEASED. A more detailed description can be found in the user guide [here](https://reactome.org/userguide/review-status) (<https://reactome.org/userguide/review-status>).

StableIdentifier

A unique identifier associated with a database object that does not change over time. Stable Identifiers have the format R-XXX-YYYYYY.Z where R stands for Reactome and invariant. XXX is the three letter species code (see appendix XX for species codes). If the instance applies to all species (e.g. a simple entity such as ATP), the code is "ALL". If the instance applies to none or multiple but not all species, the code is "NUL". YYYYYY is the database identifier of the instance. If the instance is modified between database releases, the version number (Z) in the *IdentifierVersion* attribute is incremented.

StableIdentifierHistory

This class is used for tracking, and each instance represents a stable identifier with a particular minor version that was present at one time in the history (either still existing

currently on at one time in the past and no longer). The class is used with "StableIdentifierReleaseStatus" to indicate which release numbers had this minor version and if/when it was changed (i.e. replaced, removed, incremented, etc.)

StableIdentifierReleaseStatus

Instances of this class are used as values for StableIdentifierHistory's status attribute to indicate the status (i.e. "EXISTS", "INCREMENTED", "REPLACED", "REMOVED", etc.) for a given release version.

Summation

A free text description of an **Event** or **physicalEntity**. Citations that provide useful background information, but that are not sources of primary data for the event or entity, can be linked to summations. (**LiteratureReferences** providing experimental data for the details of an event should be linked directly to the event). Attributes: *Text*- description of the event
LiteratureReference- paper(s) that support the text description, but not the primary evidence for the event. See Summation example for [FAM83B, \(FAM83A, FAM83D\) bind EGFR](#).

Taxon

A controlled vocabulary populated manually by Reactome from the [NCBI Taxonomy Database](#), to provide terms to identify the *species* of events and genome-encoded physical entities. Taxonomy terms of higher rank than species, and their relationships, are maintained in Reactome to facilitate computational reasoning and data mining. Each taxon instance includes the taxon's *name* as assigned by NCBI, its NCBI identifier (in the form of a Reactome *crossReference*), and its NCBI-assigned *supertaxon*. This class is maintained by the Editor-in-Chief and Managing Editor. Taxon terms of species rank are used for annotation of gene products and other relevant PhysicalEntities, and events.

Species

Gene products and events have **species**-level NCBI-derived **taxon** terms as attributes. This class is maintained by the Editor-in-Chief and Managing Editor.

_Release

A class which indicates a Reactome version number and its date of release. Also, an attribute of the class `_updateTracker` that indicates the release number and date of a specified Reactome database release.

_UpdateTracker

Describes the changes that were made to an instance at a specified Reactome release relative to the previous release. Specifies the DBID and name of the instance that has changed (an event or PhysicalEntity), the release number and date of that release that the change occurred, and a list of changes made to the entity (see appendix R9 for a list of changes that are tracked)

Reactome Attributes

_displayName

This attribute contains the name of the instance that will be displayed on the Reactome website. It is automatically filled in by the curator tool each time a new instance is created, using attribute values supplied for the instance by the curator. For example, the `_displayName` of an event consists of the event's manually generated *name* and its manually selected *species*.

accession

Holds the numerical portions of identifiers assigned to GO terms in the local copies of the GO ontologies. Should not be manually edited.

accessUrl

Template that is used to form the URL that will be used to link to a particular record in an external database. Generally, this should not need to be touched. Contact developers if you think any changes are necessary.

activity

contains the GO Molecular Function ontology. An Activity term is used to cross-reference a Reactome CatalystActivity. Curators should never create instances of class Activity directly. If curators want to use a GO term that is not in Reactome (yet) contact Managing Editor.

address

This is an attribute for the affiliation class. Enter the address of the research institute (etc).

affiliation

An Affiliation is the name and address of an institution, e.g., Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory 1 Bungtown Road, Cold Spring Harbor NY USA.

author

This attribute must be filled in for instances of LiteratureReference, (where it refers to name of the author of a particular reference), for InstanceEdit (where it refers to the curator that has generated the instanceEdit), and for events.

comment

This attribute is used for SequenceDatabaseIdentifier class instances and contains any cation in the cell. Is an attribute of PhysicalEntities and Events. Note that complexes with components that span multiple cellular locations should specify one primary location as the compartment and the location of the other components will be automatically filled into the “includedLocation” attribute during the database release process. For example, a transmembrane complex with components in the extracellular space, plasma membrane, and cytosol would have plasma membrane specified as the compartment.

componentOf

An attribute of GO_CellularComponent that is specified by the Gene Ontology and describes the GO Cellular Component instances that are parent terms. Imported from GO.

coordinate

Refers to the amino acid residue location at which a modification occurs within a protein.

created

Automatically filled in with the name of the curator/developer creating the instance and date/time stamp that the instance was created.

crossReference

This attribute holds references to the equivalent instance in other databases. For example, the small molecule 4MAA has the KEGG COMPOUND identifier COMPOUND:C01036 in its *crossReference* attribute.

databaseIdentifier

Holds database identifiers from external databases like UniProt and ChEBI (but not GO – see *Accession* attribute). Has attributes for the *referenceDatabase* and the *identifier* in that database.

dateTime (on InstanceEdit)

A timestamp generated automatically when the central database is updated from a curator tool project. Do not edit it manually.

DB_ID

These are the unique stable identifiers applied to each instance in the Reactome database. They are generated automatically when newly created instances are first submitted to the database. They should never be modified or manually created by a curator.

definition

This attribute is used in Event, PhysicalEntity, Activity, Evidencetype and GO_BiologicalProcess instances. The definition of a Reactome Activity is the official Gene Ontology definition for the equivalent GO Molecular Function term. The GO_BiologicalProcess definition is the official Gene Ontology definition for the corresponding Biological process term. The Evidencetype definition is taken from the GO evidence code definitions.

description

This is found in the class 'SequenceDBI'. This is for the 'Description DE' line from SwissProt.

editor

Choose or create a Person instance/s for the editor/s. Used to determine the information for the frontpage.

containedIn

endCoordinate

The amino acid residue location at which an EntityWithAccessionedSequencepart ends.

figure

Certain events in Reactome are associated with a descriptive illustration. See, for example, [Autophagy](#). When such an illustration exists, the figure attribute of the event is populated with a figure instance containing the location of the image file on the server in its URL attribute. The URL has the format: figures/.../[FigureFileName].svg

firstname

The first name of a person. Optional attribute – can be left blank. Reactome uses only the first letter of the first name (entered separately in the *initial* attribute) to create names of people for display on the web site.

formula

The chemical formula of a **SimpleEntity**. For example, ATP = C₁₀H₁₆N₅O₁₃P₃.

functionalStatusType

Describes the functional consequence of this genetic change (gain-of-function, loss-of-function, decreased_transcript_level etc). With sequenceVariant, functionalStatusType makes up **FunctionalStatus**, which is used to fill the *functionalStatus* attribute of EntityFunctionalStatus

geneIdentifier

This attribute is for storing information about what is the gene that this transcript/protein originates from. This is really just a shortcut. If the current instance is a gene identifier then this should be left empty. Accepts multiple values in order to be able to point to the SAME gene in different databases, e.g. EMBL, HUGO, Ensembl.

geneName

GN lines from sequence record.

hasComponent

Holds instances of **PhysicalEntity** that are components of a **Complex**.

hasEvent

Holds instances of **Event** that are grouped into a **Pathway**. They should be entered in the order as they appear in the **Pathway**. On **BlackBoxEvent** this attribute holds **Event** instances to describe known steps within the **BlackBoxEvent**, e.g. the reactions of the fatty acid beta oxidation cycle.

hasMember

Takes individual reactions for an instance of **ReactionlikeEvent** that represents a group of reactions via the use of an **EntitySet**. Such individual reactions do not need to be spelled out, unless they have a distinct feature like a literature reference or specific regulation.

identifier

This attribute holds the actual database identifier number for a given **Databaselfentifier** instance.

inferredFrom

Points to the event or entity in another species that this event/entity has been inferred from. If the inference is based on computation only, this is indicated under evidenceType (= IEA).

initial

This attribute holds the initials of a person represented in a **Person** instance.

input

The input **PhysicalEntities** of a given **ReactionLikeEvent** are each entered individually.

instanceOf

Only used for GO classes and is populated/updated automatically.

InteractionEvent

This class is designed to model simple interactions between any physical entities. It is introduced to be used for data imported from other data sources including protein-protein interactions or other types of interactions.

journal (on LiteratureReference)

The name of the scientific journal in which the reference was published (or the title of a book). For references retrieved from PubMed with the curator and author tools, this slot is filled automatically.

keyword

Contains keywords associated with the sequence. This is pulled in (if available) automatically from the external database.

literatureReference (on summation)

Paper/s that support the text description, but not the primary evidence for the event. This shows up as hyperlinked lines on a web browser.

modification

For a given modifiedResidue instance, enter the simpleEntity that represents the specific modification of the residue within the modified protein. For example, for the "ModifiedResidue" instance: "Orthophosphate on Serine [nucleus] 428 of SPTREMBL:O46469", the modification would be "Orthophosphate".

modified

Filled in automatically when a database instance is modified.

name

A short textual description of the event/entity/etc. For some classes it is a defining attribute, so it should be chosen carefully to be unique.

Ontology

Internal definition and not instantiable for holding data. It is the content of the protégé file defining the database.

orthologousEvent

Points to equivalent events in other species. In contrast to 'inferredFrom' this attribute is attached to the events in both species - it only indicates equivalence, not inference.

output

The output **PhysicalEntities** of a given event are each entered individually.

pages

The inclusive page numbers of a **LiteratureReference**. For references retrieved from PubMed with the curator and author tools, this attribute is filled automatically.

precedingEvent

Points to the preceding event(s), which is usually events whose output is used as input for the present event. The preceding event can also point to a pathway, but make sure the connection is always given on the reaction level as well (this is important when it comes to visualization).

proteinIdentifier

This attribute is for storing information about what the protein this transcript/gene produces. This is really just a shortcut. If the current instance is a protein identifier then this should be left empty. Accepts multiple values in order to be able to point to the same proteins in different databases, e.g. EMBL, HUGO, Ensembl, RefSeq.

pubMedIdentifier (on literatureReference)

The pubmed identifier (number only). This information must be manually supplied by the curator.

reactionType

A *controlledVocabulary* that provides attributes to classify *reactionLikeEvents*. Currently in use only to distinguish reactions involving drugs by modes of action.

drugActionType

Reactions that have *drugs* and *sets or complexes containing drugs* as inputs and output have a *drugAction* attribute taken from the IUPHAR / Guide to Pharmacology [glossary](#) to classify the effect of the drug on the reaction (agonist, channel blocker, etc.).*

requiredInputComponent

Takes an input component that is essential for this event to happen, e.g. a defined domain of a protein. Use *Domain*, with the appropriate coordinates filled in.

Note: To be used only for 'non-trivial statements'. For example, repeating an entity here that is identical to a *PhysicalEntity* given for input is not helpful.

relatedSpecies (on event)

This attribute is used in events involving more than one species (e.g event involving host-pathogen or symbiotic interactions) to denote the "bystander" species in the event. For example, in the event such as flagellin of *Escherichia coli* binds to human TLR5, the process is occurring on the human cell membrane and involves protein from the bystander bacterial species. Thus, human would be entered in the *species* attribute and *E.coli* would be entered as *relatedSpecies*. For additional information and use cases, see this [document](#).

residue

This is to hold the residue (like serine or tyrosine) which is modified. The value is an instance of class ReferenceGroup or ReferenceMolecule, i.e. an instance representing serine.

resourceIdentifier

This attribute is used to add identifiers registered in the identifiers.org web site for ReferenceDatabase instances. It is added for QA purposes and should not affect curation work. The attribute is string, single-valued, and optional.

reverseReaction

Choose a Reaction that is the reverse of the current Reaction.

reviewer (on Event)

The name of the person who reviewed the event. These attribute values are the source of the reviewers given for high-level events listed on the Reactome table of contents.

secondaryIdentifier

Generated automatically.

sequenceOntology

SequenceOntology encompasses terms representing the variant features and attributes of biological sequence derived from an ExternalOntology Sequence Ontology (<http://www.sequenceontology.org/>). SequenceOntology terms are used to populate the *structuralVariant* attribute of **FunctionalStatus**.

species

This attribute holds the name of the species in which the described physicalEntity or Event is occurring. The *species* attribute on event identifies the environment where the reaction is happening. This should almost always be human for human Reactome curation. The exceptions are when we have annotated pathways in other species for inference (e.g Mus) or when we are specifically annotating another species pathways as part of another project (e.g Gallus and Mycobacterium tuberculosis). In disease or immune system processes, the host would be listed as the "species".

When annotating a process involving host-pathogen interactions, the *relatedSpecies* attribute should be used to list the pathogen (bystander) species. See the *relatedSpecies* attribute definition and use cases for a more detailed description. **Note:** When creating a chimeric reaction to be used for inference (i.e one that involves entities from multiple species and (usually) observed in vitro) ALL species should be listed in the species attribute.

startCoordinate

The amino acid residue location at which an EntityWithAccessionedSequence starts.

structuralVariant

Field takes terms from [SequenceOntology](#) and describes the nature of the underlying genetic change that gives rise to the variant. With FunctionalStatusType, structuralVariant makes up FunctionalStatus, which is used to fill the *functionalStatus* attribute of EntityFunctionalStatus.

summation

A succinct free-text description of the instance, typically an event, with which it is associated.

superTaxon

This refers to the "parent" for a given taxon within the NCBI taxonomy hierarchy. For example the SuperTaxon for both Rattus and Mus is Murina and the SuperTaxon for Murina is Muridae.

surname

The family name of a **person**.

text

Holds the text of the summation.

templateEvent

Allows making a reference to a general process that underlies a **BlackBoxEvent**, e.g. 'Gene Expression' as template for the synthesis of a specific protein. This attribute has never been used - should it be removed from the data model?

title

The title of a **LiteratureReference**. For references retrieved from PubMed with the curator and author tools, this attribute is filled automatically.

transcriptIdentifier

This attribute is for storing information about what is the transcript that this protein originates from or that this gene produces. This is really just a shortcut. If the current instance is a transcript identifier then this should be left empty. Accepts multiple values in order to be able to point to the same gene and proteins in different databases, e.g. EMBL, Ensembl, RefSeq.

url

Holds URL for site which gives "summary information" about the database including a description of what information the db contains. This attribute should not need to be modified manually.

volume

The volume number of the *journal* in a **LiteratureReference**. For references retrieved from PubMed with the curator and author tools, this attribute is filled automatically.

year

The year a **LiteratureReference** was published. For references retrieved from PubMed with the curator and author tools, this slot is filled automatically.

Graph database specific classes

DBInfo

Generic information about the current version of the graph database used.

GO_Term

Gene Ontology term that is used by Reactome events as cross references. Can be GO_BiologicalProcess, GO_CellularComponent or GO_MolecularFunction.

Interaction

Parent label for all kind of molecular interactions brought into Reactome automatically from other databases, based on referenced evidence in a reviewed publication.

TopLevelPathway

A specific kind of Pathway which covers a broad topic of cellular biology. The top-level pathways represent the highest level of the hierarchical organisation of events in Reactome, as displayed in [Pathway Browser](#).

UndirectedInteraction

A kind of molecular interaction for which no information is available about the directionality of the interaction that forms a bond between two molecules.

name	short name	location	Notes
(1,4-alpha-glycosyl)(n-2)		cytosol	
(1,4-alpha-glycosyl)n		cytosol	
(24R, 25R) 3alpha,7alpha,12alpha,24-tetrahydro-		peroxisomal matrix	
(24R, 25R) 3alpha,7alpha,24-trihydroxy-5beta-Ct		peroxisomal matrix	
(2R) Pristanoyl-CoA		peroxisomal matrix	
(2S) Pristanoyl-CoA		peroxisomal matrix	
(Glc)1 (GlcNAc)2 (Man)7bc		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
(Glc)1 (GlcNAc)2 (Man)8b		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
(Glc)1 (GlcNAc)2 (Man)8c		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
(Glc)1 (GlcNAc)2 (Man)9		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
(Glc)1 (GlcNAc)2 (Man)9		endoplasmic reticulum quality control compartmer	
(Glc)1 (GlcNAc)2 (Man)9		ER to Golgi transport vesicle membrane	
(Glc)1 (GlcNAc)2 (Man)9		Golgi membrane	
(Glc)1 (GlcNAc)2 (Man)9 (PP-Dol)1		integral to luminal side of endoplasmic reticulum	
(Glc)2 (GlcNAc)2 (Man)9 (Asn)1		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
(Glc)2 (GlcNAc)2 (Man)9 (PP-Dol)1		integral to luminal side of endoplasmic reticulum	
(Glc)3 (GlcNAc)2 (Man)9 (Asn)1		Golgi lumen	
(Glc)3 (GlcNAc)2 (Man)9 (Asn)1		integral to luminal side of endoplasmic reticulum	
(Glc)3 (GlcNAc)2 (Man)9 (PP-Dol)1		integral to luminal side of endoplasmic reticulum	
(GlcNAc)2 (Man)2 (PP-Dol)1		integral to cytosolic side of endoplasmic reticulum	
(GlcNAc)2 (Man)3 (PP-Dol)1		integral to cytosolic side of endoplasmic reticulum	
(GlcNAc)2 (Man)5 (Asn)1		Golgi lumen	
(GlcNAc)2 (Man)5 (PP-Dol)1		integral to cytosolic side of endoplasmic reticulum	
(GlcNAc)2 (Man)5 (PP-Dol)1		integral to luminal side of endoplasmic reticulum	
(GlcNAc)2 (Man)6 (PP-Dol)1		integral to luminal side of endoplasmic reticulum	
(GlcNAc)2 (Man)7 (PP-Dol)1		integral to luminal side of endoplasmic reticulum	
(GlcNAc)2 (Man)7aa		cytosol	
(GlcNAc)2 (Man)7aa		endoplasmic reticulum quality control compartmer	
(GlcNAc)2 (Man)7bc		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
(GlcNAc)2 (Man)7bc		Golgi lumen	
(GlcNAc)2 (Man)8 (Asn)1		Golgi lumen	
(GlcNAc)2 (Man)8 (PP-Dol)1		integral to luminal side of endoplasmic reticulum	
(GlcNAc)2 (Man)8a		cytosol	
(GlcNAc)2 (Man)8a		endoplasmic reticulum quality control compartmer	
(GlcNAc)2 (Man)8a		Golgi lumen	
(GlcNAc)2 (Man)8b		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
(GlcNAc)2 (Man)8b		endoplasmic reticulum quality control compartmer	
(GlcNAc)2 (Man)8b		Golgi lumen	
(GlcNAc)2 (Man)8c		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
(GlcNAc)2 (Man)8c		endoplasmic reticulum quality control compartmer	
(GlcNAc)2 (Man)8c		Golgi lumen	
(GlcNAc)2 (Man)9		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
(GlcNAc)2 (Man)9		endoplasmic reticulum quality control compartmer	
(GlcNAc)2 (Man)9		Golgi lumen	
(GlcNAc)2 (Man)9 (PP-Dol)1		integral to luminal side of endoplasmic reticulum	
(GlcNAc)3 (Man)3 (Asn)1		Golgi lumen	
(GlcNAc)3 (Man)5 (Asn)1		Golgi lumen	
(GlcNAc)4 (Man)3 (Asn)1		Golgi lumen	
(R)-2-hydroxyglutarate	2HG	cytosol	
(R)-2-hydroxyglutarate	2HG	mitochondrial matrix	
(R)-3-aminoisobutyric acid	3AIB	cytosol	
(R)-3-aminoisobutyric acid	3AIB	mitochondrial matrix	
(S)-1-Pyrroline-5-carboxylate		mitochondrial matrix	
(S)-2-hydroxyglutarate	2HG	mitochondrial matrix	
(S)-3-Hydroxybutanoyl-CoA	3HB-CoA	mitochondrial matrix	
(S)-3-Hydroxydodecanoyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
(S)-3-Hydroxyhexadecanoyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
(S)-3-Hydroxytetradecanoyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
(S)-dihydroorotate		cytosol	
(S)-Hydroxydecanoyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
(S)-Hydroxyhexanoyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
(S)-Hydroxyoctanoyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
(S)-Lactate	LACT	cytosol	Looked at LA but linoleic acid and lauric acid can also be LA
(S)-Lactate	LACT	extracellular region	Looked at LA but linoleic acid and lauric acid can also be LA
(S)-Malate	MAL	cytosol	
(S)-Malate	MAL	mitochondrial matrix	
[4Fe-4S](1+)		cytosol	
[4Fe-4S](2+)		cytosol	

name	short name	location	Notes
[4Fe-4S](2+)		cytosol	
1,24,25-trihydroxyvitamin D3	vitD3(OH)3	mitochondrial matrix	
1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D3	vitD3(OH)2	mitochondrial matrix	
1,2-diacylglycerol	DAG	cytosol	
1,2-diacyl-glycerol 3-phosphate	PA	cytosol	
1,2-Dihydroxy-3-oxo-methylthiopentene (1-)		cytosol	
1,3-Bisphospho-D-glycerate		cytosol	
1,3-diaminopropane	Dap	cytosol	
10-formyltetrahydrofolate	10-ftph	cytosol	
10-formyltetrahydrofolate polyglutamate		cytosol	
11,12-EET	11,12EET	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
11,14,17-eicosatrienoic acid	ETE	extracellular region	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Polysaturated_fatty_acid
11-deoxycorticosterone	DOC	cytosol	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/chebi/searchId.do?chebiId=CHEBI:16973
11-deoxycorticosterone	DOC	mitochondrial matrix	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/chebi/searchId.do?chebiId=CHEBI:16973
11-deoxycortisol		cytosol	
11-deoxycortisol		mitochondrial matrix	
12-hydroxy-5,8,11,14-eicosatetraenoic acid	20-HETE	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	http://www.chemspider.com/Chemical-Structure.4446281.html
13(5)-hydroxyoctadecadienoic acid	13-HODE	nucleoplasm	
14,15-EET	14,15EET	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
17alpha-hydroxyprogrenolone		cytosol	
17alpha-hydroxyprogesterone		cytosol	
18-hydroxyarachidonate		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
18-hydroxycorticosterone		mitochondrial matrix	
19-hydroxyarachidonic acid		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
19-hydroxyprostaglandin H2	19-OH PGH2	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
1-acyl-glycerol 3-phosphate		cytosol	
1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene	DNCB	cytosol	http://www.inchem.org/documents/icsc/icsc/eics0416.htm
1D-myo-Inositol 1,3,4,5,6-pentakisphosphate	I(1,3,4,5,6)P5	cytosol	
1D-myo-Inositol 1,3,4,5-tetrakisphosphate	I(1,3,4,5)P4	cytosol	
1D-myo-Inositol 1,3,4,6-tetrakisphosphate	I(1,3,4,6)P4	cytosol	
1D-myo-Inositol 1,3,4-trisphosphate	I(1,3,4)P3	cytosol	
1D-myo-Inositol 1,4,5-trisphosphate	I(1,4,5)P3	cytosol	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/chebi/searchId.do?chebiId=CHEBI:16595
1D-myo-Inositol 1,4,5-trisphosphate	I(1,4,5)P3	platelet dense tubular network membrane	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/chebi/searchId.do?chebiId=CHEBI:16595
1D-myo-Inositol 3,4,5,6-tetrakisphosphate	I(3,4,5,6)P4	cytosol	
1-hexadecylglycerol-3-phosphate	HXDG3P	cytosol	
1L-myo-Inositol-1-phosphate	I1P	cytosol	
1-methyl-4-phenyl-pyridinium	MPP	cytosol	
1-methyl-4-phenyl-pyridinium	MPP	extracellular region	
1-Palmitoyl dihydroxyacetone phosphate		peroxisomal matrix	
2,3-Dioxo-methiopentane-1P (2-)		cytosol	
2,4-dinitrophenyl-S-glutathione	DNP-S-GSH	cytosol	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/chebi/searchId.do?chebiId=CHEBI:8927
20alpha,22beta dihydroxyCHOLEsterol	DHCHOL	mitochondrial inner membrane	
20-OH-leukotriene B4	20HLTB4	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/chebi/searchId.do?chebiId=CHEBI:15646
22beta-hydroxyCHOLEsterol	22HCHOL	mitochondrial inner membrane	
24-hydroxyCHOLEsterol	24HCHOL	endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
24-hydroxyCHOLEsterol	24HCHOL	extracellular region	
25(R) DHCA-CoA		cytosol	
25(R) DHCA-CoA		peroxisomal matrix	
25(R) TetraHCA-CoA		cytosol	
25(R) TetraHCA-CoA		peroxisomal matrix	
25(R) THCA-CoA		cytosol	
25(R) THCA-CoA		peroxisomal matrix	
25(S) 3alpha,7alpha,12alpha-trihydroxy-5beta-Chol		peroxisomal matrix	
25(S) 3alpha,7alpha-dihydroxy-5beta-CHOLest-24		peroxisomal matrix	
25(S) DHCA-CoA		peroxisomal matrix	
25(S) THCA-CoA		peroxisomal matrix	
25-hydroxyCHOLEsterol	25HCHOL	cytosol	
27-hydroxyCHOLEsterol	27HCHOL	endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
27-hydroxyCHOLEsterol	27HCHOL	extracellular region	
27-hydroxyCHOLEsterol	27HCHOL	mitochondrial matrix	
27-hydroxyCHOLEsterol 3-sulfate	27HCHOL-SO4	cytosol	
2-acetylaminofluorene-N-sulfate	AAFNS	cytosol	http://ctd.mdibl.org/detail.go?type=chem&acc=C047043
2-acyl-1-palmitoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphoCHOLine		endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
2-acylglycerols	2AGs	extracellular region	
2-acyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphoCHOLine		endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
2-Amino-3-carboxymuconate semialdehyde	ACS	cytosol	http://www.hmdb.ca/metabolites/HMDB01330
2-Aminomuconate	2AM	cytosol	
2-Aminomuconate semialdehyde	2AMA	cytosol	

name	short name	location	Notes
2-Arachidonoylglycerol	2AG	extracellular region	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/chebi/searchId.do?chebiId=CHEBI:52392
2-Arachidonoylglycerol	2AG	plasma membrane	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/chebi/searchId.do?chebiId=CHEBI:52392
2-Chloroethylene oxide	2CEO	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
2'-deoxyadenosine	dA	cytosol	
2'-deoxyadenosine	dA	extracellular region	
2'-deoxyadenosine	dA	mitochondrial matrix	
2'-deoxyadenosine 5'-diphosphate	dADP	cytosol	
2'-deoxyadenosine 5'-diphosphate	dADP	mitochondrial matrix	
2'-deoxyadenosine 5'-diphosphate	dADP	nucleoplasm	
2'-deoxyadenosine 5'-monophosphate	dAMP	cytosol	
2'-deoxyadenosine 5'-monophosphate	dAMP	extracellular region	
2'-deoxyadenosine 5'-monophosphate	dAMP	mitochondrial matrix	
2'-deoxycytidine	dC	cytosol	
2'-deoxycytidine	dC	mitochondrial matrix	
2'-deoxycytidine 5'-diphosphate	dCDP	cytosol	
2'-deoxycytidine 5'-diphosphate	dCDP	mitochondrial matrix	
2'-deoxycytidine 5'-diphosphate	dCDP	nucleoplasm	
2'-deoxycytidine 5'-monophosphate	dCMP	mitochondrial matrix	
2-deoxy-D-ribose 1-phosphate	dRibP	cytosol	
2'-deoxyguanosine	dG	cytosol	
2'-deoxyguanosine	dG	mitochondrial matrix	
2'-deoxyguanosine 5'-diphosphate	dGDP	cytosol	
2'-deoxyguanosine 5'-diphosphate	dGDP	mitochondrial matrix	
2'-deoxyguanosine 5'-diphosphate	dGDP	nucleoplasm	
2'-deoxyguanosine 5'-monophosphate	dGMP	cytosol	
2'-deoxyguanosine 5'-monophosphate	dGMP	mitochondrial matrix	
2'-deoxyinosine	dI	cytosol	
2'-deoxyinosine	dI	mitochondrial matrix	
2'-deoxyinosine 5'-monophosphate	dIMP	cytosol	
2'-deoxyinosine 5'-monophosphate	dIMP	mitochondrial matrix	
2'-deoxyuridine	dU	cytosol	
2'-deoxyuridine	dU	mitochondrial matrix	
2'-deoxyuridine 3'-monophosphate	dU3MP	cytosol	
2'-deoxyuridine 5'-diphosphate	dUDP	cytosol	
2'-deoxyuridine 5'-diphosphate	dUDP	mitochondrial matrix	
2'-deoxyuridine 5'-diphosphate	dUDP	nucleoplasm	
2'-deoxyuridine 5'-monophosphate	dU5MP	mitochondrial matrix	
2-Hydroxyphytanoyl-CoA	3S2HPhy-CoA	peroxisomal matrix	http://www.hmdb.ca/metabolites/HMDB01295
2-lysophosphatidylchol.ine	LPC	extracellular region	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/chebi/searchId.do?chebiId=CHEBI:17504
2-mercaptoethanol	BME	cytosol	http://www.sigmaaldrich.com/catalog/ProductDetail.do?D7=0&N5=SEARCH_CONCAT_PNO BRAND_KEY&N4=M7154 SIGMA&N25=0&Q5=ON&F=SPEC
2-Methyl-3-oxopropanoate	MOPP	mitochondrial matrix	http://www.chemspider.com/Chemical-Structure.290.html
2-oxobutanoate	2-Ketobutyrate	cytosol	
2-oxoglutaric acid	2OGA	cytosol	
2-oxoglutarate	2OG	cytosol	
2-Oxoglutarate	2OG	extracellular region	http://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlelanding/2011/CS/C0CS00203H
2-Oxoglutarate	2OG	mitochondrial matrix	http://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlelanding/2011/CS/C0CS00203H
2-Oxoglutarate	2OG	nucleoplasm	http://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlelanding/2011/CS/C0CS00203H
2-Oxoglutarate	2OG	peroxisomal matrix	http://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlelanding/2011/CS/C0CS00203H
2-Phenylethylamine	PEA	cytosol	
2-Phenylethylamine	PEA	extracellular region	
2-Phospho-D-glycerate	2PG	cytosol	
2-trans-4-cis-decadienoyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
2-trans-Dodecenoyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
3-(4-Hydroxyphenyl)pyruvate		cytosol	
3-(indol-3-yl)pyruvic acid		cytosol	
3,16-dihydroxypalmitate	DHPALM	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
3,3'-diiodothyronine	(I)2-T4	cytosol	
3,3'-diiodothyronine 4-sulfate	(I)2-T4-SO4	cytosol	
3,4-dihydroxybenzoate	DHBENZ	cytosol	
3,5,3'-triiodothyronine	(I)3-T4	cytosol	
3,5,3'-triiodothyronine	(I)3-T4	extracellular region	
3,5,3'-triiodothyronine 4-sulfate	(I)3-T4-SO4	cytosol	
3',5'-Cyclic AMP	cAMP	cytosol	
3',5'-Cyclic AMP	cAMP	plasma membrane	
3',5'-Cyclic GMP	cGMP	cytosol	
3,7,24THCA		cytosol	
3,7,24THCA		mitochondrial matrix	
3,7,24THCA-CoA		cytosol	

name	short name	location	Notes
3,7,24THCA-CoA		peroxisomal matrix	
3-acetamidopropanal		peroxisomal matrix	
3alpha,7alpha,12alpha,24(S)-tetrahydroxy-5beta		mitochondrial matrix	
3alpha,7alpha,12alpha-trihydroxy-5beta-CHOLes		peroxisomal matrix	
3alpha,7alpha,12alpha-trihydroxy-5beta-CHOLes		mitochondrial matrix	
3alpha,7alpha,24(S)-trihydroxy-5beta-CHOLest		mitochondrial matrix	
3alpha,7alpha-dihydroxy-5beta-CHOLest-24-one-		peroxisomal matrix	
3alpha,7alpha-dihydroxy-5beta-CHOLest-26-al		mitochondrial matrix	
3-aminopropanal	APrOH	peroxisomal matrix	
3-Dehydroquininate	3DHQ	cytosol	
3-Dehydroshikimate	3DHSK	cytosol	
3-hydroxy 4-methoxybenzoate		cytosol	
3-Hydroxyanthranilate	3HAA	cytosol	
3-hydroxyhexacosanoyl-CoA		peroxisomal matrix	
3-Hydroxy-L-kynurenine		cytosol	
3-Hydroxy-N6,N6,N6-trimethyl-L-lysine	HTM-K	cytosol	
3-Hydroxy-N6,N6,N6-trimethyl-L-lysine	HTM-K	mitochondrial matrix	
3-hydroxyoctadecanoyl-CoA		cytosol	
3-hydroxypalmitate	HPALM	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
3-hydroxypristanoyl-CoA		peroxisomal matrix	
3-ketohexacosanoyl-CoA		peroxisomal matrix	
3-ketopristanoyl-CoA		peroxisomal matrix	
3-ketosphinganine		endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
3-Methoxy-4-hydroxyphenylglycol		cytosol	
3-Methyladenine	MADE	nucleoplasm	
3-methyleneindolenine	3MEIN	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/11592314
3-methylguanosine cap		cytosol	
3-methylguanosine cap		nucleoplasm	
3-methylindole	MIND	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
3-oxo-(7,10,13,16)-docosatetraenoyl-CoA		cytosol	
3-oxobehenoyl-CoA		cytosol	
3-oxocerotoyl-CoA		cytosol	
3-Oxodecanoyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
3-Oxododecanoyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
3-Oxohexanoyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
3-oxooctadecanoyl-CoA		cytosol	
3-Oxoctanoyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
3-Oxopalmitoyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
3-oxopropanoate	OPROP	mitochondrial matrix	
3-Oxotetradecanoyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
3-Phospho-D-glycerate	3PG	cytosol	
3-trans-decenoyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
3-ureidoisobutyric acid	UIBA	cytosol	
3-Ureidopropionate	UPROP	cytosol	
4-phosphopantetheine	PPANT	cytosol	
4-(2-aminophenyl)-2,4-dioxobutanoic acid		cytosol	
4-(2-aminophenyl)-2,4-dioxobutanoic acid		mitochondrial matrix	
4-(4-(dimethylamino)styryl)-N-methylpyridinium	4-Di-2-ASP	cytosol	http://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlelanding/2011/CS/C0CS00203H
4-(4-(dimethylamino)styryl)-N-methylpyridinium	4-Di-2-ASP	extracellular region	http://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlelanding/2011/CS/C0CS00203H
4,4-dimethylCHOLesta-8(9),14,24-trien-3beta-ol	4,4DMCHTOL	endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
4,4-dimethylCHOLesta-8(9),14,24-trien-3beta-ol	4,4DMCHTOL	nuclear envelope	
4,4-dimethylCHOLesta-8(9),24-dien-3beta-ol	14DMLANOL	endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
4,4-dimethylCHOLesta-8(9),24-dien-3beta-ol	14DMLANOL	nuclear envelope	
4,8,12-trimethyltridecanoyl-CoA	4,8,12-TMTD-CoA	peroxisomal matrix	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/chebi/searchld.do?sessionId=428A7ADEA1A391863B0A2A35062EE56D?chebiid=CHEBI:3A15495
4,8-dimethylnonanoylcarnitine		peroxisomal matrix	
4,8-dimethylnonanoyl-CoA		peroxisomal matrix	
4a-hydroxytetrahydrobiopterin		cytosol	
4-aminobenzoate	ABENZ	cytosol	
4-Aminobiphenyl	ABPH	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
4-aminosalicylate	ASAL	cytosol	
4-Androstene-3,17-dione	ADION	cytosol	
4-carboxyCHOLesta-8(9),24-dien-3beta-ol	4CZYMOL	endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
4-CHOLesten-7alpha,12alpha-diol-3-one		endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
4-CHOLesten-7alpha,12alpha,24(S)-triol-3-one		endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
4-CHOLesten-7alpha,12alpha,27-triol-3-one		endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
4-CHOLesten-7alpha,24(S)-diol-3-one		endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
4-CHOLesten-7alpha,27-diol-3-one		endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
4-CHOLesten-7alpha-ol-3-one		endoplasmic reticulum membrane	

name	short name	location	Notes
4-cis-decenoyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
4-Fumarylacetoacetate	4FAA	cytosol	
4-hydroxy-9-cis-retinoic acid	HcRA	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
4-hydroxy-all-trans-retinoic acid	HatRA	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
4-hydroxybutyrate	HBUT	mitochondrial matrix	
4-hydroxycyclophosphamide	HCPM	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
4-hydroxydebrisoquine	HDBQ	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
4-hydroxyestradiol-17beta	4-OH-Estradiol	cytosol	http://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/summary/summary.cgi?cid=1743#Synonyms
4-hydroxy-L-proline	HPRO	cytosol	
4-hydroxy-L-proline	HPRO	extracellular region	
4-Hydroxyphenylacetaldehyde	HPHAC	cytosol	
4-hydroxyphenytoin	HPHT	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
4-hydroxytolbutamide	HTOLB	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
4-Imidazolone-5-propanoate		cytosol	
4-Maleylacetoacetate	4MAA	cytosol	
4-methyl,4-carboxyCHOLesta-8(9),24-dien-3beta	4C4MZYMOL	endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
4-methylCHOLesta-8(9),24-dien-3beta-ol	4MZYMOL	endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
4-methylCHOLesta-8(9),24-dien-3-one	dh4MZYMOL	endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
4-methylpentan-1-ol	MePeOH	cytosol	
4-Methylthio-2-oxobutanoate (1-)		cytosol	
4-Trimethylammoniobutanal	TEABL	cytosol	
4-Trimethylammoniobutanoate	TEABT	cytosol	
5,10-methenyltetrahydrofolate polyglutamate		cytosol	same as entry 297 below?
5,10-methylenetetrahydrofolate polyglutamate	MTHFPG	cytosol	
5,6-Dihydrothymine	DHT	cytosol	
5,6-Dihydrouracil	DHU	cytosol	
5,6-Dihydrouracil	DHU	nucleoplasm	
5,6-EET		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
5-acetylamino-6-formylamino-3-methyluracil	AFMU	cytosol	http://www.chemspider.com/Chemical-Structure.97287.html
5-alpha-dihydrotestosterone	DHTEST	cytosol	
5-aminolevulinate	dALA	cytosol	
5-aminolevulinate	dALA	mitochondrial matrix	
5beta-CHOLestan-3alpha,7alpha,12alpha-triol		mitochondrial matrix	
5beta-CHOLestan-3alpha,7alpha-diol		mitochondrial matrix	
5beta-CHOLestan-3alpha,7alpha,12alpha,24(S),2		mitochondrial matrix	
5beta-CHOLestan-3alpha,7alpha,12alpha,24(S)-triol		cytosol	
5beta-CHOLestan-3alpha,7alpha,12alpha,24(S)-triol		mitochondrial matrix	
5beta-CHOLestan-3alpha,7alpha,12alpha,27-tetrol		cytosol	
5beta-CHOLestan-3alpha,7alpha,12alpha,27-tetrol		mitochondrial matrix	
5beta-CHOLestan-3alpha,7alpha,12alpha-triol		cytosol	
5beta-CHOLestan-3alpha,7alpha,24(S),27-tetrol		mitochondrial matrix	
5beta-CHOLestan-3alpha,7alpha,24(S)-triol		cytosol	
5beta-CHOLestan-3alpha,7alpha,24(S)-triol		mitochondrial matrix	
5beta-CHOLestan-3alpha,7alpha,26-triol		cytosol	
5beta-CHOLestan-3alpha,7alpha,26-triol		mitochondrial matrix	
5beta-CHOLestan-3alpha,7alpha-diol		cytosol	
5beta-CHOLestan-7alpha,12alpha,24(S)-triol-3-one		cytosol	
5beta-CHOLestan-7alpha,12alpha,27-triol-3-one		cytosol	
5beta-CHOLestan-7alpha,24(S)-diol-3-one		cytosol	
5beta-CHOLestan-7alpha,27-diol-3-one		cytosol	
5beta-CHOLestan-7alpha-ol-3-one		cytosol	
5beta-CHOLestan-7alpha-ol-3-one		cytosol	
5beta-CHOLestan-7alpha,12alpha-diol-3-one		cytosol	
5'-Deoxyadenosine	dADE	cytosol	
5-formiminotetrahydrofolate	FITHF	cytosol	
5-HpETE		cytosol	
5-hydroxyindole acetaldehyde	HIALD	mitochondrial matrix	
5-Hydroxyindole acetic acid	HIAA	mitochondrial matrix	
5-Hydroxyindoleacetaldehyde	HIALD	cytosol	same as 329
5-hydroxyomeprazole	HOMZ	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
5-Hydroxytryptamine	5HT	cytosol	
5-hydroxytryptamine N-methyl conjugate	5HT-N-CH3	cytosol	
5-hydroxytryptophan	5HTP	cytosol	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/5-Hydroxytryptophan
5-hydroxyuracil	5OHU	nucleoplasm	
5-L-gamma-glutamyl amino acid	GGAA	extracellular region	
5-methyltetrahydrofolate	MTHF	cytosol	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Levomefolic_acid
5-methyltetrahydrofolate	MTHF	extracellular region	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Levomefolic_acid
5-methyltetrahydrofolate polyglutamate	MTHFPG	cytosol	
5'-Methylthio-ribose-1P (2-)		cytosol	

name	short name	location	Notes
5'-Methylthio-ribose-1P (2-)		cytosol	
5-oxo-EET		extracellular region	
5-oxoproline	OPRO-	cytosol	
5-phosphoribosylamine	PRA	cytosol	
5-phosphoribosylglycinamide	PRGA	cytosol	
6beta-hydroxytestosterone	6BHT	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
6-hydroxypaclitaxel	HPTXL	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
6-Mercaptopurine	6MP	cytosol	
6-Mercaptopurine	6MP	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
6-Methylmercaptopurine	6MMP	cytosol	
6-Methylmercaptopurine	6MMP	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
6-Phospho-D-gluconate	PDG	cytosol	
7 alpha-hydroxyCHOLEsterol	7HCHOL	endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
7-dehydroCHOLEsterol	7DHCHOL	cytosol	
7-methylguanosine 5'-diphosphate	7-MeGDP	cytosol	
7-methylguanosine 5'-monophosphate	7-MeGMP	cytosol	
7-methylguanosine cap		cytosol	
7-methylguanosine cap		nucleoplasm	
8,11,14-Eicosatrienoic acid	8,11,14ETA	extracellular region	
8,9-EET	8,9-EET	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
8-oxoguanine	OGUA	nucleoplasm	
9(S)-HODE	9S-HODE	nucleoplasm	
9-cis-retinoic acid	9cisRA	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
9-O-acetylneuraminic acid	OANA-	Golgi lumen	
Acetaldehyde	CH3CHO	cytosol	
Acetaldehyde	CH3CHO	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Acetaldehyde	CH3CHO	mitochondrial matrix	
Acetaldehyde	CH3CHO	nucleoplasm	
Acetaminophen	ACAP	cytosol	
Acetaminophen (Paracetamol, TN TYLENOL)	ACAP	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Acetaminophen glutathione conjugate	ACAP-GSH	cytosol	
Acetaminophen glutathione conjugate	ACAP-GSH	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Acetaminophen O-glucuronide	ACAP-UGLU	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Acetaminophen O-sulfate conjugate	ACAP-SO4	cytosol	
Acetate	CH3COO-	cytosol	
Acetate	CH3COO-	extracellular region	
Acetate	CH3COO-	mitochondrial matrix	
Acetate	CH3COO-	peroxisomal matrix	
Acetoacetate	ACA	cytosol	
Acetoacetate	ACA	extracellular region	
acetoacetate	ACA	mitochondrial matrix	
acetoacetyl-CoA	ACA-CoA	cytosol	
acetoacetyl-CoA	ACA-CoA	mitochondrial matrix	
acetophenone	APN	cytosol	
acetophenone-mercapturic acid	APN-MTA	cytosol	
acetophenone-mycithiol conjugate	APN-MYT	cytosol	
Acetylcarnitine	ACAR	peroxisomal matrix	
Acetyl-CoA	Ac-CoA	cytosol	
Acetyl-CoA	Ac-CoA	Golgi lumen	
Acetyl-CoA	Ac-CoA	mitochondrial matrix	
Acetyl-CoA	Ac-CoA	nucleoplasm	
Acetyl-CoA	Ac-CoA	peroxisomal matrix	
Acyclovir	ACV	cytosol	
Acyclovir	ACV	extracellular region	
adenine	Ade	cytosol	
adenine	Ade	extracellular region	
adenine	Ade	lysosomal lumen	
adenosine	Ade-Rib	cytosol	
Adenosine	Ade-Rib	extracellular region	
adenosine	Ade-Rib	lysosomal lumen	
adenosine 5'-monophosphate	AMP	extracellular region	
Adenosine 5'-phosphosulfate	APS	cytosol	
adenylosuccinate	ADS	cytosol	
ADP		cytosol	
ADP		endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
ADP		endosome	
ADP		extracellular region	
ADP		mitochondrial matrix	

name	short name	location	Notes
ADP		nucleoplasm	
ADP		plasma membrane	
ADP		platelet dense granule lumen	
Adrenaline	ADR	clathrin sculpted monoamine transport vesicle lumen	
Adrenaline	ADR	cytosol	
Adrenaline	ADR	extracellular region	
Adrenaline	ADR	extracellular region	
Aflatoxin B1	AFTB1	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Aflatoxin exo-8,9-oxide	AFBO	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Aflatoxin exo-8,9-oxide glutathione conjugate	AFBO-SG	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Agmatine	AGM	cytosol	
Agmatine	AGM	extracellular region	
AICAR	AICAR	cytosol	
AIR	AIR	cytosol	
Ala-tRNA(Ala)	Ala-tRNA(Ala)	cytosol	
Ala-tRNA(Ala)	Ala-tRNA(Ala)	mitochondrial matrix	
Aldosterone	ALDO	mitochondrial matrix	
all-cis-icosa-pentaenoic acid		extracellular region	
all-trans-retinal	atRAL	cytosol	
All-trans-retinoic acid	atRA	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
all-trans-retinol	atROL	plasma membrane	
alpha,alpha'-trehalose		cytosol	
alpha,alpha'-trehalose		extracellular region	
alpha,alpha'-trehalose-6-phosphate		cytosol	
alpha-D-Galactose 1-phosphate		cytosol	
alpha-D-glucose	Glc	cytosol	Glc is better
alpha-D-glucose	Glc	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	Glc is better
alpha-D-glucose	Glc	extracellular region	Glc is better
alpha-D-glucose	Glc	Golgi lumen	Glc is better
alpha-D-glucose	Glc	nucleoplasm	Glc is better
alpha-D-Glucose 6-phosphate	Glc6P	cytosol	
alpha-D-Glucose 6-phosphate	Glc6P	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
alpha-ketoadipate		cytosol	
alpha-ketoadipate		mitochondrial matrix	
alpha-keto-beta-methylvalerate	KMVA	cytosol	http://ctd.mdibl.org/detail.go?type=chem&acc=C016211
alpha-keto-beta-methylvalerate	KMVA	mitochondrial matrix	http://ctd.mdibl.org/detail.go?type=chem&acc=C016211
alpha-ketoisocaproate	KIC	cytosol	http://www.nutriline.org/article/8
alpha-ketoisocaproate	KIC	mitochondrial matrix	http://www.nutriline.org/article/8
alpha-ketisovalerate	KIV	cytosol	
alpha-ketisovalerate	KIV	mitochondrial matrix	
alpha-Linolenic acid	ALA	extracellular region	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Polyunsaturated_fatty_acid
alpha-linolenic acid	ALA	nucleoplasm	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Polyunsaturated_fatty_acid
alpha-methylacetoacetyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
alpha-methyl-beta-hydroxybutyryl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
alpha-methylbutyryl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
AMP		cytosol	
AMP		mitochondrial matrix	
AMP		nucleoplasm	
AMP		peroxisomal matrix	
Anandamide	AEA	extracellular region	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Anandamide
arachidic acid	AA	cytosol	
arachidic acid	AA	extracellular region	
Arachidonate	AA	cytosol	
Arachidonate	AA	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Arachidonate	AA	plasma membrane	
arachidonic acid	ARA	nucleoplasm	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Arachidonic_acid
arachidonoyl-CoA		cytosol	
arachidoyl-CoA		cytosol	
Arg-tRNA(Arg)		cytosol	
Arg-tRNA(Arg)		mitochondrial matrix	
Asbestos	Asb	cytosol	
Ascorbate	VitC	cytosol	
ascorbate	VitC	extracellular region	
Ascorbate	VitC	stored secretory granule	
Asn-tRNA(Asn)		cytosol	
Asn-tRNA(Asn)		mitochondrial matrix	
Aspartame	ASP	extracellular region	
Asp-tRNA(Asp)		cytosol	

name	short name	location	Notes
Asp-tRNA(Asp)		mitochondrial matrix	
ATP		cytosol	
ATP		endosome	
ATP		extracellular region	
ATP		mitochondrial matrix	
ATP		nucleoplasm	
ATP		peroxisomal matrix	
ATP		plasma membrane	
ATP		platelet dense granule lumen	
Benzene	C6H6	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Benzo(a)pyrene-7,8-diol 9,10-epoxide	BPDE	cytosol	
Benzo(a)pyrene-7,8-diol-glutathione conjugate	BPD-SG	cytosol	
Benzoic acid	BENZA	mitochondrial matrix	
Benzoyl-CoA thioester	BEZ-CoA	mitochondrial matrix	
beta-Alanine	b-Ala	cytosol	
beta-Alanine	b-Ala	extracellular region	
beta-Alanine	b-Ala	mitochondrial matrix	
Beta-carotene	b-CARO	plasma membrane	
beta-D-mannosyl diacetylchitobiosyl diphosphodol	MDCCD	integral to cytosolic side of endoplasmic reticulum	
beta-estradiol	E2	cytosol	
beta-estradiol 3-sulfate	E2-SO4	cytosol	
beta-hydroxy-beta-methylglutaryl-CoA	bHMG-CoA	cytosol	
beta-hydroxy-beta-methylglutaryl-CoA	bHMG-CoA	mitochondrial matrix	
Beta-hydroxybutyrate	bHBA	cytosol	
Beta-hydroxybutyrate	bHBA	extracellular region	
beta-hydroxyisobutyrate	bHIBA	mitochondrial matrix	
beta-hydroxyisobutyryl-CoA	bHIB-CoA	mitochondrial matrix	
betaine	BET	cytosol	
betaine	BET	extracellular region	
beta-methylcrotonyl-CoA	bMC-CoA	mitochondrial matrix	general comment about greek letters. Where we have a, b, d, g etc to denote greek characters, I hope we can fill with the actual character.
beta-methylglutaconyl-CoA	bMC-CoA	mitochondrial matrix	
Bilirubin	BIL	cytosol	
Bilirubin	BIL	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Bilirubin diglucuronide	BDG	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Bilirubin monoglucuronide	BMG	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
biliverdin	BV	cytosol	
Biotin	BTN	cytosol	
Biotin	BTN	extracellular region	
Biotin	BTN	mitochondrial matrix	
Bromide	Br-	cytosol	
Bromide	Br-	transport vesicle	
bromsulphophthalein	BSP	cytosol	
bromsulphophthalein	BSP	extracellular region	
Butanoyl-CoA	BT-CoA	mitochondrial matrix	
Butyrate	BUT	cytosol	
Butyrate	BUT	extracellular region	
Caffeine	CAF	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
CAIR	CAIR	cytosol	
Calcidiol	CDL	cytosol	
Calcidiol	CDL	extracellular region	
Calcidiol	CDL	lysosomal lumen	
Calcitriol	CDL	cytosol	
Calcitric acid	CTA	cytosol	
Calcium	Ca2+	cytosol	
Calcium	Ca2+	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Calcium	Ca2+	extracellular region	
Calcium	Ca2+	Golgi lumen	
Calcium	Ca2+	nucleoplasm	
Calcium	Ca2+	plasma membrane	
Calcium	Ca2+	platelet dense granule lumen	
Calcium	Ca2+	platelet dense tubular network lumen	
Calcium	Ca2+	platelet dense tubular network membrane	
Calcium	Ca2+	stored secretory granule	
carbamoyl phosphate	CAP	cytosol	
Carbamoyl phosphate	CAP	mitochondrial matrix	
carbon monoxide	CO	cytosol	
Carbon tetrachloride	CCl4	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Carnitine	CAR	cytosol	

name	short name	location	Notes
Carnitine	CAR	extracellular region	
Carnitine	CAR	mitochondrial intermembrane space	
Carnitine	CAR	mitochondrial matrix	
Carnitine	CAR	peroxisomal matrix	
Ceramide	CERA	cytosol	
ceramide	CERA	endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
ceramide	CERA	Golgi membrane	
ceramide	CERA	plasma membrane	
chenodeoxyCHOLate	CDCA	cytosol	
chenodeoxyCHOLate	CDCA	extracellular region	
ChenodeoxyCHOLic acid	CDCA	extracellular region	
chenodeoxyCHOLoyl-CoA	CDC-CoA	cytosol	
chenodeoxyCHOLoyl-CoA	CDC-CoA	peroxisomal matrix	
Chloride	Cl-	cytosol	
Chloride	Cl-	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Chloride	Cl-	extracellular region	
Chloride	Cl-	transport vesicle	
Chloroquine	CLQ	cytosol	
Chloroquine	CLQ	extracellular region	
CHOLate	CCA	cytosol	
CHOLate	CCA	extracellular region	
CHOLate	CCA	peroxisomal matrix	
CHOLest-5-ene-3beta,7alpha,24(S)-triol		endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
CHOLest-5-ene-3beta,7alpha,25-triol		cytosol	
CHOLest-5-ene-3beta,7alpha,27-triol		endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
CHOLesta-5,7,24-trien-3beta-ol	7dhDESOL	endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
CHOLesta-7,24-dien-3beta-ol	CHdOL	endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
CHOLesta-8(9),24-dien-3-one	ZYMONONE	endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
CHOLesterol	CHOL	clathrin-coated endocytic vesicle membrane	
CHOLesterol	CHOL	cytosol	
CHOLesterol	CHOL	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
CHOLesterol	CHOL	endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
CHOLesterol	CHOL	endosome lumen	
CHOLesterol	CHOL	endosome membrane	
CHOLesterol	CHOL	extracellular region	
CHOLesterol	CHOL	lipid particle	
CHOLesterol	CHOL	mitochondrial inner membrane	
CHOLesterol	CHOL	mitochondrial intermembrane space	
CHOLesterol	CHOL	mitochondrial matrix	
CHOLesterol	CHOL	plasma membrane	
CHOLesterol	CHOL	transport vesicle membrane	
CHOLesterol esters	CHEST	clathrin-coated endocytic vesicle membrane	
CHOLesterol esters	CHEST	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
CHOLesterol esters	CHEST	endosome lumen	
CHOLesterol esters	CHEST	endosome membrane	
CHOLesterol esters	CHEST	extracellular region	
CHOLesterol esters	CHEST	plasma membrane	
CHOLesterol sulfate	CHOL-SO4	cytosol	
CHOLic acid	CCA	extracellular region	
CHOLine	Cho	cytosol	
CHOLine	Cho	extracellular region	
CHOLine phosphate	ChoP	cytosol	
CHOLoyl-CoA	CHO-CoA	cytosol	
CHOLoyl-CoA	CHO-CoA	peroxisomal matrix	
Chondroitin sulfate	CHS	extracellular region	
Chorismate	CRSM	cytosol	
Cimetidine	CIM	cytosol	
Cimetidine	CIM	extracellular region	
cis,cis-3,6-Dodecadienoyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
Citrate	CIT	cytosol	
Citrate	CIT	extracellular region	
Citrate	CIT	mitochondrial matrix	
Clonidine	CLON	cytosol	
Clonidine	CLON	extracellular region	
CMP	CMP	nucleoplasm	
CMP-sialic acid	CMP-SA	cytosol	
CMP-sialic acid	CMP-SA	Golgi lumen	
CO2		cytosol	

name	short name	location	Notes
CO2		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
CO2		mitochondrial intermembrane space	
CO2		mitochondrial matrix	
CO2		nucleoplasm	
CO2		peroxisomal matrix	
Co2+		mitochondrial matrix	
CoA-SH		cytosol	
CoA-SH		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
CoA-SH		mitochondrial matrix	
CoA-SH		peroxisomal matrix	
Cobamide coenzyme	VitB12 coenzyme	mitochondrial matrix	
Copper	Cu2+	cytosol	
Copper	Cu2+	extracellular region	
Copper	Cu2+	Golgi lumen	
Copper	Cu2+	plasma membrane	
Copper	Cu2+	stored secretory granule	
Copper A	CuA	mitochondrial inner membrane	
Coproporphyrinogen I	COPROI	cytosol	
Coproporphyrinogen III	COPROII	cytosol	
Coproporphyrinogen III	COPROIII	mitochondrial intermembrane space	
Corticosterone	CORST	mitochondrial matrix	
Cortisol	CORT	cytosol	
Cortisol	CORT	mitochondrial matrix	
Cortisone	COR	cytosol	
Coumarin	COUM	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Creatine	CRET	cytosol	
Creatine	CRET	extracellular region	
Creatinine	CREAT	cytosol	
Creatinine	CREAT	extracellular region	
Crotonoyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
crotonyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
CTP		cytosol	
CTP		mitochondrial matrix	
CTP		nucleoplasm	
Cyclophosphamide	CPM	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
cystathionine	CYSTA	cytosol	
cysteinylglycine	Cys-Gly	cytosol	
cysteinylglycine	Cys-Gly	extracellular region	
Cys-tRNA(Cys)		cytosol	
Cys-tRNA(Cys)		mitochondrial matrix	
cytidine	Cyt-Rib	cytosol	
cytidine	Cyt-Rib	extracellular region	
cytidine	Cyt-Rib	lysosomal lumen	
cytidine 5'-diphosphate	CDP	cytosol	
cytidine 5'-diphosphate	CDP	mitochondrial matrix	
cytidine 5'-diphosphate	CDP	nucleoplasm	
cytidine 5'-monophosphate	CMP	cytosol	
cytidine 5'-monophosphate	CMP	extracellular region	
cytidine 5'-monophosphate	CMP	Golgi lumen	
cytosine	Cyt	cytosol	
cytosine	Cyt	extracellular region	
DAHP(3-)	DAHP(3-)	cytosol	
D-Alanine	D-Ala	cytosol	
D-Alanine	D-Ala	extracellular region	
D-Aspartate	D-Asp	cytosol	
D-Aspartate	D-Asp	extracellular region	
dATP	dATP	cytosol	
dATP	dATP	mitochondrial matrix	
dATP	dATP	nucleoplasm	
D-beta hydroxybutyrate	βHBA	mitochondrial matrix	
D-chiro-inositol	CHI	cytosol	
D-chiro-inositol	CHI	extracellular region	
dCMP	dCMP	cytosol	
dCTP	dCTP	cytosol	
dCTP	dCTP	mitochondrial matrix	
dCTP	dCTP	nucleoplasm	
Deamino-NAD+	DA-NAD+	cytosol	
Deamino-NAD+	DA-NAD+	nucleoplasm	

name	short name	location	Notes
Debrisoquine	DSQ	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Debrisoquine O-glucuronide	DSQ-OG	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
decanoic acid	DECA	cytosol	
Decanoic acid	DECA	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
decanoic acid	DECA	extracellular region	
Decanoyl-CoA	DEC-CoA	mitochondrial matrix	
Dehydroascorbate	DHvitC	cytosol	
dehydroascorbate	DHvitC	extracellular region	
Dehydroascorbate	DHvitC	stored secretory granule	
dehydroepiandrosterone	DHEA	cytosol	
Dehydroepiandrosterone	DHEA	cytosol	
dehydroepiandrosterone sulfate	DHEA-SO4	cytosol	
Dehydroepiandro-sterone sulfate	DHEA-SO4	cytosol	
Dehydroepiandro-sterone sulfate	DHEA-SO4	extracellular region	
delta3-isopentenyl pyrophosphate	IPPP	cytosol	
DeoxyCHOLic acid	DOCA	extracellular region	
Dephospho-CoA	DP-CoA	cytosol	
D-Erythrose 4-phosphate	E4P	cytosol	
desacetylmicothiol	DAMT	cytosol	
Desipramine	DESI	cytosol	
Desipramine	DESI	extracellular region	
desmosterol	DESMOL	endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
Dexamethasone	DEXA	nucleoplasm	
Dextromethorphan	DEXM	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Dextrorphan	DEXT	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
D-fructose	Fru	cytosol	
D-fructose	Fru	extracellular region	
D-Fructose 1,6-bisphosphate	Fru(1,6)P2	cytosol	
D-Fructose 1-phosphate	Fru(1)P	cytosol	
D-Fructose 2,6-bisphosphate	Fru(2,6)P2	cytosol	
D-Fructose 6-phosphate	Fru(6)P	cytosol	
D-galactose	Gal	cytosol	
D-galactose	Gal	extracellular region	
D-Glucono-1,5-lactone 6-phosphate		cytosol	
D-glucosamine 6-phosphate	GlcN6P	cytosol	
D-Glucose 1-phosphate	Glc1P	cytosol	
D-Glyceraldehyde	GA	cytosol	
D-Glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate	GA3P	cytosol	
dGTP		cytosol	
dGTP		mitochondrial matrix	
dGTP		nucleoplasm	
DHCA		cytosol	
DHCA		mitochondrial matrix	
diacylglycerols	DAGs	extracellular region	
diacylglycerols	DAGs	Golgi membrane	
diacylglycerols	DAGs	plasma membrane	
diaminobutyrate	DAB	cytosol	
diaminobutyrate	DAB	extracellular region	
digoxin	DIGX	cytosol	
digoxin	DIGX	extracellular region	
dihydroceramide	DHCE	endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
Dihydrofolate	DHF	cytosol	
Dihydroxyacetone phosphate	DHAP	cytosol	
Dihydroxyacetone phosphate	DHAP	mitochondrial matrix	
Dihydroxyacetone phosphate	DHAP	peroxisomal matrix	
Diiodotyrosine	DIT	extracellular region	
Dimethylallyl pyrophosphate	DMAPP	cytosol	
dipyrromethane	DIPY	cytosol	
D-mannose	Man	cytosol	
D-mannose	Man	endoplasmic reticulum quality control compartment	
D-mannose	Man	extracellular region	
D-mannose	Man	Golgi lumen	
D-Mannose 1-phosphate	Man1P	cytosol	
D-Mannose 6-phosphate	Man6P	cytosol	
D-methylmalonyl-CoA	MEMA-CoA	mitochondrial matrix	
Docosahexaenoic acid	DHA	extracellular region	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Polyunsaturated_fatty_acid
Docosapentaenoic acid	DPA	extracellular region	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Polyunsaturated_fatty_acid
Docosatetraenoic acid	DTTA	extracellular region	

name	short name	location	Notes
Dodecylcarboxylate	DDCX	cytosol	
Dodecylcarboxylate	DDCX	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Dodecylcarboxylate	DDCX	extracellular region	
Dolichol	DOL	integral to cytosolic side of endoplasmic reticulum	
Dolichyl beta-D-glucosyl phosphate	DbGP	endoplasmic reticulum quality control compartment	
Dolichyl beta-D-glucosyl phosphate	DbGP	integral to cytosolic side of endoplasmic reticulum	
Dolichyl beta-D-glucosyl phosphate	DbGP	integral to luminal side of endoplasmic reticulum	
Dolichyl diphosphate	DOLDP	integral to cytosolic side of endoplasmic reticulum	
Dolichyl phosphate	DOLP	endoplasmic reticulum quality control compartment	
Dolichyl phosphate	DOLP	integral to cytosolic side of endoplasmic reticulum	
Dolichyl phosphate	DOLP	integral to luminal side of endoplasmic reticulum	
Dolichyl phosphate D-mannose	DOLPM	integral to luminal side of endoplasmic reticulum	
Dopa	Dopa	cytosol	
Dopamine	DA	clathrin sculpted monoamine transport vesicle lumen	
Dopamine	DA	cytosol	
Dopamine	DA	extracellular region	
Dopamine 3-O-sulfate	DAOS	cytosol	
D-ribose 1-phosphate	R1P	cytosol	
D-ribose 5-phosphate	R5P	cytosol	
D-Ribulose 5-phosphate	RU5P	cytosol	
D-Serine	D-Ser	cytosol	
D-Serine	D-Ser	extracellular region	
D-sorbitol 6-phosphate	Sor6P	cytosol	
D-tryptophan	D-Trp	extracellular region	
dTTP		nucleoplasm	
dUMP		cytosol	
dUMP		nucleoplasm	
dUTP		cytosol	
dUTP		mitochondrial matrix	
dUTP		nucleoplasm	
D-Xylulose 5-phosphate	XY5P	cytosol	
e-		endosome membrane	
e-		extracellular region	
eicosapentaenoic acid	EPA	nucleoplasm	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Polyunsaturated_fatty_acid
Elaidic acid	ELDA	extracellular region	
electron	e-	cytosol	
electron	e-	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
EPSP(4-)	EPSP(4-)	cytosol	
Ergothioneine	ERGT	cytosol	
Ergothioneine	ERGT	extracellular region	
Estradiol-17beta	EST17b	cytosol	
Estrogen	ESTG	extracellular region	Is a collective name
estrone	E1	cytosol	http://www.gfmer.ch/Endo/Lectures_08/sexual_hormones.htm
Estrone	E1	cytosol	http://www.gfmer.ch/Endo/Lectures_08/sexual_hormones.htm
estrone 3-sulfate	E1S	cytosol	http://www.gfmer.ch/Endo/Lectures_08/sexual_hormones.htm
estrone 3-sulfate	E1S	extracellular region	http://www.gfmer.ch/Endo/Lectures_08/sexual_hormones.htm
Ethanol	EtOH	cytosol	
Ethanol	EtOH	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
ethenoadenine	EtAD	nucleoplasm	
ethenocytosine	EtCYS	nucleoplasm	
Ethylene	C2H4	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Ethylene oxide	EO	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
ezetimibe	EZE	extracellular region	
ezetimibe	EZE	plasma membrane	
FAD		cytosol	
FAD		endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
FAD		mitochondrial inner membrane	
FAD		mitochondrial intermembrane space	
FAD		mitochondrial matrix	
FAD		mitochondrial outer membrane	
FAD		peroxisomal matrix	
FADH2		mitochondrial inner membrane	
FADH2		mitochondrial matrix	
FAICAR		cytosol	
Farnesyl pyrophosphate	FAPP	cytosol	
Fatty Acids	FAs	extracellular region	
fatty acyl CoA	FACoA	cytosol	
Fe ⁺⁺	Fe ²⁺	peroxisomal matrix	

name	short name	location	Notes
Fe2+	Fe2+	phagocytic vesicle	
ferriheme	FeHM	cytosol	
ferriheme	FeHM	extracellular region	
ferriheme	FeHM	mitochondrial outer membrane	
FGAM	FGAM	cytosol	
Flavin mononucleotide	FMN	cytosol	
flavin mononucleotide	FMN	mitochondrial inner membrane	
Flavin mononucleotide	FMN	peroxisomal matrix	
Fluoride	FL-	cytosol	
Fluoride	FL-	transport vesicle	
fMet-Leu-Phe	FMLP	extracellular region	
Folate	FOLA	cytosol	
Folate	FOLA	extracellular region	
formaldehyde	CH2O	cytosol	
Formaldehyde	CH2O	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Formaldehyde	CH2O	nucleoplasm	
formamidopyrimidine	FAPY	nucleoplasm	
Formate	HCOOH	cytosol	
Formate	HCOOH	extracellular region	
Formate	HCOOH	peroxisomal matrix	
Formyl-CoA	FOR-CoA	peroxisomal matrix	
Formylkynurenine	NFK	cytosol	
formylmycothiol	FMYC	cytosol	
Fumarate	FUMA	cytosol	
Fumarate	FUMA	mitochondrial matrix	
GABA		clathrin sculpted gamma-aminobutyric acid transp	
GABA		cytosol	
GABA		extracellular region	
GABA		mitochondrial matrix	
GABA		synaptic vesicle	
gamma-glutamyl group	gGLUT	cytosol	
gamma-glutamyl group	gGLUT	extracellular region	
gamma-glutamyl-L-cysteine	gGLuCys	cytosol	
gamma-Linolenic acid	GLA	extracellular region	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Polyunsaturated_fatty_acid
GDP		cytosol	
GDP		endosome	
GDP		extracellular region	
GDP		Golgi lumen	
GDP		mitochondrial matrix	
GDP		nucleoplasm	
GDP		plasma membrane	
GDP		platelet dense granule lumen	
GDP-alpha-D-mannose	GDP-Man	cytosol	
GDP-alpha-D-mannose	GDP-Man	Golgi lumen	
GDP-L-fucose	GDP-Fuc	cytosol	
GDP-L-fucose	GDP-Fuc	Golgi lumen	
Geranyl pyrophosphate	GPP	cytosol	
GlcNAc-Ins	GlcNAc-Ins	cytosol	
GlcNAc-Ins-P	GlcNAc-Ins-P	cytosol	
Gln-tRNA(Gln)	Gln-tRNA(Gln)	cytosol	
Gln-tRNA(Gln)	Gln-tRNA(Gln)	mitochondrial matrix	
glucosaminyl-inositol	GlcNI	cytosol	
glutaryl-CoA	GL-CoA	mitochondrial matrix	
Glutathione	GSH	cytosol	
Glutathione	GSH	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Glutathione	GSH	extracellular region	
Glu-tRNA(Glu)		cytosol	
Glu-tRNA(Glu)		mitochondrial matrix	
Glycerol		cytosol	
glycerol	Glycerol	extracellular region	
Glycerol-3-phosphate	G3P	cytosol	
Glycerol-3-phosphate	G3P	mitochondrial matrix	
glycine	Gly	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Glycine	Gly	extracellular region	
Glycine	Gly	lysosomal lumen	
Glycine	Gly	mitochondrial intermembrane space	
Glycine	Gly	mitochondrial matrix	
glycine	Gly	peroxisomal matrix	

name	short name	location	Notes
Glycine	Gly	synaptic vesicle	
glycochenodeoxyCHOLate	GCDC	cytosol	
glycochenodeoxyCHOLate	GCDC	extracellular region	
glycochenodeoxyCHOLate	GCDC	peroxisomal matrix	
glycoCHOLate	GC	cytosol	
glycoCHOLate	GC	extracellular region	
glycoCHOLate	GC	peroxisomal matrix	
glycogen	Glyg		
Glycolate	Glycolate	peroxisomal matrix	
Glycosaminoglycan	GAG	extracellular region	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Glycosaminoglycan
Glyoxylate		mitochondrial matrix	
Glyoxylate		peroxisomal matrix	
Gly-tRNA(Gly)		cytosol	
Gly-tRNA(Gly)		mitochondrial matrix	
GMP		cytosol	
GMP		extracellular region	
GMP		Golgi lumen	
GMP		nucleoplasm	
GTP		cytosol	
GTP		endosome	
GTP		ER to Golgi transport vesicle membrane	
GTP		extracellular region	
GTP		mitochondrial matrix	
GTP		nucleoplasm	
GTP		plasma membrane	
GTP		platelet dense granule lumen	
Guanidine	Gu	cytosol	
Guanidine	Gu	extracellular region	
Guanidinoacetate	GAA	cytosol	
Guanidinoacetate	GAA	mitochondrial intermembrane space	
guanine	Gua	cytosol	
guanine	Gua	extracellular region	
guanosine	Gua-Rib	cytosol	
guanosine	Gua-Rib	extracellular region	
guanosine	Gua-Rib	lysosomal lumen	
H+		clathrin sculpted acetylCHOLine transport vesicle lumen	
H+		clathrin sculpted monoamine transport vesicle lumen	
H+		cytosol	
H+		early endosome lumen	
H+		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
H+		endosome lumen	
H+		extracellular region	
H+		Golgi lumen	
H+		late endosome lumen	
H+		lysosomal lumen	
H+		mitochondrial intermembrane space	
H+		mitochondrial matrix	
H+		nuclear envelope	
H+		peroxisomal matrix	
H+		phagocytic vesicle	
H+		platelet dense tubular network lumen	
H+		synaptic vesicle	
H2O		cytosol	
H2O		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
H2O		extracellular region	
H2O		mitochondrial matrix	
H2O		nucleoplasm	
H2O		peroxisomal matrix	
H2O		plasma membrane	
H2O		stored secretory granule	
H2O2		cytosol	
H2O2		extracellular region	
H2O2		mitochondrial intermembrane space	
H2O2		peroxisomal matrix	
Halothane	HALO	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
HCO3-		cytosol	
HCO3-		extracellular region	
HCO3-		mitochondrial matrix	

name	short name	location	Notes
heme		cytosol	
heme		extracellular region	
heme		mitochondrial matrix	
heme		mitochondrial outer membrane	
heme		peroxisomal matrix	
heme		plasma membrane	
Heparan 4-sulfate	H4S		
Heparan 6-sulfate	H6S		
Heparan 4,6-disulfate	HSE		
Heparin	HPIN		
Heparan sulfate alpha-D-glucosaminide		extracellular region	
Heparan sulfate N-acetyl-alpha-D-glucosaminide		extracellular region	
Hexacosanoyl-CoA	C26:0 CoA	cytosol	http://www.hmdb.ca/metabolites/HMDB06459
Hexacosanoyl-CoA		peroxisomal matrix	http://www.hmdb.ca/metabolites/HMDB06459
hexadec-2-enal		cytosol	
hexadecanal	HXAL	cytosol	
Hexadecanol	HXOL	peroxisomal matrix	
Hexanoate	HXA	extracellular region	
Hexanoyl-CoA	HX-CoA	mitochondrial matrix	
Hippuric acid	HIPA	mitochondrial matrix	
Histamine	Hist	clathrin sculpted monoamine transport vesicle lum	
Histamine	Hist	cytosol	
Histamine	Hist	extracellular region	
His-tRNA(His)		cytosol	
His-tRNA(His)		mitochondrial matrix	
HMG CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
HNK-1 carbohydrate		plasma membrane	
Homocysteine	HCYS	cytosol	
Homogentisate	HGTA	cytosol	
Hyaluronic acid	HUA	cytosol	
Hydrogen	H2	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Hydrogen bromide	HBr	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
hydrogen iodide	HI	extracellular region	
Hydroxycoumarin	HCOU	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Hydroxymethylbilane	HMBL	cytosol	
hypoxanthine	Hyp	cytosol	
hypoxanthine	Hyp	extracellular region	
Hypoxanthine	Hyp	nucleoplasm	
iE-DAP		cytosol	
Ile-tRNA(Ile)		cytosol	
Ile-tRNA(Ile)		mitochondrial matrix	
Imipramine	IMIP	cytosol	
Imipramine	IMIP	extracellular region	
Imiquimod	IMIQ	cytosol	
Imiquimod	IMIQ	endosome membrane	
IMP	IMP	cytosol	
Indole	INDOL	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
inorganic sulfate	SO4(2-)	cytosol	
inorganic sulfate	SO4(2-)	extracellular region	
inosine	Ino	cytosol	
inosine	Ino	extracellular region	
inosine	Ino	lysosomal lumen	
inosine 5'-monophosphate	IMP	extracellular region	
Inositol	Ins	cytosol	
Inositol	Ins	extracellular region	
Iodide	I-	cytosol	
Iodide	I-	extracellular region	
Iodide	I-	transport vesicle	
Iodine	I2	extracellular region	
iron (3+)	Fe3+	cytosol	
iron (3+)	Fe3+	extracellular region	
iron (ferric)	Fe3+	cytosol	
iron (ferric)	Fe3+	endosome lumen	
iron (ferric)	Fe3+	endosome membrane	
iron (ferric)	Fe3+	extracellular region	
iron (ferric)	Fe3+	mitochondrial inner membrane	
iron (ferrous)	Fe2+	cytosol	
iron (ferrous)	Fe2+	endosome lumen	

name	short name	location	Notes
iron (ferrous)	Fe2+	extracellular region	
iron (ferrous)	Fe2+	mitochondrial inner membrane	
iron (ferrous)	Fe2+	mitochondrial matrix	
iron (ferrous)	Fe2+	nucleoplasm	
iron (oxidation state not specified)	Fe	cytosol	
isobutyryl-CoA	ISB-CoA	mitochondrial matrix	
Isocaproic aldehyde	ISCAL	cytosol	
Isocaproic aldehyde	ISCAL	mitochondrial matrix	
Isocitrate	ISCIT	cytosol	
Isocitrate	ISCIT	mitochondrial matrix	
Isocitrate	ISCIT	peroxisomal matrix	
Isoniazid	ISNZ	cytosol	
Isoprotenerol	ISPOL	extracellular region	
isovaleryl-CoA	ISV-CoA	mitochondrial matrix	
kynurenic acid	KYNA	cytosol	
kynurenic acid	KYNA	mitochondrial matrix	
L-2-Aminoadipate	2AMA	mitochondrial matrix	
L-2-Aminoadipate 6-semialdehyde	2AMAS	mitochondrial matrix	
lactose	Lac	extracellular region	
L-Alanine	L-Ala	cytosol	
L-Alanine	L-Ala	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
L-Alanine	L-Ala	extracellular region	
L-Alanine	L-Ala	lysosomal lumen	
L-Alanine	L-Ala	mitochondrial matrix	
L-Alanine	L-Ala	peroxisomal matrix	
lanosterol	LNSOL	endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
L-Arginine	L-Arg	cytosol	
L-Arginine	L-Arg	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
L-Arginine	L-Arg	extracellular region	
L-Arginine	L-Arg	lysosomal lumen	
L-Arginine	L-Arg	mitochondrial intermembrane space	
L-Arginine	L-Arg	mitochondrial matrix	
L-Asparagine	L-Asn	cytosol	
L-Asparagine	L-Asn	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
L-Asparagine	L-Asn	extracellular region	
L-Asparagine	L-Asn	lysosomal lumen	
L-Asparagine	L-Asn	mitochondrial matrix	
L-Aspartate	L-Asp	cytosol	
L-Aspartate	L-Asp	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
L-Aspartate	L-Asp	extracellular region	
L-Aspartate	L-Asp	lysosomal lumen	
L-Aspartate	L-Asp	mitochondrial matrix	
Lauroyl-CoA	LAU-CoA	mitochondrial matrix	
L-Citrulline	L-Cit	cytosol	
L-Citrulline	L-Cit	mitochondrial matrix	
L-cysteine	L-Cys	cytosol	
L-cysteine	L-Cys	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
L-cysteine	L-Cys	extracellular region	
L-cysteine	L-Cys	lysosomal lumen	
L-cysteine	L-Cys	mitochondrial matrix	
L-Cystine	L-Cyst	cytosol	
L-Cystine	L-Cyst	extracellular region	
Leukotriene A4	LTA4	cytosol	
Leukotriene B4	LTB4	cytosol	
Leukotriene B4	LTB4	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Leukotriene B4	LTB4	extracellular region	
Leukotriene C4	LTC4	cytosol	
Leukotriene C4	LTC4	extracellular region	
Leukotriene D4	LTD4	extracellular region	
Leukotriene E4	LTE4	extracellular region	
Leu-tRNA(Leu)		cytosol	
Leu-tRNA(Leu)		mitochondrial matrix	
L-Glutamate	L-Glu	clathrin sculpted glutamate transport vesicle lume	
L-Glutamate	L-Glu	cytosol	
L-Glutamate	L-Glu	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
L-Glutamate	L-Glu	extracellular region	
L-Glutamate	L-Glu	lysosomal lumen	
L-Glutamate	L-Glu	mitochondrial matrix	

name	short name	location	Notes
L-Glutamate	L-Glu	synaptic vesicle	
L-Glutamate 5-semialdehyde	L-Glu5S	mitochondrial matrix	
L-Glutamine	L-Gln	cytosol	
L-Glutamine	L-Gln	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
L-Glutamine	L-Gln	extracellular region	
L-Glutamine	L-Gln	lysosomal lumen	
L-Glutamine	L-Gln	mitochondrial matrix	
L-glycine	Gly	cytosol	
L-Histidine	L-His	cytosol	
L-Histidine	L-His	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
L-Histidine	L-His	extracellular region	
L-Histidine	L-His	lysosomal lumen	
L-Histidine	L-His	mitochondrial matrix	
Li+	Li+	cytosol	
Li+	Li+	extracellular region	
lignoceric acid	LGCA	cytosol	
lignoceric acid	LGCA	extracellular region	
limit dextrans		extracellular region	
linoleic acid	LINA	cytosol	
linoleic acid	LINA	extracellular region	
linoleic acid	LINA	nucleoplasm	
linoleoyl-CoA	LIN-CoA	mitochondrial matrix	
Lipoamide	LIPAM	mitochondrial matrix	
Lipoate	LIPA	cytosol	
Lipoate	LIPA	extracellular region	
Lipoxin A4	LXA4	extracellular region	
L-Isoleucine	L-Ile	cytosol	
L-Isoleucine	L-Ile	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
L-Isoleucine	L-Ile	extracellular region	
L-Isoleucine	L-Ile	lysosomal lumen	
L-Isoleucine	L-Ile	mitochondrial matrix	
lithoCHOLate	LCHA	cytosol	
lithoCHOLate sulfate	LCHAS	cytosol	
LithoCHOLic acid	LCHA	extracellular region	
L-Kynurenine	L-KYN	cytosol	
L-Kynurenine	L-KYN	mitochondrial matrix	
L-Leucine	L-Leu	cytosol	
L-Leucine	L-Leu	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
L-Leucine	L-Leu	extracellular region	
L-Leucine	L-Leu	lysosomal lumen	
L-Leucine	L-Leu	mitochondrial matrix	
L-Lysine	L-Lys	cytosol	
L-Lysine	L-Lys	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
L-Lysine	L-Lys	extracellular region	
L-Lysine	L-Lys	lysosomal lumen	
L-Lysine	L-Lys	mitochondrial matrix	
L-Methionine	L-Met	cytosol	
L-Methionine	L-Met	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
L-Methionine	L-Met	extracellular region	
L-Methionine	L-Met	lysosomal lumen	
L-Methionine	L-Met	mitochondrial matrix	
L-methylmalonyl-CoA	L-MM-CoA	mitochondrial matrix	
long-chain fatty acids	LCFA	cytosol	
long-chain fatty acids	LCFA	extracellular region	
long-chain fatty acids	LCFA	peroxisomal matrix	
Loperamide	LPAM	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
L-Ornithine	L-Orn	cytosol	
L-Ornithine	L-Orn	extracellular region	
L-Ornithine	L-Orn	mitochondrial intermembrane space	
L-Ornithine	L-Orn	mitochondrial matrix	
LPA		extracellular region	
L-Palmitoylcarnitine		mitochondrial intermembrane space	
L-Palmitoylcarnitine		mitochondrial matrix	
L-Phenylalanine	L-Phe	cytosol	
L-Phenylalanine	L-Phe	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
L-Phenylalanine	L-Phe	extracellular region	
L-Phenylalanine	L-Phe	lysosomal lumen	
L-Phenylalanine	L-Phe	mitochondrial matrix	

name	short name	location	Notes
L-Proline	L-Pro	cytosol	
L-Proline	L-Pro	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
L-Proline	L-Pro	extracellular region	
L-Proline	L-Pro	lysosomal lumen	
L-Proline	L-Pro	mitochondrial matrix	
L-serine	L-Ser	cytosol	
L-serine	L-Ser	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
L-serine	L-Ser	extracellular region	
L-serine	L-Ser	lysosomal lumen	
L-serine	L-Ser	mitochondrial matrix	
L-Threonine	L-Thr	cytosol	
L-Threonine	L-Thr	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
L-Threonine	L-Thr	extracellular region	
L-Threonine	L-Thr	lysosomal lumen	
L-Threonine	L-Thr	mitochondrial matrix	
L-Tryptophan	L-Trp	cytosol	
L-Tryptophan	L-Trp	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
L-Tryptophan	L-Trp	extracellular region	
L-Tryptophan	L-Trp	lysosomal lumen	
L-Tryptophan	L-Trp	mitochondrial matrix	
L-Tyrosine	L-Tyr	cytosol	
L-Tyrosine	L-Tyr	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
L-Tyrosine	L-Tyr	extracellular region	
L-Tyrosine	L-Tyr	lysosomal lumen	
L-Tyrosine	L-Tyr	mitochondrial matrix	
L-Valine	L-Val	cytosol	
L-Valine	L-Val	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
L-Valine	L-Val	extracellular region	
L-Valine	L-Val	lysosomal lumen	
L-Valine	L-Val	mitochondrial matrix	
Lys-tRNA(Lys)		cytosol	
Lys-tRNA(Lys)		mitochondrial matrix	
Magnesium	Mg2+	cytosol	
Magnesium	Mg2+	endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
Magnesium	Mg2+	extracellular region	
Magnesium	Mg2+	Golgi membrane	
Magnesium	Mg2+	peroxisomal matrix	
Magnesium	Mg2+	plasma membrane	
Magnesium	Mg2+	platelet dense granule lumen	
Malonyl-CoA		cytosol	
maltose	Mal	cytosol	
maltose	Mat	extracellular region	
maltotriose		extracellular region	
Manganese	Mn2+	cytosol	
Manganese	Mn2+	extracellular region	
MDP	MDP	cytosol	
Melatonin	MLT	cytosol	
Melatonin	MLT	extracellular region	
Metformin	MTF	cytosol	
Metformin	MTF	extracellular region	
methacrylyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
Methimazole	MTZ	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Methimazole S-oxide	MTZ-SOX	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Met-tRNA(Met)		cytosol	
Met-tRNA(Met)		mitochondrial matrix	
Mevalonate	MVA	cytosol	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mevalonate
Mevalonate-5-phosphate	MVA5P	cytosol	
Mevalonate-5-pyrophosphate	MVA5PP	cytosol	
Mg++	Mg2+	mitochondrial matrix	
Mn2+	Mn2+	mitochondrial matrix	
Mn2+	Mn2+	phagocytic vesicle	
MoCo	MoCo	cytosol	
molybdate(2-)	MoO4(2-)	cytosol	
Molybdopterin	MPT	cytosol	
Molybdopterin	MPT	cytosol	
Monoiodotyrosine	MIT	extracellular region	
mycothiol	MSH	cytosol	
mycothione	MSSM	cytosol	

name	short name	location	Notes
Myristic acid	MYS A	cytosol	
Myristic acid	MYS A	extracellular region	
myristoyl-CoA	MYS-CoA	cytosol	
myristoyl-CoA	MYS-CoA	mitochondrial matrix	
N-(L-Arginino)succinate		cytosol	
N,N'-diacetylchitobiosyl(diphosphodoli)CHOL	DCDPDOL	integral to cytosolic side of endoplasmic reticulum	
N-1-methylnicotinamide	MNA	cytosol	
N-1-methylnicotinamide	MNA	extracellular region	
N4-acetylsulfanilamide		cytosol	
N6,N6,N6-Trimethyl-L-lysine		mitochondrial matrix	
N-acetyl-5-hydroxytryptamine	Ac5HT	cytosol	
N-Acetylbenzoquinoneimine	NABQI	cytosol	
N-Acetylbenzoquinoneimine	NABQI	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
N-Acetyl-D-glucosamine 1-phosphate	AcGlcN1P	cytosol	
N-Acetyl-D-glucosamine 6-phosphate	AcGlcN6P	cytosol	
N-acetyl-D-glucosaminyl-diphosphodoliCHOL		integral to cytosolic side of endoplasmic reticulum	
N-acetylisoniazid	NACISNZ	cytosol	
N-Acetyl-L-glutamate	NacGlu	mitochondrial matrix	
N-acetyl-p-aminobenzoate	NacPAB	cytosol	
N-acetyl-p-aminosalicylate	NacPAS	cytosol	
N-acetylspermidine	NASPM	cytosol	
N-acetylspermidine	NASPM	peroxisomal matrix	
N-acetylspermine	NASPN	cytosol	
N-acetylspermine	NASPN	peroxisomal matrix	
NAD+		cytosol	
NAD+		mitochondrial matrix	
NAD+		peroxisomal matrix	
NADH		cytosol	
NADH		mitochondrial matrix	
NADH		peroxisomal matrix	
NADP+		cytosol	
NADP+		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
NADP+		extracellular region	
NADP+		mitochondrial matrix	
NADP+		nuclear envelope	
NADP+		peroxisomal matrix	
NADPH		cytosol	
NADPH		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
NADPH		extracellular region	
NADPH		mitochondrial matrix	
NADPH		nuclear envelope	
NADPH		peroxisomal matrix	
N-arachidonyl glycine	NAGLY	extracellular region	
N-carbamoyl-L-aspartate		cytosol	
N-demethylated loperamide		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
NECML	NECML	extracellular region	
N-epsilon-(1-(1-carboxy)ethyl)lysine		extracellular region	
N-ethylsuccinimide	NETSU	cytosol	
N-ethylsuccinimide-mercapturic acid		cytosol	
N-ethylsuccinimide-mycothioli conjugate		cytosol	
N-Formimino-L-glutamate		cytosol	
N-Formyl-GAR	N-Formyl-GAR	cytosol	
N-glycoprotein	NGP	Golgi lumen	
NH3		cytosol	
NH3		nucleoplasm	
NH4+		cytosol	
NH4+		extracellular region	
NH4+		mitochondrial matrix	
NH4+		peroxisomal matrix	
N-hydroxy-2-acetylaminofluorene	NH2AAF	cytosol	
N-Hydroxy-4-aminobiphenyl	NHABP	cytosol	
N-Hydroxy-4-aminobiphenyl		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
N-hydroxy-4-aminobiphenyl O-acetylated conjug		cytosol	
N-hydroxy-4-aminobiphenyl O-glucuronide		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
N-hydroxy-4-aminobiphenyl O-sulfate		cytosol	
Niacin	VitB3	extracellular region	
Nicotinamide	NAM	cytosol	
Nicotinate	NCA	cytosol	

name	short name	location	Notes
Nicotinate D-ribonucleotide		cytosol	
Nicotinate D-ribonucleotide		nucleoplasm	
Nicotine		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Nicotine N-glucuronide		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Nitrate	HNO3	cytosol	
Nitrate	HNO3	transport vesicle	
Nitric oxide	NO	cytosol	
N-methylpyridinium ion	MP+	cytosol	
n-Oleylethanolamide		extracellular region	
Noradrenaline	NAd	clathrin sculpted glutamate transport vesicle lumen	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Norepinephrine
Noradrenaline	NAd	clathrin sculpted monoamine transport vesicle lumen	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Norepinephrine
Noradrenaline	NAd	cytosol	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Norepinephrine
Noradrenaline	NAd	extracellular region	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Norepinephrine
Noradrenaline	NAd	stored secretory granule	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Norepinephrine
O-acetylCHOLine	AcCho	clathrin sculpted acetylCHOLine transport vesicle lumen	
O-acetylCHOLine	AcCho	cytosol	
O-acetylCHOLine	AcCho	extracellular region	
O-acetylCHOLine	AcCho	plasma membrane	
O-acetylserine	AcSer	cytosol	
Octanoic acid		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Octanoyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
Octanoyl-CoA		peroxisomal matrix	
O-hexadecylglycerone phosphate		cytosol	
O-hexadecylglycerone phosphate		peroxisomal matrix	
Oleic acid	OLEA	cytosol	
Oleic acid	OLEA	extracellular region	
omega-Hydroxydodecanoic acid		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Omeprazole	Losec	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
O-phospho-L-serine		cytosol	
orotate		cytosol	
orotidine 5'-monophosphate		cytosol	
Orthophosphate	Pi	cytosol	
Orthophosphate	Pi	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Orthophosphate	Pi	extracellular region	
Orthophosphate	Pi	mitochondrial matrix	
Orthophosphate	Pi	nucleoplasm	
Orthophosphate	Pi	plasma membrane	
Orthophosphate	Pi	platelet dense granule lumen	
Oxalate	OX	peroxisomal matrix	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Oxalate
Oxaliplatin		cytosol	
Oxaliplatin		extracellular region	
Oxaloacetate	OA	cytosol	
Oxaloacetate	OA	mitochondrial matrix	
oxidized glutathione	OGSH	cytosol	
Oxindole		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Oxygen	O2	cytosol	
Oxygen	O2	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Oxygen	O2	extracellular region	
Oxygen	O2	mitochondrial intermembrane space	
Oxygen	O2	mitochondrial matrix	
Oxygen	O2	nucleoplasm	
Oxygen	O2	peroxisomal matrix	
Oxygen	O2	stored secretory granule	
Paclitaxel	PTXL	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
PAF	PAF	extracellular region	
Palmitate	Palm	cytosol	
Palmitate	Palm	extracellular region	
Palmitate	Palm	peroxisomal matrix	
Palmitate	Palm	plasma membrane	
palmitic acid	Palm	nucleoplasm	
Palmitoleic acid	Pmoa	extracellular region	
palmitoyl-CoA	PalmCoA	cytosol	
palmitoyl-CoA	PalmCoA	mitochondrial matrix	
palmitoyl-CoA	PalmCoA	peroxisomal matrix	
p-aminohippurate	pAHP	cytosol	
p-aminohippurate	pAHP	extracellular region	
Pantothenate	PanK	cytosol	
Pantothenate	PanK	extracellular region	

name	short name	location	Notes
PAP [adenosine 3',5'-bimonophosphate]	PAP	cytosol	
PAP		Golgi lumen	
PAPS 3'-phospho-5'-adenylyl sulfate]	PAPS	cytosol	
PAPS	PAPS	Golgi lumen	
Paraxanthine		cytosol	
Paraxanthine		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Pb ⁺⁺	Pb ²⁺	cytosol	
Pb ⁺⁺	Pb ²⁺	mitochondrial matrix	
Pentadecanoic acid		extracellular region	
Pentanoate	Valerate	extracellular region	
Phenol	PhOH	cytosol	
Phenol	PhOH	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Phenyl sulfate		cytosol	
Phenylacetaldehyde		cytosol	
phenylacetate		mitochondrial matrix	
phenylacetyl glutamine		mitochondrial matrix	
phenylacetyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
Phenytoin		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Phe-tRNA(Phe)		cytosol	
Phe-tRNA(Phe)		mitochondrial matrix	
Phosphatidyl CHOLine	PC	endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
Phosphatidyl CHOLine	PC	Golgi membrane	
Phosphatidyl CHOLine	PC	plasma membrane	
phosphatidylCHOLines	PCs	extracellular region	
phosphatidylethanolamine	PE	external side of plasma membrane	
phosphatidylethanolamine	PE	internal side of plasma membrane	
Phosphatidylinositol-3,4,5-trisphosphate	PI(3,4,5)P3	endocytic vesicle membrane	
Phosphatidylinositol-3,4,5-trisphosphate	PI(3,4,5)P3	endosome membrane	
Phosphatidylinositol-3,4,5-trisphosphate	PI(3,4,5)P3	plasma membrane	
Phosphatidylinositol-4,5-bisphosphate	PI(4,5)P2	plasma membrane	
phosphatidylserine	PS	external side of plasma membrane	
phosphatidylserine	PS	internal side of plasma membrane	
PhosphoCHOLine	PCho	plasma membrane	
Phosphocreatine	Pcr	cytosol	
Phosphoenolpyruvate	PEP	cytosol	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/chebi/searchId.do?chebiId=CHEBI:18021
Phosphoenolpyruvate	PEP	mitochondrial matrix	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/chebi/searchId.do?chebiId=CHEBI:18021
phosphoethanolamine	PETA	cytosol	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/chebi/searchId.do?chebiId=CHEBI:17553
phospholipids	PL	clathrin-coated endocytic vesicle membrane	
phospholipids		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
phospholipids		endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
phospholipids		endosome lumen	
phospholipids		endosome membrane	
phospholipids		extracellular region	
phospholipids		plasma membrane	
phospholipids		transport vesicle membrane	
Phospho-pantothenate		cytosol	
Phosphopantothenoylcysteine		cytosol	
Phytanate		peroxisomal matrix	
Phytanoyl-CoA		peroxisomal matrix	
phytoceramide		endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
phytosphingosine		endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
phytosterols		cytosol	
phytosterols		extracellular region	
PI(3,4)P2		plasma membrane	
Pioglitazone	Actos	nucleoplasm	
p-nitrophenol		cytosol	
p-nitrophenol sulfate		cytosol	
Porphobilinogen		cytosol	
Potassium	K ⁺	cytosol	
Potassium	K ⁺	extracellular region	
PQQ [pyrroloquinoline quinone]	PQQ	stored secretory granule	
Precursor Z		cytosol	
pregn-5-ene-3,20-dione		cytosol	
pregn-5-ene-3,20-dione-17-ol		cytosol	
pregnenolone	PREG	cytosol	
Pregnenolone	PREG	cytosol	
Pregnenolone	PREG	mitochondrial matrix	
pregnenolone sulfate	PREGS	cytosol	

name	short name	location	Notes
presqualene diphosphate	PSQP	cytosol	
Pristanat		peroxisomal matrix	
Pristanic acid		peroxisomal matrix	
Procainamide		cytosol	
Procainamide		extracellular region	
Progesterone	P4	cytosol	
Propionate	EtCOO- or C2H5COO-	cytosol	
Propionate	EtCOO- or C2H5COO-	extracellular region	
propionyl CoA		peroxisomal matrix	
Propionylcarnitine		peroxisomal matrix	
propionyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
Prostacyclin	PGI2	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Prostacyclin	PGI2	extracellular region	
Prostaglandin D2	PGD2	cytosol	
Prostaglandin D2	PGD2	extracellular region	
Prostaglandin E1	PGE1	cytosol	
Prostaglandin E1	PGE1	extracellular region	
Prostaglandin E2	PGE2	cytosol	
Prostaglandin E2	PGE2	extracellular region	
Prostaglandin F2alpha	PGF2a	cytosol	
Prostaglandin F2alpha	PGF2a	extracellular region	
Prostaglandin F2-alpha	PGF2a	extracellular region	
Prostaglandin G2	PGG2	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Prostaglandin H2	PGH2	cytosol	
Prostaglandin H2	PGH2	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Protoporphyrin IX		mitochondrial intermembrane space	
Protoporphyrin IX		mitochondrial matrix	
Protoporphyrinogen IX		mitochondrial intermembrane space	
Pro-tRNA(Pro)		cytosol	
Pro-tRNA(Pro)		mitochondrial matrix	
PRPP	PRPP	cytosol	
Putrescine		cytosol	
Putrescine		peroxisomal matrix	
Pyridine	PY	cytosol	
Pyridoxal	PXL	cytosol	
Pyridoxal phosphate	PXLP	cytosol	
Pyridoxamine	PXA	cytosol	
Pyridoxamine phosphate	PXAP	cytosol	
Pyridoxine	PDX	cytosol	
Pyridoxine phosphate	PDXP	cytosol	
pyrophosphate	PPI	cytosol	
pyrophosphate	PPI	extracellular region	
pyrophosphate	PPI	mitochondrial matrix	
pyrophosphate	PPI	nucleoplasm	
Pyrophosphate	PPI	peroxisomal matrix	
pyrophosphate	PPI	platelet dense granule lumen	
Pyruvate	PYR	cytosol	
Pyruvate	PYR	extracellular region	
Pyruvate	PYR	mitochondrial matrix	
Pyruvate	PYR	peroxisomal matrix	
q-dihydrobiopterin	qDHB	cytosol	
Quinidine	QND	cytosol	
Quinidine	QND	extracellular region	
quinine	QN	cytosol	
quinine	QN	extracellular region	
Quinolate	QUIN	cytosol	
R-848		cytosol	
R-848		endosome membrane	
Retinyl palmitate	RPALM	cytosol	
Retinyl palmitate	RPALM	extracellular region	
Riboflavin	RIB	cytosol	
ROS		cytosol	
Rosiglitazone	RGZ	extracellular region	
Rosiglitazone	RGZ	nucleoplasm	
S-2-(hydroxyethyl)-glutathione		endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Saccharin	SACC	extracellular region	
saccharopine	SACN	mitochondrial matrix	
S-adenosylhomocysteine	SAH	cytosol	

name	short name	location	Notes
S-adenosylhomocysteine	SAH	nucleoplasm	
S-Adenosylmethionine	SAMA	cytosol	
S-adenosylmethionine	SAM	cytosol	
S-adenosylmethionine	SAM	nucleoplasm	
SAICAR	SAICAR	cytosol	
Salicylate	SAL	mitochondrial matrix	
Salicylate-CoA thioester		mitochondrial matrix	
Salicyluric acid	SUA	mitochondrial matrix	
Sedoheptulose 7-phosphate		cytosol	
semidehydroascorbate	SHAS	cytosol	
Serotonin	5HT	clathrin sculpted monoamine transport vesicle lum	
Serotonin	5HT	extracellular region	
Serotonin	5HT	platelet dense granule lumen	
Ser-tRNA(Ser)		cytosol	
Ser-tRNA(Ser)		mitochondrial matrix	
Shikimate	SKM	cytosol	
Shikimate 3-phosphate	SKMP	cytosol	
sialic acid	SA	cytosol	
sialic acid		endocytic vesicle membrane	
Sialic acid		Golgi membrane	
sialic acid		lysosomal lumen	
sialic acid		plasma membrane	
Silicon dioxide	SiO2	cytosol	
siroheme	SRHM	cytosol	
S-methyl-2-mercaptoethanol	MMETOH	cytosol	
S-methylthio adenosine	MTAD	cytosol	
sodium ion	Na+	cytosol	
Sodium ion	Na+	early endosome lumen	
sodium ion	Na+	extracellular region	
sodium ion	Na+	Golgi lumen	
Sodium ion	Na+	late endosome lumen	
Spermidine	SPM	cytosol	
Spermidine	SPM	extracellular region	
Spermidine	SPM	peroxisomal matrix	
Spermine	SPN	cytosol	
Spermine	SPN	extracellular region	
Spermine	SPN	peroxisomal matrix	
sphinganine	SPA	cytosol	
sphinganine	SPA	endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
sphinganine 1-phosphate	SPAP	cytosol	
Sphingomyelin	SPHM	cytosol	
Sphingomyelin	SPHM	extracellular region	
sphingomyelins	SPHM	Golgi membrane	
sphingomyelins	SPHM	plasma membrane	
sphingosine	SPG	cytosol	
sphingosine	SPG	endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
sphingosine	SPG	extracellular region	
sphingosine	SPG	Golgi membrane	
Sphingosine-1-phosphate	S1P	cytosol	
Sphingosine-1-phosphate	S1P	extracellular region	
Squalene	SQNE	cytosol	
Squalene 2,3 epoxide	SQOX	cytosol	
stearate	STEA	cytosol	
Stearate	STEA	extracellular region	
stearic acid	STEA	extracellular region	
stearoyl-CoA	ST-CoA	cytosol	
Succinate	SUCCA	cytosol	
Succinate	SUCCA	extracellular region	
Succinate	SUCCA	mitochondrial matrix	
Succinate	SUCCA	nucleoplasm	
Succinate	SUCCA	peroxisomal matrix	
succinate semialdehyde	SUCCSA	mitochondrial matrix	
Succinyl-CoA	SUCC-CoA	mitochondrial matrix	
sucrose	Suc	extracellular region	
Sugar phosphate	SUGP	nucleoplasm	
Sulfanilamide	SAMD	cytosol	
sulfate	SO4(2-)	plasma membrane	
sulfide	S(2-)	cytosol	

name	short name	location	Notes
sulfide (2-)	S(2-)		
sulfite	H2SO3	cytosol	
sulfur	S	cytosol	
sulfurated MoCo		cytosol	
Tamoxifen	TAM	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Tamoxifen N-glucuronide	TAMNG	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Tamoxifen N-oxide	TAMO	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
taurine	TAU	cytosol	
taurine		extracellular region	
taurine		peroxisomal matrix	
taurochenodeoxyCHOLate	TCCA	cytosol	
taurochenodeoxyCHOLate		extracellular region	
taurochenodeoxyCHOLate		peroxisomal matrix	
tauroCHOLate	TCA	cytosol	
tauroCHOLate		extracellular region	
tauroCHOLate		peroxisomal matrix	
tauroithoCHOLate	TLCA	cytosol	
tauroithoCHOLate sulfate	TLCAS	cytosol	
tauroithoCHOLate sulfate		extracellular region	
Testosterone	TES	cytosol	
Testosterone	TES	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
tetracosanoyl-CoA		cytosol	
tetracosanoyl-CoA		peroxisomal matrix	
TetraHCA		cytosol	
TetraHCA		mitochondrial matrix	
Tetrahydrobiopterin	THBP	cytosol	
Tetrahydrofolate	THF	cytosol	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Folic_acid
Tetrahydrofolate	THF	mitochondrial matrix	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Folic_acid
Tetramethylammonium	TMAM	cytosol	
Tetramethylammonium	TMAM	extracellular region	
THCA		cytosol	
THCA		mitochondrial matrix	
THF-polyglutamate		cytosol	
THF-polyglutamate		mitochondrial matrix	
Thiamin	THMN	cytosol	
Thiamin	THMN	extracellular region	
Thiamin diphosphate	TDP	cytosol	
Thiamin diphosphate	TDP	mitochondrial matrix	
Thiamin pyrophosphate	TPP	peroxisomal matrix	
Thiamin triphosphate	TTP	cytosol	
Thromboxane A2	TXA2	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Thromboxane A2	TXA2	extracellular region	
Thr-tRNA(Thr)		cytosol	
Thr-tRNA(Thr)		mitochondrial matrix	
thymidine	Thy-dRib	cytosol	
thymidine	Thy-dRib	extracellular region	
thymidine	Thy-dRib	lysosomal lumen	
thymidine	Thy-dRib	mitochondrial matrix	
thymidine 5'-diphosphate	TDP	cytosol	
thymidine 5'-diphosphate	TDP	mitochondrial matrix	
thymidine 5'-monophosphate	TMP	extracellular region	
thymidine 5'-monophosphate	TMP	mitochondrial matrix	
thymine	Thy	cytosol	
thymine	Thy	extracellular region	
thymine	Thy	nucleoplasm	
Thyroxine	T4	cytosol	
Thyroxine	T4	extracellular region	
tiglyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
TMP thymidine 5'-monophosphate	TMP	cytosol	
Tolbutamide	TBM	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
torcetrapib		extracellular region	
trans,cis-Lauro-2,6-dienoyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
trans-2,3-dehydrohexacosanoyl-CoA		peroxisomal matrix	
trans-2,3-dehydropristanoyl-CoA		peroxisomal matrix	
trans-Dec-2-enoyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
trans-Hex-2-enoyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
trans-Hexadec-2-enoyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
trans-Oct-2-enoyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	

name	short name	location	Notes
trans-octadec-2-enoyl-CoA		cytosol	
trans-Tetradec-2-enoyl-CoA		mitochondrial matrix	
triacylglycerol	TAG	cytosol	
triacylglycerols	TAGs	clathrin-coated endocytic vesicle membrane	
triacylglycerols	TAGs	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
triacylglycerols	TAGs	endoplasmic reticulum membrane	
triacylglycerols	TAGs	endosome lumen	
triacylglycerols	TAGs	endosome membrane	
triacylglycerols	TAGs	extracellular region	
triacylglycerols	TAGs	plasma membrane	
Trifluoroacetylchloride	TFAC	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Trimethylamine N-oxide	TMAO	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Trimethylamine	TMA	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
tRNA(Ala)		cytosol	
tRNA(Ala)		mitochondrial matrix	
tRNA(Arg)		cytosol	
tRNA(Arg)		mitochondrial matrix	
tRNA(Asn)		cytosol	
tRNA(Asn)		mitochondrial matrix	
tRNA(Asp)		cytosol	
tRNA(Asp)		mitochondrial matrix	
tRNA(Cys)		cytosol	
tRNA(Cys)		mitochondrial matrix	
tRNA(Gln)		cytosol	
tRNA(Gln)		mitochondrial matrix	
tRNA(Glu)		cytosol	
tRNA(Glu)		mitochondrial matrix	
tRNA(Gly)		cytosol	
tRNA(Gly)		mitochondrial matrix	
tRNA(His)		cytosol	
tRNA(His)		mitochondrial matrix	
tRNA(Ile)		cytosol	
tRNA(Ile)		mitochondrial matrix	
tRNA(Leu)		cytosol	
tRNA(Leu)		mitochondrial matrix	
tRNA(Lys)		cytosol	
tRNA(Lys)		mitochondrial matrix	
tRNA(Met)		cytosol	
tRNA(Met)		mitochondrial matrix	
tRNA(Phe)		cytosol	
tRNA(Phe)		mitochondrial matrix	
tRNA(Pro)		cytosol	
tRNA(Pro)		mitochondrial matrix	
tRNA(Ser)		cytosol	
tRNA(Ser)		mitochondrial matrix	
tRNA(Thr)		cytosol	
tRNA(Thr)		mitochondrial matrix	
tRNA(Trp)		cytosol	
tRNA(Trp)		mitochondrial matrix	
tRNA(Tyr)		cytosol	
tRNA(Tyr)		mitochondrial matrix	
tRNA(Val)		cytosol	
tRNA(Val)		mitochondrial matrix	
Trp-tRNA(Trp)		cytosol	
Trp-tRNA(Trp)		mitochondrial matrix	
TTP thymidine 5'-triphosphate	TTP	cytosol	
TTP thymidine 5'-triphosphate	TTP	mitochondrial matrix	
Tyramine	TYR	cytosol	
Tyr-tRNA(Tyr)		cytosol	
Tyr-tRNA(Tyr)		mitochondrial matrix	
ubiquinol	QH2	mitochondrial inner membrane	
ubiquinone	CoQ	mitochondrial inner membrane	
UDP	UDP	extracellular region	
UDP	UDP	Golgi lumen	
UDP-D-galactose	UDP-Gal	cytosol	
UDP-D-galactose	UDP-Gal	Golgi lumen	
UDP-GalNAc		cytosol	
UDP-GalNAc		Golgi lumen	

name	short name	location	Notes
UDP-GlcNAc		cytosol	
UDP-GlcNAc		Golgi lumen	
UDP-glucose	UDP-Glc	cytosol	
UDP-glucose	UDP-Glc	extracellular region	
UDP-glucose	UDP-Glc	Golgi lumen	
UDP-glucuronic acid	UDP-GCU	cytosol	http://www.hmdb.ca/metabolites/HMDB00127
UDP-glucuronic acid	UDP-GCU	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	http://www.hmdb.ca/metabolites/HMDB00127
UDP-N-acetyl-D-glucosamine	UDP-AcGlcN	cytosol	
UDP-N-acetyl-D-glucosamine	UDP-AcGlcN	Golgi lumen	
UDP-xylose	UDP-Xyl	cytosol	
UDP-xylose	UDP-Xyl	Golgi lumen	
UMP	UMP	cytosol	
UMP	UMP	Golgi lumen	
UMP	UMP	nucleoplasm	
uracil	Ura	cytosol	
uracil	Ura	extracellular region	
Uracil	Ura	nucleoplasm	
Urate		cytosol	
Urate		extracellular region	
Urea		cytosol	
Urea		extracellular region	
Urea		mitochondrial matrix	
uridine	Ura-Rib	cytosol	
uridine	Ura-Rib	extracellular region	
uridine	Ura-Rib	lysosomal lumen	
uridine	Ura-Rib	mitochondrial matrix	
uridine 2'-monophosphate	U2MP	cytosol	
uridine 2'-monophosphate	U2MP	mitochondrial matrix	
uridine 3'-monophosphate	U3MP	cytosol	
uridine 3'-monophosphate	U3MP	mitochondrial matrix	
uridine 5'-diphosphate	U5DP	cytosol	
uridine 5'-diphosphate	U5DP	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
uridine 5'-diphosphate	U5DP	mitochondrial matrix	
uridine 5'-diphosphate	U5DP	nucleoplasm	
uridine 5'-monophosphate	U5MP	extracellular region	
uridine 5'-monophosphate	U5MP	mitochondrial matrix	
Urocanate	UCA	cytosol	
Uroporphyrinogen I	URO1	cytosol	
Uroporphyrinogen III	URO3	cytosol	
UTP uridine 5'-triphosphate	UTP	cytosol	
UTP uridine 5'-triphosphate	UTP	extracellular region	
UTP uridine 5'-triphosphate	UTP	mitochondrial matrix	
UTP uridine 5'-triphosphate	UTP	nucleoplasm	
Val-tRNA(Val)		cytosol	
Val-tRNA(Val)		mitochondrial matrix	
Vinyl chloride	VC	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Vitamin D3	VD3	cytosol	
Vitamin D3	VD3	extracellular region	
vitamin K epoxide	VKO	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
vitamin K hydroquinone	VKHQ	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Xanthine	XAN	cytosol	
XMP	XMP	cytosol	
Zinc 2+ [zinc (2+)]	Zn2+	Golgi lumen	
Zinc 2+	Zn2+	Golgi membrane	
Zinc 2+	Zn2+	stored secretory granule	
Zn++	Zn2+	cytosol	
Zn++	Zn2+	endocytic vesicle membrane	
Zn++	Zn2+	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	
Zn++	Zn2+	endosome lumen	
Zn++	Zn2+	extracellular region	
Zn++	Zn2+	nucleoplasm	
Zn++	Zn2+	plasma membrane	
Zn++	Zn2+	synaptic vesicle	
Zn2+		mitochondrial matrix	
Zn2+		phagocytic vesicle	
zymosterol	ZSOL	endoplasmic reticulum membrane	

Appendix C7: Preceding Event tool

Review of the Curator Tool PrecedingEvent Suggestion Feature

Event Hierarchy

- Show in All
- IκBα variant leads to EDA-ID
 - Incorporation Of Extended And Processed Telomeres
 - Initial resection of double-strand break ends
 - Interaction of MEKK1 with TRAF6
 - Joining of adjacent Okazaki fragments of the C...
 - K63 polyubiquitinated RIP2 associates with the C...
 - KAT5 acetylates ATM at DNA DSBs
 - KAT5 acetylates ATM at shortened telomeres
 - KDM4A,B bind H4K20Me2
 - KPNA2 translocates NBN to the nucleus
 - Ligand binds to TLR10

Complex Hierarchy

Entity List

Overview Search Instances

of TAK1-dependent IKK and NF-κB activation , IκBβ deficiency causes SCID, IκBα variant leads to EDA-ID, and IKKβ deficiency causes anhidrotic ectodermal dysplasia with immunodeficiency

Search by ID

- Automatic Layout
- Show Compartment in Name
- Hide Private Notes
- Tight Node Bounds
- Wrap Text into Nodes
- Update Node Features
- Update Disease Objects Color
- Update Drug Objects Color
- Hide doNotRelease Events
- Draw Pathway

Paste

Edit Properties

Infer Reaction Relationships

Export Diagram

Slide to Zoom:

Graphic Editor Property Editor

Event Hierarchy

- Show in All
- IκBα variant leads to EDA-ID
 - Incorporation Of Extended And Processed Telomeres
 - Incorporation Of Extended And Processed Telomeres
 - Initial resection of double-strand break ends
 - Interaction of MEKK1 with TRAF6
 - Interaction of MEKK1 with TRAF6
 - Joining of adjacent Okazaki fragments of the C-strand
 - K63 polyubiquitinated RIP2 associates with the NEMO
 - KAT5 acetylates ATM at DNA DSBs
 - KAT5 acetylates ATM at shortened telomeres
 - KDM4A,B bind H4K20Me2
 - KPNA2 translocates NBN to the nucleus
 - Ligand binds to TLR10

Complex Hierarchy

Entity List

Overview Search Instances

of TAK1-dependent IKK and NF-κB activation, IKKβ deficiency causes SCID, IκBα variant leads to EDA-ID, and IKKβ deficiency causes anhidrotic ectodermal dysplasia with immunodeficiency

Escape Entities

Edit entities that should be escaped for analysis:

ADP, ATP, CO2, GDP, GTP, H+, H2O, Pi

Include entity set members for analysis

Include drugs for analysis

OK Cancel

Slide to Zoom:

Event Hierarchy

Show in All

- Second phosphorylation of IRAK1 by IRAK4 bou...
- Secreted CD14 binds LPS
- TAK1 is activated
- TAK1-dependent IKK and NF- κ B activation**
 - CHUK, IKK β B and IKK γ B form IKK comple...
 - Activated TAK1 mediates phosphorylation
 - Activated TAK1 phosphorylates IKK β B
 - Ubiquitination of IKK γ B by TRAF6
 - NF κ B inhibitor binds NF κ B complex
 - Active IKK Complex phosphorylates NF- κ B
 - NF κ B complex is transported from cytosol
- Regulation of NF- κ B signaling
- TIFA oligomerization

Complex Hierarchy

Entity List

Overview Search Instances

of TAK1-dependent IKK and NF- κ B activation, IKK β B deficiency causes SCID, IkBA variant leads to EDA-ID, and IKK γ B deficiency causes anhidrotic ectodermal dysplasia with immunodeficiency

Reaction Relationship Inference

Review the following inferred relationships and check ones you want to approve:

PrecedingReaction	FollowingReaction	SharedEntity	Action	Reject Reason
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Active IKK Complex phosphorylates NF- κ B inhibi...	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NF κ B inhibitor binds NF κ B complex	NFKB1(1-433), NFKB2(1-454):RELA [cytosol]	No Action	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CHUK, IKK β B and IKK γ B form IKK complex	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Activated TAK1 mediates phosphorylation of the IKK Complex	CHUK:IKK β B:IKK γ B [cytosol]	No Action	

OK Cancel

Slide to Zoom:

- Event Hierarchy**
- Show in: All
- Second phosphorylation of IRAK1 by IRAK4 bound to MyD88
 - Secreted CD14 binds LPS
 - TAK1 is activated
 - TAK1-dependent IKK and NF- κ B activation**
 - CHUK, IKKBK and IKBKKG form IKK complex**
 - Activated TAK1 mediates phosphorylation**
 - Activated TAK1 phosphorylates IKKBK
 - Ubiquitination of IKBKKG by TRAF6
 - NF κ B inhibitor binds NF κ B complex
 - Active IKK Complex phosphorylates NF- κ B
 - NF κ B complex is transported from cytosol to nucleus
 - Regulation of NF- κ B signaling
 - TIFA oligomerization

- Complex Hierarchy**
- Entity List**

Overview Search Instances

of TAK1-dependent IKK and NF- κ B activation, IKKBK deficiency causes SCID, IkBA variant leads to EDA-ID, and IKBKKG deficiency causes anhidrotic ectodermal dysplasia with immunodeficiency

Reaction Relationship Inference

Review the following inferred relationships and check ones you want to approve:

Preceding Reaction	Following Reaction	Shared Entity	Action	Reject Reason
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Active IKK Complex phosphorylates NF- κ B inhibitor	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NF κ B inhibitor binds NF κ B complex	NFKB1(1-433), NFKB2(1-454):RELA [cytosol]	No_Action	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CHUK, IKKBK and IKBKKG form IKK complex	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Activated TAK1 mediates phosphorylation of the IKK Complex	CHUK:IKKBK:IKBKKG [cytosol]	Approve	

OK Cancel

Slide to Zoom:

Event Hierarchy

- Show in All
- ↳ SENP1,2,5 proteolytically process SUMO1
 - ↳ SIRT6 deacetylates RBBP8
 - ↳ Second phosphorylation of IRAK1 by IRAK4 bound to ...
 - ↳ Second phosphorylation of IRAK1 by IRAK4 bound to ...
 - ↳ Secreted CD14 binds LPS
 - ↳ TAK1 is activated
 - ↳ TAK1-dependent IKK and NF-κB activation
 - CHUK, IKKB and IKBK form IKK complex
 - Activated TAK1 mediates phosphorylation of the ...
 - Activated TAK1 phosphorylates IKBK
 - Ubiquitination of IKBK by TRAF6
 - NFκB inhibitor binds NFκB complex
 - Active IKK Complex phosphorylates NF-κB inhibi

Complex Hierarchy
Entity List

of TAK1-dependent IKK and NF-κB activation .IKKB deficiency causes SCID, IkBa variant leads to EDA-ID, and IKKB deficiency causes anhidrotic ectodermal dysplasia with immunodef

Reaction Relationship Inference

Review the following inferred relationships and check ones you want to approve:

PrecedingReaction	FollowingReaction	SharedEntity	Approve	Reject Reason
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Active IKK Complex phosphorylates NF-κB inhibitor	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NFκB inhibitor binds NFκB complex	NFKB1(1-433), NFKB2(1-454):RELA [cyt...	<input type="checkbox"/> Reject	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CHUK, IKKB and IKBK form IKK complex	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Activated TAK1 mediates phosphorylation of the IKK Complex	CHUK.IKKB.IKBKG [cytosol]	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No_Action	

OK Cancel

Slide to Zoom:

of TAK1-dependent IKK and NF-κB activation, IKKB deficiency causes SCID, IkBA variant leads to EDA-ID, and IKKBG deficiency causes anhidrotic ectodermal dysplasia with immunodeficiency

- Event Hierarchy**
- Show in All
- Second phosphorylation of IRAK1 by IRAK4 bound
 - Secreted CD14 binds LPS
 - TAK1 is activated
 - TAK1-dependent IKK and NF-κB activation
 - CHUK, IKKB and IKBG form IKK complex
 - Activated TAK1 mediates phosphorylation
 - Activated TAK1 phosphorylates IKKB
 - Ubiquitination of IKBG by TRAF6
 - NFκB inhibitor binds NFκB complex
 - Active IKK Complex phosphorylates NF-κB
 - NFκB complex is transported from cytosol to nucleus
 - Regulation of NF-κB signaling
 - TIFA oligomerization

- Complex Hierarchy**
- Entity List**

Reaction Relationship Inference

Review the following inferred relationships and check ones you want to approve:

PrecedingReaction	FollowingReaction	SharedEntity	Approve	Reject	Reject Reason
Active IKK Complex phosphorylates NF-κB inhibi...	NFKB inhibitor binds NFKB complex	NFKB1(1-433), NFKB2(1-454):RELA [cytosol]	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	No_Action
CHUK, IKKB and IKBG form IKK complex	Activated TAK1 mediates phosphorylation of the IKK Complex	CHUK:IKKB:IKBG [cytosol]	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Approve

OK Cancel

Slide to Zoom:

Event Hierarchy

- Show in All
- Second phosphorylation of IRAK1 by IRAK4 bound
 - Secreted CD14 binds LPS
 - TAK1 is activated
 - TAK1-dependent IKK and NF- κ B activation
 - CHUK, IKKB and IKK β form IKK complex
 - Activated TAK1 mediates phosphorylation
 - Activated TAK1 phosphorylates IKK β
 - Ubiquitination of IKK β by TRAF6
 - NF κ B inhibitor binds NF κ B complex
 - Active IKK Complex phosphorylates NF- κ B
 - NF κ B complex is transported from cytosol to nucleus
 - Regulation of NF- κ B signaling
 - TIFA oligomerization

Complex Hierarchy

Entity List

Overview Search Instances

of TAK1-dependent IKK and NF- κ B activation, IKK β deficiency causes SCID, IKBA variant leads to EDA-ID, and IKK β deficiency causes anhidrotic ectodermal dysplasia with immunodeficiency

Reaction Relationship Inference

Review the following inferred relationships and check ones you want to approve:

Preceding Reaction	Following Reaction	SharedEntity	Action	Reject Reason
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Active IKK Complex phosphorylates NF- κ B inhibitor	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NF κ B inhibitor binds NF κ B complex	NFKB1(1-433), NFKB2(1-454):RELA [cytosol]	Reject	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Abundant Molecules
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CHUK, IKKB and IKK β form IKK complex	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Activated TAK1 mediates phosphorylation of the IKK Complex	CHUK:IKKB:IKK β [cytosol]	Approve	<input type="checkbox"/> Different Cell Type
				<input type="checkbox"/> Drug molecule
				<input type="checkbox"/> Futile Cycle
				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Incorrect Order
				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Negative relationship

Slide to Zoom:

Event Hierarchy

- Show in All
- S100A8:S100A9 binds TLR4:LY96
 - SENP1,2,5 proteolytically process SUMO1
 - SIRT6 deacetylates RBBP8
 - Second phosphorylation of IRAK1 by IRAK4 bound
 - Secreted CD14 binds LPS
 - TAK1 is activated
 - TAK1-dependent IKK and NF- κ B activation
 - CHUK, I κ B κ B and I κ B κ G form IKK complex
 - Activated TAK1 mediates phosphorylation of I κ B κ B
 - Activated TAK1 phosphorylates I κ B κ B
 - Ubiquitination of I κ B κ G by TRAF6
 - NF κ B inhibitor binds NF κ B complex

Complex Hierarchy

Entity List

Overview Search Instances

... of TAK1-dependent IKK and NF- κ B activation . I κ B κ B deficiency causes SCID. I κ BA variant leads to EDA-ID. and I κ B κ G deficiency causes anhidrotic ectodermal dysplasia with immunodeficiency

Reaction Relationship Inference

Review the following inferred relationships and check ones you want to approve:

PrecedingReaction	FollowingReaction	SharedEntity	Action	Reject Reason
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Active IKK Complex phosphorylates NF- κ B inhibi...	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NF κ B inhibitor binds NF κ B complex	NFKB1(1-433), NFKB2(1-454):RELA [cytosol]	Reject	Incorrect Order
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CHUK, I κ B κ B and I κ B κ G form IKK complex	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Activated TAK1 mediates phosphorylation of the IKK Complex	CHUK:I κ B κ B:I κ B κ G [cytosol]	Approve	

OK Cancel

Slide to Zoom: [Slider]

- Event Hierarchy
- Show in All
- S100A8:S100A9 binds TLR4:LY96
 - SENP1,2,5 proteolytically process SUMO1
 - SIRT6 deacetylates RBBP8
 - Second phosphorylation of IRAK1 by IRAK4 bound
 - Secreted CD14 binds LPS
 - TAK1 is activated
 - TAK1-dependent IKK and NF-κB activation
 - CHUK, IKKBK and IKBK G form IKK complex
 - Activated TAK1 mediates phosphorylation of IKK complex
 - Activated TAK1 phosphorylates IKKBK
 - Ubiquitination of IKBK G by TRAF6
 - NFκB inhibitor binds NFκB complex

- Complex Hierarchy
- Entity List

... of TAK1-dependent IKK and NF-κB activation . IKKBK deficiency causes SCID. IkBA variant leads to EDA-ID. and IKKBK deficiency causes anhidrotic ectodermal dysplasia with immunodeficiency

Reaction Relationship Inference

Review the following inferred relationships and check ones you want to approve:

PrecedingReaction	FollowingReaction	SharedEntity	Action	Reject Reason
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Active IKK Complex phosphorylates NF-κB inhibi...	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NFκB inhibitor binds NFκB complex	NFKB1(1-433), NFKB2(1-454):RELA [cytosol]	Reject	Incorrect Order
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CHUK, IKKBK and IKBK G form IKK complex	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Activated TAK1 mediates phosphorylation of the IKK Complex	CHUK:IKKBK:IKBK G [cytosol]	Approve	

OK Cancel

Slide to Zoom: [Slider]

- Event Hierarchy**
- Show in All
- [-] TAK1 is activated
 - [+] **TAK1-dependent IKK and NF- κ B activation**
 - [x] CHUK, IKKBK and IKBKKG form IKK complex
 - [x] Activated TAK1 mediates phosphorylation of IKK
 - [x] Activated TAK1 phosphorylates IKKBK
 - [x] Ubiquitination of IKBKKG by TRAF6
 - [x] NF κ B inhibitor binds NF κ B complex
 - [x] Active IKK complex phosphorylates NF- κ B
 - [x] NF κ B complex is transported from cytosol
 - [x] Regulation of NF κ B signaling
 - [x] TIFA oligomerization
 - [x] TIRAP is phosphorylated by I κ BK
 - [x] TLR1/2 ligand binds to CD14

- Complex Hierarchy**
- Entity List**
- Overview Search Instances

of TAK1-dependent IKK and NF- κ B activation, IKKBK deficiency causes SCID, IkBA variant leads to EDA-ID, and IKBKKG deficiency causes anhidrotic ectodermal dysplasia with immunodeficiency

New PrecedingEvent registers immediately

Event Hierarchy

Show in: All

- TAK1 is activated
- TAK1-dependent IKK and NF- κ B activation
 - CHUK, IKKBK and IKBKG form IKK complex
 - Activated TAK1 phosphorylates IKKBK
 - Activated TAK1 phosphorylates IKK β
 - Ubiquitination of IKBKG by TRAF6
 - NF κ B inhibitor binds NF κ B complex
 - Active IKK Complex phosphorylates NF- κ B
 - NF κ B complex is transported from cytosol
 - Regulation of NF- κ B signaling
- TIFA oligomerization
- TIRAP is phosphorylated by TAK
- TLR1/2 ligand binds to CD14

Complex Hierarchy

Entity List

Overview Search Instances

of TAK1-dependent IKK and NF- κ B activation, IKBKG deficiency causes SCID, IkBA variant leads to EDA-ID, and IKBKG deficiency causes anhidrotic ectodermal dysplasia with immunodeficiency

[Reaction:16B184] Activated TAK1 mediates phosphorylation of the IKK Complex

Reaction Properties

Property Name	Value
Property Name	Value
name	Activated TAK1 mediates phosphorylation of th...
negativePrecedingEvent	
normalReaction	
orthologousEvent	
precedingEvent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phosphorylated TAK1 dissociates from the T... TAK1 is activated Auto phosphorylation of TAK1 bound to p-I... Activation of TAK1 complex bound to activat... Auto phosphorylation of TAK1 within the ALP... CHUK, IKKBK and IKBKG form IKK complex
reactionType	
regulatedBy	
regulationReference	
relatedSpecies	
releaseDate	2010-12-14
releaseStatus	
requiredInputComponent	
reversibleReaction	
reviewed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Kufer, TA, 2011-04-28 Ritinger, K, 2011-06-06 Wong, Edmond, 2011-06-06 Napetschnig, Johanna, 2012-11-16 Fitzgerald, Katherine A, 2012-11-13 Shamovsky, V, 2009-09-29 Homo sapiens R-HSA-168184.4 In humans, the IKKs = IkB kinase (IKK) compl...
revised	
species	
stableIdentifier	
summation	
systematicName	
@Local Repository	

New PrecedingEvent registers immediately

Event Hierarchy

Show in All

- IkBA variant leads to EDA-ID**
- Incorporation Of Extended And Processed Telo
- Incorporation Of Extended And Processed Telo
- Initial resection of double-strand break ends
- Interaction of MEKK1 with TRAF6
- Interaction of MEKK1 with TRAF6
- Joining of adjacent Okazaki fragments of the C.
- K63 polyubiquitinated RIP2 associates with the
- KAT5 acetylates ATM at DNA DSBs
- KAT5 acetylates ATM at shortened telomeres
- KDM4A,B bind H4K20Me2
- KPNA2 translocates NBN to the nucleus
- Ligand binds to TLR10

Complex Hierarchy

Entity List

Overview Search Instances

of TAK1-dependent IKK and NF-κB activation . IKKB deficiency causes SCID, IkBA variant leads to EDA-ID, and IKKKG deficiency causes anhidrotic ectodermal dysplasia with immunodeficiency

Search by ID

- Automatic Layout
- Show Compartment in Name
- Hide Private Notes
- Tight Node Bounds
- Wrap Text into Nodes
- Update Node Features
- Update Disease Objects Color
- Update Drug Objects Color
- Hide doNotRelease Events
- Draw Pathway

Paste

Edit Properties

Infer Reaction Relationships

Export Diagram

Property Editor

of TAK1-dependent IKK and NF- κ B activation, IKKBK deficiency causes SCID, IKBA variant leads to EDA-ID, and IKBKG deficiency causes anhidrotic ectodermal dysplasia with immunodeficiency

Event Hierarchy

- Show in: All
- IKBA variant leads to EDA-ID**
 - Incorporation Of Extended And Processed Tel
 - Incorporation Of Extended And Processed Tel
 - Initial resection of double-strand break ends
 - Interaction of MEKK1 with TRAF6
 - Interaction of MEKK1 with TRAF6
 - Joining of adjacent Okazaki fragments of the C-
 - K63 polyubiquitinated RIP2 associates with the
 - KAT5 acetylates ATM at DNA DSBs
 - KAT5 acetylates ATM at shortened telomeres
 - KDM4A,B bind H4K20Me2
 - KPNA2 translocates NBN to the nucleus
 - Ligand binds to TLR10

Complex Hierarchy

Entity List

Overview Search Instances

No Relationship

No relationship can be inferred in this pathway diagram.

OK

Slide to Zoom:

Rejection reason definitions:

1. Abundant molecule : small/common molecules through which you don't want to make a connection
2. Different cell type: shared molecules occur in different cell type
3. Drug molecule:
4. Futile cycle:creation of preceding event creates a loop that is not biologically meaningful.
5. Incorrect order: relationship would create an event order that does biologically relevant.
6. Negative relationship

*We have agreed to reject all recycling loops as futile cycles – for example, ubiquitin comes up quite often, same with any enzyme that we annotated through substrate binding-substrate modification-substrate dissociation steps. This is not to say that in a real cell such loops do not affect processes that consume some of the loop components, but since we don't have any kinetic parameters, we err on the side of assuming that reactants are present in excess.

Questions for discussion:

1. Which of the reasons for rejection should be chosen for a molecule entering an epithelial cell from one side and leaving it on the other side? (so that the export reaction cannot be preceding the import reaction).
2. What if we know for reasons outside the annotated pair of reactions, that they should never be connected because one is normally “off” when the other is “on”? Do we add a term for blocking that preceding – following instance, or do we NOT add it and instead check that all the coordinate regulation that causes this outcome is correctly annotated. My immediate hunch is that we do both – redundant but reliable and, as far as I can tell, also informative to users.

Appendix C8. Best Practices- using Chemical Compound Databases

Which general small molecule databases do we use?

For Reactome, the ChEBI representation of a small molecule is our definitive reference. If ChEBI lacks an entry for your molecule, request one as explained elsewhere in this document. It is appropriate to create cross-references to PubChem and KEGG Compound, but these are not an acceptable substitute for ChEBI.

Where do we use small molecules?

Normal metabolites can be small molecules (ReferenceMolecule), also the majority of drugs are (ReferenceTherapeutic). For enzymatic reactions it is recommended to refer to Rhea which always links to ChEBI. Approved drugs can be found reliably in Guide to Pharmacology (GtP), which always links to PubChem (which most of the time has a ChEBI link if it exists).

In chemical databases I just search the name, no?

What can happen if you think the name suffices:

- there can be many entries with same name in PubChem, this can also happen in ChEBI
- in ChEBI the name that you have can also be the name of a generic structural class; they differ by the wording in the definition and by having asterisks in the SMILES string
- the drug compound may be a salt and the database may have both salt and ion
- the compound may have neutral or charged entries (ions), you need to know the metabolic form to decide what entry you want
- the drug stereochemistry may not be as fully specified as in the database, or vice versa; the drug may also be a mixture, with the database not having the effective component
- databases may not list your molecule under the name, and don't have it as synonym

So you better forget about names, also because there are better ways. First, as Rhea directly links to ChEBI the only case that poses problems is if GtP links to PubChem but PubChem has no ChEBI link, but see below.

Now that I know the exact molecule, how do I find it in ChEBI?

In the case your drug from GtP has a link to PubChem you know the exact molecule. To find it in ChEBI there are two possibilities:

- PubChem has links to ChEBI (however, see Caveat)
- GtP and PubChem have the InChi key of the molecule. This string is unique to any molecule (see Technical Details below). Just copy the InChi key and put it in the ChEBI search box.
- Caveat: PubChem links to ChEBI even if the molecules are not exactly the same, so you need to check if the InChi keys match

ChEBI does not have the molecule, how to submit?

The safest and most efficient way to submit a molecule at ChEBI is to

- find the exact entry in PubChem (see above)
- copy the 'isomeric SMILES' string of the structure
- if there is no 'isomeric SMILES' copy the 'canonical SMILES' string
- start submission at ChEBI by clicking on the "submit" button at the top right of the ChEBI home page and logging in (anyone can request login credentials)
- Click on "edit" in the page that opens once you've logged in to get a fresh structure input tab click Open:

- paste string, click OK, no need to draw the molecule
- continue submission as usual

Technical Details

What is SMILES and InChi?

Molecules are 3-dimensional objects that can be accurately depicted 2-dimensionally, i.e. as structural formula. To copy/paste/search this formula (as picture) is difficult, so to work with molecules computationally, textual codes were developed that can equally

accurately define the 3-dimensional molecule, and at the same time being short strings that are easy to handle. Today, these two are used:

- **SMILES**, see https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Simplified_molecular-input_line-entry_system
- **InChi**, see https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/International_Chemical_Identifier

The chemical databases used in Reactome (ChEBI and PubChem) always have both a SMILES and an InChi string for any specific molecule.

Canonical or isomeric SMILES?

Molecules with stereogenic centers cannot be uniquely defined using canonical SMILES and need an extended code called isomeric SMILES. In short, if there is an isomeric SMILES given by the database, always use that.

The InChi strings always have every stereochemistry specifications that are present in the molecule.

What is an InChi key?

SMILES and InChi can be very long strings. Also, they are not unique, i.e., for the same molecule there can be different SMILES and different InChi strings. So, comparing the strings of two molecules cannot tell you if both molecules are identical. The InChi key solves that problem.

- see https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/International_Chemical_Identifier#InChIKey

Every InChi key is unique to its molecule, so you can use it to search for the exact molecule in databases, or even with Google in the web. The key is a hash, and so the molecule cannot be reconstructed from it alone, but databases always have both InChi and key associated. The uniqueness is not perfect -- amino acid zwitterions have the same key as the acid, and there can be very rare duplicate keys, see <https://www.inchi-trust.org/technical-faq-2/#13.3>.

V90_Sept 2024 updates

- moved from DevWiki
- all referenceMolecule instances MUST have ChEBI as the data source - PubChem and KEGG are not acceptable as a matter of editorial policy.
- update the procedure for requesting a new ChEBI term.

Project Purpose

The purpose of the Cytomics Project is to allow curation and display of specialized pathways showing the development steps of a cell lineage (i.e. development for a particular cell type).

Project Work Summary (Data and Code Changes)

The project involves updates to 5 areas:

1. Data model changes

- 5 new classes have been added to gk_central (in order of appearance in screenshot below)
 - **Marker Reference:** A type of Control Reference that associates one or more EWAS markers(i.e. protein or RNA marker) with one or more literature references for evidence of the marker(s) in a Cell instance
 - **Cell Lineage Path:** A specialized Pathway which contains only other Cell Lineage Path instances or Cell Development Step as events in the "hasEvent" attribute and has a "tissue" attribute containing an Anatomy instance
 - **Cell Development Step:** A specialized ReactionlikeEvent which contains Cell instances for its inputs and outputs and has a "tissue" attribute containing an Anatomy instance
 - **Anatomy:** A type of External Ontology from UBERON (<http://uberon.org>) describing a particular type of organ, tissue type
 - **Cell:** A specialized Physical Entity representing a type of cell in a particular state of development

The screenshot shows the Reactome Curator Tool interface. The left pane displays a class hierarchy with several classes highlighted in red: **MarkerReference**, **CellLineagePath**, **CellDevelopmentStep**, **Anatomy**, and **Cell**. The main area shows the 'ChemicalDrug: 0' class selected, with a 'Properties' table below it. The 'Properties' table has two columns: 'Property Name' and 'Value'. At the bottom, there is a 'Search Instances' section with a search bar and a table of search results.

Property Name	Value

Display Name	DB_ID	Type	Description

2. Updates to Pathway Diagram Curator code (i.e. pathway diagram visualization on curator.reactome.org) - <https://github.com/reactome/PathwayDiagram/tree/feature/cell-lineage-path>

- Convert project to use maven (creation of pom.xml file)
- Exposes a method to set a "CellLineagePath" by its db_id
- Updating hover tooltip with "CellDevelopmentStep" node in diagram
- Processing XML and rendering icons for "Cell" Physical Entities
- Add participating molecules menu for "Cell" Physical Entity to show marker physical entities
 - Change RESTful API endpoint for participating molecules to "entitySubunits" to get marker Physical Entities associated with a "Cell" Physical Entity (as well as continuing to get Physical Entities in a compositional node like a complex, set, polymer)

3. Updates to Pathway Browser Curator code (i.e. the curator website pathway browser - <https://curator.reactome.org/PathwayBrowser>) - <https://github.com/reactome/browser-curator/tree/feature/cell-lineage-paths>

- Adds model classes: *CellDevelopmentStep*, *CellLineagePath*, *Cell*, *Anatomy*, *ControlReference* and *MarkerReference* (includes new cases in *DatabaseObjectFactory* for creating instances of these, new *SchemaClass* and *PropertyType* constants, and *DatabaseObjectImages* for icons)
- Adds new DetailsPanel and Table classes: *CellPanel*, *MarkerReferencePanel*, *CellDevelopmentStepTable*, *CellLineagePathTable*, *CellTable*
- Updates DetailsPanel and Table classes:
 - *EntityWithAccessionedSequencePanel* (handles if an EWAS doesn't have a reference entity)
 - *PhysicalEntityPanel* (handles when the PhysicalEntity is a Cell)
 - *OverviewTableFactory* (handles creation of CellDevelopmentStep, CellLineagePath, Cell tables)
 - *TableRowFactory* (handles rows for a MarkerReference and an EWAS)
- Adds a method for RESTfulClient to obtain all "CellLineagePath" instances
- Updates a series of classes to work for any Event - i.e. "Pathway" or "CellLineagePath" rather than just a Pathway
 - In Selection, DiagramOpenRequestEvent, DiagramOpenedEvent, PathwayDiagramOpenRequestEvent, PathwayDiagramOpenedEvent, DiagramOpenRequestHandler, Ancestors, Path, OrthologousEventPathway, DownloadsTab, DownloadsTabPresenter, DownloadMolecule, ExpressionTab, ExpressionTabDisplay, ExpressionTabPresenter, MoleculesTab, MoleculesTabDisplay, MoleculesTabPresenter, Hierarchy, HierarchyDisplay, HierarchyPresenter, HierarchyPathLoader, HierarchyItem, HierarchyTree, GAManager, OrthologyManager, State, StateHelper, StateManger, TitleManager, ViewportPresenter, Diagram, DiagramDisplay, DiagramPresenter

- NOTE: Some of these changes could be reverted since "CellLineagePath" has become a sub-class of "Pathway" in the data model instead of Event sub-class type
- Adds war and compiler plugins for pom.xml
- Updates dev and curator server URLs to dev.reactome.org and curator.reactome.org

4. RESTful API endpoints for querying the curator relational database gk_central (NOTE: This is a separate API from the Content Service which queries the graph database) -

<https://github.com/reactome/RESTfulAPI/tree/feature/cell-lineage-paths>

- Adds new methods in org.reactome.restfulapi.RESTfulAPIResource
 - **/entitySubunits/{dbId}**
 - Similar to /complexSubunits/{dbId}, but also returns Marker physical entities for Cell instances
 - **/cellLineagePaths/{speciesName}**
 - Returns CellLineagePath instances that exist for a given species ("Homo sapiens" by default)

5. RTF pathway report downloader (i.e. RTF download button in "Download" tab of Pathway Browser Details Panel - <https://curator.reactome.org/PathwayBrowser/#/DTAB=DT>) -

<https://github.com/reactome/Release/tree/feature/cell-lineage-path>

- Updates rtfexporter in the Release repository (website/cgi-bin/rtfexporter)
- Changes call to ReactomeDatabaseReader from "init_pathways" to "init_events" to work for CellLineagePath instances
- Updates Perl module files
 - DocumentGeneration/ReactomeDatabaseReader.pm
 - Methods added to initialize and set events (i.e. both Pathways and CellLineagePaths) and get events by db_id
 - "get_chapters_from_events_text_units", "get_instance_text_units" method updated to process "CellLineagePath" instances
 - ReactomeReaction/Node.pm
 - Adds case and constant for color and rendering parameters for "Cell" diagram node
 - Graphics/SimpleDraw/Box.pm
 - Adds method for rendering "Cell"
 - Utils.pm
 - Updates method for obtaining "Pathway" events to obtaining sub-events in Events in "CellLineagePath" also

- Creates method to get top level Events (i.e. both Pathways and CellLineagePaths) and top level CellLineagePath instances

Viewing the Project

The project in its current state is deployed at <https://curator.reactome.org>. The entry point for all Cytomics work is under the "Developmental Biology" pathway in the Pathway Browser in the subpathway "Developmental Cell Lineages"

<https://curator.reactome.org/PathwayBrowser/#/R-HSA-9734767&PATH=R-HSA-1266738>

The screenshot shows the Reactome Pathway Browser interface. The left sidebar displays the 'Event Hierarchy' with 'Developmental Cell Lineages' selected. The main content area shows a list of developmental cell lineages for the Musculoskeletal, Respiratory, Digestive, Cardiovascular, Endocrine, Urinary, Reproductive, Nervous, and Integumentary systems. The 'Developmental Cell Lineages' pathway is highlighted, and its details are shown below, including the stable identifier R-HSA-9734767.1.

Selecting a "CellLineagePath" (from the Pathway Hierarchy):

The screenshot shows the Reactome Pathway Browser interface with the 'Development of keratinocytes in interfollicular skin epidermis' pathway selected. The left sidebar shows the 'Event Hierarchy' with 'Developmental Cell Lineages of the Integumentary System' and 'Developmental Cell Lineages of the Skin' selected. The main content area displays a diagram of the pathway, showing the progression from a keratinogenic stem cell to a transit-amplifying cell, then to a keratinocyte of the spinosum layer, and finally to a cornocyte of the corneum layer. The pathway is regulated by EGF, Ca2+, and RA. The details section below the diagram shows the stable identifier R-HSA-9725554.1, the GO Biological Process 'keratinocyte development', and the author 'Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2021-03-29'.

Selecting a "Cell Development Step" (from the Pathway Hierarchy or Pathway Diagram):

The screenshot shows the Reactome Pathway Browser interface. The left sidebar displays the Event Hierarchy, with 'Developmental Cell Lineages of the Integumentary System' expanded to 'Developmental Cell Lineages of the Epidermis', and 'Development of keratinocytes in interfollicular skin' selected. The main area shows a pathway diagram with five cell types: keratinogenic stem cell of skin epidermis basal layer, transit-amplifying cell of epidermis basal layer, keratinocyte of spinosum layer of epidermis, keratinocyte of granulosum layer of epidermis, and corneocyte of corneum layer of epidermis. The 'Keratinogenic stem cell produces transit amplifying cell in the basal layer of skin epidermis' step is highlighted. Below the diagram, the 'Description' tab is active, showing the following details:

- Description:** Keratinogenic stem cell produces transit amplifying cell in the basal layer of skin epidermis. Species: Homo sapiens
- Input:** keratinogenic stem cell of skin epidermis basal layer
- Output:** transit-amplifying cell of epidermis basal layer
- Positively regulated by:** Positive regulation by 'EGF [extracellular region]'
- Following Event(s):** Transit-amplifying cell of basal layer produces keratinocyte of spinosum layer in skin epidermis [Homo sapiens]
- Tissue:** skin epidermis

Represents GO Biological Process

Selecting a "Cell" Physical Entity (from the Pathway Hierarchy or Pathway Diagram):

The screenshot shows the Reactome Pathway Browser interface. The left sidebar displays the Event Hierarchy, with 'Developmental Cell Lineages of the Integumentary System' expanded to 'Developmental Cell Lineages of the Epidermis', and 'Development of keratinocytes in interfollicular skin' selected. The main area shows a pathway diagram with five cell types: keratinogenic stem cell of skin epidermis basal layer, transit-amplifying cell of epidermis basal layer, keratinocyte of spinosum layer of epidermis, keratinocyte of granulosum layer of epidermis, and corneocyte of corneum layer of epidermis. The 'keratinogenic stem cell of skin epidermis basal layer' is highlighted. Below the diagram, the 'Description' tab is active, showing the following details:

- Description:** keratinogenic stem cell of skin epidermis basal layer. Species: Homo sapiens
- Stable Identifier:** R-HSA-9725559.1
- Organ:** skin of body
- Tissue:** skin epidermis
- Tissue layer:** stratum basale of epidermis

Opening the Markers menu for a "Cell" Physical Entity (by right-clicking or clicking the blue info icon when hovering over a "Cell" glyph in the Pathway Diagram)

The screenshot shows the Reactome Pathway Browser interface. The left sidebar displays the Event Hierarchy, with 'Developmental Cell Lineages of the Epidermis' selected. The main pathway diagram shows a sequence of cell types: keratinogenic stem cell of skin epidermis basal layer, transit-amplifying cell of epidermis basal layer, keratinocyte of spinosum layer of epidermis, keratinocyte of granulosum layer of epidermis, and corneocyte of corneum layer of epidermis. A blue info icon is clicked on the stem cell, opening a 'Markers' menu. The menu lists various molecules and markers, including CSPG4 mRNA [cytosol], NUMB [plasma membrane], TP63 [nucleoplasm], DLL1 [plasma membrane], KRT19 [cytosol], CSPG4 [plasma membrane], LRIG1 mRNA [cytosol], ITGA6(24-1130) [plasma membrane], LRIG1 [plasma membrane], ITGB4 [plasma membrane], and ITGB1 [plasma membrane]. The 'Molecules' tab is active, showing a list of these molecules with their descriptions and download options.

Displaying the "Molecules Tab" (in the "Details Panel"):

The screenshot shows the Reactome Pathway Browser interface with the 'Molecules Tab' selected in the 'Details Panel'. The pathway diagram is the same as in the previous screenshot. The 'Molecules' tab is active, showing a list of molecules associated with the selected cell type. The list includes:

- Chemical Compounds (1/2):
 - 29108 ^{Cl} calcium(2+) [ChEBI:29108] (1x)
 - 15367 ^{Cl} all-trans-retinoic acid [ChEBI:15367] (1x)
- Proteins (0/27)
- DNA/RNA (0/2)

The 'Molecules' tab also shows a description: 'Keratinogenic stem cell produces transit amplifying cell in the basal layer of skin epidermis' and a 'Download' button.

Displaying the "Structures Tab" (for a selected "Cell" in the "Details Panel"):

The screenshot shows the Reactome Pathway Browser interface. The top navigation bar includes the Reactome logo, version 3.4.1, and the pathway name 'Pathways for: Homo sapiens'. The left sidebar displays an event hierarchy with 'Developmental Cell Lineages' expanded to 'Developmental Cell Lineages of the Epidermis'. The main area shows a cell lineage diagram with five cell types: 'keratinogenic stem cell of skin epidermis basal layer', 'transit-amplifying cell of epidermis basal layer', 'keratinocyte of spinosum layer of epidermis', 'keratinocyte of granulosum layer of epidermis', and 'corneocyte of corneum layer of epidermis'. Signaling molecules 'EGF', 'Ca2+', and 'RA' are shown above the diagram. Below the diagram, the 'Structures' tab is active, displaying two structure entries with UniProt IDs, chain information, resolution, coverage, PDB ranges, and UniProt ranges.

Running the Project Locally

1. Create a new directory for the project in the location you choose and open a terminal at this location
2. Git clone the Pathway Diagram Curator, Pathway Browser Curator, and (optionally) RESTful API repositories

git clone <https://github.com/reactome/browser-curator>

git clone <https://github.com/reactome/PathwayDiagram>

git clone <https://github.com/reactome/RESTfulAPI> (optional)

3. Run RESTfulAPI connected to a Reactome database (optional)

- Navigate to the RESTful API directory and open a terminal
- Run "git checkout cell-lineage-paths"
- Open "web/WEB-INF/applicationContext.xml" and update the constructor arguments for MySQLAdaptor bean (replace the values in bold) to connect to a running Reactome database

```
<bean id="dba" class="org.gk.persistence.MySQLAdaptor">
    <constructor-arg index="0" value="DB_HOST"/>
    <constructor-arg index="1" value="DB_NAME"/>
    <constructor-arg index="2" value="DB_USER"/>
    <constructor-arg index="3" value="DB_PASS"/>
</bean>
```

- Compile the RESTful API as a war file and deploy to a local Tomcat Server or run the project through Eclipse as a Tomcat application

3. Maven install the PathwayDiagram jar so it is available locally

```
cd PathwayDiagram  
git checkout cell-lineage-path  
mvn clean install  
cd ..
```

4. Edit the browser-curator web.xml file to configure the RESTful API used

- Open a terminal and navigate to the browser-curator directory
- Run "git checkout cell-lineage-paths"
- Open the file "src/main/webapp/WEB-INF/web.xml"
- Change the proxyhost value (in bold below) to the server hosting the RESTful API (leave as "localhost" if running a local version of the RESTful API)

```
<!-- RESTful WS PROXY Configuration (ONLY USED IN DEV MODE) -->  
  
<servlet>  
  <servlet-name>ReactomeRESTfulAPI</servlet-name>  
  <servlet-class>org.reactome.server.utils.proxy.ProxyServlet</servlet-class>  
  <init-param>  
    <param-name>proxyHost</param-name>  
    <param-value>localhost</param-value>  
  </init-param>  
  <init-param>  
    <param-name>proxyPort</param-name>  
    <param-value>8080</param-value>  
  </init-param>  
  <!-- Comment the following one to connect to https -->  
  <init-param>  
    <param-name>proxyProtocol</param-name>  
    <param-value>http</param-value>  
  </init-param>  
  <init-param>  
    <param-name>proxyPath</param-name>
```

```
<param-value>/ReactomeRESTfulAPI/RESTfulWS</param-value>
</init-param>
</servlet>
```

5. Compile and run the browser-curator

```
cd browser-curator
```

```
mvn clean compile; mvn gwt:devmode
```

6. Launch the Pathway Browser by clicking "Launch Default Browser"

Definitions

Anatomy - See "Data Model Changes" description for "Project Work Summary" section

Cell - See "Data Model Changes" description for "Project Work Summary" section

Cell Development Step - See "Data Model Changes" description for "Project Work Summary" section

Cell Lineage Path - See "Data Model Changes" description for "Project Work Summary" section

Marker Reference - See "Data Model Changes" description for "Project Work Summary" section

Pathway Browser Curator - An older version of the Reactome Pathway Browser to navigate curated Reactome pathways (i.e. both publicly released and not released). It includes a Pathway Hierarchy (i.e. a collection of general, top-level pathways with nested specific, lower-level pathways) to select a pathway to view, the Pathway Diagram to visualize and interact with the pathway components, and the Pathway Details Panel to provide more information for a selected pathway, reaction, physical entity from the Pathway Hierarchy or Pathway Diagram.

Pathway Diagram Curator - An older version of the Reactome Pathway Diagram display used as a component part of the Pathway Browser for visualizing curation data

RESTful API - A Reactome repository and service which, when hosted on a server, provides URLs to obtain data from a Reactome database in XML and JSON format

RTF (Rich-text format) - A text file with a specialized markup for describing visual elements in the doc

Known Issues/Bugs

- Selection of a CellLineagePath or CellDevelopmentStep in the Pathway Diagram does not highlight the corresponding selection in the Pathway Hierarchy
- Selection of a CellLineagePath or CellDevelopmentStep in the PathwayHierarchy jumps in the scroll to centre the higher level event

Opportunity for Feedback/Future Work

-

Appendix C10: Multiple disease reactions and EntityFunctionalStatus when using disease variant subsets

Should I create one or two disease reactions?

1. The question is, when different mutation affects say enzyme function in different ways (binding to substrate vs loss of enzyme activity) can the two types be represented as a single disease event in which the catalysis reaction is defective?

Here's the story:

I recently finished annotating loss-of-function mutations in MUTYH, a DNA glycosylase involved in base excision repair. For more details, please see [here](#). To see failed reaction in gk_central, the DB_ID is 9605313.

There are about 30 MUTYH disease variants that have been functionally studied, most of them are missense, some are frameshift-caused truncations, and there's also an in-frame insertion.

All loss-of-function mutants lose, to a various extent, the catalytic ability. For some mutants, in addition to catalytic ability, studies also looked at substrate binding, with findings that some mutants can still bind the substrate but cannot process it, some cannot bind, some have reduced binding.

Three questions:

1) ONE OR TWO FAILED EVENTS?

I decided to annotate only one failed event, describing the loss of catalytic activity: "Defective MUTYH mutants do not cleave adenine mispaired with 8-oxoguanine". I believe this failed event captures and displays crucial information about MUTYH loss-of-function.

If I were to annotate an additional failed event: "Defective MUTYH mutants do not recognize and bind adenine opposite to an 8-oxoguanine", another disease pathway would need to be created, involving only mutants that do not bind to the substrate, in order for this failed event and the failed catalysis event to be displayed properly. I do not think that this addition would provide a significant extra information to the users.

Do you agree or do you think that another failed event would add value?

CONCLUSION #1: When there is evidence that a mutation affects both substrate binding and catalytic activity, it is beneficial to point this out by creating two failed reactions, one for binding, one for catalytic activity. This approach provides a more detailed mechanistic annotation of mutant proteins.

2) MULTI-VALUED ENTITY FUNCTIONAL STATUS?

Entity functional status is a multi-valued attribute. Therefore, I have added loss-of-function entity functional status due to various types of mutations to the failed reaction, as was done before for already published reactions. Users should be able to tell from disease EWAS names which disease variant is affected by what type of mutation.

This is how the functional status displays:

This is similar to PTEN functional status released many years ago:

and BRAF gain-of-function:

and CFTR loss-of-function mutants:

And ABCB4 loss-of-function mutants:

And many others.

CONCLUSION #2: EntityFunctionalStatus, which is used to categorize a disease RLE (gain- or a loss-of-function, or and to describe the underlying reason for the change in behavior), is a multivalued attribute. In a disease reaction, when a wt protein is replaced with a *set* (set A) of its disease variants, such that the function of each disease set member is affected in a *similar* way by different types of underlying mutations (such as loss of function due to gain of stop or loss of function due to missense mutation) the set can all be described with a single EntityFunctionalStatus (i.e loss of function of “set”), associating with it as many different sequence ontology terms as applicable in the “functionalStatus”. For example, in the reaction R-HSA-2317387 “PTEN cancer mutants do not dephosphorylate PIP3”, EntityFunctionalStatus is “loss of function of PTEN Mutants [cytosol], and includes two sequence ontology terms: “loss of function via stop gained” and “loss of function via missense variant”.

The screenshot shows a web interface for a reaction. At the top, there are tabs for Description, Molecules, Structures, Expression, Analysis, and Downloads. The reaction name is "PTEN cancer mutants do not dephosphorylate PIP3" with ID "R-HSA-2317387.2" and Species "Homo sapiens". Below the reaction name, there is a section for "Functional status" which includes the text "loss of function of PTEN Mutants [cytosol]". Underneath this, there is a "Physical entity" section with a dropdown menu showing "PTEN Mutants [cytosol]". Below that, there is a "Functional Status:" section with two highlighted items: "loss of function via stop gained" and "loss of function via missense variant". At the bottom, there is an "Input" section with two radio buttons: "PI(3,4,5)P3 [plasma membrane]" and "H2O [cytosol]".

This is how this annotation looks in the Curator Tool:

The screenshot shows a window titled "[EntityFunctionalStatus:5674405] loss_of_function...". Below the title bar is a table with the following data:

Property Name	Value
functionalStatus	loss_of_function via missense_variant loss_of_function via stop_gained
physicalEntity	PTEN Mutants [cytosol]
DB_ID	5674405
_displayName	loss_of_function of PTEN Mutants [cytosol]
created	Orlic-Milacic, Marija, 2015-02-12
modified	
stableIdentifier	

3) SHOULD THERE BE SUBSETS IN A SET OF MUTANTS THAT CORRESPOND TO MUTATION TYPE?

In the case of PTEN mutants, mutants were separated into subsets based on the type of mutation. However, in the case of MUTYH, BRAF, CFTR and ABCB4, there was no subgrouping of mutants based on mutation type.

Is subgrouping of mutants necessary, does it add anything, or should users simply figure out who is who from standardized mutant names?

CONCLUSION #3: Although not formally required so far, it is beneficial for the users to group disease set members into subsets that correspond to underlying mutation types, so that the number of subsets is equal to the numerical value of the EntityFunctionalStatus of a reaction in which this mutant set participates (e.g. if three different sequence ontology terms are listed under EntityFunctional status, the mutant set should have three subsets; for example, if the EntityFunctionalStatus lists the following: loss_of_function_via_missense_variant and loss_of_function_via_stop_gained, the mutants set "X mutants" that participates in the reactions should have subsets X_missense_variants and X_nonsense_variants.

So far, we have not been consistent with creating subsets of mutants based on sequence variant type. In the majority of cases, no subsets have been created.

Here are some examples to illustrate how this looks in practice.

- 1) In the above-mentioned reaction R-HSA-2317387 "[PTEN cancer mutants do not dephosphorylate PIP3](#)", EntityFunctionalStatus is "loss of function of PTEN Mutants [cytosol]", and includes two sequence ontology terms: "loss of function via stop gained" and "loss of function via missense variant". The mutant set "[PTEN Mutants](#)" includes two subsets, "PTEN Phosphatase Domain Missense Mutants" and "PTEN Truncation Mutants". The first subsets (missense mutants) corresponds to the functional status "loss of function via missense variant", while the second subset (truncation mutants) corresponds to the functional status "loss of function via stop gained".

In order to implement the rule for creating subsets, we should come up with an unambiguous list of sequence variant-related naming terms for mutant subsets.

2) In the reaction R-HSA-3311014 “SMAD4 MH2 Domain Mutants do not bind phosphorylated SMAD2 and SMAD3”, EntityFunctionalStatus lists two terms: “loss of function via stop gained” and “loss of function via missense variant”.

Functional status

loss of function of SMAD4 MH2 domain mutants

Physical entity:

 SMAD4 MH2 domain mutants [cytosol]

Functional Status:

loss of function via stop gained

loss of function via missense variant

The mutant set, “SMAD4 MH2 domain mutants”, however, contains no subsets:

Functional status

loss of function of SMAD4 MH2 domain mutants

Physical entity:

 SMAD4 MH2 domain mutants [cytosol]

Species: Homo sapiens

Synonyms: SMAD4 MH2 domain mutants

Has members:

 SMAD4 A406T [cytosol]

 SMAD4 D351G [cytosol]

 SMAD4 D351H [cytosol]

 SMAD4 D351Y [cytosol]

 SMAD4 D351del [cytosol]

 SMAD4 K428T [cytosol]

 SMAD4 P356L [cytosol]

 SMAD4 P356R [cytosol]

 SMAD4 R361C [cytosol]

 SMAD4 R361H [cytosol]

 SMAD4 R515T [cytosol]

Has candidates:

 SMAD4 K428R [cytosol]

 SMAD4 R361G [cytosol]

 SMAD4 R361S [cytosol]

 SMAD4 R515* [cytosol]

Users can tell who is who if they know naming rules for mutations at the protein level.

target	target_id	target_name	target_uniprot	target_ensembl_gene	target_species	ligand	ligand_id	ligand_pubchem	approved_drug	type	action	action_comment	selectivity	endogenous	primary_target	concentration	affinity_units	affinity_high	affinity_medium	affinity_low	original_affinity	original_affinity	original_affinity	original_affinity	original_affinity	original_affinity	assay_descriptor	receptor_site	ligand_context	pubmed_id				
betae-cs2-1-sub-1-adenoreceptor	29	ADRB2	P07550	ENSG00000199252	Human	levocabastol	670	135500222	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Non-selective	1	1							0.55000012													
betae-cs2-1-sub-2-adenoreceptor	29	ADRB2	P07550	ENSG00000199252	Human	nadofol	554	135560780	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Non-selective	1	1																				
betae-cs2-1-sub-3-adenoreceptor	29	ADRB2	P07550	ENSG00000199252	Human	propionolol	564	135560858	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Non-selective	1	1																				
betae-cs2-1-sub-4-adenoreceptor	29	ADRB2	P07550	ENSG00000199252	Human	isotalol	7207	179103870	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Non-selective	1	1																				
betae-cs2-1-sub-5-adenoreceptor	29	ADRB2	P07550	ENSG00000199252	Human	timolol	665	135561023	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Non-selective	1	1																				
betae-cs2-1-sub-6-adenoreceptor	30	ADRB3	P13845	ENSG00000188778	Human	antipragol	7445	179104017	1	Agonist	Agonist	Selective	1	1																				
betae-cs2-1-sub-7-adenoreceptor	30	ADRB3	P13845	ENSG00000188778	Human	bupranolol	550	135560933	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Non-selective	1	1																				
betae-cs2-1-sub-8-adenoreceptor	30	ADRB3	P13845	ENSG00000188778	Human	levocabastol	670	135560938	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Non-selective	1	1																				
betae-cs2-1-sub-9-adenoreceptor	30	ADRB3	P13845	ENSG00000188778	Human	propionolol	564	135560858	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Non-selective	1	1																				
B-Raf proto-oncogene, serine/threonine kinase	1943	BRAF	P19506	ENSG00000197784	Human	cabafentol	6484	179103108	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	1	1																				
B-Raf proto-oncogene, serine/threonine kinase	1943	BRAF	P19506	ENSG00000197784	Human	negafentol	5863	179102184	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	1	1																				
B-Raf proto-oncogene, serine/threonine kinase	1943	BRAF	P19506	ENSG00000197784	Human	venlafentol	5883	179102156	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	1	1																				
Bruton tyrosine kinase	1948	BTK	Q06187	ENSG00000100871	Human	acalabrutinib	8912	131024693	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Selective	1	1																				
Bruton tyrosine kinase	1948	BTK	Q06187	ENSG00000100871	Human	ibrutinib	8912	131024693	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Selective	1	1																				
Bruton tyrosine kinase	1948	BTK	Q06187	ENSG00000100871	Human	brutinib	6912	179103494	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	1	1																				
B-sub-2-sub-1-receptor	42	BDKRB2	P30411	ENSG00000198398	Human	icattant	667	135625196	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Selective	1	1																				
B-sub-2-sub-1-receptor	42	BDKRB2	P30411	ENSG00000198398	Human	icattant	667	135625196	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Not Determined	1	1																				
B-sub-2-sub-2-receptor	42	BDKRB2	P30411	ENSG00000198398	Human	icattant	667	135625196	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Not Determined	1	1																				
butyrylcholinesterase	2471	BChE	P06276	ENSG00000114200	Human	isofluridine	6602	179103215	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	1	1																				
butyrylcholinesterase	2471	BChE	P06276	ENSG00000114200	Human	isofluridine	6602	179103215	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	1	1																				
butyrylcholinesterase	2471	BChE	P06276	ENSG00000114200	Human	isofluridine	6602	179103215	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	1	1																				
Ca ²⁺ channel	708	ANO1	Q5OX46	ENSG00000131620	Human	crofezomar	7453	187051756	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Selective	1	1																				
carbonic anhydrase 7	2508	CA14	ORLX37	ENSG00000118208	Human	ethoxzolamide	6914	179103420	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	1	1																				
carbonic anhydrase 7	2749	CA7	P43166	ENSG00000198748	Human	acetazolamide	6792	179103299	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	1	1																				
carbonic anhydrase 7	2749	CA7	P43166	ENSG00000198748	Human	biphenamide	6797	179103403	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	1	1																				
carbonic anhydrase 7	2749	CA7	P43166	ENSG00000198748	Human	chlorothalidone	7147	179103272	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	1	1																				
carbonic anhydrase 7	2749	CA7	P43166	ENSG00000198748	Human	metazolamide	6828	179103434	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	1	1																				
Calc receptor	54	CASR	P14180	ENSG00000306828	Human	calcitriol	3308	179103043	1	Agonist	Agonist	Not Determined	1	1																				
Calc receptor	54	CASR	P14180	ENSG00000306828	Human	calcitriol	3308	179103043	1	Agonist	Agonist	Not Determined	1	1																				
Carboxylesterase 1	528	CACNA1B	Q13988	ENSG00000098128	Human	eflornithin	2298	135659185	1	Channel blocker	Antagonist	Non-selective	1	1																				
Carboxylesterase 1	528	CACNA1B	Q13988	ENSG00000098128	Human	eflornithin	2298	135659185	1	Channel blocker	Antagonist	Non-selective	1	1																				
Carboxylesterase 1.2	529	CACNA1C	Q13988	ENSG00000115087	Human	verapamil	2406	135651305	1	Channel blocker	Antagonist	Non-selective	1	1																				
Carboxylesterase 1.3	530	CACNA1D	Q13988	ENSG00000197388	Human	nifedipine	2334	135659723	1	Channel blocker	Inhibitor	Not Determined	1	1																				
Catechol-O-methyltransferase	2472	COMT	P21964	ENSG00000200210	Human	entacapone	6647	179103030	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	soluble enzyme	Not Determined	1	1																			
Catechol-O-methyltransferase	2472	COMT	P21964	ENSG00000200210	Human	entacapone	6647	179103030	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	membrane-bound	Not Determined	1	1																			
Catechol-O-methyltransferase	2472	COMT	P21964	ENSG00000200210	Human	opicapone	8988	131024796	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Selective	1	1																				
Catechol-O-methyltransferase	2472	COMT	P21964	ENSG00000200210	Human	tolcapone	6646	179103259	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	soluble enzyme	Not Determined	1	1																			
Catechol-O-methyltransferase	2472	COMT	P21964	ENSG00000200210	Human	tolcapone	6646	179103259	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	membrane-bound	Not Determined	1	1																			
CB1 cannabinoid receptor	56	CNR1	P21964	ENSG00000118432	Human	AMeTA- ¹ - ¹ - ¹	2424	135651250	1	Agonist	Partial agonist	Not Determined	1	1																				
CCB4	61	CCB4	P51679	ENSG00000183913	Human	magnesiumlactubate	6477	179103091	1	Antibody	Inhibition	Selective	1	1																				
CCS2	62	CCS2	P15991	ENSG00000198701	Human	maggotrin	898	135659201	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Not Determined	1	1																				
CD19	2784	CD19	P15991	ENSG00000117445	Human	milvexian	7992	246656873	1	Antibody	Binding	Selective	1	1																				
CD19	2784	CD19	P15991	ENSG00000117445	Human	salixtilamab	1131	434122191	1	Antibody	Binding	Selective	1	1																				
CD2	2600	CD2	P08729	ENSG00000198724	Human	salixtilamab	1131	434122191	1	Antibody	Binding	Selective	1	1																				
CD20 (membrane-spanning 4-domains, s	2628	MS4A1	P11836	ENSG00000196738	Human	fortumab	6777	179103383	1	Antibody	Binding	Not Determined	1	1																				
CD20 (membrane-spanning 4-domains, s	2628	MS4A1	P11836	ENSG00000196738	Human	obinitumab	6941	179103523	1	Antibody	Binding	Not Determined	1	1																				
CD20 (membrane-spanning 4-domains, s	2628	MS4A1	P11836	ENSG00000196738	Human	ocrolizumab	6788	179103383	1	Antibody	Binding	Not Determined	1	1																				
CD20 (membrane-spanning 4-domains, s	2628	MS4A1	P11836	ENSG00000196738	Human	ofatumumab	6778	179103384</																										

target	target_id	target_name	target_uniprot	target_ensembl_gene	target_species	ligand	ligand_id	ligand_publication	approved_drug	type	action	action_comment	selectivity	endogenous	primary_target	concentration	affinity_units	affinity_high	affinity_medium	affinity_low	original_affinity	assay_descriptor	receptor_site	ligand_comment	pubmed_id									
COX-2	1376	PTGS2	P3554	ENSG00000173165	Human	phenylazone	7273	17910347	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	1	1																				
COX-2	1376	PTGS2	P3554	ENSG00000173165	Human	proxicam	7273	17910347	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	1	1																				
COX-2	1376	PTGS2	P3554	ENSG00000173165	Human	rofecoxib	2893	17910242	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Selective	1	1					6.5		6.09999905													
COX-2	1376	PTGS2	P3554	ENSG00000173165	Human	aspirin	7298	17910371	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	1	1							5.59999943	IC50												
COX-2	1376	PTGS2	P3554	ENSG00000173165	Human	valdecoxib	7298	17910243	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	1	1							8.30000011	IC50												
c-kit oncogene 1, receptor tyrosine kinase	1840	ROS1	P08892	ENSG0000047936	Human	lorlatinib	7476	18705179	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	1	1							11.30000019	Ki												
CCR4 (CCR19)	2850	SLAMF7	Q9M225	ENSG00000206751	Human	elotuzumab	8361	25216637	1	Antibody	Binding	Selective	1	1							8.050000191	Ki												
CT receptor	43	CACLR	P03268	ENSG00000137869	Human	calcitonin (salmon)	6073	17910362	1	Agonist	Full agonist	Not Determined	1	1							11.10000038	Full agonist												
CXCR4	71	CXCR4	PE1073	ENSG00000121966	Human	plentafur	844	13564932	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Not Determined	1	1							6.99999909	Ki												
CXCR4	71	CXCR4	PE1073	ENSG00000121966	Human	plentafur	844	13564932	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Not Determined	1	1							6.190000057	IC50												
CXCR4	71	CXCR4	PE1073	ENSG00000121966	Human	plentafur	844	13564932	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Not Determined	1	1							6.300000191	Ki												
cystin dependent kinase 4	1576	CKDK4	PI1802	ENSG00000135446	Human	piroxicam	7380	17910362	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	1	1							10	IC50												
cystin dependent kinase 4	1576	CKDK4	PI1802	ENSG00000135446	Human	rofecoxib	7380	17910365	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Selective	1	1							10	IC50												
cystin dependent kinase 6	1578	CKDK6	Q00534	ENSG00000110210	Human	piroxicam	7380	17910362	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	1	1							7.800000191	IC50												
CYP11B1	1369	CYP11B1	P15038	ENSG00000108882	Human	metoprolol	8224	18101909	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	1	1							14.800000153	IC50												
CYP19A1	1362	CYP19A1	P11511	ENSG00000137869	Human	amnoglutathimide	7054	17910363	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	1	1							-	-												
CYP19A1	1362	CYP19A1	P11511	ENSG00000137869	Human	anastrozole	5137	179101629	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	1	1							7.800000172	IC50												
CYP19A1	1362	CYP19A1	P11511	ENSG00000137869	Human	exemestane	7073	17910362	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Selective	1	1							7.300000191	IC50												
CYP19A1	1362	CYP19A1	P11511	ENSG00000137869	Human	fadrozole	8311	25216623	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not selective	1	1							8.350000381	IC50												
CYP19A1	1362	CYP19A1	P11511	ENSG00000137869	Human	letrozole	5509	17910186	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Selective	1	1							10.699999981	Ki												
CYP19A1	1362	CYP19A1	P11511	ENSG00000137869	Human	letrozole	5509	17910186	1	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Selective	1	1							4.400000028	Ki												
CyL1T-sub-1+sub-receptor	269	CYSLTR1	Q9Y271	ENSG00000173198	Human	montelukast	3340	17910370	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Selective	1	1							8.500000191	IC50												
CyL1T-sub-1+sub-receptor	269	CYSLTR1	Q9Y271	ENSG00000173198	Human	montelukast	3340	17910370	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Selective	1	1							8.500000191	IC50												
CyL1T-sub-1+sub-receptor	269	CYSLTR1	Q9Y271	ENSG00000173198	Human	montelukast	3340	17910370	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Selective	1	1							8.460000343	IC50												
CyL1T-sub-1+sub-receptor	269	CYSLTR1	Q9Y271	ENSG00000173198	Human	montelukast	3340	17910370	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Selective	1	1							8.460000343	IC50												
CyL1T-sub-1+sub-receptor	269	CYSLTR1	Q9Y271	ENSG00000173198	Human	montelukast	3340	17910370	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Selective	1	1							8.460000343	IC50												
CyL1T-sub-1+sub-receptor	269	CYSLTR1	Q9Y271	ENSG00000173198	Human	montelukast	3340	17910370	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Selective	1	1							8.460000343	IC50												
CyL1T-sub-1+sub-receptor	269	CYSLTR1	Q9Y271	ENSG00000173198	Human	montelukast	3340	17910370	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Selective	1	1							8.460000343	IC50												
CyL1T-sub-1+sub-receptor	269	CYSLTR1	Q9Y271	ENSG00000173198	Human	montelukast	3340	17910370	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Selective	1	1							8.460000343	IC50												
CyL1T-sub-1+sub-receptor	269	CYSLTR1	Q9Y271	ENSG00000173198	Human	montelukast	3340	17910370	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Selective	1	1							8.460000343	IC50												
CyL1T-sub-1+sub-receptor	269	CYSLTR1	Q9Y271	ENSG00000173198	Human	montelukast	3340	17910370	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Selective	1	1							8.460000343	IC50												
CyL1T-sub-1+sub-receptor	269	CYSLTR1	Q9Y271	ENSG00000173198	Human	montelukast	3340	17910370	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Selective	1	1							8.460000343	IC50												
CyL1T-sub-1+sub-receptor	269	CYSLTR1	Q9Y271	ENSG00000173198	Human	montelukast	3340	17910370	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Selective	1	1							8.460000343	IC50												
CyL1T-sub-1+sub-receptor	269	CYSLTR1	Q9Y271	ENSG00000173198	Human	montelukast	3340	17910370	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Selective	1	1							8.460000343	IC50												
CyL1T-sub-1+sub-receptor	269	CYSLTR1	Q9Y271	ENSG00000173198	Human	montelukast	3340	17910370	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Selective	1	1							8.460000343	IC50												
CyL1T-sub-1+sub-receptor	269	CYSLTR1	Q9Y271	ENSG00000173198	Human	montelukast	3340	17910370	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Selective	1	1							8.460000343	IC50												
CyL1T-sub-1+sub-receptor	269	CYSLTR1	Q9Y271	ENSG00000173198	Human	montelukast	3340	17910370	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Selective	1	1							8.460000343	IC50												
CyL1T-sub-1+sub-receptor	269	CYSLTR1	Q9Y271	ENSG00000173198	Human	montelukast	3340	17910370	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Selective	1	1							8.460000343	IC50												
CyL1T-sub-1+sub-receptor	269	CYSLTR1	Q9Y271	ENSG00000173198	Human	montelukast	3340	17910370	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Selective	1	1							8.460000343	IC50												
CyL1T-sub-1+sub-receptor	269	CYSLTR1	Q9Y271	ENSG00000173198	Human	montelukast	3340	17910370	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Selective	1	1							8.460000343	IC50												
CyL1T-sub-1+sub-receptor	269	CYSLTR1	Q9Y271	ENSG00000173198	Human	montelukast	3340	17910370	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Selective	1	1							8.460000343	IC50												
CyL1T-sub-1+sub-receptor	269	CYSLTR1	Q9Y271	ENSG00000173198	Human	montelukast	3340	17910370	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Selective	1	1							8.460000343	IC50												
CyL1T-sub-1+sub-receptor	269	CYSLTR1	Q9Y271	ENSG00000173198	Human	montelukast	3340	17910370	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Selective	1	1							8.460000343	IC50												
CyL1T-sub-1+sub-receptor	269	CYSLTR1	Q9Y271	ENSG00000173198	Human	montelukast	3340	17910370	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Selective	1	1							8.460000343	IC50												
CyL1T-sub-1+sub-receptor	269	CYSLTR1	Q9Y271	ENSG00000173198	Human	montelukast	3340	17910370	1	Antagonist	Antagonist	Selective	1	1							8.460000343	IC50												
CyL1T-sub-1+sub-receptor	269	CYSLTR1	Q9Y271	ENSG00000173198	Human	montelukast	3340	179																										

target	target_id	target_name	target_uniprot	target_ensembl_id	target_species	ligand	ligand_id	ligand_pubchem	approved_drug	type	action	action_comment	selectivity	endogenous	primary_target	concentration	affinity_units	affinity_high	affinity_medium	affinity_low	original_affinity	original_affinity_original	original_affinity_original	original_affinity_original	original_affinity_assay	descriptor_text	ligand_context	pubmed_id		
BERT	628	SLC6A4	P31845	ENSG00000108575	Human	noradrenaline	2493	13595920	-	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Non-selective	-	-	-	-	8	15599967	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
BERT	628	SLC6A4	P31845	ENSG00000108576	Human	paroxetine	4790	179191492	-	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Selective	-	-	-	-	pK _i	6.60000381	Ki	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	6537921		
BERT	628	SLC6A4	P31845	ENSG00000108576	Human	paroxetine	4790	179191492	-	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	-	-	-	-	pK _i	10.1000038	Ki	0.07999998	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2704939		
BERT	628	SLC6A4	P31845	ENSG00000108576	Human	propranolol	7285	179103859	-	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Selective	-	-	-	-	pK _i	7.71000038	Ki	19.60000038	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	6537921	
BERT	628	SLC6A4	P31845	ENSG00000108576	Human	sertraline	4798	179101500	-	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Selective	-	-	-	-	pK _i	6.100000381	Ki	0.700000001	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1949000021	
BERT	628	SLC6A4	P31845	ENSG00000108576	Human	tricyclic	7317	179103890	-	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Non-selective	-	-	-	-	pK _i	6.829999924	Ki	149	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	6537921	
BERT	628	SLC6A4	P31845	ENSG00000108576	Human	venlafaxine	7321	179103894	-	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Selective	-	-	-	-	pK _i	5.750000172	Ki	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2037347	
BERT	628	SLC6A4	P31845	ENSG00000108576	Human	fluoxetine	7427	179103900	-	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Non-selective	-	-	-	-	pK _i	9.300000191	Ki	8.900000191	1.580000043	-	-	-	0.6	-	-	-	18492634/15144504	
BERT	628	SLC6A4	P31845	ENSG00000108576	Human	fluoxetine	7351	179103923	-	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Non-selective	-	-	-	-	pK _i	8.600000191	Ki	1.600000204	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	21489038	
sigma non-opioid intracellular receptor 1	2552	SIGMAR1	Q99720	ENSG00000147965	Human	(-)-piperitone	1606	139650066	-	Antagonist	Antagonist	Non-selective	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
SMO	239	SMO	Q99835	ENSG00000128652	Human	guselkumab	8231	245666879	-	Antagonist	Antagonist	Not Determined	-	-	-	-	-	8.200000181	EC50	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2400543	
SMO	239	SMO	Q99835	ENSG00000128652	Human	vorinostat	8199	245666879	-	Antagonist	Antagonist	Not Determined	-	-	-	-	-	8.200000387	Ki	6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2305352	
SMO	239	SMO	Q99835	ENSG00000128652	Human	vitaminD3	6975	179103854	-	Antagonist	Antagonist	Selective	-	-	-	-	-	pK _i	7.79999992	Ki	16.20000076	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	6537921	
Sodium/glucose cotransporter 1	916	SLC6A2	P31380	ENSG00000100170	Human	sildenafil	8512	252186824	-	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	-	-	-	-	pK _i	7.440000087	EC50	36	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2279142	
Sodium/glucose cotransporter 1	916	SLC6A2	P31380	ENSG00000100170	Human	sildenafil	4582	179101300	-	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Non-selective	-	-	-	-	pK _i	8.309999919	EC50	6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2236516	
Sodium/glucose cotransporter 2	916	SLC6A2	P31380	ENSG00000140675	Human	digoxin	4904	179101315	-	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Selective	-	-	-	-	pK _i	9.300000191	EC50	0.40000001	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2087036	
Sodium/glucose cotransporter 2	916	SLC6A2	P31380	ENSG00000140675	Human	empagliflozin	4754	179101464	-	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Non-selective	-	-	-	-	pK _i	8.5	EC50	3.200000048	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2198934	
Sodium/glucose cotransporter 2	916	SLC6A2	P31380	ENSG00000140675	Human	empagliflozin	8376	252186808	-	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Selective	-	-	-	-	pK _i	9.000000042	EC50	0.819999974	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	21446906	
Sodium/glucose cotransporter 2	916	SLC6A2	P31380	ENSG00000140675	Human	pragliflozin	9394	329083496	-	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Selective	-	-	-	-	pK _i	8.130000114	EC50	1.799999962	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	22139434	
Sodium/glucose cotransporter 2	916	SLC6A2	P31380	ENSG00000140675	Human	sildenafil	8312	252186824	-	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	-	-	-	-	pK _i	8.799999711	EC50	1.799999962	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2279142	
Sodium/potassium transporting ATPase alpha	833	ATP1A1	P05023	ENSG00000163399	Human	digoxin	6762	179103286	-	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Family selective	-	-	-	-	pK _i	8.539999962	EC50	3.900000095	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2288551
sodium/potassium transporting ATPase alpha	833	ATP1A1	P05023	ENSG00000163399	Human	acetylcholine	6794	179103400	-	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Family selective	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
sodium/potassium transporting ATPase alpha	833	ATP1A1	P05023	ENSG00000163399	Human	destrodoxine	6896	179103412	-	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Family selective	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
sodium/potassium transporting ATPase alpha	833	ATP1A1	P05023	ENSG00000163399	Human	digoxin	6762	179103286	-	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Family selective	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
sodium/potassium transporting ATPase alpha	833	ATP1A1	P05023	ENSG00000163399	Human	digoxin	4726	179101437	-	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Family selective	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
SST1-5alpha-1 receptor	355	SSTR1	P30874	ENSG00000139874	Human	pasireotide	2018	135652473	-	Agonist	Full agonist	Not Determined	-	-	-	-	pK _i	9.600000381	EC50	8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
SST1-5alpha-2 receptor	355	SSTR2	P30874	ENSG00000139874	Human	lanreotide	2031	135652202	-	Agonist	Full agonist	Selective	-	-	-	-	pK _i	9.600000381	EC50	8	8.999999909	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1547717
SST1-5alpha-2 receptor	355	SSTR2	P30874	ENSG00000139874	Human	lanreotide	2018	135652473	-	Agonist	Full agonist	Not Determined	-	-	-	-	pK _i	9.600000381	EC50	9	8.999999909	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	879372/2607979/1058788/7988478/6652348
SST1-5alpha-2 receptor	355	SSTR2	P30874	ENSG00000139874	Human	vapreotide	2054	135652473	-	Agonist	Full agonist	Not Determined	-	-	-	-	pK _i	10.10000038	EC50	1.800000191	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	679372/7984876
SST1-5alpha-3 receptor	357	SSTR3	P32745	ENSG00000183473	Human	lanreotide	2018	135652473	-	Agonist	Full agonist	Not Determined	-	-	-	-	pK _i	9.600000381	EC50	8.800000191	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1547717
SST1-5alpha-3 receptor	357	SSTR3	P32745	ENSG00000183473	Human	vapreotide	2054	135652473	-	Agonist	Full agonist	Not Determined	-	-	-	-	pK _i	7.600000005	EC50	7.400000005	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	879372/2607979/1058788/7988476
SST1-5alpha-5 receptor	359	SSTR5	P35346	ENSG00000142009	Human	lanreotide	2031	135652202	-	Agonist	Full agonist	Not Determined	-	-	-	-	pK _i	9.300000191	EC50	7.400000005	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	679372/2607979/1058788/9600011/988478/6765
SST1-5alpha-5 receptor	359	SSTR5	P35346	ENSG00000142009	Human	pasireotide	2018	135652473	-	Agonist	Full agonist	Not Determined	-	-	-	-	pK _i	9.800000191	EC50	8.800000191	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1547717
SST1-5alpha-5 receptor	359	SSTR5	P35346	ENSG00000142009	Human	pasireotide	2018	135652473	-	Agonist	Full agonist	Not Determined	-	-	-	-	pK _i	9.199999969	EC50	7.300000191	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	879372/2607979/1058788/9600011/7798478/6765
steroid 5 alpha-reductase 2	2633	SRD5A2	PT1213	ENSG00000140919	Human	finasteride	6818	179103424	-	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	-	-	-	-	pK _i	8.740000038	EC50	14.60000038	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3735591
Thrombopoietin receptor	1722	MPL	P40238	ENSG00000117400	Human	eltrombopag	6961	179103542	-	Agonist	Agonist	Selective	-	-	-	-	pK _i	7.420000076	EC50	38	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1873499	
Thrombopoietin receptor	1722	MPL	P40238	ENSG00000117400	Human	lusotrombopag	10052	37973220	-	Agonist	Agonist	Selective	-	-	-	-	pK _i	7.420000076	EC50	38	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2927481
Thrombopoietin receptor	1722	MPL	P40238	ENSG00000117400	Human	romiplostim	6974	19103593	-	Agonist	Agonist	Not Determined	-	-	-	-	pK _i	7.420000076	EC50	38	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	6773364
Thyroidalase synthase	2642	THMS	P04818	ENSG00000176890	Human	capacetate	6799	179103405	-	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	-	-	-	-	pK _i	6.539999962	EC50	290	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	10631692/15709193
Thyroid hormone receptor-Alpha	588	TRHR	P10828	ENSG00000132651	Human	methimazole	7403	179103075	-	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Selective	-	-	-	-	pK _i	6.539999962	EC50	290	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2279300
Thyroid hormone receptor-Alpha	588	TRHR	P10828	ENSG00000132651	Human	desmethylthyroxine	6951	179103263	-	Agonist	Agonist	Not Determined	-	-	-	-	pK _i	6.539999962	EC50	290	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	6773364
Thyroid hormone receptor-Beta	589	TRHB	P10828	ENSG00000151900	Human	desmethylthyroxine	6951	179103263	-	Agonist	Agonist	Not Determined	-	-	-	-	pK _i	6.539999962	EC50	290	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	6773364
thyroid peroxidase	2526	TPO	P07202	ENSG00000119705	Human	methimazole	6649	179103262	-	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	-	-	-	-	pK _i	6.539999962	EC50	290	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	748042
thyroid peroxidase	2526	TPO	P07202	ENSG00000119705	Human	propylthiouracil	6659	179103263	-	Inhibitor	Inhibition	Not Determined	-	-	-	-	pK _i	6.539999962	EC50	290	-	-								

Appendix C12. Disease-specific gene expression

Here is the short question, before my lengthy explanation- can there be a disease reaction (ie it has a disease tag on it) that has no specific disease participants in it ie again -all the participants are genetically WT? Can a complex or an entity be labeled with a disease tag if there is no genetic modification to it?

In this particular case, my fusion protein NPM-ALK (disease tagged) is known to phosphorylate STAT3, which goes on to activate (disease-specific) gene expression. STAT3 itself is wild-type, and it is also believed to be activated by WT ALK.

In the WT ALK signaling pathway, STAT3 is shown as [being phosphorylated](#), [dimerizing](#) and [translocating to nucleus](#), where it does nuclear gene expression things.

In the disease pathway, STAT 3 is shown as binding and being [phosphorylated](#) by ALK fusions, but the dimerization and translocation are not specifically shown. In earlier annotations, STAT3 is just shown as a [regulator of gene expression](#) events, which avoids the issue that I am now trying to work around, below.

I now need to annotate an event where, in the context of NPM-ALK signaling, phosphorylated STAT3 binds to a gene promoter to promote expression, so I need the physical entity (which is still just WT) in the nucleus. I was just about to make a BBE showing that after phosphorylation in the cytosol by ALK fusions (disease tagged reaction), STAT3 is released, dimerizes and translocates to the nucleus, where it will be free to bind to any gene I want it to regulate.

The problem is that none of those components of my proposed downstream reactions (nuclear p-STAT3, the genes it is going to regulate) are inherently disease in themselves.

1. Can I make my BBE showing a cytosolic ALK mutant: p_Y STAT3 complex (disease tagged) yielding nuclear p_Y-STAT3 (in reality WT, but needed as a disease entity)? 2. After that, can I use this WT-but-disease activated p_Y-STAT3 to activate WT-but-disease-activated genes? This reaction would need to be tagged with a disease tag even though all the entities are WT.

2. Alternately, I could make a disease-tagged p-STAT3 EWAS and dimer complex, even though they are genetically WT, and use that in my disease-specific reactions. In this model, the disease reactions are consistent (the reactions contain an entity with a disease tag on it), but the entity is inconsistent (no genetic modification, but tagged with a disease tag).

3. As I was doing this curation, I found myself reconsidering whether the complex formed by the (WT) gene and (WT) transcription factor (in this specific instance, the p-Y STAT3:geneX complex) should really be disease labelled, as indicated in both schematics, or whether just the gene expression that is regulated by that complex should be.

Discussion:

Why do you need this phosphorylated STAT3 and its downstream reactions to be disease tagged:

1. Is it phosphorylated on particular residues by the NMP-ALK fusion protein that aren't normally phosphorylated by ALK?
2. Is such a high quantity of phosphorylated STAT3 produced that it saturates all STAT3 binding sites in the genome and starts binding to regulatory elements of genes that it normally does not regulate?

If reason 1 is in place, then a disease-specific phosphorylated STAT3 could be tagged with a disease tag, and any aberrant transcriptional events that it regulates would be tagged by a disease tag (but not products of these transcriptional events, as they are normal proteins). I had a similar case in "Deregulated CDK5 triggers multiple neurodegenerative pathways in Alzheimer's disease models", where e.g. transcription factor FOXO3 is aberrantly phosphorylated ([reaction 8870558](#)) by a disease-specific complex CDK5:p25, producing a disease-specific FOXO3 phosphorylation product, which then stimulates the expression of pro-apoptotic genes, e.g. [BCL2L11](#).

If reason 2 is in place, then a complex of STAT3 and a target gene that it normally does not bind to would be tagged with a disease tag. The black box event of gene expression regulated by this complex would also be disease tagged, but not the product of this black box event. [This would be similar to tagging the ERBB2 homodimer and the reactions it takes part in with disease tags](#). Although ERBB2 homodimer consists of two normal ERBB2 proteins, it is disease-tagged because it is not normally present in the cell (normally low level of ERBB2

expression prevents homodimerization; homodimerization happens when ERBB2 is amplified or overexpressed in cancer).

If neither 1) nor 2) are true, then I don't see the need for disease tags after STAT3 phosphorylation. It would be the case of disease-specific pathway merging with the normal pathway, as is the case with other gain-of-function pathways. If Reactome does not have annotations of downstream STAT3 targets that are relevant for ALK signaling, they should be included as part of the normal pathway (an imaginary "Transcriptional regulation by STAT3", and the disease pathway should point to this pathway. If the comprehensive annotation of such normal pathway is out of scope, perhaps a portion of it can be annotated as a starter and the remainder filled in later, or they should be included in the normal ALK signaling diagram for the time being.

Conclusion:

A disease event must involve at least one entity that is disease-tagged (and that is not genetically normal). The best solution in this case is to have the NPM-ALK fusion (legitimately disease tagged) as a positive regulator of either or both of the downstream (WT entities only) STAT3-gene binding event and the (WT entities only) gene expression event that it stimulates, as shown, and to mark the events with a disease tag.

Appendix C13. Deep extraction of events

Deep extracting events in a local project

In the **Event Browser** view, select the pathway that contains all of the events that you want to include. It is best to select the smallest pathway that still contains all the events that you'd like to review.

Check this out into a local project.

To extract “top down”:

1. Select all ReactionLikeEvents (RLE) right click and select “update from database”(make a note of # of RLE instances)
2. If number of RLEs increases in the “update” you'll need to select all and update again.
3. Repeat this process until the number of RLEs stabilizes *A total of 2 rounds of updates should extract all component reactions as well as their immediate referrers ...e.g reactions in the “inferredFrom” slots.*
4. Select all CatalystActivities, right click and select “update from database”
5. Select all EntitySets (note starting #) right click and select “update from database”. Repeat until the number of sets stabilizes (note the **final** # of sets).
6. Select all Complexes and update as described above. After you've updated complexes, recheck # of set. If sets have increased, repeat step 5 on sets. Then recheck complexes. Repeat this loop until neither number increases (note the **final** # of sets).
7. Select all GenomeEncodedEntity update from DB.
8. Select all Polymer and update (check number of EntitySets and Complexes to see if they'e increased. If so, repeat step 5 or 6 as necessary).
9. Select “OtherEntity” and update from DB.
10. Select SimpleEntity and update from DB.

Project extraction should now be complete. Don't forget to save!

Appendix C14. Remote Attribute Search Tool

This tool can be used to search within a data class for instances with specified attributes (or with specified attributes of attributes). For example you can search for all reactions whose input includes complexes containing a given ReferenceEntity.

To search Reactome curator, use (new):

http://curator.reactome.org/cgi-bin/remotearch2?DB=gk_central

To search reactomerelease, use (new);

https://release.reactome.org/cgi-bin/remotearch2?DB=slice_test

Non-functional Remote Attribute Search on gk_central and live site (2024)

[To search gk_central, use:

<http://reactomerelease.oicr.on.ca/cgi-bin/remotearch2>

To search the live site, use:

http://www.reactome.org/cgi-bin/remotearch2?DB=gk_current

Examples of how to use the remotearch tool can be found below.

Remotearch examples

1. Simple

class - EWAS

hasModifiedResidue

psiMod

name (regex) phospho

curator.reactome.org

search tool for experts in Reactome data model

REACTOME
A CURATED PATHWAY DATABASE

About Reactome Data Schema Pathway Browser Contact

e.g. O95631, NTN1, signalir Search

THIS SITE IS USED FOR CURATION AND TESTING
IT IS NOT STABLE, IS LINKED TO AN INCOMPLETE DATA SET, AND IS NOT MONITORED FOR PERFORMANCE. WE STRONGLY RECOMMEND THE USE OF OUR PUBLIC SITE

Restrict search to a class EntityWithAccessionedSequence

Fields

hasModifiedResidue psiMod name matching REGULAR EXPRESSION phospho

Search

Produces 3366 matches on curator (Sept 2024).

This lists EWASs as that is the class you queried.

Choose to display results as **custom table** showing:

DB_ID

name[0] (this limits to 1st name) *or*

name (this prints off all names separated by pipes)

Once you have listed the attributes you wish to have displayed, click the “View selected instances” to generate the results.

Like this:

```
#DB_ID #name[0]
9700461 p-7Y ALK Y1278S
9909362 p-S-PER3
206197 Phospho (2 sites) Erk2
206159 Phospho ARM
2197668 p-Y291-WAS
442924 phosphorylated MAPKAPK3
9656067 p-S338,Y341,T492,S494,S621 RAF1 S259T
420350 pFyn(Y531)
9860512 p-Y464-PIK3R2
2454244 p-Y65-FCER1G
1996341 p-6Y-EGFR A289T
8957037 p-AMELX
9009184 p-S286.S304-Runx2-P2
```

2. ADD an additional filter example

class - PhysicalEntity

hasMember

name (regex) - cyclin -> 83 matches

AND

compartment

name (regex) - cytosol -> 30 matches

Restrict search to a class

Fields

<input type="checkbox"/>	hasMember	<input type="text" value="name"/>	<input type="text" value="matching REGULAR EXPRESSION"/>	<input type="text" value="cyclin"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	compartment	<input type="text" value="name"/>	<input type="text" value="matching REGULAR EXPRESSION"/>	<input type="text" value="cytosol"/>

3. Upstream example

class EWAS

hasComponent:Complex

name regex polymerase

-> 139 matches

AND

species name regex sapiens

-> 63 matches

V90_Sept 2024

- moved from DevWiki
- examples updated with images
- grey out references to gk_central and live site remote attribute search

Appendix C15. Remove duplicates MSExcel

Identifying list members that are unique to one of two lists using Microsoft Excel

This is a procedure describing how to take two lists and compare entries to identify those that are present in only one of the two lists. This procedure can be useful, for example, to compare the list of proteins in the gk_central vs. live site to find those that are unreleased.

Identifying list members that are unique

1. Create a new file that contains two columns to be compared.
2. Select the cell ranges (both columns).
3. Under conditional formatting, choose "Highlight Cell Rules" then "Duplicate Values"
4. Format cell that contain.... "Duplicate" values with a colour. Click OK
5. Under "Sort and Filter" Select Filter.
6. For each column, Select "Sort by Color" under the little arrow choosing the colour of the unique values above (this is no color by default)
7. This should produce a list with uncoloured (unique) values at the top of the column(s).

Appendix C16: RHEA/GO alignment

Alignment with the RHEA reaction database involves:

- Pinpointing the exact RHEA ID of a reaction.
Note that UniProt always gives the number of the directionally undefined reaction while our reactions are unidirectional, so you can't simply copy from Uniprot. You can find the unidirectional ID at the RHEA page under "Cross-references".
- Add the RHEA ID in the crossReference slot of the reaction. Multiple IDs are possible and sometimes needed
- Check if participants are identical to RHEA. ReferenceMolecules of SimpleEntities must point to the same ChEBI items as in RHEA.
- In case of additions/deletions of participants, fix all diagrams containing the reaction
- Communicate any star changes because of the above

Alignment with the GO process tree involves:

- Filling the goBiologicalProcess slot of any BlackBoxEvent you encounter
- Filling the goBiologicalProcess slot of any ReactionlikeEvent with a GO process entry IF that event is part of a process different from (and not a subprocess of) the process the whole pathway is associated with. This is a minimal way to make sure Reactome contains no incorrect GO process annotations. In obvious cases redesign of pathways might be necessary.
- Similar considerations apply to goBiologicalProcess slots of pathways. Try minimal changes first. Pathway redesigns should be part of wholesome revisions where everything can happen

